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Influence of Missiological Training on Trainers' Competences and Christian Maturity in the Selected Mission Training Institutions in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

Globally, missionaries are supposed to receive prerequisite training to help them navigate their mission engagement. However, some still operate as if they are sent out unprepared. Despite some empirical evidence on missiological training and practices among Christian organisations in Nigeria, there seems to be little attention paid to the influence of mission education on trainers' outcomes. Therefore, this study investigated influence of missiological training (MT) on trainers' competences (TC) and Christian maturity among selected mission training institutions in Southwest, Nigeria. Descriptive Survey Research Design was adopted using Trainers' Competence and Outcome Questionnaire (TCOQ) $r = .864$. Population of the study involves all mission training institutions and trainers, affiliated to Nigeria Evangelical Missions Association (NEMA) with a total sample of 82 mission trainers selected from five NEMA- members. MT has a significant influence on enhancing the trainers' ability to conceive a well-developed curriculum as rated by 70.7% of the respondents. Influence of missiological training on: trainers' language and culture learning experiences was rated by respondents as 67.1%, on skills in cross-cultural evangelism and church planting (75.6%), on discipleship and mentor relationship skills (62.2%), ability to manage people with sensitivity (67.1%) and on trainers' wisdom and Interaction in cross-cultural and diverse situations (70.7%), on trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge

(52.4%); trainers' understanding of theological, socio-political, economic, and ethnic realities (54.9%), understanding local political and social situations (62.2%), keeping trainers updated on global mission activities, and in keeping trainers updated on missiological thinking and writing (65.9%). MT enhances trainers' clearer understanding of Missio-Dei was rated high by 85.4% of the respondents, 68.3% on enhancing a shift in worldview, and 80.5% on recognizing that mission is a task for all believers, and equipping for effective missionary training in different contexts. The study concludes that influence of missiological training was found to be significant on: trainers' capacity to effectively run mission training programs, trainers' Christian maturity, on trainers' ministry skills and experience, on trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge, and on trainers' vision for mission training. Based on this study's findings, it is highly recommended that more field missionaries should be encouraged to step aside for a while to acquire further education.

Keywords: Missiological Training, Trainers' Competencies, Training Outcomes, Trained Missionary, Missionary Trainer

Introduction

Over the centuries, missionaries have done excellent work, even as the majority of them did not have missiology training. An author corroborated emphasizing that all that is needed to preach the gospel is more of "death to self" and less of academic training¹. Missiology training was not required to become a missionary or to perform well in the practice of missions. Missionaries who answered the call to missions then did not rely on their university degree or any form of missiology training to be missionaries on the field. One major revival killer is training for higher degrees, training in Bible Colleges and seminaries where, according to an author, there is a shift from using the Bible as the main text to studying how Jesus lived and taught. Thus, the life and message of the student are based on higher philosophy and criticism rather than on the principles of Christ².

The growth of the church worldwide has given rise to new missionary movements. These movements are driven by a genuine passion for sharing the Gospel with those who have not yet heard it. However, it is essential that missionaries receive proper training to avoid potential problems and tragedies that can arise when they are sent out

unprepared. Therefore, there is a demand for specialized training to ensure that missionaries are well-equipped for their important task³.

Training should produce men fashioned for specific tasks especially when we go to God for the secret of how God made His men relevant in His plans. Training should produce men with the Master's heart not just His head. Men who shall carry out God's mission. Men who will go and make disciples for Christ among nations. It takes a disciple to make another. There might be serious consequences when missionaries are sent out with inadequate or no preparation at all. It could be more precarious when the trainer himself is not properly trained. Fulfilling the great commission i.e. making disciples of Jesus from every tribe, tongue, people, and nation is a very important job. This truth places a demand on Church leaders to employ the most effective means available to prepare every believer in Jesus to accomplish this mission of making disciples who can disciple others. According to the doctrine of the Christian faith, the eternal destiny of billions of people hangs in the balance.

Training and Education are words that, technically and by definitions, may be explained differently but conceptually they are means of achieving an end. The end in this case is to produce an effective mission practitioner. Whatever the setting is, whether Bible School, Mission School, Theological Seminary, Sunday School, Church-Based Training Programme, etc. as long as Jesus is the foundation and the Holy Bible is the main manual and reference point, then the primary purpose should be first to produce men after the Master. Men with the Master's heart and also His head. Instructions from God by a teacher are bound to produce effective missionaries. The purpose of any mission training institution is to produce missionaries who will be able to effectively engage a people group. Effectively engaging a people seeks to establish a minimum benchmark that will help set the stage whereby the church planting movement can thrive even if it does not immediately give rise to church planting. There are four essential elements have been highlighted for an effective engagement of a people group with the gospel⁴: Apostolic effort in residence, commitment to work in the local language and culture, commitment to long-term ministry, and showing in a manner consistent to see a church planting movement emerge⁴.

Who is an effective missionary? When is a missionary said to be effective on the field? What makes a missionary effective? These are questions

that make an investigation of the influence of missiology training on training outcomes imperative. Missiological training for effective missionary service therefore seeks to produce men and women who will have the competence to actualize the four essential elements.

Therefore, this study investigated the influence of missiological training (MT) on training outcomes (TO); trainers' capacity to run effective mission training, trainers' Christian maturity, trainers' ministry skills and experience, trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge, and trainers' vision for mission training among missionary institutions in Southwest, Nigeria.

Imperativeness of Missiological Training

A scholar investigated what missionary training model can best prepare Christians for cross-cultural services. The conclusions are that, though, the inclination towards academic learning is paramount, Missiology is central, Character formation is vital, becoming a Christ-like model is a goal, Prayer is the lamp light, and Evangelism is a main concern and non-stop activity⁵.

A mission practitioner observed that great cultural change in the world has thwarted both young and old so that many are unable to engage successfully in cross-cultural church planting and that the greatest cause of this is a lack of skill in cross-cultural church planting. Some agencies, wrote, the mission practitioner, report, as high as 47% of their personnel leave the field in the first five years while others stay longer but do not succeed in planting churches. We cannot expect them to do a job they have never been trained to do⁶.

Training for Cross-Cultural Church-planting is a program that speaks to all the important weaknesses that lead to missionary attrition because it integrates the competencies needed to do cross-cultural church planting. These are spiritual disciplines, family dynamics, team building, and work experience, nurturing children, and learning to partner with national peers⁷. A mission practitioner, who worked twelve years in India among different religious sects and communities in Asia, training how to disciple peoples of another culture through Biblical Story, wrote, that birthing kingdom communities (fellowships oriented around allegiance to Jesus and life in his kingdom) are much more a craft than the pursuit of an academic subject. Therefore, a more suitable model for training is needed beyond the typical Bible school or seminary structure.

Craftsmen have been trained through a master–apprenticeship model, he wrote further, that a Master in a trade or skill trains apprentices to the level of competency he has attained⁸. In the manner in which Jesus trained the twelve disciples in the New Testament, He expected the trained practitioners to gain experience and be able to help other apprentices and eventually rise to the level of master trainer themselves. Paul referred to himself as a “wise master builder,” using craftsmanship terminology⁹.

The personal attributes that help a person to be more competent at crossing cultures as they interact with people from other cultures, scoring high in some cross-cultural competence attributes may not increase a person’s cross-cultural competence, based on the culture. Results revealed that competence in the areas of relationship orientation, interpersonal skills, cultural interest, inquisitiveness, inclusiveness, and self-efficacy, is also very important²². Thus, making disciples of Jesus from every tribe, tongue, people, and nation is the most important job in the world. It therefore demands the most effective training available¹⁰.

One outstanding outcome of disciple-making is the transformation of the lives of people. And the expected outcome from a disciple that is transforming is an ability to disciple others. Preparing believers to make disciples in every tribe and tongue, demands our best efforts. This is what the researcher describes as mission training, the goal of which is that believers are trained to be disciple-makers. There is an example in the Holy Bible when Jesus spent three years mentoring, discipling, and teaching twelve men¹¹. These trainees learned by watching and listening to the master who later sent them out to practise what they had seen lived out before them. This was a type of hands-on practice, or apprenticeship whereby skills and competency were mastered¹².

Missiological Training and Training Outcomes for Trainers

In a sponsored Missionary Training seminar, the working groups came up with a summary of attributes of a missionary trainer’s life and ministry that are key essentials leading to a successful training ministry. The attributes were categorised as Christian maturity, ministry skills and experience, teaching and equipping skills, and interdisciplinary knowledge¹³.

Table 1 presents essential outcomes of a trainer.

Table 1: Essential Attributes of a Missionary Trainer

Christian Maturity	Ministry Skills and Experience	Teaching And Equipping Skills	Interdisciplinary Knowledge
<p>1. Maintains spiritual disciplines in personal relationship with God.</p> <p>2. Is building an ample knowledge of and growing in obedience to the Word of God.</p> <p>3. Is characterized by the fruit/gifts of the Spirit.</p> <p>4. Practices an effective prayer life.</p>	<p>1. Has successful cross-cultural experience in ministry (from language learning and community entry to effective evangelism and church planting, teaching and church-development).</p> <p>2. Develops effective disciple and mentor relationships.</p> <p>3. Able to manage people and projects</p>	<p>1. Is a good listener and effective communicator.</p> <p>2. Focuses on practical and relevant course (and field) work.</p> <p>3. Able to teach using various techniques and resources.</p> <p>4. Brings a wealth of practical and personal experience.</p> <p>5. Can foster good interpersonal and team dynamics.</p> <p>6. Accurately evaluates people and guides them to</p>	<p>1. Relates theological knowledge to missiological practice, especially regarding socio-political, economic, and ethnic realities.</p> <p>2. Is familiar with local, political and social situations and organizations.</p> <p>3. Prior training and experience in appropriate to the institution's goals.</p> <p>4. Keeps abreast of other missionaries and mission activities worldwide.</p> <p>5. Has a biblical and historical grasp of the local and global church</p> <p>6. Keeps updated on missiological thinking and writing.</p>

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| 5. Promotes a biblical relationship with the church. | with sensitivity and wisdom. | effectiveness . |
| 6. Exercises good stewardship. Gives priority to a balanced family life. | 4. Interacts well with others in cross-cultural and diverse situations. | 7. Lifestyle models what is being taught. |
| 7. Lives a sacrificial and simple lifestyle. | 5. Has personal maturity to sustain open and honest relationships. | 8. Motivates people to want to learn. |
| 8. Has vision and passion for mission. | 6. Enters into cooperative relationships with diverse peoples. | 9. Not afraid to demonstrate cross-cultural and ministry dynamics before students. |
| 9. Builds accountability relationships. Is respectful of | 7. Demonstrates cultural sensitivity and respect. | |

spiritual
authority.
10.
Possesses
a
teachable
spirit.

Source: G. J. Kayser Development of Competence-Oriented Missionary Training. A Workshop Manual. Bethany International, (2003) \USA. pp 90¹³.

Trainers' Ministry Skills and Experience

A review of cross-cultural research in intercultural studies suggests five primary skills and five secondary skills needed for competent cross-cultural ministry. The primary skills are:

1. Interaction and management skills
2. Immediacy skills
3. Social relaxation skills
4. Expressive skills
5. Other orientation skills (adaptability to other people, empathy, open-mindedness, and accurate perception of others' verbal and non-verbal communication).

The review identified the secondary skills to include:

1. Task and social skills,
2. Innovativeness skill
3. Problem-solving and conflict management skills¹⁴.

Skill and competence required to live in an alien culture have to be acquired if we are going to reduce the rate of “casualties” and missionary attrition¹⁵. Churches in many parts of the world responded to this by developing types of missionary training programs, each varying according to the diverse needs of missionary trainees, available facilities, and funds¹⁶.

Missionary training aims to see many unreached individuals and people groups evangelised and disciplined as followers of Jesus Christ. The level of involvement in missions for which people are being prepared will determine the training program. Targets of training could be people who are called to be missionaries and need missionary training. They may be

without formal theological training, or without the means or time to go through the regular school of missions. Candidates for training could be believers who need to be mobilised for involvement in missions.

Thus, training programs come in various formats. There are training packages for discipling the nations essentially for those who will go to the field for missionary service different from training programs for mobilising the church for mission involvement. Training programs can be designed as a refresher course for serving missionaries. As touching the great commission mandate, those who want to labour correctly are few compared to the plenteousness of the harvest¹⁷. And the available few (full of passion and zeal) are not trained. Training is the intermediate phase between "calling" and "sending" which we always want to jump. The imperativeness of training, therefore, places a demand upon those to whom God has committed missionary training assignments sent to track men down as they are rushing into the harvest, they know nothing about¹⁸.

When we use the two words "Training and Education" interchangeably we are using them to mean the same thing. Technically and by definitions they may be explained differently but conceptually to us, they are means of achieving an end. The end in this case is to produce effective mission practitioners. Whatever the setting is, whether Bible School, Mission School, Theological Seminary, Sunday School, Church-Based Training program, etc., as long as Jesus is the foundation and the Holy Bible is the main manual and reference point, then the primary purpose should be first to produce men after the Master, Jesus Christ. Men with the Master's heart and also His head¹⁹.

Trainers' Christian Maturity

A mission practitioner noted that instructions from God by a teacher are bound to produce effective missionaries. Jesus spent most of his interactive sessions with the people answering questions and it is only when questions are asked that answers can be deduced. This is fundamental to the academic process and this generation needs answers which emanate from the right questions. He wrote further that; training will expose the trainee to 'what to do' but might not do it for the trainee in various circumstances. He wrote that training teaches the way now and enables the trainee to discover his or her way later amidst various

situations. It is the principles learned and the examples shared that remain as guiding pillars to the practical future of the student¹⁸.

Training is not a quick fix; it is an introduction to a line of thinking, specialty, skills acquisition, and understanding. It is as one vigorously aspires to grow along the line of one's training that one eventually excels in that direction. It is only when learning (a result of being trained) and studying (a result of discovery for oneself) are harnessed that a scholar is equipped and distinguished. Even the Bible spoke lightly of those who are ever learning and never coming to the knowledge of the truth because of their inability in their ensuing activities (post-training life): "The word they heard did not profit them not been mixed with faith in them that heard it"¹⁸. This is a peculiarity of Christian training gone wrong, wrote the mission practitioner, Christian training must be mixed and internalised with faith. Believing in Jesus Christ and acting on his words are essential elements of fruitful Christian training¹⁸.

Sharing the gospel may not necessarily require a degree or education, but education can help us fully understand God's word and share the Gospel in different cultural contexts. While no formal education may be required to become a missionary, education is recommended before going overseas as a missionary so they can properly share the Gospel with a different culture³¹. A college degree in business or education would help the missionary bring a skill overseas. Education can be key to effectively communicating the gospel, but it is important to know exactly what you want to pursue. While education is not required for missionaries, continued the Scholar, it is encouraged. Education can help missionaries to become ready to share the Gospel cross-culturally²⁰. The education that one is exposed to before going overseas is not only for oneself. That education received will be what you teach others. "In all thy getting, get understanding"²¹.

The response of the disciples to a particular teaching sermon of Jesus displays their lack of understanding, Jesus' reply to their response further confirms this: "That's enough", Jesus says²². When they further demonstrated their mediocrity and lack of understanding by cutting a man's ear with their sword, Jesus' response was the same²³. Hence, as missionaries and trainers, who want the will of God done, there is need to have an understanding of the times, events around us, and the world and their spiritual implications e.g. Global events and their relationship to the end times, an understanding of God's will for nations. In other

words, we need to be educated about events happening around us and their effects on the destiny of mankind.

How can we tell you were properly trained? The issue of training is simple and clear, but the issue of ascertaining levels of training is very subjective in today's world. However, there are two types of judges whose opinions count for all trainees. The first type of judge is the public judge; Jesus said, "By this shall all men know you are my disciple, your love one for another"²⁴.

The second type of judge is to have empirical evidence, which this research work is expected to do. Certain scholars wrote about missionary training comparing formal and non-formal approaches. He wrote that trainees are admitted to missionary training centres based on missionary calling and gifts, rather than on strict academic qualifications which apply to the formal education approach²⁵.

The outcome of training is not a private or exclusive preserve of congregational testimony alone. It is subject to the affirmation of the world through specific biblical cognitive values spelled out by Jesus himself. Again, in the Holy Scriptures, the Apostle wrote "Let your moderation be made known (evident) to all men"²⁶.

Missionary training centres do not offer a general education course or even a general bible training course, but rather a focused missionary training program. Each subject taught in the training centre is only scheduled for as long as is necessary to communicate the principles and develop the skills in question; most missionary training centres do not follow an academic term or semester calendar. Furthermore, the subjects taught are not dictated by tradition or social expectations but are chosen to prepare the trainee for effective cross-cultural ministry. Missionary training centres, like other non-formal education organisations, occasionally award certificates of completion to trainees but rarely award degrees²⁷.

These obvious strengths of non-formal education, they continued, can be taken full advantage of when we focus on recruiting effective trainers and developing curricula that will equip trainees with the character qualities and practical skills competency needed for cross-cultural ministry. Effective trainers employ the power of training by example for trainees to observe in ministry situations and are often taken into "field" situations to practise cross-cultural and ministry skills²⁸.

Despite the differences between formal and non-formal approaches, attempts to combine the two are common in missionary training. For example, a bible school may offer a missionary training course or a missionary training centre may expand its curriculum to offer a full list of bible school courses. Although it appears economical to support one educational institution instead of two, combining a bible school and a missionary training centre is difficult. However, there are certain fundamental problems we must watch out for when we attempt to combine the two. Missionary training (non - formal approach) classes often are smaller than more general bible school (formal approach) classes. Developing spiritual gifts and ministry skills also requires more missionary trainers than the number of lecturers needed for Bible school instruction. Consequently, non-formal missionary training programs often are more expensive (per trainee) than (formal) Bible school programs²⁹.

The emphasis of bible schools, seminaries, and university (formal) education programs is on “standards,” “degrees,” and “accreditation.” Non-Formal education programs, on the other hand, value practical training. Missionary candidates who study missions in a bible school may still need the practical training offered by missionary training centres³⁰.

Although all missionary training centres teach from the bible, most missionary candidates should complete a basic bible school course before entering missionary training. Bible schools and missionary training centres need to view their training programs as complementary, not as competitive. For the reasons mentioned above, missionary training centres that attempt to offer a formal bible school program may jeopardise their primary training mission. Affiliation of missionary training centres with bible schools, seminaries, and departments of religious studies in regular universities can be explored. To do this, admission criteria, curricular scope and focus, and training motivation and methods would be looked into³¹.

A trainer’s job goes beyond the classroom. He mentors. A trainer is to stimulate the development of true spirituality and discipleship, proven within the context of community. Being asked to serve as a mentor is an honour¹⁹. It indicates that the ministry has faith in your abilities and trusts you to have a positive impact on the trainee. Poor attempt at mentoring may be worse than no mentoring at all. Our mentoring must

be tailored to suit the trainees, the organisation, and the desired outcomes. Someone with a negative attitude should not serve as a mentor. Apprenticeship is a process where an experienced person meets with a less experienced person to learn a skill to the point where the apprentice will be able to know and practise the skill learned on his own. An internship is another model of non-formal education to develop from an academically trained individual to one who can perform his ministry with the close observation of the mentor until he is made to do so without supervision¹⁹.

Trainers' Interdisciplinary Knowledge

Trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge has to do with relating theological knowledge to missiological practice, especially regarding socio-political, economic, and ethnic realities. Trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge has to do with becoming more familiar with local, political, and social situations and organizations, and exposure to the need for training and experience appropriate to training goals. Trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge keeps trainers abreast of others and gives trainers a biblical and historical grasp of the local and global church. Trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge keeps trainers updated on missiological thinking and writing.

Trainers' Vision For Mission Training, And Capacity to Run Effective Mission Training

The perception of people involved in ministry of what ministry is, affects greatly what is shall receive as ministry vision. With a proper understanding of the biblical concept of ministry, the vision for ministry will be in line with the global program of God, Christ, and the Church. Any person's vision for ministry will be developed in line with what he/she understands to be the meaning of ministry. God has made His program for the earth so clear in the Scriptures and God's servants, both in the bible days and contemporary times have developed and continued to develop ministry vision according to their understanding of what God's program is³².

The correctness of the individual's understanding of God's program will determine the correctness of the ministry's vision. The burden of developing mission training was birthed by the increasing number of churches that are catching the vision for missionary involvement and are

commissioning missionaries in their thousands. The challenge this increase poses on the Church is that this task force must be equipped for cross-cultural ministry³³.

Statement of the Problem

While a great deal of literature exists on the influence of education attainment on job performance in different organisations, issues relating to the Influence of missiological training on trainers' competences and Christian maturity have scarcely been addressed. Presumably, the level of missiological training attained, hypothetically predicts or serves as an indicator of the skill levels, competence, or performance, expected of the missionary. Hence, the need for empirical study on the influence of missiological training on trainers' competences and Christian maturity.

Therefore, this study examines the influence of missiological training on trainers' competences and Christian maturity among missionaries of selected missiological training institutions in Southwest Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the Influence of Missiological Training on Trainers' Competences and Christian maturity among missionaries in Southwest Nigeria. The objectives are to:

1. ascertain the influence of missiological training on trainers' capacity to run effective mission training
2. assess the influence of missiological training on trainers' Christian maturity
3. ascertain the influence of missiological training on trainers' ministry skills and experience
4. appraise the influence of missiological training on trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge
5. ascertain the influence of missiological training on trainers' vision for mission training

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of missiological training on trainers' capacity to run effective mission training?

2. What is the influence of missiological training on trainers' Christian maturity?
3. What is the influence of missiological training on trainers' ministry skills and experience?
4. What is the influence of missiological training on trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge?
5. What is the influence of missiological training on trainers' vision for mission training?

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population consists of all missiologists, and mission trainers, of Nigeria Evangelical Missions Association (NEMA) member training institutions in Southwestern Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure was employed whereby, initially, a purposive sampling method was utilized for the analysis of curriculum contents. Following this, a random sampling technique was utilized to select 82 missiologists who serve as trainers in the selected five (5) institutions. 1. Gospel Faith Missions International School of Missions (GOFAMINT) Ojoo, Ibadan. Oyo State. Redeemed Christian School of Missions (RECSOM), Ede, Osun State, 3. LIFE Theological Seminary School of Missions, (FOURSQUARE), Foursquare camp, Ajebo, Ogun state, 4. Wale Oke College of Missions and Evangelism, (WOCOME) and 5 Evangelical Christians Winning All (ECWA) Theological Seminary Igbaja, (ETSI), (being a theological seminary accessed by missionaries in the fields). Random sampling technique was adopted to select a total of 82 mission trainers who are affiliated and non-affiliates or mission volunteer trainers who are not on full-time engagement with the five (5) selected missiological training institutions. A duly validated instrument named “Trainers’ Competence and Outcome Questionnaire (TCOQ)” $r=0.864$, was used for data gathering and data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Data collection involved circulation of the questionnaire through Google Forms via the link: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScThpIOdDbbWHELn2ZjSMZ3fdXG3ZgU7oGvVARl7zZ5j3Dpmw/viewform?usp=sf_link. Demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 2a and Table 2b.

Table 2a. Demographic distribution of Respondents' Information by Missiological Institution Affiliation, Age, Gender, and Nationality (N=82)

		Frequ ency	Perce nt (%)
Missiolo gical Instituti ons	GOFAMINT School of Missions, Ibadan, Oyo State	6	7.3
	RECSOM, Ede, Osun State	14	17.1
	LIFE Theological School of Mission, Ajebo, Ogun State	13	15.9
	ECWA Theological Seminary, Igbaja, Kwara State	2	2.4
	Wale Oke College of Missions and Evangelism, Ibadan, Oyo State	3	3.7
	Non-Affiliated/Volunteer Mission Trainers	44	53.6
Gender	Male	59	72.0
	Female	23	28.0
Age	20-29	3	3.7
	30-34	4	4.9
	35-39	13	15.9
	40-44	9	11.0
	45 and above	53	64.6
	Mean = 4.28 Std. Deviation = 1.125		
National ity	Nigerian	79	96.3
	Not Specified	3	3.7

Source: Fieldwork 2024

Table 2a presents the locations and status of the missiological training institutions whose curriculum contents were analysed. Two of the institutions are located in Oyo state, while the other three are in Osun, Ogun and Kwara states, (approximately 70%) of the states in the

Southwest region of Nigeria. Four of the institutions are of the “School of Mission” status while one is of “Seminary” status.

Table 2a further presents the demographic distribution of respondents’ information by missiological institution affiliation, age, gender, and nationality. The table reveals that the majority of the respondents 44, (53.6) are Non-Affiliated/Volunteer Mission Trainers who are not on full-time engagement with the selected missiological training institutions but serves as volunteers, associates, and adjunct trainers to the selected missiological institution.

Invariably, missiological training is mostly undertaken informally by mission trainers due to the fact that remuneration is not based on regular salary on monthly basis. Gender distribution reveals a predominance of male respondents (72.0%) compared to female respondents (28.0%), indicating a gender imbalance in the field. This could reflect broader societal or organizational trends in mission training institutions.

Again, the age distribution of the respondents is skewed towards the older age groups. A substantial majority (64.6%) are aged 45 years and above, indicating that the respondents are likely to be experienced and possibly hold senior positions in their respective institutions. The age groups of 35-39 years and 40-44 years comprise 15.9% and 11.0% of the sample, respectively, while younger age groups (20-29 years and 30-34 years) make up smaller proportions, 3.7% and 4.9%, respectively. The mean age of 4.28 with a standard deviation of 1.125 underscores a mature sample with a central tendency towards the older age brackets.

Predominantly, the respondents are Nigerian, accounting for 96.3% of the total sample, with a small percentage (3.7%) not specifying their nationality. This suggests a homogenous group in terms of nationality, potentially reflecting the local context of the study.

Table 2b. Demographic Distribution of Respondents' Information by Secular Education, Missiological Training, Status/Job Function, Years of Involvement in Mission Training, Nature of Mission Field Engagement and Locations (N=82)

		Freq uenc y	Perce nt (%)
Secular Education	Secondary School Certificate	3	3.7
	National Certificate in Education	3	3.7
	OND	2	2.4
	HND	9	11.0
	Bachelor's Degree	29	35.4
	Master's Degree	25	30.5
	Doctorate	11	13.4
Missiological Training	Certificate	21	25.6
	Diploma	19	23.2
	Bachelor's Degree	9	11.0
Status	Master's Degree	27	32.9
	Doctorate	6	7.3
	Resident Trainer in a mission training institution	20	24.4
	Trainer in a mission training institution	16	19.5
	Itinerant mission trainer	8	9.8
	Mission Mobilizer	24	29.3
	Trainer/lecturer in mission departments of Bible Colleges and seminaries	9	11.0
	Trainer without any formal education	1	1.2
	Others	4	4.9
	Job Function	Provost/Head of School	11
Guest Lecturer/Trainer		63	76.8
Others		8	9.8
Years of	5-10 years	48	58.5
	10-15 years	12	14.6

Enga geme nt in Missi on Trai ning Natu re of Missi on Field Enga geme nt and Loca tion	15-20 years	12	14.6
	20-25 years	5	6.1
	25 years and above	5	6.1
	Among Least-Reached people	21	25.6
	Among Reached people group	8	9.8
	Among Rural people	29	35.3
Urban Mission	6	7.3	
Blank	18	21.9	

Source: Fieldwork 2024

Table 2b presents the demographic distribution of respondents' information by secular education, missiological training, status/job function, years of engagement in mission training, nature of mission field engagement, and locations. The respondents, as revealed in Table 2b possess a range of secular educational qualifications, with 35.4% holding a Bachelor's degree, 30.5% a Master's degree, and 13.4% a Doctorate. Other qualifications include HND (11.0%), National Certificate in Education (3.7%), Secondary School Certificate (3.7%), and OND (2.4%).

This diversity in educational attainment suggests a well-educated cohort with varying levels of academic achievement. In terms of missiological education, the majority have attained a Master's degree (32.9%) or a Certificate (25.6%). Other qualifications include Diploma (23.2%), Bachelor's degree (11.0%), and Doctorate (7.3%). This distribution reflects a growing commitment to missiological education among the respondents.

Regarding job functions, a large majority (76.8%) serve as Guest Lecturers/Trainers, reflecting that majority of the respondents are trainers. Other roles include Provosts/Heads of Schools (13.4%) and unspecified roles (9.8%), suggesting a diversity of job functions within the sample. In terms of status/job function, respondents' roles are varied, with Mission Mobilizers making up the largest group (29.3%). Resident Trainers in mission training institutions (24.4%) and Trainers in mission training institutions (19.5%) also constitute significant proportions. Other roles include Itinerant Mission Trainers (9.8%), Trainers/Lecturers in mission departments of Bible Colleges and Seminaries (11.0%), Trainers without formal education (1.2%), and those in unspecified roles (4.9%). This distribution highlights a preponderance of more of trainers who are mission mobilisers, than trainers who are either resident or guest trainers in mission training institutions.

The length of service in their roles and responsibilities varies, with a majority (58.5%) having served for 5-10 years. This suggests the levels of experience within this time frame. Smaller percentages have served for 10-15 years (14.6%), 15-20 years (14.6%), 20-25 years (6.1%), and over 25 years (6.1%), indicating the scarcity of more experienced trainers within this time frame.

Table 2b further reveals the nature of mission field engagement of respondents. A significant proportion (78.0%) of respondents have practical experience on mission fields post-training. This experience which is primarily in rural areas (45.3%), followed by least-reached groups (32.8%), urban areas (9.4%), and reached groups (12.5%), reflects that majority of mission trainers have laboured in rural areas and among least – reached people group, both being a priority group in missionary endeavours. The duration of mission field experience varies, with the majority (53.1%) having 5-10 years of experience. Other durations include 10-15 years (12.5%), 15-20 years (9.4%), 20-25 years (10.9%), and over 25 years (14.1%). This diverse range of field experience highlights the practical engagement of respondents in mission work.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question One: What is the influence of missiological training on trainers' capacity to run effective mission training?

Table 3: Influence of Missiological training on Trainers' Capacity to run Effective Mission Training (N = 82)

S/N	Statements (Trainer's Vision for Mission Training)	Not Significant Freq. (%)	Significant Freq. (%)	Very Significant Freq. (%)	Mean	SD
1.	My understanding of mission-Dei (God's program) became clearer.	1 (1.2%)	11 (13.4%)	70 (85.4%)	2.84	0.400
2.	Before my missiological training, I possessed a solid comprehension of mission-Dei (God's program)	27 (32.9%)	26 (31.7%)	29 (35.4%)	2.02	0.831
3.	My worldview was shifted from missions as a task for some special people to that of all believers for Missio-Dei	7 (8.5%)	19 (23.2%)	56 (68.3%)	2.60	0.645
4.	Helps me to have a correct understanding of what effective missionary	0 (0%)	16 (19.5%)	66 (80.5%)	2.80	0.399

training is in
 different
 contexts.

Source: Fieldwork, 2024; **Average Grand Mean = 2.5671**

Table 3 presents finding on research question one which revealed that missiological training has a significant influence on making the trainers understanding of Missio-Dei becoming clearer by the rating of 85.4% of the respondents. A significant shift in worldview, recognising that mission is a task for all believers, was brought helped 80.5% of the respondents to understand effective missionary training in different contexts, demonstrating a significant influence of missiological training. The finding also revealed that missiological training has a very significant impact on trainers' ability to conceive a well-developed curriculum as rated by 70.7% of the respondents, while 75.6% of respondents rated the influence of missiological training on the understanding of strategies for missionary training in different contexts as very significant. 76.8% of the respondents rated the influence of missiological training on the implementation of these strategies as highly significant.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of missiological training on trainers' Christian maturity?

Table 4: Influence of Missiological training on Trainers' Christian Maturity (N = 82)

S/N	Statements (Trainers' Christian Maturity)	Not Significant Frequency (%)	Significant Frequency (%)	Very Significant Frequency (%)	Mean	SD
1.	Maintaining spiritual disciplines in a personal	2 (2.4%)	7 (8.5%)	73 (89%)	2.87	0.409

	relationship with God					
2.	Knowledge of and growing in obedience to the Word of God	0 (0%)	9 (11%)	73 (89%)	2.89	0.315
3.	Practicing an effective prayer life	0 (0%)	10 (12.2%)	72 (87.8%)	2.88	0.329
4.	In having a biblical relationship with the church	1 (1.2%)	13 (15.9%)	68 (82.9%)	2.82	0.420
5.	In the exercise of good stewardship	0 (0%)	8 (9.8%)	74 (90.2%)	2.90	0.299
6.	In giving priority to a balanced family life	3 (3.7%)	12 (14.6%)	67 (81.7%)	2.78	0.498
7.	Missiological training influenced me in living a sacrificial and simple lifestyle	1 (1.2%)	13 (15.9%)	68 (82.9%)	2.82	0.420
8.	Missiological training clarified my vision for mission and rekindled my passion for mission.	1 (1.2%)	11 (13.4%)	70 (85.4%)	2.84	0.400

9.	Making me more teachable	2 (2.4%)	18(22%)	62(75.6%)	2.73	0.498
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Average Grand Mean = 2.836

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 presents the finding on the influence of missiological training on trainers’ Christian maturity; on their ability to maintain spiritual disciplines, such as prayer and Bible study, their obedience to the Word of God, their prayer life, and their relationships within the church, and family life, was very significant as rated by 89.0% for their ability to maintain spiritual disciplines, such as prayer and Bible study, 89.0% for their obedience to the Word of God, 87.8% for their prayer life. Influence of missiological training on trainers’ prayer life was rated by respondents as 82.9%, and 81.7% on family life, 81.7%.

Research Question Three: What is the extent of influence of missiological training on trainers’ ministry skills and experience?

Table 5: Influence of Missiological training on Trainers’ Ministry Skills and Experience (N = 82)

S/N	Statements (Trainers’ Ministry Skills and Experience)	Not Significant Freq. (%)	Significant Freq. (%)	Very Significant Freq. (%)	Mean	SD
1.	My missiology training gave me a language and culture learning experience	0 (0%)	27 (32.9%)	55 (67.1%)	2.67	0.473
2.	During my missiology training, I acquired skills in effective cross-	1 (1.2%)	19 (23.2%)	62 (75.6%)	2.74	0.466

	cultural evangelism and church planting					
3.	My discipleship and mentor relationship skills were developed at the mission school	2 (2.4%)	32 (39%)	48 (58.5%)	2.56	0.547
4.	My ability to manage people with sensitivity and wisdom was helped at the mission school	4 (4.9%)	29 (35.4%)	49 (59.8%)	2.55	0.591
5.	I learned how to interact well with others in cross-cultural and diverse situations in the mission school	3 (3.7%)	21 (25.6%)	58 (70.7%)	2.67	0.546

Average Grand Mean = 2.6390

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 5 presents finding on research question three on the influence of missiological training on trainers' ministry skills and experience; language and culture learning experiences, skills in cross-cultural evangelism and church planting, discipleship and mentor relationship skills, ability to manage people with sensitivity and wisdom and Interaction in cross-cultural and diverse situations was also very significant.

Influence of missiological training on: trainers' language and culture learning experiences was rated by respondents as 67.1%, on skills in cross-cultural evangelism and church planting (75.6%), on discipleship and mentor relationship skills (62.2%), ability to manage people with

sensitivity (67.1%) and on trainers' wisdom and Interaction in cross-cultural and diverse situations (70.7%).

Research Question Four: What is the extent of influence of missiological training on trainer's interdisciplinary knowledge?

Table 6: Influence of Missiological training on Trainer's Interdisciplinary Knowledge (N=82)

S/N	Statements (Trainer's Interdisciplinary Knowledge)	Not Signifi cant Freq. (%)	Signifi cant Freq. (%)	Very Signifi cant Freq. (%)	Mean	SD
1.	In relating theological knowledge to missiological practice, especially regarding socio-political, economic, and ethnic realities	5 (6.1%)	34 (41.5%)	43 (52.4%)	2.46	0.61 3
2.	In becoming more familiar with local, political, and social situations and organizations	5 (6.1%)	32 (39%)	45 (54.9%)	2.49	0.61 4
3.	I am exposed to the need for training and experience appropriate to my goals	2 (2.4%)	17 (20.7%)	63 (76.8%)	2.74	0.4 92

4.	Keeps me abreast of other missionaries and mission activities worldwide	4 (4.9%)	27 (32.9%)	51 (62.2%)	2.57	0.5 89
5.	Gives me a biblical and historical grasp of the local and global church	1 (1.2%)	19 (23.2%)	62 (75.6%)	2.74	0.4 66
6.	Keeps me updated on missiological thinking and writing	4 (4.9%)	24 (29.3%)	54 (65.9%)	2.61	0.5 83

Average Grand Mean = 2.6037

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 6 presents finding on influence of missiological training on trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge revealed high significant ratings of influence of missiological training on trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge (52.4%); trainers' understanding of theological, socio-political, economic, and ethnic realities (54.9%), understanding local political and social situations (62.2%), keeping trainers updated on global mission activities, and in keeping trainers updated on missiological thinking and writing (65.9%).

Research Question Five: What is the extent of influence of missiological training on trainer's Vision for mission training?

Table 7: Influence of Missiological training on Trainer’s Vision for Mission Training

S/N	Statements (Trainer’s Vision for Mission Training)	Not Significant Freq. (%)	Significant Freq. (%)	Very Significant Freq. (%)	Mean	SD
1.	My understanding of mission-Dei (God’s program) became clearer.	1 (1.2%)	11 (13.4%)	70 (85.4%)		
2.	Before my missiological training, I possessed a solid comprehension of mission-Dei (God’s program)	27 (32.9%)	26 (31.7%)	29 (35.4%)		
3.	My worldview was shifted from missions as a task for some special people to that of all believers for Missio-Dei	7 (8.5%)	19 (23.2%)	56 (68.3%)		
4.	Helps me to have a correct understanding of what effective missionary training is in different contexts.	0 (0%)	16 (19.5%)	66 (80.5%)		

Average Grand Mean = 2.604

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 7 presents finding on influence of missiological training on trainers' vision for mission training, i.e. on enhancing a clearer understanding of *Missio-Dei*, enhancing a shift in worldview, recognising that mission is a task for all believers, and equipping for effective missionary training in different contexts, was significant as rated by the respondents; Influence of missiological training on enhancing trainers' clearer understanding of *Missio-Dei* was rated high by 85.4% of the respondents, 68.3% on enhancing a shift in worldview, and 80.5% on recognising that mission is a task for all believers, and equipping for effective missionary training in different contexts

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the demographic information and observation from data revealed a predominance of male respondents compared to female respondents indicating a gender imbalance in the field. Again, the age distribution of the respondents is skewed towards the older age groups with a substantial majority being 45 years and above. A large majority of the respondents serve as Guest Lecturers/Trainers, reflecting that majority of the respondents are trainers. Other roles include Provosts/Heads of Schools.

In terms of respondents' roles; findings highlight preponderance of more of trainers who are mission mobilisers, than trainers who are either resident or guest trainers in mission training institutions. Again, findings revealed a significant proportion of respondents have practical experience on mission fields (in rural areas, among least-reached groups, urban areas, and reached groups), post-training reflecting that majority of mission trainers have laboured in rural areas and among least – reached people group, both being a priority group in missionary endeavours.

Finding on research question one revealed that missiological training has a significant influence on trainers' capacity to run capacity to run effective mission training by making the trainers understanding of *Missio-Dei* becoming clearer. Missiological Training, causes a significant shift in worldview, causing trainers to recognise that mission is a task for all believers. Furthermore, missiological training helps trainers to understand effective missionary training in different contexts. Finding resonates with an author's position that the perception of people involved in ministry of what ministry is, affects greatly what is shall

receive as ministry vision. God has made His program for the earth so clear in the Scriptures and God's servants, both in the bible days and contemporary times have developed and continued to develop ministry vision according to their understanding of what God's program is³⁴. The correctness of the individual's understanding of God's program will determine the correctness of the ministry's vision¹⁹.

Finding for research question two revealed that missiological training has a significant influence on trainers' Christian maturity by its impact on trainers' ability to maintain spiritual disciplines, such as prayer and Bible study. Further, findings revealed that missiological training has a significant influence on trainers' demonstration of their obedience to the Word of God, on trainers' prayer life, and relationships within the church. Again, findings revealed that missiological training has a significant influence on trainers' family life. This aligns with the attributes listed as key essentials leading to a successful training ministry of a missionary trainer's life and ministry by a scholar. Christian maturity is one of the attributes¹³.

Finding further supports the "Be" domain of the *Know-Be-Do* outcome framework (Pioneer characteristics (spiritual maturity, discipline and commitment, confidence and strength in the lord, purposefulness and sensitivity to the spirit's guidance, zeal and giftedness etc)¹³.

Finding on research question three revealed that missiological training has significant influence on trainers' ministry skills and experience. This is obvious from the influence of missiological training on trainers' language and culture learning experiences, skills in cross-cultural evangelism and church planting, discipleship and mentor relationship skills, ability to manage people with sensitivity and wisdom and Interaction in cross-cultural and diverse situations. This aligns with the attributes listed as key essentials leading to a successful training ministry of a missionary trainer's life and ministry by a scholar. Ministry skills and experience is one of the attributes¹³. Again, finding aligns with the "Do" domain, of the *Know-Be-Do* outcome framework (Pioneer ministry skills (field-entry, evangelism, church-planting, and church-development skills)¹³.

Finding on research question four revealed that missiological training has significant influence on trainers' interdisciplinary knowledge by broadening trainers' trainers' understanding of theological, socio-political, economic, and ethnic realities, understanding local political

and social situations. Again, missiological training has significant influence on keeping trainers updated on global mission activities, and on missiological thinking and writing. Finding is supported by a list of other Training areas and expected outcomes for a trained missionary that were highlighted during an exercise that was carried out during the first consultation of mission trainers in Nigeria as. These include Church Relations (is a committed member of a church, maintains a good testimony, knows how to subject self to church etc); Cultural Anthropology (is able to analyse his own culture, is conscious of his own ethnocentricity, is informed on ethnic groups within the country, respects other cultures, knows biblical anthropology, promotes Christian transformation of culture etc); Inter-Personal Relationships (applies biblical principles to relationship, knows how to manage inter-personal conflict, maintains good family relationships, looks for relationships with other unlike self, has basic understanding of psychology, knows how to listen to others and respond appropriately etc); Cross-Cultural Communication (demonstrates a desire to know the host culture, is willing to identify with host culture, knows what is effective communication, knows how to manage culture shock, overcomes racial prejudice - solves communication problems, interprets verbal and non-verbal messages etc)¹³.

Finding for research question five, revealed the significant influence that missiological training has on trainers' vision for mission training. Findings revealed that missiological training enhances trainers' clearer understanding of *Missio-Dei*, and a shift in worldview, causing the trainers to recognise that mission is a task for all believers, and equipping for effective missionary training in different contexts. This is supported by an author's position that with a proper understanding of the biblical concept of ministry, the vision for ministry will be in line with the global program of God, Christ, and the Church. Any person's vision for ministry will be developed in line with what he/she understands to be the meaning of ministry¹⁹.

Recommendations

Based on this study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Capacity-Building for Trainers is recommended for trainers (Upskilling and personal development, Refresher courses for

- serving missionaries, Workshops, Seminars, and advanced courses in missiology to keep trainers updated on emerging trends and challenges in missions.
2. Missiological training institution should make spiritual formation a priority in training; thereby, ensuring that missiological training includes robust theological teachings focused on personal faith development, biblical knowledge, and Christ-centered living. Incorporate disciplines like prayer, fasting, meditation on Scripture, and reflective journaling into the training process. Emphasize growth in character, humility, and servant leadership as core components of Christian maturity.
 3. Enhancement of mission training curriculum by making it contextually relevant and tailoring the curriculum to the cultural, social, and ministry settings where trainers and trainees work
 4. Enhancement of the mission training curriculum with course contents from other disciplines such as Anthropology, Leadership and Management, Pastoral Psychology, among others.
 5. Lastly, trainers are encouraged to sharpen their vision by Continuing Education, access opportunities for Research.

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Preach and Heal: Mission Mandates for the Twelve in Luke 9:1-6, and the Twenty-First Century Mission Strategies of Selected Mission Agencies in Nigeria

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Abstract

Jesus was strategic in his earthly ministry by going to places to preach and heal. He went about proclaiming the good news of the kingdom and making the sick, afflicted, and oppressed whole again in their body, soul, and spirit. For continuity and the growth of the church, Jesus raised his disciples and gave them the mandates and strategies to go, preach and heal. This study explores the missionary mandates and strategies given to the Twelve in Luke 9:1-6 and their relevance to contemporary mission strategies in the twenty-first century. The passage in Luke 9 outlines Jesus' instructions to his disciples, emphasizing the dual mandate to "preach the kingdom of God" and "heal the sick." These foundational directives not only shaped the early Christian mission but also provide critical insights for modern missionary endeavors. This researcher selected five prominent mission agencies in Nigeria, reviewed their mandates and mission strategies to see their alignment with Luke 9:1-6. This paper argues that while the mission strategies in Luke 9:1-6 can be modified, the integration of preaching and healing remains fundamental for effective mission work, as it addresses both the spiritual and physical needs of people.

Keywords: Preach, Heal, Mission Mandates, Mission Strategies, Mission Agencies, The Twelve, Twenty-First Century

Introduction

Jesus called the Twelve and at a point he sent them to preach and to heal as recorded in Luke 19:1-6. He gave the mandates and the strategies to fulfill the mandates. These Twelve preached, healed and the church grew. In Acts 2 over three thousand were converted through Peter's preaching. While in Acts 3, at the Beautiful Gate, a disabled man was raised. Such instances of preaching and healing continued, and these resulted in the church growth. *This research is an attempt to understand the mandates and the strategies used by the Twelve as instructed by Jesus and compare with the twenty-first-century*

strategies for church growth. Are the mandates and the strategies in Luke 19:1-6 the same as the twenty-first-century's strategies? What are the differences in the strategies and what are the factors responsible for the differences? What is the primacy of preaching and healing to mission? These questions are answered through the interpretation of Luke 9:1-6 using hermeneutics principles, and review of vision, mission, and strategies of five selected prominent mission agencies in Nigeria.

In Luke account chapter 9, Jesus called those the author referred to as “the Twelve” together. Luke used the Markan designation “the Twelve” but does not employ the Matthean phrase “the twelve disciples” or “twelve apostles” to describe those who were called by Jesus to be sent out to proclaim the kingdom and heal those who were sick (van Aarde, 1999). van Aarde (1999) argues that “there is no historical evidence that Jesus was responsible for the concept “the Twelve” or the phenomenon “the apostles.” However, it is generally understood from the gospels that “the Twelve” refers to the twelve disciples Jesus called to be with him and that he might send them out (Mark 3:14). According to Luke 6:14-16, these are Simon Peter, Andrew, James, John, Philip, Bartholomew, Matthew, Thomas, James son of Alphaeus, Simon who was called Zealot, Judas son of James, and Judas Iscariot.

Jesus called the Twelve and they had been following him for quite some time on missions. He had taught them kingdom principles by his teaching, preaching, and performing miracles. But a time came that Jesus changed his strategy “from being the one on mission to being the one making disciples who go on mission” (Hoffman, November 24, 2013) In Luke 9:1-6 we have an instance where Jesus commissioned the Twelve to go on the mission to preach and heal.

The Mandate to Preach

The author of the book of Luke reported in chapter 9:2 that Jesus sent out the Twelve to “preach the kingdom of God.” The first mandate was to preach, and the content of what to preach was the kingdom of God. The English word *preach* or *proclaim* is translated from the Greek word *Kerusso*. “Luke 9:6 uses ‘proclaim the gospel’ (euangelizomai), but in 9:2 Luke uses ‘proclaim’ (kerusso) to describe their commissioning by Jesus” (Farrell, 1997). Writing about the Kingdom of God in Jesus’ Message, Leon Siwecki (2019) sees Jesus in the Gospel as the representative (Lk 17:20-21), the revealer (Mt 11:25-26), the champion

(Mk 3:27), the initiator (Mt 11:12), and the instrument (Mt 12:28) of the Kingdom of God. Jesus was concerned not only with salvation but with the kingdom of God as the definitive vision (Thinane, 2024). The kingdom of God is paramount to Jesus' sending out the Twelve to preach. Coming into the kingdom of God by the recipients of the gospel preached is the goal of the mandate to preach for the Twelve. The terminology and imagery of the Kingdom of God is central to the whole of Jesus's ministry and his announcement of the good news of salvation (Bredenhof, 2021). In carrying out the mandate to preach, Rinawaty and Hannas reiterate that Christian missionaries should master preaching material, various preaching types and techniques, and thereby the sermons become dynamic, biblical and meet everyone's needs.

The Mandate to Heal

When Jesus gave the mandate to heal to the Twelve, he used the Greek word *iaomai* which means to heal or cure (Kittel & Friedrich, 1985). *Iaomai* was the healing approach Jesus used almost exclusively. This was instantaneous miracle healing which involves a release of divine healing power and is often coupled with casting out demons (Virkler & Virkler, 2014). Hill (2007) raises some questions in her attempt to formulate a New Testament theology of health, sickness, and healing. She asks, "What does the Bible have to say about health, sickness, and healing? Can believers expect health and if necessary, receive healing?" She argues that the New Testament writers' theology of health, sickness and healing was shaped by the Old Testament theology, and "further molded by their by their contact with Jesus and by their personal reflections on the implications of the New Covenant." When God finished the creation, he made an assessment and saw that everything was very good. Sickness and death were not part of the "very good," but they came because of sin and the Fall (Hill, 2007). However, God is sovereign to heal all kinds of sicknesses and diseases. Reviewing the healing ministry of Jesus in the Synoptics, Hill (2007) gives the following summary:

Jesus was a healer and exorcist. Healings and exorcisms were considered an indication of spiritual power over Satan or the effects of sin. Jesus' disciples also performed exorcisms and healings. Jesus did not follow any one pattern for his healing ministry. The result of an

attempted healing was always a success, regardless of the means used. His healing ministry evoked in the crowds a sense of admiration and wondering whether Jesus was indeed the awaited Messiah. Jesus' ministry of healing was considered by the Synoptists to be the fulfillment of the Old Testament.

Healing can be medical or spiritual. Medical healing by medications or herbs can be called *healing through medicine* while the spiritual healing that comes in the name of Jesus Christ by prayer, anointing of the sick person or laying of hands can be called *healing beyond medicine* or *healing without medicine*. Spiritual healing was performed by Jesus without medication, and it was always beyond what can be explained by science through experiments or laboratory tests. This kind of healing mandate Jesus gave the twelve to go preach and perform. Kee (2005) asserts that from Jesus' time, "healing is not only the symbol, but also the substance of God's redemption of his people."

Spiritual healing was performed by the Twelve and other disciples in various forms through the name of Jesus Christ. Among the various forms of healing by the Twelve were Peter's, who spoke to the disabled beggar at the Beautiful Gate, "Silver or gold I do not have, but what I do have I give you. In the name of Jesus Christ of Nazareth, walk" (Acts 3:6). Peter held the man's right hand and helped him, and he became healed, standing strong on his feet. At another instance, Peter's shadow brought healing to many who were sicked. In Samaria, as Philip proclaimed the gospel, people listened, and the sick became healed (Acts 8:4-8). The mode of healing in the Gospels is simple and involves no empirical therapy (Kittel & Friedrich, 1985).

Medicine, miracles, and magic are the three identified means of healing sicknesses and disease. According to Kee (2005), medicine involves "diagnosis of human ailments and prescription based on a combination of theory about and observation of the body, its functions and malfunctions." Zeff (1997) explains that in the mainstream medicine the diagnosis and treatment of disease is done by a medical doctor who determines the specific nature and name of the disease before the application of various tools which are provided by science and experience to treat a condition. Whereas, naturopathic medicine emphasizes health restoration rather than disease treatment by helping the patient to create conditions for good health. Naturopathic medicine

encourages active involvement of the patient rather than the physician. Healing is operationally defined by Egnew (2005) as “the personal experience of the transcendence of suffering.” It is argued that there is no agreement among academics as to what exactly the process of healing entails. However, some elements of healing are identified by Szawarska (2020) as follows, healing actively engages the patient, it is multidimensional, creative, meaning making and it leads to restoration of balance and the acceptance of status quo by the patient.

Healing Authority of Jesus

Botha (1996) asserts that “Jesus of Nazareth, the historical person, has power over unclean spirits and a variety of illnesses, and with his power he restores people to their place in the community.” Jesus surpassed the traditional healers of the first century by his miraculous healing power that healed the sick such as the woman with twelve-year hemorrhage who could not be healed by all the physicians she consulted despite spending all she had. At the healing of a demon-possessed man in Matthew 12:28, Jesus was accused of using demonic power by the Pharisees to heal, but he asserted that his healing is by the Spirit of God. Shin (2023) declares that Jesus’ “healing ministry in the Mediterranean world was different from the sorcerers and magicians, it was based on his messianic ministry and the power of God’s Holy Spirit rather than on general medical methods.” This same authority Jesus gave to his disciples to heal in his name. Although no particular case of healing was mentioned in Luke 9 when the Twelve returned to Jesus, the demonstration of healing authority by the Twelve can later be seen from how Peter healed the disabled man at the Beautiful Gate, he said, “in the name of Jesus Christ of Nazareth, walk” and the disabled man began to walk immediately. H. C. Kee (2005) concludes that healing and other miracles reported in the gospels and Acts of the Apostles are divine confirmations of the authority of Jesus and the apostles.

Mission strategies for the Twelve in Luke 9:1-6

Some missionary strategies are derived from studying Luke 9:1-6, 10. These strategies include call into mission work, spiritual empowerment of the missionaries, education, or orientation for the missionaries, sending or mobilization to the field, and reporting to the sending authority.

1. **Call into mission work (verse 1):** The Twelve disciples had been with Jesus for some time, but a time came that he needed to send them out to preach and heal. There were other disciples of Jesus but the Twelve were specially chosen to go on mission in Luke 9. The writer of Luke used the Greek word *sugkaleo* to describe this call. *Sugkaleo* means “to call together to oneself” (Thayer's Expanded Greek Definition). Jesus called the Twelve together to himself to give them the mission mandates and the mission strategies in reaching out with the gospel. The call was to impart them with power and authority for mission. In the twenty-first century, denominational and non-denominational mission agencies play the role of sending missionaries like Jesus did by recruiting those who have been specifically called by God as missionaries and deploying them to locations wherein they can be productive (Ward, 1999). There is no mission without the called ones who will go and perform the mandates.
2. **Spiritual empowerment of the missionaries (verse 1):** The authority is needed from Jesus by the Twelve to give them courage to go, to overcome spiritual forces wherever they go to preach, and to enable them perform healing of various kinds of diseases and cast out demons like their master. The concept of power and authority in doing mission was reiterated by Jesus after his resurrection as evident in his discourse with his disciples in texts like Matthew 28:18 “*All authority in heaven and on earth has been given to me,*” Luke 24:49 “*I am going to send you what my Father has promised; but stay in the city until you have been clothed with power from on high,*” and Acts 1:8 “*But you will receive power when the Holy Spirit comes on you; and you will be my witnesses in Jerusalem, and in all Judea and Samaria, and to the ends of the earth.*” Like the Twelve, the missionaries lack power and authority in themselves to go, preach and heal. Missionaries need spiritual empowerment to perform the mandates.
3. **Education or orientation for the missionaries (verse 2):** Jesus clearly instructed the Twelve during the orientation before sending them out to preach and heal. He told them to “Take nothing for the journey.” He charged them to go by faith and not to bother about materials needs. Although the approach, “Take nothing for the journey” changed in Luke 22:35-36 because Luke 9 was a short-term mission outreach. They were also educated on how to respond

to hostility through peaceful dispositions to the host community. Evolving from Jesus' orientation to the Twelve, the twenty-first century has expanded the scope of orientation into missionary training and formal missions' education. Missionary training is organised by mission agencies, and this is more of practical than theoretical. The curriculum for the training involves strategies for evangelism and discipleship, establishing rapport across cultures, and dealing with culture shock. While formal missions' education refers to the curriculum at universities designed to contribute to the expansion of Christianity across cultures (Nehrbass, Dunaetz, & Jow, 2024). The twenty-first century mission strategy emphasizes cultural competence or cultural intelligence for cross-cultural mission (Prill, 2023).

4. **Sending or mobilisation to the field (verse 6):** Having been called, spiritually empowered, and trained on how to do mission, Jesus released the Twelve and they went to proclaim the good news and heal people. Missiological training should not take a long time to cause unnecessary delay in the mobilisation of the missionaries in the twenty-first century. While on the field, regular retraining should be organised by the mission agencies and opportunities for further formal missions' education in the university or seminary should be given to the missionaries to enable efficient performance.
5. **Reporting to the sending authority (verse 10a.):** In verse six, the Twelve left Jesus to go on the mission they were sent, but that was not enough to know whether the mandates were fulfilled until they returned and gave their reports in verse ten. Reporting to the sending authority is significant to mission work. "While some missionaries resent any accountability other than directly to God, the experiences of totally independent and free-lance missionaries have demonstrated the need for accountability" (Ward, 1999). It is therefore important to learn from the Twelve, how they reported their activities back to Jesus. Missionaries should give adequate reports of their activities to their sending mission agencies.

The Twenty-First Century Mission Mandates and Strategies

In discussing the twenty-first century mission mandates and strategies, five prominent mission agencies operating in Nigeria are selected to review their mandates, visions, and missions to see how they align with Luke 9:1-6. The selected mission agencies in Nigeria are Calvary

Ministries (CAPRO), Evangelical Missionary Society, Global Mission Board, Messiah Arena, and Nigeria Evangelical Missions Association (NEMA).

Calvary Ministries

Calvary Ministries was formerly known as Calvary Production and from that former name the acronym CAPRO was formed. This mission agency started in 1975 as a spontaneous outreach to the Muslims of Northern Nigeria beginning from Zaria and has now become an international non-denominational Missions Agency (Calvary Ministry, 2024). Her vision is to “see indigenous, autonomous and self-propagating communities of believers among unreached people groups of Africa and the rest of the World,” and her mission is to “identify unreached people groups of Africa and the rest of the World, and in partnership with the Church, mobilise, train and send workers to preach and teach the holistic Gospel of Jesus Christ until an indigenous, autonomous and self-propagating body of believers emerge.” Her strategy is embedded in the Great Commission of Jesus to his disciples in Matthew 28:19. Her community outreaches include healthcare, water, sanitation, hygiene, disaster relief, emergency response, and community church mobilization project, among other activities.

Evangelical Missionary Society

Evangelical Missionary Society (EMS) is the mission agency of the Evangelical Church winning All (ECWA). The agency envisions all nations worshipping God through Jesus Christ and her mission is to glorify God by equipping believers to holistically evangelise the world for Jesus Christ (Evangelical Missionary Society, 2024). EMS’ areas of ministry and strategies include medical, training of missionaries, school, radio ministry, and sports ministry.

Global Missions Board

The Nigerian Baptist Convention was borne out of the mission efforts of the Southern Baptist Convention and in her response to missions in Nigeria, a mission agency was formed in 1953 which later became known as the Global Missions Board of The Nigerian Baptist Convention. Her missions started among “the Unreached People in Shendam area, near Jos, in present day Plateau State” (Global Missions Board, 2024). The

agency's vision is "Reaching all nations for Christ (Matthew 28: 19a; Matthew 24: 14)" and her mission is to advance the Great Commission to all Nations through the Nigerian Baptist Convention by networking with other Great Commission Christian, such that all nations might come to the saving, worshipping and serving faith in Jesus Christ.

Messiah Arena

Messiah Arena is a Nigeria based mission agency comprises of Christian professionals. It is an interdenominational mission organisation with the vision "that none should perish" (1 Timothy 2:4). At the core of her "value offering" is salvation message, followed by free medical care, community transformation, and free welfare packages. As part of her strategies, the Messiah Arena preaches the gospel at every given opportunity, calls missionaries for mission fields, trains missionaries, and provides periodic free medical care, scholarship, and mentoring to the youths (Messiah Arena, 2024).

Nigeria Evangelical Missions Association (NEMA)

NEMA was established in 1982 to build synergy among the indigenous denominational and non-denominational mission agencies in Nigeria (Olanrewaju, 2024). NEMA has over 160 registered members across the six geo-political zones of Nigeria comprising mission agencies, denominations and para-church groups with active involvement in frontier missions. The association's vision is to see "a completed Great Commission through the active involvement of the Nigerian Church and Missions Movement in all the unreached nations of the world" (National Evangelical Missions Association, 2024). NEMA as an umbrella body for mission agencies in Nigeria is committed to increase the level of mission awareness and participation of the Nigerian Church, empowerment of the church and mission leaders, foster partnership and networking between the Nigerian Church and the Global Missions Networks. Her major role is to unite Nigerian Church and missions agencies for the completion of the Great Commission.

Discussion and Findings on the Mission Mandates and Strategies of the Selected Mission Agencies in Nigeria

Regarding the mission mandates, the five selected mission agencies emphasized fulfilment of the "Great Commission" as given in Matthew

28:19 where Jesus commissioned his disciples for world outreach with the gospel. In Luke 9:1-6, Jesus called the Twelve and sent them to the villages nearby but for the twenty-first century's mission agencies, evangelising and discipling the nations of the world are the core objectives. These agencies emphasized mostly the aspect of a mandate to go and preach in Luke 9:1-6 in their visions and mission statements than the other mandate to heal. Although pictures of medical outreaches can be seen on the websites of all the selected mission agencies showing where they organised free medical outreaches. The healing mandate given to the Twelve was purely done through the "power and authority to drive out all demons and to cure diseases" given by Jesus, whereas the twenty-first century mission agencies depict more of medical healing. The twenty-first century mission strategies as exhibited by the selected mission agencies show more alignment with the strategies in Luke 9:1-6 but with a minor variation. The major observable variation in the strategies is that none of the agencies emphasized non-involvement of money or other resources in doing missions. Obviously, all the agencies have a means of raising funds or seeking support for their works as request for partnership are made on their web pages. Meanwhile, the reason for the variation is not far-fetched, the mission exploit in Luke 9:1-6 was for a short while as the Twelve were expected by Jesus to return soon with reports of their exploits. Also, that outreach was at the elementary stage of mission outreach and further instructions would be given by Jesus later in Luke 22:35-36.

Then Jesus asked them, "When I sent you without purse, bag or sandals, did you lack anything?" "Nothing," they answered. He said to them, "*But now if you have a purse, take it, and also a bag; and if you don't have a sword, sell your cloak and buy one.*"

The strategies of not going with "a staff, bag, bread, money, or extra shirt" in Luke 9:3 changed in Luke 22:36. This latter instruction of *if you have a purse, take it, and a bag* supersedes or overrules the former instruction given to the Twelve. No doubt, the twenty-first century mission agencies cater for their missionaries and their family's needs such as accommodation, feeding, children education, and transportation on the mission fields. The twenty-first century missionaries go to the mission fields with their valuables.

Conclusion

The dual mission mandates to preach and heal were conducted by the Twelve through the power and authority given to them by Jesus. The primacy of mission mandates to preach and heal remain fundamental from Jesus to the Twelve and to the twenty-first century mission agencies and their missionaries. The selected twenty-first mission agencies' emphasis is on fulfilment of the "Great Commission" through evangelism and discipleship. These mission agencies emphasized the mandate to go and preach in Luke 9:1-6 in their visions and mission statements more than the other mandate to heal. In fulfilling the healing mandate, the twenty-first century mission agencies depict more of medical healing through medical outreaches. While doing a medical outreach is commendable, we must be deliberate in exercising the spiritual power and authority to heal in Jesus' name as it was done by the Twelve.

Jesus' strategies of calling the Twelve into mission work, empowering them spiritually, educating them on how to go, sending them to the field, and returning to give reports of their mission exploits are still effective strategies used by the twenty-first century mission agencies. The selected mission agencies recruit missionaries, train, send out to the fields, and receive reports from the missionaries. The only deviation from Luke 9 mission strategies is on the instruction not to go with "a staff, bag, bread, money, or extra shirt" (Luke 9:3). The twenty-first century mission agencies seek for supports from their partners to make provisions such as accommodation, feeding, transportation, children education, salary, and pension for their missionaries.

Irrespective of the differences between the mission strategies in Luke 9:1-6 and the twenty-first century mission strategies, the mandate to preach and heal remain sacrosanct from Jesus to the Twelve and to the twenty-first century mission agencies. We must go to preach and heal everywhere.

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Cultural Awareness, Flexibility and Mission Engagement among Field Missionaries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria

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Abstract

Cross-cultural missionaries face numerous challenges in their place of assignment, leading to high rates of attrition, ineffectiveness, and shortened tenure. The study adopted descriptive survey research design and it involved twenty (20) cross-cultural field missionaries of New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries working in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria; who were purposive sampled as workers with mission certification training experience and, due to the peculiarity of attrition within the location of their mission fields. The instrument for data collection was an interview guide with predetermined sets of closed-ended questions. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics with frequencies and percentages. Findings on cultural awareness revealed high prevalence rating as; Understanding and appreciation of the culture of the host community (100%), respect for cultural differences (100%), recognizing your own biases and stereotypes (100%), challenge your own biases and stereotypes (90%), navigated cultural misunderstanding (90%), and educate yourself in different cultural practices (90%). Again, finding further revealed the extent of flexibility; adapt to different situations (85%); adapt to different environments (90%), open to new ideas (75%), seek out opportunities to learn (90%), seek out opportunities to grow (80%), compromise and find common ground (75%) and adjust to communication style (90%). Findings suggested that cultural awareness and flexibility plays a crucial role in determining cross-cultural missionary retention, effectiveness and longevity. Findings underscore the importance of cultural awareness and flexibility in the success and longevity

of missionaries working in diverse cultural contexts. It was recommended that cross-cultural missionaries must engage in cultural immersion experiences to understand and appreciate the customs, traditions, and values of the local community. They must also be adaptable to changing circumstances and be willing to modify approaches based on local feedback. They must adjust their expectations and be prepared for unexpected challenges that may arise in a cross-cultural setting.

Keywords: Cross-Cultural Missionary, Missionary Attrition, Cultural Awareness, Flexibility, Intercultural Competence

Introduction

Intercultural competence which includes; cultural awareness and flexibility are essential skills for cross-cultural missionaries working in the context of global perspective. They allow cross-cultural missionary to effectively navigate cultural differences, communicate their message effectively and respectfully, and build trust and rapport with the local communities of their place of assignment (Sternberg, 2023). Intercultural competence (cultural awareness and flexibility) is very important for cross-cultural missionaries working in Africa, as the continent is incredibly diverse, with a wide range of cultures, languages, and customs. Without the ability to navigate these cultural differences, missionaries may struggle to build relationships with the local population of their place of assignment, understand their needs, and effectively share the gospel. Intercultural competence (cultural awareness and flexibility) is particularly essential for cross-cultural missionaries working in Nigeria. Nigeria is a country with a diverse population made up of over 250 ethnic groups, each with their own languages, customs, and traditions (Oana-Antonia, 2019). Without the ability to navigate these cultural differences, missionaries may struggle to effectively communicate with local people, build relationships, and understand their needs (Owoade, 2023).

Cross-cultural missionary attrition has been identified as a significant challenge facing the mission work and the cross-cultural missionary themselves. Missionary attrition is the rate at which cross-cultural missionaries are suddenly leaving their mission fields and going back to their various homes. Missionary attrition not only has a negative impact

on the individual missionaries and their families but also on the effectiveness of mission work as a whole (Sternberg, 2023).

Cross-cultural missionaries with intercultural competence (cultural awareness and flexibility) effective in adapting to the local culture and customs of the people they are working with, which can help to build trust and rapport with the local communities. This, in turn, can help to promote understanding and tolerance between cultures, which is essential for the success of missionary work (Alexandria, 2022).

Contextualization of Intercultural Competence and Cross-Cultural Missionary Work

Having intercultural competence as a missionary in Nigeria involves several key aspects:

- 1) Cultural Awareness:** Missionaries need to have a deep understanding of the cultural diversity and nuances within Nigeria. This includes familiarizing themselves with the language, history, traditions, and religious beliefs of the specific communities they aim to work with. This knowledge will enable them to approach their missionary work with sensitivity and respect (Sierra-Huedo & Nevado-Llopis 2022).
- 2) Adaptability:** Cross-cultural missionary work often requires flexibility and adaptability. Missionaries should be open to learning and incorporating local customs and practices into their approach. This not only helps in building trust and rapport but also shows a genuine interest in the well-being of the community. Adapting to local norms can also aid in contextualizing the message and making it more relatable to the local population (Sierra-Huedo & Nevado-Llopis 2022).

Intercultural competence is vital for cross-cultural missionaries in Nigeria. It enables them to navigate cultural differences, communicate effectively, and build meaningful relationships with the diverse population they serve. By embracing cultural awareness, developing strong communication skills, and being adaptable, missionaries can enhance their effectiveness in spreading their message and positively impacting the communities they work with (Cressy, 2021).

Indicators of Intercultural Competence: Cultural Awareness as an Indicator of Intercultural Competence

In today's increasingly globalized world, cultural awareness plays a crucial role in promoting effective communication and understanding between individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. Developing intercultural competence is vital for fostering positive relationships and collaboration across cultures (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022). The followings are the components of cultural awareness as an indicator of intercultural competence:

- 1) **Definition and Components of Cultural Awareness:** Cultural awareness refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and appreciate the values, beliefs, customs, and behaviors of different cultures. It encompasses a range of factors, including knowledge of cultural practices, empathy, open-mindedness, and self-reflection. This awareness allows individuals to approach intercultural encounters with respect and sensitivity (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022).
- 2) **Cultural Awareness as the Foundation of Intercultural Competence:** Cultural awareness is a fundamental building block for intercultural competence. It provides individuals with the necessary understanding of diverse cultural perspectives, values, and norms. Through cultural awareness, individuals can recognize and appreciate similarities and differences, which forms the basis for effective cross-cultural communication and collaboration (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022).
- 3) **Enhancing Intercultural Competence through Cultural Awareness:** Cultural awareness enhances intercultural competence in several ways:
 - a. **Improved Communication:** Cultural awareness enables individuals to adapt their communication styles, taking into account cultural nuances such as non-verbal cues, directness, and tone. This adaptability promotes effective dialogue and minimizes misunderstandings (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022).
 - b. **Enhanced Empathy:** Understanding different cultural perspectives fosters empathy, enabling individuals to appreciate alternative viewpoints and navigate diverse social contexts with sensitivity. This empathy forms the basis for building trust and forming strong intercultural relationships (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022).
 - c. **Mitigation of Stereotypes:** Cultural awareness challenges preconceived notions and stereotypes by exposing individuals to accurate information about diverse cultures. This helps break

down barriers and promotes a more inclusive and accepting mindset.

To navigate today's increasingly interconnected world, developing intercultural competence is essential. Cultural awareness serves as a foundational element for building intercultural competence. It allows for effective communication, understanding, and the ability to challenge stereotypes, ultimately fostering meaningful connections and collaborations between individuals from different cultural backgrounds. By valuing cultural awareness as an indicator of intercultural competence, we can promote a more inclusive and harmonious global society (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022).

Limitations of Cultural Awareness as an Indicator of Intercultural Competence

Intercultural competence is vital in today's globalized world, as it enables individuals to effectively navigate and communicate across different cultural contexts. However, by solely relying on cultural awareness as an indicator of intercultural competence have its own limitations (Sercu, 2023).

- 1) **Insufficient Practical Application:** Merely understanding different cultural norms, traditions, and values is not sufficient for effective intercultural communication. Practical application of this knowledge is necessary. As a scholar argues, intercultural competence involves the ability to appropriately adjust communication styles, behavior, and attitudes to suit specific cultural contexts (Sercu, 2023).
- 2) **Inadequate Understanding of Individual Differences:** Cultural awareness tends to focus on generalizations about a particular group's culture. However, it overlooks the vast diversity that exists within cultures. Neglecting individual differences and over-relying on generalizations can lead to misunderstandings and stereotyping. A researcher suggests, understanding culture on a deeper level involves recognizing the unique experiences, perspectives, and identities of individuals within a cultural group (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022).
- 3) **Limited Scope of Cultural Awareness:** Cultural awareness often concentrates on knowledge about visible cultural aspects such as language, customs, and traditions. While this understanding is valuable, it may not capture the nuanced, deeper layers of cultural identity, values, and beliefs. Two scholars working together

emphasize the importance of going beyond surface-level awareness to grasp the underlying foundations of cultural dynamics (Rodríguez-Izquierdo, 2022).

The Need for a Comprehensive Approach for Cultural Awareness as an Indicator of Intercultural Competence

While cultural awareness is unquestionably important, it alone cannot fully capture the complexity of intercultural competence. The limitations of cultural awareness include insufficient practical application, inadequate understanding of individual differences, and its limited scope. To develop true intercultural competence, individuals must also cultivate intercultural sensitivity and enhance their communication skills. By acknowledging these limitations and adopting a comprehensive approach, individuals can strive for more effective intercultural communication and understanding (Adams, A. 2019).

- 1) Intercultural Sensitivity:** Intercultural competence requires more than surface-level awareness; it necessitates intercultural sensitivity. By being mindful of cultural differences, recognizing biases, and demonstrating empathy, individuals can better adapt to various cultural contexts. Intercultural sensitivity enables individuals to understand the perspectives of others and respond appropriately (Woicolesco, et al., 2022).
- 2) Communication Skills:** In addition to cultural awareness, individuals need strong communication skills to effectively engage in intercultural interactions. Active listening, effective verbal and nonverbal communication, and the ability to navigate through conflicts are crucial. Two researchers emphasize the importance of developing these skills to enhance intercultural competence (Woicolesco, et al., 2022).

Flexibility as an Indicator of Intercultural Competence

Intercultural competence has become a vital skill in various domains, including business, education, and diplomacy. Among the many attributes associated with intercultural competence, flexibility stands out as a key indicator of one's ability to adapt and thrive in multicultural settings (Dong, et al., 2024).

- 1) Definition and Importance of Flexibility in Intercultural Competence:** Flexibility is the capacity to adjust one's thoughts,

behaviors, and perceptions in response to diverse cultural contexts. It encompasses open-mindedness, adaptability, and a willingness to embrace new and different ideas and practices. Intercultural competence relies heavily on flexibility as it allows individuals to navigate the complexities of cultural differences and build meaningful connections (Metin, 2021).

- 2) **Adaptability in Cross-Cultural Situations:** Being flexible is crucial in adapting to unfamiliar cultural practices, norms, and values. This includes adjusting communication styles, recognizing non-verbal cues, and understanding cultural nuances. By being flexible, individuals can reduce misunderstandings, bridge communication gaps, and build trust and rapport with people from different cultures (Metin, 2021).
- 3) **Openness to New Perspectives:** Flexibility also entails being receptive to diverse viewpoints and being willing to challenge one's own assumptions and biases. By embracing multiple perspectives, individuals with intercultural competence can foster understanding and collaboration across cultures. This openness leads to innovative thinking and problem-solving, contributing to both personal and professional growth (Metin, 2021).
- 4) **Emotional Intelligence and Flexibility:** Flexibility requires emotional intelligence, which involves understanding and managing emotions, both within oneself and in others. Emotional intelligence enables individuals to perceive, understand, and respond appropriately to emotional cues from different cultural backgrounds. By being flexible in emotional expression and regulation, individuals demonstrate respect and empathy, fostering stronger intercultural relationships (Metin, 2021).
- 5) **Continuous Learning and Development:** Flexibility as an indicator of intercultural competence also encompasses a commitment to continuous learning and self-reflection. Cultivating cultural sensitivity and understanding is an ongoing process that requires individuals to engage in self-directed learning, seek feedback, and reflect on their experiences. Through continuous learning, individuals can enhance their intercultural competence and adapt to ever-evolving cultural dynamics (Metin, 2021). Flexibility plays a significant role as an indicator of intercultural competence. The ability to adapt, embrace different perspectives, and actively engage in ongoing learning are core elements of

flexibility. By being flexible, individuals can successfully navigate and bridge cultural differences, leading to effective communication, collaboration, and meaningful connections with people from diverse backgrounds. Developing and honing flexibility is instrumental in fostering intercultural competence in an increasingly multicultural world (Metin, 2021).

The Limitations of Flexibility as an Indicator of Intercultural Competence

Intercultural competence refers to the ability to interact effectively and appropriately with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. It involves a range of skills, knowledge, and attitudes that enable individuals to understand, appreciate, and adapt to different cultural contexts. While flexibility is considered one of the key indicators of intercultural competence and by examining the constraints associated with flexibility, we can gain a deeper understanding of the complexity of intercultural competence (Andrea, et al, 2023).

- 1) Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity:** Flexibility alone may not guarantee cultural awareness and sensitivity. Intercultural competence goes beyond adapting to different situations; it requires individuals to have a profound understanding and empathy towards diverse cultures. Embracing cultural differences and avoiding ethnocentrism are crucial components of intercultural competence that cannot be fully captured by flexibility. Therefore, relying solely on flexibility can lead to an oversimplified understanding of intercultural competence (Andrea, et al, 2023).
- 2) Deep Cultural Knowledge:** Flexibility may also fall short in providing individuals with the necessary depth of cultural knowledge. Effective intercultural interactions often require a solid foundation of understanding cultural norms, values, beliefs, and practices. Merely adapting to different cultural contexts without adequate knowledge and understanding can result in superficial interactions or unintentional cultural misunderstandings. Thus, flexibility should be accompanied by cross-cultural knowledge to enable individuals to navigate intercultural encounters effectively (Hong, 2021).
- 3) Emotional and Communication Skills:** Flexibility does not fully address the emotional and communication skills necessary for intercultural competence. Effective intercultural communication requires individuals to be attentive listeners, skilled in managing

conflicts, and capable of navigating non-verbal cues. These skills go beyond being flexible and demand a higher level of emotional intelligence and communication competence. Hence, focusing solely on flexibility may overlook these important aspects of intercultural competence (Adams, 2019).

- 4) Cultural Sensitivity and Adaptation:** Lastly, flexibility may inadvertently reinforce cultural adaptation biases. By emphasizing flexibility alone, there is a risk of expecting individuals from non-dominant cultures to adapt and conform to the norms of the dominant culture. This can perpetuate power imbalances and hinder genuine intercultural understanding. A comprehensive indicator of intercultural competence should consider both the ability to adapt and the recognition and appreciation of diverse cultural perspectives. While flexibility is essential in intercultural communication, it is insufficient as a comprehensive indicator of intercultural competence. The limitations outlined above highlight the need for a multifaceted approach that encompasses cultural awareness, knowledge, emotional intelligence, and communication skills. By understanding, appreciating, and adapting to diverse cultures require a more nuanced approach that transcends mere adaptability. By recognizing and addressing these limitations, individuals can develop a deeper understanding of intercultural competence and contribute to more effective cross-cultural interactions (Adams, 2019).

Review of Empirical Studies

Schauer (2020) substantiated through a study on “Enhancing Cross-Cultural Missionary Retention: The Role of Cultural Awareness and Intercultural Competence” The study affirm that cross-cultural missionary work involves interaction with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. To ensure successful engagement, it is crucial for missionaries to possess cultural awareness and develop intercultural competence. Below are the modalities mentioned:

- 1) Cultural Awareness in Cross-Cultural Missionary Retention:** Cultural awareness, also referred to as cultural sensitivity, represents an individual's knowledge and recognition of their own cultural values and beliefs, as well as an appreciation of the customs and behaviors of other cultures. This awareness plays a fundamental role in cross-cultural missionary retention (Schauer, 2020).

- 2) **Enhancing Understanding:** Understanding and appreciating the cultural values and beliefs of the local community allows missionaries to build stronger relationships, thereby increasing the likelihood of retention. Cultural awareness fosters empathy and compassion, minimizing the potential for misunderstandings and conflicts (Schauer, 2020).
- 3) **Effective Communication:** Cross-cultural missionaries who possess cultural awareness can effectively navigate communication barriers, both verbal and nonverbal. By recognizing cultural nuances in communication styles, nonverbal cues, and language usage, missionaries can adapt their communication strategies to be more effective, thereby improving their ability to connect with the local community (Schauer, 2023).
- 4) **Building Trust and Relationships:** Retaining cross-cultural missionaries often relies on building trust and establishing strong relationships within the community. Intercultural competence allows missionaries to navigate cultural differences, demonstrate respect, and avoid unintentional offenses, leading to greater trust and acceptance (Schauer, 2020).
- 5) **Conflict Resolution and Adaptability:** Intercultural competence equips missionaries with skills to manage conflicts and adapt to the host culture's customs and practices (Schauer, 2020). Resolving conflicts arising from cultural clashes does promote higher retention rates by fostering a more harmonious and productive working environment (Schauer, 2023).

Papadopoulou, et al., (2022) also wrote extensively on the topic “importance of cultural awareness and intercultural competence” and ascertained that cultural awareness and intercultural competence mutually reinforce each other, contributing to improved cross-cultural missionary retention. By developing competencies in these areas, missionaries can enhance their effectiveness, job satisfaction, and overall well-being during their cross-cultural service.

Papadopoulou, et al., (2022) went further by writing that cultural awareness and intercultural competence are vital for cross-cultural missionary retention. By recognizing, respecting, and adapting to diverse cultural differences, missionaries can build stronger relationships, communicate effectively, and resolve conflicts with the local community. In this way, maintaining focus on cultural awareness and intercultural competence acts as a catalyst for successful

engagement and long-term commitment. Future studies should continue to explore and develop strategies to enhance cultural awareness and intercultural competence within the context of cross-cultural missionary work (Papadopoulou, et al., 2022).

Pavel, (2020) corroborated the arguments through the study on “flexibility and intercultural competence for cross-cultural missionary retention” by saying that successful missionary work in cross-cultural settings necessitates the cultivation of two crucial skills: flexibility and intercultural competence. The importance of these skills for missionary retention did emphasizing their role in establishing effective cross-cultural relationships and facilitating meaningful engagement with diverse communities. The modalities mentioned are as follows:

- 1) **Flexibility in Cross-Cultural Missionary Work:** Flexibility is the ability to adapt to new and changing circumstances, a trait that is particularly relevant in cross-cultural settings. Flexibility allows missionaries to adjust their approaches, perspectives, and strategies, enabling them to navigate unfamiliar cultural terrain more effectively. One key aspect of flexibility is the willingness to embrace ambiguity and uncertainty (Owoade, 2023), which allows missionaries to respond to unexpected challenges and cultural nuances with grace and understanding (Pavel, 2020).
- 2) **Intercultural Competence in Cross-Cultural Missionary Work:** Intercultural competence refers to the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to engage with diverse cultures in respectful and effective ways. This competence involves empathy, cultural sensitivity, and a capacity for effective communication. Intercultural competence equips missionaries to understand and appreciate cultural differences, fostering trust and collaboration within multicultural communities (Owoade, 2023). It also helps avoid cultural misunderstandings and conflicts that can impede missionary effectiveness (Pavel, 2020).
- 3) **The Relationship between Flexibility and Intercultural Competence:** Flexibility and intercultural competence are closely interconnected in cross-cultural missionary work. The ability to adapt and remain open-minded allows missionaries to continuously learn and enhance their intercultural competence. Flexibility enables missionaries to embrace new perspectives, challenge preconceived notions, and adjust their behavior to effectively navigate cultural diversity (Owoade, 2023). Conversely, developing intercultural

competence provides a foundation for embracing flexibility and adapting to evolving cultural realities (Pavel, 2020).

- 4) **Enhancing Cross-Cultural Missionary Retention:** Flexibility and intercultural competence significantly contribute to missionary retention in cross-cultural contexts. The ability to navigate cultural challenges and maintain effective relationships fosters long-term commitment and sustainable engagement. Missionaries with higher flexibility and intercultural competence exhibited greater resilience, adaptability, and overall satisfaction in their work (Owoade, 2023). By honing these skills, missionaries can build stronger connections with the communities they serve, leading to improved sustained impact. Flexibility and intercultural competence are essential skills for cross-cultural missionary retention. They empower missionaries to adapt to new cultural landscapes, build meaningful relationships, and effectively engage with diverse communities (Owoade, 2023). The interconnectedness of flexibility and intercultural competence highlights the importance of cultivating both skills simultaneously. By developing and nurturing these qualities, missionaries can navigate the complexities of cross-cultural missionary work, leading to increased retention, improved effectiveness, and greater long-term impact (Owoade, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

The research problem identified is the relationship between intercultural competence and cross-cultural missionary retention. The gaps in the literature that was addressed in this thesis include a lack of comprehensive studies on how intercultural competence influences missionary retention rates. The key objectives of the study are to ascertain how cultural awareness impacts missionary retention and ascertain the importance of flexibility in enhancing missionary longevity. Focusing on these objectives and addressing the gaps in the existing literatures, the aim of this paper has provided valuable insights into the relationship between intercultural competence and cross-cultural missionary retention. This research has the potential to enhance the reader's understanding of the factors that influence missionary success in diverse cultural environments and inform strategies to improve retention rates in cross-cultural missionary work.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine cultural awareness, flexibility and missions engagement of field missionaries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. ascertain the level of awareness of the culture of the host communities among field missionaries involved in cross-cultural missions of New Life Gospel for all Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria.
- ii. ascertain the extent to which field missionaries are flexible in their cross-cultural missions engagement under New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. what is the level of awareness of the culture of the host communities among field missionaries involved in cross-cultural missions of New Life Gospel for all Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria.
- ii. what is the extent to which field missionaries are flexible in their cross-cultural missions engagement under New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria.

Methodology

This research adopted descriptive survey research design. This affords the researcher in gathering data from a large number of respondents on events or activities that have taken place in retrospect. The design is fit for the study because the researcher is only interested in gathering data on respondents' experiences. New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries comprised of 12 Zones in Nigeria with the Headquarters at International Camping Ground located at Oloola, in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The population for this study comprised all the fifty (50) cross-cultural missionaries of New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries working in Abia and Anambra states in Nigeria. The cross-cultural missionaries working in Abia and Anambra State mission fields of the New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries were of two categories namely: 1) those without formal training; and 2) those with mission certification training experiences. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to select twenty

(20) cross-cultural missionaries (those working with mission certification training experience under the New Life Gospel for all Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria), due to the peculiarity of attrition of their mission fields (Details has presented in Table 1). The instruments for the data collection for this research are questionnaire and interview. A predetermined set of open-ended questions were used to collect data from the respondents, through interviews. The instrument called; Intercultural Competences and Cross-cultural Missionary Retention Question (InCoCcMiReQ) was developed by the researcher and used to gather data for the study. The instrument was completed by the twenty (20) cross-cultural missionaries (with mission certification experience training experiences) working in the Abia and Anambra State in Nigeria. The researcher, in an attempt to reduce the numbers of non-respondent and to enhance proper data collection, used the interview guide to carry out the interview with the participants, for the data collection for this research.

Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) and thematic analysis.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents

S/N	Variable		Frequencies	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	20	100.0%
		Female		0%
2	Age	10 – 20 Years	0	0%
		21 – 30 Years	0	0%
		31 – 40 Years	0	10 %
		41 – 50 Years	5	30 %
		51 – 60 Years	9	25 %
		61 – 70 Years	6	35 %
3	Year of Service	0 – 5 Years	0	0 %
		6 – 10 Years	1	5 %
		11 – 20 Years	4	20 %
		21 – 30 Years	10	50 %
		31 – 40 Years	4	20 %

4	Marital Status	41 – 50 Years	1	5%
		Married	20	100%
5	Mission Certification	Single	0	0%
		Divorce	0	0%
		With Mission Certification	10	50%
		Experience		
6	Working Status	Without formal training	10	50%
		Full-Time	20	100%
7	Nationality	Part-Time	0	0%
		Nigeria	20	100%
		Non-Nigeria	0	0%

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork 2024

Table 1 presents the demographic information of the respondents. The table revealed that the gender of the respondents was only male with 100%; and it also revealed that the age range distribution of the respondents, the table revealed that 10 % were of 31 – 40 years, while 30 % were of 41–50 years and 25 % were 51–60 years, and 35 % were 61–70 years respectively. In addition, the table also revealed the years of service of the respondents: 50% of the respondents were of 21-30 years of service, 20% were of both 11-20 & 31-40 years of service, 5% were of both 6–10 & 41-50 years of service respectively. The table also revealed that the marital status of the respondents was only married with 100%. The table revealed that the Mission Certification of the respondents was 50% with Mission Certification Experience and 50% without formal training respectively. The table also revealed that the working status of the respondents was 100% working on full-time basis only and that all the respondents were 100% nationality of Nigeria.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Results and discussion of findings are presented according to the research questions as follows:

Research Question One: What is the level of awareness of the culture of the host community of the mission field of cross-cultural missionaries in New Life Gospel for all Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria?

Table 2: Level of awareness of the culture of the host community of the mission field of cross-cultural missionary in New Life Gospel for all Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria

S/N	Statements	Yes	No	Not Sure	Remarks
1	Do you actively sought to understand and appreciate a culture different from your own?	20 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	Very High
2	Do you demonstrate respect for cultural differences in your daily interactions with others?	20 (100.0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0.0%)	Very High
3	Are you able to recognize your own biases and stereotypes when engaging with people from different cultures?	20 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	Very High
4	Are you able to challenge your own biases and stereotypes when	18 (90.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (10.0%)	Very High

	engaging with people from different cultures?				
5	Have you successfully navigated a cultural misunderstanding or miscommunication ?	18 (90.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (10.0%)	Very High
6	Is it necessary to educate yourself about different cultural practices, traditions, and customs?	18 (90.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (10.0%)	Very High

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork 2024

Table 2 presents finding on research question one with regards to the level of cultural of field missionaries' of New Life Gospel for all Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria. The exhibited cultural awareness includes ability to recognize and understand the different customs, beliefs, and practices of various cultural groups. Table 4.2 show the level awareness of the culture of the host communities among field missionaries involved in cross-cultural missions of New Life Gospel for all Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria. Table 2; revealed that the Understanding and appreciation of culture (100%), Respect for cultural differences (100%), Recognizing your own biases and stereotypes (100%), Challenge your own biases and stereotypes (90%), navigated cultural misunderstanding (90%), and educate yourself in different cultural practices (90%). Therefore, the mean of the percentages is $=100+100+100+90+90+90 = 570/6 = 95\%$. Finding on research question one revealed that there is high level (95%) of awareness of the culture of the host communities among field missionaries involved in cross-cultural missions of New Life Gospel for All Nations ministries in Abia and Anambra states in Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What is the extent of flexibility among the cross-cultural missionaries of New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria?

Table 3: The extent of flexibility among the cross-cultural missionaries of New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria

S/N	Statements	Yes	No	Not Su	Remarks
1	Can you adapt to different situations with ease?	17 (85%)	0 (0%)	3 (15%)	Very High
2	Can you adapt to different environments with ease?	18 (90%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	Very High
3	Are you open to new ideas on how to handle unexpected changes or disruptions to your plans?	15 (75%)	0 (0%)	5 (25%)	Very High
4	Do you actively seek out opportunities to learn outside of your comfort zone?	18 (90%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	Very High
5	Do you actively seek out opportunities to grow outside of your comfort zone?	16 (80%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	Very High
6	Are you able to compromise and find common ground when faced with conflicting opinions?	15 (75%)	1 (5%)	4 (20%)	Very High
7	Can you adjust your communication style	18 (90%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	Very High

to effectively interact
with people from
diverse backgrounds
or cultures?

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork 2024

Table 3 presents finding on research question two with regards to the extent of flexibility among the cross-cultural missionaries of New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra States, Nigeria. The extent of flexibility includes ability to adapt and adjust easily to new situations or changes.

Table 3 show the extent to which field missionaries are flexible in their cross-cultural missions engagement under New Life Gospel for All Nations Ministries in Abia and Anambra states, Nigeria. The table revealed that Adapt to different situations (85%), Adapt to different environments (90%), Open to new ideas (75%), Seek out opportunities to learn (90%), Seek out opportunities to grow (80%), Compromise and find common ground (75%), and Adjust your communication style (90%). Therefore, the mean of the percentages is = $85+90+75+90+80+75 = 495/6 = 82.5\%$.

Finding on research question two revealed that there is very high (82.5%) flexibilities among the field missionaries engagement that are involved in cross-cultural mission under New Life Gospel for All Nations ministries in Abia and Anambra states in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Finding on research question one revealed that there is high level (95%) of awareness of the culture of the host communities of field missionaries involved in cross-cultural missions of New Life Gospel for All Nations ministries in Abia and Anambra states in Nigeria. Further, finding from the oral interview conducted also aligned with the finding on research question one, as its in agreement with the comments of respondents, that the missionaries has gotten a high level of cultural awareness (i.e.) they actively sought to understand and appreciate a culture different from their own; demonstrate respect for cultural differences in their daily interactions with others; able to recognize their own biases and stereotypes when engaging with people from different cultures; able to

challenge their own biases and stereotypes when engaging with people from different cultures; successfully navigated a cultural misunderstanding or miscommunication, and find it necessary to educate themselves about different cultural practices, traditions, and customs.

Finding on research question one is in congruent with (Schauer, 2023), who wrote that cultural awareness, also referred to as cultural sensitivity, represents an individual's knowledge and recognition of their own cultural values and beliefs, as well as an appreciation of the customs and behaviors of other cultures. Thus, awareness plays a fundamental role in cross-cultural missionary retention Papadopoulou, et al., (2022). Finding on research question two revealed that there is very high (82.5%) flexibilities among the field missionaries engagement that are involved in cross-cultural mission under under New Life Gospel for All Nations ministries in Abia and Anambra states in Nigeria. Again, the oral interview conducted aligned with the finding on research question two, as its in agreement with the comments of respondents, that the missionaries has gotten a high extent of flexibility (i.e.) they can adapt to different situations with ease; can adapt to different environments with ease; open to new ideas on how to handle unexpected changes or disruptions to their plans; open to new ideas on how to handle unexpected changes or disruptions to their plans; actively seek out opportunities to learn outside of their comfort zone; actively seek out opportunities to grow outside of their comfort zone; able to compromise and find common ground when faced with conflicting opinions; and can adjust their communication style to effectively interact with people from diverse backgrounds or cultures. This has also revealed the reasons for them still been remaining at their places of assignment as at the time the researcher conducted the interview. The writings of Owoade (2023) and Pavel (2020) aligned with the finding in research question three, that, successful missionary work in cross-cultural settings necessitates the cultivation of two crucial skills: flexibility and intercultural competence. Owoade, (2023) and Papadopoulou, et al., (2022) also wrote on the importance of these skills for missionary retention, emphasizing their role in establishing effective cross-cultural relationships and facilitating meaningful engagement with diverse communities

Conclusion

The research findings suggest that intercultural competence (cultural awareness and flexibility) plays a crucial role in determining cross-cultural missionary retention. The findings underscore the importance of these factors in the success and longevity of missionaries working in diverse cultural contexts. These findings did inform training programs and support systems aimed at improving missionary retention rates in cross-cultural settings. The results indicated that missionaries who possess strong intercultural skills (cultural awareness and flexibility) are more likely to succeed in their roles and stay committed to their missions. These insights emphasize the importance of prioritizing intercultural training and support systems to enhance missionary retention, effectiveness and longevity of missionaries working in diverse cultural contexts in cross-cultural settings.

Recommendations

For cross-cultural missionaries to enhance intercultural competence and improve missionary retention: By prioritizing cultural awareness and flexibility, cross-cultural missionaries can enhance their intercultural competence, foster meaningful connections with the local community, and ultimately contribute to improved missionary retention, effectiveness and longevity of missionaries working in diverse cultural contexts in cross-cultural settings.

- 1)** Cross-cultural missionary must engage in cultural immersion experiences to understand and appreciate the customs, traditions, and values of the local community. They must attend language classes to communicate effectively and show respect for the native language. The field missionaries must also study the history and socio-cultural dynamics of the local community to grasp the context in which they will be operating.
- 2)** Cross-cultural missionary must be adaptable to changing circumstances and be willing to modify approaches based on local feedback. The field missionaries must embrace uncertainty and be open to trying new methods of engaging with the community. They must adjust their expectations and be prepared for unexpected challenges that may arise in a cross-cultural setting.

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Understanding Biblical Sexuality from an African Traditional Cultural Perspective with Reference to Iwoland

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Abstract

Human sexuality can be defined as whole range of physical, emotional, mental, social and spiritual expressions of being male or female. Sexual intercourse is expressed by various terms or verbs and euphemisms in the Old Testament. In the contemporary society, sexual immoralities have come from permissive societies under the garb of human rights and freedom. The biblical data with respect with other biblical materials share same common traits with Africa waging war against sexual immoralities. Iwoland like any other African society treats sex with utmost respect owing to the recognition of the fact that it is divinely ordained for the purpose of procreation for the race. In order to ensure justice and high moral standard, Iwo established some taboos and covenants, abrogating or prohibiting some undesirable actions (with serious appeal to their gods, spirit forces and ancestors) and with stiff curses for any breach of those covenants/taboo. It is concluded that sex is not necessarily wrong in itself. Yet not all sex is physically or spiritually beneficial. The fact that people know that certain acts destroyed their relationship with the divine, should make one aware that God does reveal Himself to humanity. It is therefore recommended that people (Christians) should live for God and not for sexual enjoyment. It is unethical to rejoice in the gift of God and yet neglect the giver. Hence, it is high time proper understanding of sexual purity via religion is promoted.

Keywords: Human Sexuality, Sexual Purity, Sexual Intercourse, African, Iwoland

Introduction

One of the major and current issues of interest, concern and debate in our present world is sex and sexuality. Sex is the Physical activity between two people in which they touch each other's sexual organs, and which may include sexual intercourse. It is the creation of God and a very big subject in the Bible. Sexuality according to the oxford Dictionary is

the feelings and activities connected with a person's sexual desires. Hence, Human sexuality can be defined as whole range of physical, emotional, mental, social and spiritual expressions of being male or female. By referring to sex and sexuality in this study, it means not to focus on sex alone but also our growing relationship to each other in society and as well as our relationship with the creator. In this light, sex is examined as a whole in the light of Biblical revelation and from African perspective.

The biblical foundation for understanding human sexuality is found in the first two chapters of the Bible. Genesis 1 and 2 deal directly and extensively with human sexuality. The profound portrayal of God's original design for human sexuality at the beginning of the Bible constitutes the foundation for the rest of the narrative and discourse on human sexuality and encapsulates the fundamental principles of a theology of sexuality. In this case two aspects of sexuality may be identified:

Firstly, the aspect of sexuality that relates to our being male and female. This has to do with intuitive knowledge and recognition of what manhood and womanhood are made of. In the clause concerning human kind's creation as male and female in Gen. 1:27, it is noted first of all, that sexual differentiation is presented as a creation by God. The sexual distinction between male and female is fundamental to what it means to be human. To be human is to live as a sexual person. A Scholar put it this way, "we cannot say man without having to say male or female and also male and female. Man exists in this differentiation, in this duality" According to biblical text, the word אָדָם "*ha'adam*" means "the human" and not "man" in the sense of male gender as some translations put it. It is a generic term meaning "human person" or "humanity". It is observed that sexuality is distinct from gender yet intimately linked to it. It is the social construction of a biological drive. However, human sexuality, understood in this sense, excludes sexual intercourse, but rather that the two sexes live in mutual connectedness and understanding of each other. Hence, the Edenic paradigm of human sexuality finds expression in a heterosexual relationship and remained the norm throughout the canonical Old Testament scriptures.

The second aspect of human sexuality has to do with the knowledge of sex. The scripture refers to this type of knowledge as

“knowing” יָדָע , (*yada*) in Hebrew Bible, which obviously refers to sexual intercourse. Adam, in this context, was referred to as knowing his wife and she conceived (Gen. 4:1).

Sexuality in the Old Testament

Sexual intercourse is expressed by various terms or verbs and euphemisms in the Old Testament. These include among others: for Godly sexual intercourse, the verb used is usually “to know” (*yada*). The verb can have reference to the man as subject (e.g Gen 4:1, 17, 25, 24:16; 38:26, Judges 19:25), woman as object (e.g Gen.19:22; 21:11), the theological significance of *yada* as a term for sexual intercourse is discussed in connection with the first usage of this term in a sexual sense in Gen. 4:1. Bo’el “to go into” (Gen. 6:4; 16:2, 4; 19:31; 29:21, 23, 30; 30:3; Josh 15:18; Judg. 16:1; 2 Sam. 3:7, 12, 24; 16:2; 22; Eze 17:44; Ps 51:2; 1 Chr. 2:21, 7:23 etc). For illicit sexual relations, the terminology includes “to approach.” (*qarab or nagas*), e.g *qarab*: Gen 20:4-6; Lev. 18:6, 14, 19, 20:16; Deut 22:14; Ezek 18:6, *nagas*: Exo 19:15. *sakab'im*; “to lie with” (Gen 19:32-35; 26:10; 30:15; 16:34:2; Exo 22:16; 15:18, 33; 19:20; Num. 5:13, 19; Deut 22:22, 23; 1 Sam. 2:22; 2 Sam 11:4; 11:11; Ezek 23:8 etc. For reference to homosexuality and bestiality: Lev. 18:22; Exod 22:18 (ET 22:19) Deut 27:21. *Yada* “always refers to heterosexual coitus” whereas *sakab* refers to homosexual, bestial, and heterosexual unions. *Natan sekobet*, “use (one’s) penis for sex”, e.g lev.18:20 should be translated, “you shall not use your penis for sex” (Milgrom, Leviticus 17 – 22, 1550., Lev. 18:23; 20:15; Num 5:20) and the further related terminology “lie ... with a woman” (Lev 18:22) or emission of semen, lit., “lying of seed” (Lev. 15:18). Other euphemism related to sexual relationship implied in the expression “become one flesh” (Gen. 2: 24) and is sometimes connoted by the verbs “to love” (*ahab/aheb*), e.g. Gen 24:67; 1Kings 11:1; Ezek 16:37. The emphasis of this term when used of sexual intercourse, is more on the experiencing and desiring of sexual relations than on the act itself. Sometimes a distinction of meaning is completed by using the active form rather than the stative, and the Hebrew word for “to take (a woman/wife)” is *laqah*, (Gen 34:2; Exod 2:1; 2Sam 11:4). The clause *gala 'erwat*, “uncover the nakedness of” is used to describe incontinent sexual intercourse (Lev 18:6-17; 20:18; Ezek 22:10) as well as other illicit sexual intercourse (Lev 18:18-19). The verb

raba, is used for the sex act of a human female with an animal (bestiality), or of an animal with another animal. The verb is probably an Aramaic loan word meaning “to copulate” (Lev 18:23; 20:16; cf 19:19). The word “*to’eba*” is the only term used in both Leviticus 18:22 and in 20:13 to describe homosexuality among the other vices. Targums directly link Gen. 19 with Leviticus 18 and 20. Ezekiel identifies the sin of Sodom as “abomination” (*to’eba*) in addition to other vices (16:49-50). The use of “abomination” (*to’eba*) and other phrases in 1 Kings 14:24 identifies the verse with the unmistakable prohibitions of sodomy in the code of Holiness in Leviticus 18:22 and 20:13.

Furthermore, the creation pattern of heterosexual human relationships in Edenic paradigm remained the norm throughout the canonical Old Testament scriptures. The narrative of human existence outside Eden begins with an affirmation of sexual intercourse (Gen. 4:1) as part of the created order, and to be enjoyed and celebrated between man and woman not to be linked in any way with divine sexual activity or public rituals of the cults and with a clear indication that the method of the original creation in Gen. 1-2 was the divine word and not by sex between the gods.

In contrast with the Israelite conception of sex as a creation ordinance and of a monotheistic God beyond the polarity of sex, the Ancient Near East, in particular, the Mesopotamian religions abounded with both male and female deities, and their myths often described the creation and continuing fertilities as occurring by means of sex among these deities. Sexual immorality linked with the pagan fertility. For instance, Cult rituals formed an integral part of the sin at Baal of peor, as with the worship of the golden calf at Sinai. However, in the Mosaic legal material, it becomes evident that the Biblical legislation formally rejects ritual sex in harmony with the perspective that has emerged from the golden-calf and Baal of Peor narratives. Hence, Deuteronomy 23:18 specifically forbids an Israelite from becoming a temple prostitute.

Also, the practice of plural marriage in particular, polygyny, was acknowledged and accepted within the law codes. For instance, the Babylonian Code of Hammurabi (ca. 1700 B C) acknowledged the practice of polygyny, allowing for a husband to take a concubine if his wife was infertile (as in the case of Abraham) or to take a second wife if his first wife became deceased or tried to obtain a divorce by means of public scandal. In the patriarchal period, there are several biblical

examples of plural marriages in terms of polygyny. Although these biblical narratives provide no explicit verbal condemnation of this practice, the narratives present each account in such a way as to underscore a theology of disapproval. None of the pentateuchal legislation concerning marital forms commands polygamous relationships, although remarriage after a man's first wife died is allowed.

In addition, A Scholar offers a survey of customs and traditions regarding family values and sexuality in the Ancient Middle East and biblical time. He presents the conventional view point that patriarchal hospitality was so highly regarded that it might override the strict considerations of women's chastity. The host would thus sacrifice the chastity of his wife, mistress or unmarried virginal daughters to safeguard his guest's honour and protection. Genesis 19 and Judges 19 present two cases in which virginal daughters and one's wife are offered to outsiders when the protection and honour of a guest are at stake. He thus claims that the custom of sexual hospitality practiced in the region sheds a different light on the dichotomy of patriarchal code versus female chastity. This custom which has been reported from various Arabian tribes, throws additional light on the mores and the relative evaluation of hospitality versus female chastity which constitutes the background of the sexual incidents described in Genesis 19 and Judges 19. A religious conviction impends on the custom. The tribes that practiced it believed that if they failed to perform the rite, nature would show its displeasure by way of a catastrophe. This belief connects sexual hospitality to cultic mysteries that propagate magical correspondence between fecundity cults, nature and divinity, one could categorize sexual among customs of sacred or cultic sexuality. The custom seems inherently male oriented as it concerns a situation of patriarchal hospitality in which female chastity is waived for the pleasure of a male guest. However, some aspects of the custom favour a woman's interest. Both the women and the guest concerned have to comply and neither may refuse the other. The guest must sleep with the hostess, disregarding her age or appearance and vice versa.

In general, Sexual hospitality and sacred sexuality challenge two major objectives of patriarchal dominance as presented in the Hebrew Bible: pre-nuptial intercourse and adultery. Confluent customs of fertility like sexual hospitality and sacred render pre-nuptial intercourse and

adultery imperative. Reversibly, the Mosaic constitution outlaws them. The Mosaic constitution targeted the abolition of these rites, and the Hebrew God alone claimed the objectives of fertility of women and Land.

Moreover, it has already been generally accepted that cults of sacred sexuality were practiced in the Ancient Near East and among the Israelites to various degrees. To this, the prophets unwittingly served as authentic reporters (Hosea 1-4, Ezekiel 16, 22, Jeremiah 3:2-3, 7:18, 44:15-20, 26). The fact that it was forbidden and vehemently opposed speaks for an early cultic history and the irresistible influence of neighbouring cultures.

However sexual hospitality could have thus been practiced alongside with other fecund templates in the peninsula as well as in ancient Israel even if sexual hospitality as such was not practiced among the Israelites themselves, it could still surface in the Hebrew Bible as a literary theme representing the custom practiced by neighbouring cultures in the Arabian Peninsula.

Biblical Hermeneutics in Typical African Societies

In contemporary society, sexual immoralities have come from our permissive societies under the garb of human rights and freedom. We are aware of several complications arising from indiscriminate sex, some of which are threats to human existence, the reality of HIV/AIDS and other sexually transmitted diseases; perversions of sex in forms of homosexuality, lesbianism, oral sex, same-sex marriage; instability of marriage and homes, divorce; rape, polyandry, polygyny, to mention but a few. Issues and problems arising from indiscriminate sex are not only growing in Africa, as elsewhere in the world, they are becoming more and more complex.

The relevance of biblical hermeneutics can provide enriching insights and tools for application in Africa if it takes African heritage and experience of marriage and sex seriously. However, while the presupposition that African world view comes close to the Biblical world especially of the Old Testament is a fact, it is to be noted however that there are certain congruencies as well as divergences between the two world views:

The biblical data with respect to Holiness code as is with other biblical material share same common traits with Africa waging war against

sexual immoralities. A few highlights would therefore suffice. Marriage in the Old Testament and in African society was both a social and religious institution. It has been noted that marriage in typical African societies was not only a social institution, but a religious one. It was a family, clan and community affair. That explains why transgression of marriage laws affected the entire family, clan or community. Marriage was for procreation, spiritual, protection, pleasure, and security.

Both the holiness code and African tradition had laws and sections specifically related to marriage and sex, while God provided the standards and punishment for marriage and sex, African community drew taboos and sanctions to marriage and sex from gods, goddess, divinities, deities and ancestors. The punishments share same commonalities such as death, hunger, excommunication, social stigma and cutting of such families from the people.

In both Old Testament and African society, virginity was upheld highly as sexual promiscuity was an abomination. Incest, homosexuality, adultery and bestiality were “abomination”. Unwanted pregnancies and bastards were not accepted in both societies. Betrothal did not allow for what is called “trial marriage”. Like in Holiness code, marriage in Africa was held in high esteem and was to be safe guarded, but the requirements allowed for some abuses in some cases. The standard of virginity held in Old Testament seems to be stricter and found force in the covenant relationship with God than that of Africa.

In Old Testament, the man was allowed some freedom in adultery cases while the woman was more vulnerable. This was also typical of the African society too. Homosexuality was also abhorred in Holiness code just as in Africa. It was rare as incest and gang rape were discouraged.

Several terms and euphemisms are used in both Holiness code and African society to refer to sexual union or sexual intercourse. Talking openly about sex and naming sexual organs was a taboo in both societies. The acts of circumlocution are often engaged in order to avoid a direct reference to a sexual act or organ. Both societies do not have sexual relations with woman during menstruation (niddah) or with a bleeding woman as a result of child birth or disease.

Both societies made levirate marriage a necessity. A levirate marriage legislated for in Deuteronomy 25:5-10 was meant to preserve the homogeneity of the family, preserve the name of its male members, safeguard the family estate and ensure the welfare of the widow (Gen.

28; Ruth 4). It was therefore meant not only to provide an heir but also to prevent dispute and litigation which would be more likely to occur if a widow were to marry outside the family.

While the biblical holiness code measure shares some common traits with the African traditional measure, it is noted however that there are also certain divergences between the two. For instances, the concept of “social sex” found in African society was foreign to Holiness code and the Old Testament generally. Also, the concept of “Cohabitation” which is called “trial marriage” which has become an accepted social custom today in Africa is strange to the Holiness code and Old Testament.

The rate of homosexuality which was in Leviticus is very few in Africa. This is found among down-trodden and the rich who have elevated it to a level of ritual, in search of fortunes such as power, money and fame. Similarly, lesbianism (female – female sex) is also known among girls who belong to the cults and the high-class ladies in the society.

However, it is instructive to note that marriage in the Old Testament revelation is no model for a doctrine of marriage.” The imperfections and examples of marriage and sex abuse in the Old Testament make it inadequate to provide the basis for formulation of any theology on marriage and sex in Africa.

Sex and Sexuality in Iwoland

Iwoland is situated in the western area of Osun State, Nigeria. The ancient town is located mid-way between two capital cities, Osogbo and Ibadan. Iwo is situated at a distance of about 44 kilometres from Ibadan, 36 kilometres from Oyo and 48 kilometres from Osogbo. The Iwo indigenes and the adjoining towns and villages are one of the several Yoruba-speaking groups in Osun State claiming historical relationship with Ile-Ife, the traditional home of all the Yoruba. These people had to leave Ife in order to free themselves from the socio-political insecurity, which pervaded Ife then. They determined not to return to Ife and prepared to remain at their new abode call Iwo which literally means “*Kasimaawoo*” “let us keep watch if the new abode would be prosperous for habitation.” The town is surrounded by more than twenty-five towns and villages which have been divided into official three Local Government Areas; they are Iwo, Ayedire and Ola-Oluwa. Iwoland is populated by Muslims and Christians with meagre Traditional religions.

Iwo based on its religious mentality about sex, forbids adultery, homosexuality, masturbation, lesbianism, incest, to mention but a few. These are not only taken as sexual immoralities, they are taken also as sins against God on the one hand, and the society on the other hand. Thus, anyone who commits any of these offences will be ostracized. Anyone quilt of incest, bestiality and homosexuality will be excommunicated. The following measures are taken in Iwo to avoid the misuse of sex, which include:

Cultural taboos: Societies across the world place high premium on sexual purity. This is also true of Iwo which has taboos, norms, values and rules on sexual practices. The Iwo like any other African society treats sex with utmost respect owing to the recognition of the fact that it is divinely ordained for the purpose of procreation for the race. In order to ensure justice and high moral standard, Iwo established some taboos and covenants, abrogating or prohibiting some undesirable actions (with serious appeal to their gods, spirit forces and ancestors) and with stiff curses for any breach of those covenants/taboo.

G.P. Murdock was right when he said,

“All societies have faced the problem of reconciling the need of controlling sex with that of giving it adequate expression, and all have solved it by some combination of cultural taboos, permissions and injunctions... sex behaviour is specifically enjoined by obligatory regulations where it appears directly to sub serve the interest of society.”

As a result of this, the Iwo accepts the act of sex as a natural need. To protect against sexual abuse, Iwo culture enjoins men and women to marry one another. Unwanted pregnancies and bastards were not accepted and betrothal did not allow for “trial marriage”. In respect the private parts, they do not call male and female private parts by their real biological names. They call them names that people would not easily associate with sex. Hence, talking openly about sex and naming sexual organs was a taboo. It is in the light of this fact that marriage is practiced and honoured in Iwo town.

Abstinence: The Iwo attitude to sex was firmly placed in the Institution of marriage. They consider the proper use of sex to be sacred and must therefore be safe guarded. Two things are necessary before marriage, abstinence from sexual intercourse and some degree of sublimation of the instinct of sex. In fact, Iwo culture teaches the need

for men to be chaste during puberty rites. Puberty rites geared towards educating the younger ones. Iwo society does not condone fornication and adultery, instead they encourage virginity which was a mark of honour to the girl and her parents especially the mother, when the girl was “found at home” by her husband on their maiden night. However, while the culture stipulates that, the girl ought to be chaste, it is silent on the part of the male. This is not because man should not be chaste, but because women are more vulnerable to sexual related diseases than men.

Punitive measures: Sexual offences were taken seriously in Iwo town. Various punitive measures were taken against offenders of sexual laws. Punishment measure like the payment of fines, public flogging and stigmatization served as a deterrent to others would-be violators of sexual taboos. Fornication and adultery are abhorred and adequate punitive measures are meted out to violators. For instance, women suspected of committing adultery were tried and if they were guilty they would be put to shame. Where pregnancy occurred as a result of adultery, the culprit was punished by paying fine. Also, sex before marriage leading to pregnancy was a disgrace and had to be punished. Hence these values and ethics on sex were safely guarded and made Iwo society to be morally sound.

Magical Medicine: To caution people from engaging in promiscuity, the society made provision for magical medicine known as *Magun*, meaning “don’t climb” or “*teso*” which is placed on a female to discourage promiscuity. Whenever it is placed on a woman, any man who has a sexual intercourse with her will suffer one injury or the other and most times, death. According to Ogunsakin-Fabarebo, there are over thirty-five types of *magun*.

Levirate marriage: Levirate marriage makes a woman an object that could be passed on within the family fold. It is an attempt to care for the widow and the offspring. It preserves the homogeneity of the family, preserves the name of its male members, safeguard the family estate and ensure the welfare of the widow. In Iwo town, Levirate marriage was therefore meant not only to provide an heir but also to prevent dispute and litigation which would be more likely to occur if a widow were to marry outside the family.

However, the adoptions of alien’s values i.e. westernization have produced a lot of crisis and effects that are currently manifesting in the society today. The abandonment of the Iwo ethics on the matter of sex

has brought about sexual immoralities such as promiscuity, prostitution, and rape in the society. Orhunger rightly captures the situation at Iwoland when he says “foreign culture is copied wrongly and the local ones forgotten”

Conclusion

From the look of things, it is seen that sex is a secular matter. But the fact, we need to understand from the outset, is that as far as Africans are concerned, sex is interpreted to have spiritual flavour. It is in the light of this that sex today is not only a social issue, but also a theological one, and discussing it is very important, given the spread of STIs in our continent generally, and particularly in Nigeria. The problems that often arise as a result of sex abuse.

However, in many cases, Africans are similar to prohibitions found in the Bible. It is clear from what has been said above that sex is not necessarily wrong in itself. Yet not all sex is physically or spiritually beneficial. The fact that these people knew that certain acts destroyed their relationship with the divine, should make us aware that God does indeed reveal Himself to humanity. Paul makes this exact point when he says that the requirements of the law of God are written in people’s heart (Rom. 2:13-15). Therefore, sexual purity, which seem to be full of ‘do not’s’ is reality of good news. It is the path we must tread if we are to experience life in all its fullness.

Recommendations

1. Sexual pleasure is a gift from God and as a result it must not be rejected or shunned, the moment it is carried out with the fear of the Lord. Christians should derive motivation from this and seek to be more positive as they live. Self-discipline, prudence and moderation are God’s requirements as Christians enjoy their sexual lives that are amazing gifts from God.
2. The “Sexual ethical teaching” dug out from Religion, in this work makes this work unique. It is ethical for human beings to enjoy sexual life but it is not ethical to be unethical in their sexual dispositions. Consequently, Christian couples must be available for one another. They should not expose their partners to sexual temptations. God’s position pertaining sexual union has not

- changed: no sex before marriage; no sex outside marriage (Heb. 13: 4).
3. Christian homes should be citadels of peace and joy where water of sexuality is freely and joyfully shared between husbands and wives. This 'sexual ethical teaching' is an urgent need in the society today. African elders and the church of God should set the pace for young ones and adults to follow.
 4. Consequently, people (Christians) should live for God and not for sexual enjoyment. Life lived without living association with God is futile. It is unethical to rejoice in the gift of God and yet neglect the giver.
 5. Hence, it is high time proper understanding of sexual purity via religion is promoted.

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Digital Technology Tools and Worship Engagement of Youths in The Redeemed Christian Church of God, Youth Province-12, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Digital technology tools such as social media platforms are fundamentally reshaping human experiences; especially, with regards to religious worship experience and spiritual formation activities. While digital technology tools have the potential to guarantee rich worship engagements, there is a pressing need to examine whether the incorporation of social media platforms enhances or detracts worship experiences of youths; more so that there is perceived lack of understanding regarding effective use of specific social media platforms in worship. Hence, this study investigated digital technology tools and worship engagement of youths in The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) Youth Province-12, Osun State, Nigeria. The study is anchored on theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The study adopted descriptive survey research design and adopted stratified and simple random sampling techniques to select a sample of hundred and three (103) youths and sixteen (16) church leaders within the study area. Data were collected using a duly validated self-designed questionnaire and a rating scale. Summary of findings revealed a very high social media presence of churches within RCCG Youth Province 12 on WhatsApp (100%), Facebook (87.5%) and Youtube (62.5%); while extent of social media engagement recorded very high prevalence on WhatsApp is (93.8%); live streaming of church worship services on Instagram live scores 6.25% and YouTube live had 18.75%. Also, YouVersion (59.2%) emerges as the most frequently used religious mobile app. The study recommends the implementation of digital literacy

programme that promote diversified effective use of social media platforms for worship engagements with concerns real spiritual worship experiences among RCCG Churches.

Keywords: Social media, Online presence, Worship engagement, Redeemed Christian Church of God, Youths. Osun Province-12

Introduction

Digital technology is profoundly altering the human experience, particularly in the realm of spirituality and religion. As people increasingly integrate digital tools into their daily lives, the boundaries between the physical and digital worlds are blurring. This convergence is redefining the way individuals practice their faith, interact with their spiritual communities, and experience spiritual growth. For contemporary youths, who have grown up with the internet and mobile devices, this transformation is especially pronounced. As digital natives, they are seamlessly weaving technology into their spiritual practices, creating new forms of religious expression and community engagement. This seismic shift is having a profound impact on the religious and spiritual lives of young people, raising important questions about the future of faith in the digital age¹.

This technological revolution has not spared the realm of religion, where digital tools such as mobile applications, social media, web applications, multimedia, virtual reality, artificial intelligence, immersive reality, podcasts, webinars, mobile phones and online streaming tools have significantly impacted religious practices and worship experiences. As a consequence, religious communities worldwide are facing the challenge of adapting to these technological shifts to engage with their members effectively².

Mobile applications have become indispensable tools, offering believers access to religious contents, prayer guides, scriptural readings, devotionals, and other spiritual resources on their handheld devices. The convenience and availability of these apps have allowed individuals to deepen their engagement with faith on the go³. Social media platforms have emerged as powerful communication channels for religious organizations, enabling direct and instantaneous interactions with congregants. Through these platforms, religious leaders can disseminate

sermons, religious messages, and inspirational contents, fostering a sense of virtual community where members can connect and support each other, transcending geographical barriers ⁴.

Web applications and multimedia technologies have facilitated immersive and interactive worship experiences, breaking the confines of physical spaces. Believers can now partake in virtual religious ceremonies, events, and rituals, forging profound spiritual connections with others around the world ⁵. Virtual reality has taken worship experiences to unprecedented heights, transporting individuals into digitally rendered sanctuaries and sacred spaces. The sense of presence and immersion engendered by virtual reality fosters a deep spiritual connection that transcends physical limitations ⁶. Artificial intelligence has contributed to personalized worship experiences, tailoring religious content and practices to individual preferences and needs. AI-driven recommendations provide believers with personalized prayer suggestions, religious study materials, and spiritual guidance, enhancing their spiritual journey⁷. Immersive reality technologies, engaging multiple senses, enrich worship experiences by appealing to sight, sound, and touch, creating a deeper sense of spiritual immersion and transcendence. Podcasts and webinars have democratized religious education, allowing religious leaders to disseminate knowledge and wisdom to a broader audience. These digital tools facilitate ongoing learning, spiritual growth, and engagement with religious teachings ⁸. Mobile phones, being ubiquitous in today's society, serve as essential tools for worshipers to access religious content, participate in virtual events, and stay connected with their faith community ⁹. Online streaming tools have revolutionized religious services, providing congregants with opportunities to participate in real-time worship experiences from the comfort of their homes ¹⁰.

In Nigeria, a country known for its cultural diversity and religious pluralism, the influence of digital technology tools on religious experiences is particularly noteworthy ¹¹. The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), one of Nigeria's most prominent Pentecostal denominations, has experienced significant growth and influence in the country. Within the RCCG, youths represent a crucial demographic with the potential to shape the future of religious practices in the digital age¹². As technology enthusiasts and digital natives, youths often serve as early

adopters of innovative tools and are at the forefront of exploring the intersection between faith and technology¹³.

Understanding the role of digital technology tools in shaping the worship experience among youths is of paramount importance for religious organizations to effectively engage with this demographic. Digital platforms offer youth's unprecedented opportunities to access religious content, engage in virtual worship services, and build connections with fellow believers beyond physical boundaries¹⁴. However, this integration of technology raises essential questions concerning the preservation of traditional religious values and practices, the authenticity of worship experiences, and the potential risks associated with overreliance on digital mediums.

This study therefore seeks to examine the influence of digital technology tools on the worship experience among youths in RCCG, situated in the culturally and religiously vibrant state of Osun, Nigeria. Hence, the study's focus is on digital technology tools and worship experience of Youths in RCCG, Youth Province-12, Osun State, Nigeria.

Concept of Digital Technology

Digital technologies are electronic tools, systems, devices and resources that generate, store or process data. Well known examples include social media, online games, multimedia and mobile phones¹⁵. Nearly every element of modern life has been profoundly altered by digital technology, including communications, the workplace, entertainment, travel, banking, shopping, and worship experiences. Digital technologies used in religious contexts include online platforms, digital tools, and unique digital frames¹⁶. These technologies are employed to bridge, blend, and blur online and offline religious spaces and practices¹⁷. Overall, digital technologies play a significant role in shaping and facilitating religious practices and experiences in contemporary culture. In Omer Cengiz, it is reported that digital technologies are changing the way people practice religion by providing new platforms for religious practices and creating virtual communities for religious engagement. His work explored religious practices and found that digital media have become integral to daily life¹⁸. Correspondingly, the report of some scholars established that the global rate at which religion is growing on the internet and the adoption of digital media by religious groups is worth paying attention to as it gives increasing visibility and fostering

technological involvement¹⁹. More especially with the Generation Z, it has become a crucial element for Pentecostal churches (Mega-churches) such as The Redeemed Christian Church of God to leverage the technological trend so that the youth can feel ‘among’ otherwise the youth will desert the church and religious worship void of the youth will be as boring as the graveyard²⁰.

Digital technologies used in religious contexts include online platforms, digital tools, and unique digital frames. These technologies are employed to bridge, blend, and blur online and offline religious spaces and practices, integrating technology use with religious lives in digital culture². Researchers in the realm of digital religion employ a range of digital techniques including; textual analyses, interviews, and ethnography, to investigate the convergence of digital technologies and religious customs²¹. The coupling of the terms digital and religion has led to the emergence of digital religion, where religion is mediated by technologies, including software and mobile applications¹⁷. Computer-mediated communication facilitates the fusion of religion and science online, allowing religious communities to strategically assemble religious authority based on scientific sources²². Digital media informs religious practice, with rituals being enacted through digital environments, highlighting common forms of religious practice found online. A scholar outlined the following as some of the digital technological tools used for religious worship¹⁶:

1. *YouVersion Bible App*
2. *YouTube*
3. *Facebook*
4. *Zoom*
5. *Devotional Apps*
6. *Telegram*
7. *Smartphones*
8. *Digital Televisions*
9. *Video Streaming*
10. *eBooks*
11. *Digital Music*
12. *WhatsApp*

Social Media and Digital Technology Usage Among Christian Youth

Social media and digital technology have become integral to the lives of Christian youths. This phenomenon is particularly accentuated during coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, altering the landscape of church engagement. While social media platforms/digital tools offer alternative means for maintaining church life, they also present significant challenges to the users. Issues like potential over-reliance and threats to spiritual and moral values underscore the need for responsible utilization of these tools, emphasizing the importance of stewardship in the use of social media. The Church task of evangelization must take cognizance of vocally representing Christ in the digital age, by acknowledging the potential of the digital technology to reshape the concept of 'church' and widens the spectrum of voices contributing to religious conversations. Initiatives like 'The BIG Bible Project' strive to encourage diverse engagement with digital culture within the Christian community, highlighting the evolving nature of Christian communication practices in the digital era²³. The landscape of Christianity is witnessing a significant evolution through the use of social media and digital technology. This shift is transforming worship practices, as more Christians engage with apps and online platforms to express and explore their faith, diverging from traditional church settings. Platforms like *YouVersion*, with over 260 million installations worldwide, exemplify this trend, redefining how individuals access religious texts. Moreover, social media is reshaping the concept of religious outreach, empowering ordinary Christians to engage in personal discussions about faith, presenting a more authentic portrayal of the faith community. This digital shift also fosters interactive engagement during sermons, allowing congregants to participate actively, extend discussions beyond Sunday services, and infuse Christian perspectives into broader societal dialogues, including politics. Ultimately, these technological advancements mark an exciting era for Christians as they navigate and redefine their religious experiences within these new digital landscapes²⁴.

The utilization of digital technology among youths brings forth a dual impact on religious engagement. Positively, it offers unprecedented access to a diverse array of religious resources, spanning online scriptures, religious apps, and virtual communities, fostering a deeper

comprehension of faith. Conversely, excessive reliance on these tools might diminish involvement in conventional religious customs and rituals, potentially causing distractions that steer focus away from spiritual pursuits²⁵. The Pew Research Center's recent survey unveils the swiftly evolving landscape of social media among American teens aged 13 to 17. TikTok emerges as a dominant force, with 67% of teens using it, 16% of them using it almost constantly, eclipsing Facebook's declining usage from 71% to 32% since 2014-15. YouTube remains the top platform, utilized by 95% of surveyed teens, followed by *Instagram* and *Snapchat*. Shifts in platform usage dynamics have occurred over time, with Instagram and Snapchat gaining traction while *Twitter* and *Tumblr* witnessed declines among teens²⁶.

Demographic variations such as gender and racial disparities have been found to influence platform preferences by youths. Whereas, male youths gravitate toward *YouTube*, *Twitch*, and *Reddit*, while female youths favor *TikTok*, *Instagram*, and *Snapchat*. More so, black and hispanic teens also exhibit higher usage rates on several platforms compared to White teens. Usage frequency, also reveals that 35% of teens are constantly engaged on at least one of the top five platforms. Engagement levels are notably high on *TikTok* and *Snapchat*, with a significant portion of users nearly constantly active. Overall, these findings illuminate the dynamic nature usage pattern of social media among American teenagers, emphasizing *TikTok's* remarkable ascent and the shifting landscape of platform preferences²⁶.

One strategy for effectively engaging with the internet-savvy Net Generation to achieve ministry objectives in the digital age involves leveraging online platforms. This approach enables churches to navigate the complexities of digital communication and reach out to the younger demographic. To implement this strategy effectively, it is essential to understand the characteristics and preferences of the Net Generation. This includes elucidating their digital behaviors, communication preferences, and expectations regarding online interactions. By grasping these aspects, churches can tailor their online ministry efforts to effectively resonate with the Net Generation²⁷. This can be extended to subjects on website design, social media engagement, email marketing, and content creation. Authenticity, relevance, and interactivity are underscored as crucial elements in online ministry initiatives, advocating for genuine connections and meaningful interactions with

the audience. Thus, addressing common challenges and pitfalls encountered in online ministry, such as digital overload, privacy concerns, and ethical considerations, practical guidance is crucial on navigating these issues while maintaining integrity and efficacy in digital outreach endeavors²⁷.

Worship Experience

Worship experiences encompass four domains of human being.; these include: emotional, social, spiritual, cognitive domains. These domains are intertwined and they contribute to the overall worship experience. The emotional domain involves experiencing spiritual emotions such as awe and gratitude. The social domain of worship experiences involves a sense of community and interactions with other worshippers within the faith community²⁹. The spiritual domain involves experiencing closeness to God, spiritual struggle, and spiritual transformation³⁰. And the cognitive domain influence thoughts and decision-making³¹.

Worship experience has a significant impact on the identity and sense of belonging of youth in the faith community. Research has consistently shown that formal worship experiences play a vital role in shaping youth religiosity and fostering religious behaviors. Specifically, aspects such as, sense of belonging and meaning-making; openness to God's authority; opportunities for youth contribution to the community are crucial in influencing the religious development and practices of young people ³³. Additionally, youth worship emphasizes the importance of "being together" as a primary quality, which includes celebrating community through physical presence, fostering empathy and emotional connection, crossing social and ecclesiological boundaries, and sharing faith and being in God's presence³⁴. Furthermore, the sense of community in the faith community is related to a lower sense of suicidal ideation, highlighting the importance of belonging in promoting well-being among youth³⁵. Overall, worship experiences provide opportunities for youth to develop their spiritual identity, engage in personal devotional activities, and receive religious support, which contribute to their spiritual transformation, maturity, and connectedness to the faith community³⁶.

Theoretical Framework Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a widely used framework for understanding and predicting individuals' acceptance and usage of technology. It posits that the intention to use technology is influenced by factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, social influence, and trust³⁷. Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which individuals believe that using technology will enhance their performance or productivity. Perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which individuals perceive the technology as easy to use and understand³⁸. Social influence refers to the impact of others' opinions and recommendations on individuals' acceptance and usage of technology. Trust depicts the level of confidence and belief individuals have in the technology and its providers. TAM has been applied in various contexts, including insurance, higher education, online banking, and disaster management in order to understand and enhance technology acceptance and adoption³⁹.

However, there are some identified limitations to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). These limitations include the need to overcome technical barriers and improve user-friendliness of applications. Further, the complexity and multi-dimensionality of intelligent systems pose challenges to their widespread, adoption and acceptance³⁷. In the context of online banking, factors such as system quality and social influence can influence the level of trust, ease of use, and usefulness, which in turn affect the intention to use and the actual usage of online banking systems.

Research has shown that, application of TAM in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) predominantly used a quantitative approach and focused on manufacturing companies, limiting the generalizability of findings⁴⁰. In the case of e-learning portals, factors such as self-efficacy and complexity can hinder their optimal use⁴¹. In the context of Christian youths, social media, digital technology, and their worship experiences, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) assumes a pivotal role in understanding their interaction with technology:

- **Perceived Usefulness:** For Christian youths, technology's usefulness aligns with how digital platforms facilitate spiritual growth, Bible study, access to religious content, or participation

in virtual worship services. Their perception of technology's role in enhancing their spiritual journey significantly influences its adoption.

- **Perceived Ease of Use:** A user-friendly interface and comprehensible digital tools enable Christian youths to engage actively in religious activities, attend online church services, and interact with religious content easily. The ease of navigating digital platforms impacts their participation in religious practices.
- **Social Influence:** Peers, religious leaders, and community opinions play a substantial role in shaping the acceptance and use of technology among Christian youths. Recommendations, shared experiences, and social norms within religious circles influence their digital engagement for worship and spiritual growth.
- **Trust:** Christian youths' trust in digital technology for worship experiences involves confidence in the authenticity of online religious content, the security of virtual religious communities, and the reliability of platforms for spiritual guidance.

In this context, the TAM gives insights into how Christian youths navigate digital spaces for religious purposes. The model aids t comprehension of their attitudes toward and adoption of digital tools for worship, prayer, fellowship, and religious education.

However, despite the potential benefits, there exist challenges specific to this demographic:

- **Balancing Authenticity:** This is about the challenge in maintaining the authenticity of spiritual experiences in a digital realm, ensuring that online interactions genuinely contribute to their spiritual growth.
- **Distractions and Overload:** Over-reliance on digital platforms might lead to distractions or information overload, potentially diluting the depth of religious experiences or causing a sense of disconnect from traditional worship settings.
- **Engagement and Community Building:** Christian youths' adoption of technology for worship experiences must focus on fostering genuine community engagement, emphasizing relationships, discipleship, and mentorship within the digital

space.

Integrating TAM within this context enables a deeper comprehension of how Christian youths navigate, engage with, and adopt digital technology for worship experiences. It underscores the need for technological solutions that, align with spiritual values, enhance engagement, and contribute meaningfully to their faith journey.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the rapid advancement and widespread adoption of digital technology tools have transformed various aspects of society, including religious practices. Among the demography most affected by this digital revolution are youths, who often have unique experiences and expectations regarding their worship encounters. In the context of The Redeemed Christian Church of God Province-12 in Osun State, Nigeria, the utilization of digital technology tools by the youth demographic in their worship experiences is a dynamic and evolving phenomenon.

Despite the potential of digital tools to revolutionize worship engagement, significant knowledge gaps persist. Specifically, there is a pressing need to investigate the presence, usage, and adoption rates of these tools within religious communities. To bridge this knowledge gap, a focused inquiry is necessary to provide actionable insights that can inform decision-making within the church community and contribute meaningfully to the broader discussion on the role of digital technology in shaping religious practices among Nigerian youths.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of Social Media presence of RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12?
2. To what extent are RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12 are engaged in the use of social media?
3. What digital technology tools are used by youths in RCCG Youth Province-12 for their worship engagement?

Methodology

For the study, descriptive survey research design is adopted. Data were collected using a duly validated self-designed questionnaire and rating

scale. The population for the study consists of youths within RCCG Youth Province-12, Osun State, Nigeria. A sample size of 103 youths was identified through stratified and simple random sampling from RCCG Youth Province-12. Also, 16 church leaders were selected from the Province encompassing zonal pastor, area pastor, parish pastor and church worker. The data generated was subject to analysis by the researchers and presented below in simple percentage tables for easy understanding and simplicity.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (N=103)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	55	53.4%
	Female	45	43.7%
	No response	3	2.9%
Age	Under 20 years	17	16.5%
	21-30 years	51	49.5%
	31-40 years	26	25.2%
	41-50	8	7.8%
	No response	1	1.0%
Education	Secondary	17	16.5%
	ND/NCE	13	12.6%
	HND/B.Sc	54	52.4%
	Postgraduate	19	18.4%
Marital Status	Single	75	72.8%
	Married	28	27.2%
Ministerial Status	Worker	48	46.6%
	Minister	31	30.1%
	Pastor	17	16.5%
	Member	7	6.8%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 reveals the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The table revealed that out of the 103 respondents, 55 respondents representing 53.4% of the sample represented male while 45 respondents which constitutes 43.7% represented the female participants. Three of the respondents representing 2.9% chose not to indicate their gender. The gender distribution among the respondents reveals a relatively balanced representation, with a slightly higher percentage of males 55 (53.4%) than females 45 (43.7%). The table also shows that majority of the respondents 51 (49.5%) were aged between 21 and 30 years, while the least 8 (7.8%) were between 41 and 50 years and only 17 (16.5%) were below 20 years. This clearly indicated that majority of the respondents comprises a significant proportion of the youth demographic. Also, the table revealed that 54 respondents representing 52.4% of the sample had first degree education, 13 respondents representing 12.6% had National Diploma/Nigeria Certificate of Education, 19 respondents representing 18.4% had Post Graduate degrees while 17 respondents which constitute 16.5% had Secondary School education. The educational background of the respondents reflects a diverse range of academic qualifications, spanning from secondary education to postgraduate studies. In addition, majority (72.8%) were single while the least (27.2%) were married. This clearly indicated that the majority of respondents are single, comprising a significant proportion of the youth demographic. The distribution of ministerial status demonstrates the diverse roles within the church community. The table also shows the ministerial status of the respondents. The prevalence of workers and ministers indicates active participation in church activities, while pastors and members represent different levels of engagement.

Research Question One: What is the level of Social Media presence of RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12?

To answer this question, the data obtained from the church leaders within RCCG Youth Province-12 in Osun State, Nigeria was subjected to descriptive statistics and the result is presented in Table 4.2.

Table 2 Online Presence of RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12 (N=16)

S/N	Social Media Platforms	Available No %	Not Available No %
1.	WhatsApp Group	16 (100%)	0 (0.0%)
2.	Facebook	14 (87.5%)	2 (12.5%)
3.	Instagram	5 (31.25%)	11 (68.75%)
4.	Telegram	6 (37.5%)	10 (62.5%)
5.	Youtube	10 (62.5%)	6 (37.0%)
6.	Church website	3 (18.8%)	13 (81.3%)
7.	Tiktok	5 (31.3%)	11 (68.8%)
8.	Mixlr (Online Radio)	4 (25%)	12 (75%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 shows the level of social media presence of RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12. The table revealed that all surveyed churches 16 (100%) operate an active Church WhatsApp account, indicating the widespread use of this platform for church communication. The majority of churches 14 (87.5%) have an active Facebook account, making it a prevalent platform for church outreach. YouTube is the most commonly used video platform, with 10 (62.5%) of churches having an active account. The majority of churches 11 (68.8%) do not have an active TikTok account, suggesting a lower interest in this platform. Mixlr (Online Radio) is embraced only by 4 (25%) of churches. This clearly indicates that there are varied levels of online presence among RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12. WhatsApp groups have the highest adoption rate, with all churches having a presence, while church websites have the lowest adoption rate. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, YouTube, TikTok, and Mixlr show a mix of availability and non-availability across the churches surveyed.

Research Question Two: To what extent are RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12 are engaged in the use of social media?

To answer this question, the data obtained from the church leaders within RCCG Youth Province-12 in Osun State, Nigeria was subjected to descriptive statistics and the result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Extent of Social Media Engagement with the Youths (N=16)

S/N	Statements	Available No %	Not Available No %
1.	Online Streaming of Church services/programs	7 (43.8%)	9 (56.3%)
2.	WhatsApp Chat postings of Church information circulation	15 (93.8%)	1 (6.25%)
3.	WhatsApp Audio Broadcast of Sermon/Church programs	10 (62.5%)	6 (37.5%)
4.	Facebook Video posts of Sermons/Church programs	7 (43.8%)	9 (56.3%)
5.	Facebook Live of Church Service Programs	3 (18.75%)	13 (81.25%)
6.	Instagram Live of Church services/programs	1 (6.25%)	15 (93.75%)
7.	Youtube Live of Church services/programs	3 (18.75%)	13 (81.25%)
8.	Telegram message sharing of Sermons/programs	5 (31.3%)	11 (68.8%)
9.	Virtual Church services/programs	5 (31.3%)	11 (68.8%)
10.	Use of Short Message Services (SMS) for Church information circulation	8 (50%)	8 (50%)
11.	Multimedia services for Church programs	6 (37.5%)	10 (62.5%)
12.	Easy Worship (Church presentation software)	11 (68.8%)	5 (31.3%)
13.	Smart/Led Tv/Multimedia Projector for presentation purposes	10 (62.5%)	6 (37.5%)
14.	Church Media Team	9 (56.3%)	7 (43.8%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3 shows the extent of social media engagement with the youths. The findings revealed that while WhatsApp chat is widely employed for church information circulation by 93.8% of churches, online streaming of church services/programs is offered by 43.8% of surveyed churches, showing moderate adoption for virtual attendance. Furthermore, 62.5% of churches engage in WhatsApp audio broadcast of sermons/church programs, suggesting a moderate utilization for sharing audio content. Conversely, platforms like Instagram Live and YouTube Live are less utilized, with only 6.25% and 18.75% of churches utilizing them, respectively, indicating minimal engagement for streaming church services/programs. Additionally, multimedia tools such as Easy Worship software and Smart/Led TV/Multimedia Projectors are more widely adopted, with 68.8% and 62.5% of churches using them, respectively, suggesting a higher utilization for multimedia presentations and visual aids in church services. Table 3 revealed varied levels of engagement with different social media platforms and multimedia tools among RCCG Churches in the province, reflecting a diverse approach to social media interaction and multimedia utilization within the surveyed churches.

Research Question Three: What digital technology tools are used by youths in RCCG Youth Province-12 for their worship engagement? To answer this question, the data obtained from the youths within RCCG Youth Province-12 in Osun State, Nigeria was subjected to descriptive statistics and the result is as presented in Table 4a; Table 4b; Table 4c; Table 4d and Table 4e.

Table 4a Identification of Religious Mobile Apps Used (N=103)

S/ N	Religiou s Mobile Apps	Frequentl y Use No %	Occasionall y Use No %	Never Use No %	No Respons e No %
1.	<i>Youversio n</i>	61 (59.2%)	32 (31.1%)	9 (8.7%)	1 (1.0%)

2.	<i>Open Heaven Devotional</i>	46 (44.7%)	27 (26.1%)	29 (28.2%)	1 (1.0%)
3.	<i>Digital Hymnal</i>	36 (35.0%)	53 (52.0%)	13 (12.6%)	1 (1.0%)
4.	<i>Daily Scripture</i>	35 (34.0%)	40 (38.8%)	27 (26.2%)	1 (1.0%)
5.	<i>OH Prime TV</i>	5 (4.9%)	71 (68.9%)	26 (25.2%)	1 (1.0%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4a indicate varying usage patterns of mobile apps designed for religious content among the respondents. The most frequently used app is *YouVersion*, with a substantial 61 (59.2%) of respondents reporting frequent usage, while only 9 (8.7%) never use it. *Open Heavens* follows closely, with 46 (44.7%) reporting frequent use, and 29 (28.2%) never using it. *Digital Hymnal* is frequently used by 36 (35%) of respondents, and *Daily Scripture* has a usage frequency of 35 (34%). Interestingly, *OH Prime TV* sees a different pattern, with a majority 71 (68.9%) reporting never using it. These findings suggest a notable preference for *YouVersion* among the respondents, indicating its popularity as a go-to mobile app for religious content, while *OH Prime TV* seems to be less utilized among this demographic. These usage patterns provide insights into the preferences and habits of the youth within The Redeemed Christian Church of God Youth Province-12 concerning mobile apps tailored for religious purposes.

Table 4b The Usage of Social Media Platforms (N=103)

S/ N	Social Media Platform s	Frequentl y Use No %	Occasionall y Use No %	Never Use No %	No Respons e No %
1.	<i>Facebook</i>	66 (64.1%)	33 (32.0%)	8 (3.9%)	0 (0.0%)
2.	<i>Instagra m</i>	43 (41.7%)	47 (45.6%)	13 (12.6%)	0 (0.0 %)
3.	<i>Telegram</i>	39 (37.9%)	52 (50.5%)	11 (10.7%)	1 (1.0%)
4.	<i>WhatsApp</i>	95 (92.2%)	7 (6.8%)	1 (1.0%)	0 (0.0%)
5.	<i>Tiktok</i>	20 (19.4%)	35 (33.9%)	48 (46.6%)	0 (0.0%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4b highlight diverse patterns in the use of social media platforms among the respondents. Notably, *Facebook* emerges as the second most frequently used platform, with 66 (64.1%) reporting frequent usage and only 8 (3.9%) never using it. *Instagram* follows closely, with 43 (41.7%) reporting frequent use and 13 (12.6%) never using it. *Telegram* is utilized frequently by 39 (37.9%), and *WhatsApp* stands out with the highest frequency of 95 (92.2%) reporting frequent usage. In contrast, *TikTok* demonstrates a different trend, with a substantial 48 (46.6%) reporting never using it. These findings suggest a prevalent and active engagement with mainstream social media platforms, particularly *WhatsApp* and *Facebook*, among the youth in The Redeemed Christian Church of God Youth Province-12. The data provides insights into the digital social landscape of the respondents and underscores the platforms that hold significance in their daily online interactions.

Table 4.4c The Usage of Online Streaming Platforms (N=103)

S/ N	Online- Streamin g Platform s	Frequentl y Use No %	Occasionall y Use No %	Never Use No %	No Respons e No %
1.	<i>Youtube</i>	58 (56.3%)	35 (33.9%)	9 (8.7%)	1 (1.0%)
2.	<i>Stream Yard</i>	4 (3.8%)	21 (20.3%)	76 (73.8%)	2 (1.9 %)
3.	<i>Instagram Live</i>	18 (17.5%)	34 (33.0%)	50 (48.5%)	1 (1.0%)
4.	<i>Facebook Live</i>	32 (31.1%)	37 (35.9%)	34 (33.0%)	0 (0.0%)
5.	<i>Telegram Live</i>	24 (23.30%)	24 (23.3%)	53 (51.5%)	2 (1.9%)
6.	<i>Mixlr</i>	35 (33.9%)	43 (41.7%)	23 (22.3%)	2 (1.9%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4c reveals diverse engagement with live streaming and content-sharing platforms. *YouTube* is frequented by 58 (56.3%) of respondents, demonstrating its popularity, while 9 (8.7%) never use it. *StreamYard* sees limited use, with 76 (73.8%) reporting never using it. Notably, *Facebook Live* is employed by 32 (31.1%), *Instagram Live* by 18 (17.5%), and *Telegram Live* by 24 (23.3%), with varying degrees of never usage. *Mixlr* is utilized regularly by 35 (33.9%), indicating a moderate adoption. These findings highlight a prevalent use of mainstream platforms like *YouTube* and *Facebook Live* for live streaming purposes, whereas platforms like *StreamYard* and *Telegram Live* are less commonly used among the respondents. The data provides insights into the platforms that hold significance for the youth in The Redeemed Christian Church

of God Youth Province-12 in terms of live content consumption and creation.

Table 4d The Usage of Special websites/OnlineForums for Religious Discussions, Resources and for Paying Tithes/Offerings (N=103)

S/ N	Special websites/ Online Forums	Frequen tly Use No %	Occasiona lly Use No %	Neve r Use No %	No Respon se No %
1.	Dove Vision TV	18 (17.5%)	29 (28.1%)	55 (53.4 %)	1 (1.0%)
2.	RCCG.org	17 (16.5%)	50 (48.4%)	36 (34.9 %)	0 (0.0 %)
3.	RCCGYAYA.co m.ng	15 (14.6%)	27 (26.2%)	59 (57.2 %)	2 (1.9%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4d indicates varying levels of engagement among respondents on the use of special websites and online forums. *Dove Vision* is infrequently used, with 55 (53.4%) of respondents reporting never using it, while 18 (17.5%) use it frequently. *RCCG.org* sees a more balanced distribution, with 36 (34.9%) never using it, 17 (16.5%) frequently using it, and 50 (48.5%) using it occasionally. *RCCGYAYA.org* also demonstrates a significant portion 59 (57.2%) never using it, with 15 (14.6%) using it frequently. These results suggest that among the surveyed youth in The Redeemed Christian Church of God Youth Province-12, certain special websites and online forums have limited utilization, while others like *RCCG.org* have a more even distribution across frequent, occasional, and non-usage. Understanding these patterns sheds light on the online platforms that are central or peripheral to the digital experiences of the respondents within the church community.

Table 4.4e The Usage of Digital Software for Church services (N=103)

S/N	Digital Software	Frequently Use No %	Occasionally Use No %	Never Use No %	No Response No %
1.	<i>Easy Worship</i>	16 (15.5%)	35 (33.9%)	50 (48.5%)	2 (1.9%)
2.	<i>Vmix Pro</i>	3 (2.9%)	25 (24.3%)	73 (70.8%)	2 (1.9%)
3.	<i>One Stream</i>	4 (3.8%)	20 (19.4%)	77 (74.7%)	2 (1.9%)
4.	<i>OpenLP</i>	2 (2.9%)	12 (11.6%)	83 (80.5%)	5 (4.8%)
5.	<i>Share Faith</i>	5 (4.8%)	13 (12.6%)	82 (79.6%)	3 (2.9%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4e shows the data on the usage of digital software in the context of worship and religious activities, revealing varying levels of adoption among the respondents. *Easy Worship* sees usage by 16 (15.5%), with 50 (48.5%) never using it, while *VmixPro* has limited usage, with 73 (70.8%) never using it. "One Stream" demonstrates a similar trend, with a significant portion 77 (74.7%) never using it. *OpenLP* is used occasionally by 12 (11.6%), with the majority 83 (80.5%) never using it. *Share Faith* has a balanced distribution, with 82 (79.6%) never using it, and a smaller portion frequently 5 (4.8%) and occasionally 13 (12.6%) using it. These findings suggest a range of adoption levels for different digital software, with some being infrequently used or never used among the surveyed youth in The Redeemed Christian Church of God Youth Province-12. Understanding these patterns is crucial for assessing the technological landscape within the church community and informing decisions regarding the integration of digital tools in worship practices.

Discussion of Findings

Findings concerning research question one provides an insight into the availability and accessibility of Digital Technology Tools for Worship

Experience in RCCG Youth Province-12. The study revealed that all surveyed churches 100% operate an active Church *WhatsApp* account, indicating the widespread utilization of this platform for church communication¹. Additionally, the majority of churches 87.5% maintain an active *Facebook* account, suggesting its prevalence as a platform for church outreach. *YouTube* emerges as the most commonly utilized video platform, with 62.5% of churches having an active account, while the adoption rate for *TikTok* remains relatively low, with only 31.3% of churches having an active account. Furthermore, the utilization of *Mixlr* (Online Radio) is observed in only 25% of churches.

These findings underscore the diverse levels of online presence among RCCG Churches in Osun Youth Province-12, with *WhatsApp* groups exhibiting the highest adoption rate and church websites showing the lowest adoption rate. The presence of social media platforms such as *Facebook*, *Instagram*, *Telegram*, *YouTube*, *TikTok*, and *Mixlr* varies across the surveyed churches, reflecting a mix of availability and non-availability. Findings on research question two reveals the extent of social media engagement among youths in RCCG Youth Province-12. It was observed that *WhatsApp* chat serves as a prevalent tool for circulating church information, with 93.8% of churches extensively utilizing it for communication purposes. However, the adoption of online streaming for church services/programs is moderate, with only 43.8% of surveyed churches offering this feature, suggesting a cautious approach towards virtual attendance. Furthermore, a moderate utilization for sharing audio content was noted, with 62.5% of churches engaging in *WhatsApp* audio broadcast of sermons/church programs.

Conversely, platforms such as *Instagram* Live and *YouTube* Live are sparingly used, indicating minimal engagement for streaming church services/programs, with only 6.25% and 18.75% of churches employing them, respectively. On the other hand, multimedia tools like Easy Worship software and Smart/Led TV/Multimedia Projectors are more widely adopted, with 68.8% and 62.5% of churches utilizing them, respectively, suggesting a preference for multimedia presentations and visual aids during church services². These findings underscore varied levels of engagement across different social media platforms and multimedia tools among RCCG Churches in the province, reflecting a diverse approach to social media interaction and multimedia utilization within the surveyed churches.

Research question three discusses the digital technology tools utilized by youths in RCCG Youth Province-12 for their worship engagement. Among mobile apps designed for religious content, "YouVersion" emerges as the most frequently used, with 59.2% of respondents reporting frequent usage, indicating its popularity within the demographic.

Invariably, *OH Prime* TV shows limited adoption, with 68.9% of respondents reporting never using it. These findings underscore a significant preference for *YouVersion* among the respondents, emphasizing its role as a primary mobile app for accessing religious content. Furthermore, diverse engagement patterns were observed across various social media platforms, with *WhatsApp* and *Facebook* being the most commonly used platforms for communication and outreach. Mainstream platforms like *YouTube* and *Facebook Live* are prevalent for live streaming of worship services, while the utilization of special websites and online forums varies among respondents. Additionally, the adoption of digital software for worship activities exhibits diverse usage patterns, with some tools experiencing limited utilization or being entirely unused among the surveyed youth. Understanding these preferences and usage patterns is essential for assessing the technological landscape within the church community and guiding decisions regarding the integration of digital tools into worship practices.

Summary of Findings

Findings revealed very high social media presence of churches within RCCG Youth Province-12 on *WhatsApp*, *Facebook*, and *Youtube*; while extent of social media engagement among youths in RCCG Youth Province-12 recorded very high prevalence on *WhatsApp* and somewhat minimal on live streaming of church worship service on *Instagram* live and *Youtube* live. In addition, the study shows diverse adoption rates of multimedia tools among RCCG churches in the province, with Easy Worship software and Smart/LED TV/Multimedia Projectors being widely used. This indicates a preference for multimedia presentations and visual aids during church services, highlighting varied levels of engagement across different social media platforms and multimedia tools among surveyed youth churches. In addition, *YouVersion* emerges as the most frequently used mobile app designed for religious content.

Conclusion

Based on the findings presented, it's evident that churches within RCCG Youth Province-12 have established a significant presence on various social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and YouTube. This heightened presence suggests a proactive approach by these churches in utilizing digital platforms to reach and engage with their members and the wider community.

However, despite the extensive social media presence, the study indicates that the level of engagement among youths in RCCG Youth Province-12 varies across different platforms. While WhatsApp emerges as a highly engaged platform, live streaming of church worship services on platforms like Instagram Live and YouTube Live shows relatively minimal engagement. This suggests that while youths are active on social media, there may be specific preferences or barriers to engagement with certain types of content or platforms.

Moreover, the diverse adoption rates of multimedia tools among RCCG churches in the province, such as Easy Worship software and Smart/LED TV/Multimedia Projectors, underscore a preference for multimedia presentations and visual aids during church services. This highlights the importance of incorporating technology and multimedia elements to enhance the worship experience and facilitate better engagement with the youth demographic. Overall, these findings emphasize the need for churches to tailor their digital strategies and content to effectively reach and engage with youths across various social media platforms and multimedia tools.

Recommendations

1. Implement digital literacy programs within the church community to enhance access and proficiency with digital technology among youths. This can empower them to fully leverage the benefits of available digital tools.
2. Provide specialized training for Church Media Teams to enhance their skills in managing digital technology tools effectively. This ensures that these teams can contribute optimally to the integration of technology in worship services.
3. Involve youths in decision-making processes related to the integration of digital technology tools. Their active participation

ensures that the chosen tools and approaches resonate with their expectations and contribute to a more inclusive worship experience.

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Influence of Technology on the Teaching of Social Studies among Secondary School Teachers in Ibadan South Area, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Technology has revolutionized education by facilitating the adoption of innovative, student-centered teaching methods that enhance instructional effectiveness. The study investigated the use and impact of technology in Social Studies education in Ibadan South, Oyo State. Employing a descriptive survey design, it sampled 50 Social Studies teachers from 25 public Junior Secondary Schools using simple random sampling. Data was collected through a self-developed questionnaire titled “Influence of Technology on the Teaching of Social Studies Questionnaire (ITTSSQ)” and analysed with frequency counts, percentages, and mean statistics. The results revealed a moderate level of technological integration (mean = 2.45, S.D = 1.48), with teachers commonly using online resources (90%), interactive whiteboards (74%), educational software (50%), and online collaboration tools (54%). Technology significantly improved teaching quality and student outcomes, with (mean = 3.07, SD = 1.05) above the 2.5 criterion. However, challenges in integrating technology were prevalent (mean = 3.16, SD = 1.05), as reflected by high mean scores for challenge-related items. The study concluded that while technology adoption is moderate, its positive effects on teaching and learning are evident. It recommended improved access to technological infrastructure to enhance instructional effectiveness.

Keywords: Technology, Integration, Social Studies, Teachers, Student Learning Outcome

Introduction

Technology has revolutionized education, becoming essential for transformative learning experiences by enabling innovative, student-centered teaching methods tailored to diverse learning styles. Tools such as interactive software, multimedia, and internet resources enhance teaching effectiveness and student engagement, making learning more impactful and accessible (Kaylayan, 2024; Hyeung, Micheal, & Junfeng, 2019). Technology expands learning opportunities beyond classrooms, fostering lifelong learning and self-directed study. Studies confirm that technology fosters collaborative learning, and critical thinking, and connects theoretical concepts to practical applications (Akujieze, 2024). It also facilitates advanced teaching strategies and energizes learning processes through digital tools (Johnson et al., 2013; Kay, 2024). As a result, researchers, educators, and policymakers increasingly prioritize technology integration, recognizing its potential to improve educational practices and outcomes.

While technology offers immense benefits in education, its integration in Nigerian schools faces critical challenges. Key issues include inadequate infrastructure, such as unreliable electricity, poor internet connectivity, and a lack of modern computer laboratories, which hinder the implementation of digital learning tools (Luise, 2023). Additionally, the high cost of devices limits access for both students and teachers, exacerbating inequalities and reducing opportunities for engagement with digital resources. Another major challenge is insufficient teacher training in technology use. Without adequate professional development, even available tools are underutilized, impeding effective teaching and learning (Luise, 2023). These barriers create a significant gap between the potential advantages of educational technology and its actual adoption in Nigerian schools.

There is a significant disparity in access to and usage of technology between public and private schools in Nigeria. Yusuf and Balogun (2011), as cited in Alabi and Ijaiya (2022), indicate that public educational institutions often struggle with issues such as outdated technology and insufficient internet access, in contrast to private schools, which typically possess enhanced resources and facilities. This digital divide

exacerbates educational inequalities. In Oyo State, initiatives to enhance technological infrastructure and teacher training have been launched, including programs providing computers, internet access, and other digital tools (Oyo State Ministry of Education, 2019). However, the effectiveness of these efforts varies across regions, schools, and subjects. Social Studies, a key subject in Nigerian education, plays a vital role in fostering civic competence and social understanding. Historically reliant on lecture-based approaches and rote memorization, its teaching methods often lack engagement and critical thinking promotion (Johan, 2015). Effective teaching requires integrating digital resources, promoting active learning, and employing innovative strategies to align with 21st-century educational goals (Oyibe, 2015). The integration of technology in social studies education has the potential to revolutionize traditional teaching methods, fostering improved student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. By incorporating interactive simulations, virtual field trips, and digital storytelling, teachers can make social studies content more relatable and engaging, ultimately supporting the development of higher-order thinking skills such as analysis, evaluation, and creation (Ersoy, 2015; Francis, 2017). Understanding the impact of technology on teaching effectiveness and student outcomes is essential for devising strategies to optimize educational practices.

However, despite its benefits, technology integration in classrooms faces significant challenges, particularly in the Ibadan South area of Oyo State, Nigeria. While the region's schools reflect broader national efforts to incorporate technology, issues such as inadequate training for educators, a lack of necessary tools, and poor infrastructure hinder progress. Many teachers report insufficient professional development in both pedagogy and technology, which limits their ability to integrate digital tools effectively into lesson plans (Ertner, 2010; Sakin, 2017). Additionally, disparities in technological resources such as unreliable internet, a shortage of computers, and high costs of equipment due to fluctuating exchange rates exacerbate these challenges, particularly in public schools (Nathaniel, 2021; Lawal, 2014). Efforts by the Oyo State Ministry of Education to improve technological infrastructure, including providing computers and internet access, have seen mixed results due to disparities in implementation and access (Oyo State Ministry of Education, 2019). These challenges underscore the need to address the

barriers preventing the effective use of technology in social studies instruction.

This study aims to investigate and optimize the influence of technology on Social Studies teaching among secondary school teachers in Ibadan South, Oyo State. By focusing on this region's unique context, the study seeks to fill a research gap and provide insights into the strategies necessary to enhance teaching practices and learning outcomes through effective technology integration. To achieve the aim of the study the following research questions were raised

Research Questions

- i. What is the current level of technological integration in teaching Social Studies among secondary school teachers in the study area?
- ii. What types of technology are commonly used and their frequency of use in teaching Social Studies?
- iii. To what extent does technology influence the teaching effectiveness of Social Studies and student outcomes in the study area?
- iv. What are the challenges that secondary school teachers encounter when integrating technology into Social Studies instruction in the study area?

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive survey research design. This is because the research design enables the researchers to gather relatively limited data from relatively large cases. The population used for the study comprised all Social Studies teachers in Public Secondary in Ibadan South local government of Oyo State. The sample size for the study consisted of twenty (50) Social Studies teachers selected using the simple random sampling technique from 25 public Junior Secondary Schools in Ibadan South local government, Oyo State. The research instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled "Influence of Technology on the Teaching of Social Studies Questionnaire (ITTSSQ)." The questionnaire is divided into five sections. Section A consists of the respondents' demographic data while section B consists of statements to elicit information on the level of technological integration in teaching social studies among secondary school teachers. Section C consists of statements to elicit information on

the types of technology that are commonly used and their frequency of use. Section D consists of a statement to elicit information on the influence of technology on social studies teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Section E consists of statements to elicit information on secondary school teachers' challenges when integrating technology into social studies instruction. The response option was a Likert-type scale of measurement Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The data collected from the study was analysed using frequency counts, percentages, and mean statistics to address the research questions.

Results

Research Question One: What is the current level of technological integration in teaching social studies among secondary school teachers in the study area?

To address this research question, data collected using a 10-item instrument on technological integration in teaching social studies were scored using a four-point Likert scale. Responses of "Strongly Agree" (SA) were assigned a score of '4', "Agree" (A) was assigned '3', "Disagree" (D) was assigned '2', and "Strongly Disagree" (SD) was assigned '1'. These 10 items were used to measure the level of technological integration in teaching social studies among secondary school teachers in Ibadan South in Oyo State as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Technological Integration

STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD	Mea n	Std. Dev
Frequency = 50						
I frequently use digital resources such as interactive maps in my social studies lessons	21	9	8	12	2.56	1.79
I don't utilise interactive whiteboards to present lessons and engage students in social studies classes	7	10	13	30	2.48	1.73
I actively seek out new technology resources to enhance my teaching.	10	5	18	17	2.50	0.93

I incorporate educational software designed for social studies to enhance my teaching and students' learning experiences	4	11	19	16	2.06	1.04
I effectively use multimedia tools (e.g., PowerPoint presentations) in my Social Studies instruction.	8	27	7	8	2.70	0.97
I don't know how to conduct assessments and quizzes online to evaluate my students on social studies topics.	12	12	14	12	2.48	0.93
I have received adequate training on how to integrate technology effectively in my social studies teaching.	7	13	11	14	2.06	0.90
I integrate social media platforms (e.g., Twitter, Facebook) to discuss current events and historical topics relevant to social studies	11	6	18	15	2.62	1.78
I feel confident in my ability to use technology to enhance my teaching of social studies	19	10	9	12	2.72	1.50
I assess students' technology skills and provide support as needed in my Social Studies lessons	11	7	22	10	2.38	1.39
Grand Mean					2.45	1.48

Note: SA Strongly Agreed, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree, Std. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Table 1 presents the frequency of response options, mean scores, and standard deviations for all items. The results show that 5 items have mean scores below the criterion mean of 2.5, while 5 items have mean scores of 2.5 and above. Additionally, the grand average for mean and standard deviation is 2.45 and 1.48, respectively. These results indicate a moderate level of technological integration in teaching social studies among secondary school teachers in Ibadan South in Oyo State.

Research Question Two: What types of technology are commonly used and their frequency of use in teaching social studies?

To answer the question, the frequency and percentage of each type of technology and the frequency of their use by teachers were calculated and presented in Figures 1 and 2 respectively.

Figure 1: Percentage of Commonly Used Technology

Figure 2: Percentage of Teachers Using Each Type of Technology

Figure 1 shows the types of technology used by secondary school teachers in teaching social studies, along with the number and percentage of teachers utilising each type as shown in Figure 2. Online resources are the most widely used, with 90% of teachers incorporating them into their teaching. Interactive whiteboards follow closely, utilized by 74% of teachers, while email, used by 64%, remains an important tool for communication and sharing materials. Online collaboration tools and educational software are moderately integrated, with 54% and 50% adoption rates, respectively. Multimedia presentations are employed by 40% of teachers. However, social media platforms and online tests are the least utilized, with only 30% of teachers using them.

Research Question Three: To what extent does technology influence the teaching effectiveness of social studies and student outcomes in the study area?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the extent of Influence of Technology

STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD	Mea n	Std. Dev
Frequency = 50						
Technology with the use of Internet facilities enables effective teaching and learning of Social Studies in schools	21	19	8	2	3.18	0.79
Technology like computers, projectors, slides, etc. complicates Social Studies teaching.	37	10	3	0	3.62	1.23
Application of technology in teaching and learning of Social Studies has improved the performance of students	20	10	13	7	2.86	0.93
E-learning has made teaching and learning of Social Studies interesting	24	11	9	6	3.06	1.04
The use of technology has enhanced student engagement in social studies lessons	28	12	7	3	3.30	0.89
email as a tool for communicating with students and providing feedback on their assignments is not effective	14	12	11	13	2.54	0.93
Technology in social studies class improved students' critical thinking skills	17	23	7	3	2.94	0.90
technology has helped students retain information learned in social studies?	21	15	7	7	3.00	1.18
Technology has facilitated better collaboration among students in social studies	19	20	9	2	3.12	1.30
Technology has made the teaching of social studies effective	21	17	7	5	3.08	1.39
Grand Mean					3.07	1.05

Note: SA= Strongly Agreed, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree, Std. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Table 2 presents the frequency of response options, mean, and standard deviation for all items measuring the influence of technology on teaching effectiveness and student outcomes in Social Studies. The results indicate that item 1 has a mean score of 3.18, which exceeds the criterion mean of 2.5. This suggests that respondents acknowledge the effectiveness of Internet facilities in enhancing the teaching of Social Studies in schools. Similarly, all other items have mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.5. Additionally, the grand average for mean and standard deviation is 3.07 and 1.05, respectively implying that the application of technology in teaching and learning Social Studies has significantly improved the quality of instruction and student learning outcomes.

Research Question Four: What are the challenges that secondary school teachers encounter when integrating technology into social studies instruction in the study area?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Challenges Facing Technology Integration

STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD	Mea n	Std. Dev
Frequency = 50						
Availability of technical support for technology integration in the school.	16	12	8	15	2.62	1.07
I face difficulties in accessing adequate technological resources (e.g., computers, tablets, projectors) for my social studies classes	37	12	0	0	3.68	0.93
There are relevant and sufficient training or professional development opportunities for integrating technology into your social studies teaching	30	10	3	7	3.20	1.13
No reliable internet connectivity to use online resources	24	11	9	6	3.08	1.04

time constraints prevent me from effectively integrating technology into the social studies curriculum	25	18	2	5	3.26	1.29
lack of administrative support or encouragement affects my ability to integrate technology into your social studies teaching	28	12	5	5	3.16	1.03

Grand Mean **3.16** **1.05**

Note: SA= Strongly Agreed, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree, Std. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Table 3 shows the frequency of the response options, mean, and standard deviation for all the items. These 6 items show the challenges facing the effective integration of technology into teaching social studies in secondary schools. these factors include inadequate access to technological resources and support, inadequate training and professional development, no reliable internet connectivity, time constraints, and financial constraints. The results show that all items have their mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.5. This implies that all the items were accepted as secondary school teachers' challenges when integrating technology into social studies instruction in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

The findings highlight a moderate level of technology integration in social studies instruction among secondary school teachers in Ibadan South, Oyo State. While certain technologies, such as online resources and interactive whiteboards, are widely adopted and effectively enhance teaching and learning, others, including social media platforms and online tests, are underutilized due to barriers like privacy concerns and distractions. This aligns with prior research by Ibikunle, Ogunsanmi and Lijofi (2024), indicating that while technology is used, it is not consistently or fully integrated into teaching practices. The varied adoption rates suggest that teachers have diverse experiences with technology, and some tools are used more effectively than others (Aina et al., 2019). High usage of online resources underscores their role in

modern education, offering vast information and interactive content. Similarly, interactive whiteboards and educational software facilitate engaging lessons and adaptive learning. Email remains crucial for communication, while multimedia presentations and collaboration tools support visual learning and teamwork. However, the low integration of social media platforms and online tests indicates the need for strategies to address these challenges and maximize their potential. Respondents generally perceive technology as having a positive impact on teaching effectiveness and student outcomes in social studies, supported by high mean scores across evaluated items. This consensus highlights a shared acknowledgment of technology's benefits, emphasizing its value in enhancing educational practices. However, the study also identifies significant challenges, including inadequate access to resources, insufficient training, unreliable internet connectivity, and financial constraints. These challenges, recognized by all respondents, underscore the need for a comprehensive approach to improving technology integration. Efforts should focus on enhancing resources, infrastructure, and professional development to ensure that technology can be fully leveraged in social studies instruction. The finding is consistent with a previous study by Nathaniel, Philip-kpae and Dickson (2019) that highlights similar barriers and the need for targeted interventions to address them.

Conclusion

There is a moderate adoption of technology in teaching Social Studies, however, its positive impact on instruction quality and student outcomes is clear. Also, addressing the identified challenges is crucial for more effective and widespread integration of technology in education. This will enable secondary school teachers to fully leverage technological tools, thereby enriching the educational experience and outcomes for students in Social Studies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are hereby made.

- i. All schools should be adequately equipped with the necessary technological infrastructure to support effective teaching and learning.
- ii. Technology integration should be a core component of teacher professional development to ensure that educators are well-prepared to incorporate digital tools into their teaching practices.
- iii. Increased funding from government and private sectors should be advocated to support the integration of technology into education.
- iv. Policies that support and encourage the use of technology in education should be developed and implemented.

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Transformational Leadership Approach and its Impact on Church Growth in Local Baptist Churches in Oyo and its Environs

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Abstract

A leadership style determines how leaders implement plans and strategies to accomplish given objectives while accounting for stakeholder expectations and the well-being and soundness of their team. Thus, no local church can grow and be sustained beyond her leader. Studies have been made on transformational leadership's principles, dimensions and development. However, this study investigated the impacts of transformational leadership on church growth among local Baptist churches in Oyo and its environs. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The study's sample size consisted of 300 respondents purposefully selected randomly from fifty (50) local Baptist churches in Oyo and its environs. Primary data source includes questionnaire and structured interview guide. Secondary data source includes books, journals, magazines, periodicals and Internet sources. The findings showed that well-organized management of resources, increase productivity, improve team building, increase in spiritual growth of the church, creativity and innovation, and actualization of church goals are the impacts of transformational leadership approach on church growth among local Baptist churches in Oyo and its environs. The study conclude that transformational leadership approach affords everyone involved in the organization to move at the same pace and get the goals and the missions of the organization achieved. The study, therefore, recommended that that leaders in Local Baptist churches in Oyo and its environs adopt transformational leadership approach as leadership model for church growth.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Church Growth, Local Baptist Churches and Oyo

Introduction

The Church which is the gathering of believers has goals that are clearly stated in the Bible which is the expected level the local church should be operating. No local church can grow and be sustained beyond her leader. Nihinlola (2010) explained that in the most basic form and everyday use, leadership is the position occupied by a person who guides or directs a group, team, organization, etc. Some other definitions incorporate the purpose or essence of leadership such as service, influence, guidance, transformation, etc. Leadership styles are generally classified as dictatorial/authoritarian, authoritative, consultative, participative, democratic and *laisser-faire* (Akintunde, 2007). These various styles have to do with the use of power and authority in leadership. While the autocratic styles involve decision making without consultation with followers, the other extreme is permissive leaders who simply allow the organization to run without giving any clear directives. While different circumstances may call for different styles, the best leadership style generally is the consultative-participative styles whereby the leader involves his followers in decision-making process.

A leadership style determines how leaders implement plans and strategies to accomplish given objectives while accounting for stakeholder expectations and the wellbeing and soundness of their team. Leadership styles have been studied in various forms to establish the appropriate or most effective leadership style that motivates and influences others to accomplish set goals. The major tenet of effective leadership style is the degree to which it builds follower trust (Klan, 2008). There are different types of leadership style and the focus on this study is on transformational leadership approach. Transformational leadership is the process by which a person interacts with others and is able to create a solid relationship that results in a high percentage of trust that will later result in an increase of motivation both intrinsic and extrinsic in both leaders and followers. The essence of transformational leadership is that leaders transform their followers through their inspirational nature and personalities. These attributes provide a sense of belonging for the followers as they can easily identify with the leader and its purpose. Transformational leadership approach affords everyone involved in the organization to move at the same pace and get the goals and the missions of the organization achieved. Generally, a lot of studies have been carried out on the subject of

transformational leadership style. Studies by Ifatokun (2023), Adebayo (2023), Ishola (2021), Morillo-Shone, (2015), Mwambazambi & Banza, (2014), among others attest to this fact. However, the aforementioned studies have not sufficiently investigated transformational leadership approach and its impacts on church growth in local Baptist churches in Oyo and its environs. The aim is to examine the impact of transformational leadership approach on church growth among Local Baptist Churches (LBCs) in Oyo and its environs. A local Baptist church is a religious organization that belongs to the Baptist denomination and is located in a specific community or region. A local Baptist church is a religious organization that plays an important role in the spiritual, social and cultural life of its community. It provides a supportive community for members to worship learn and grow in their faith, as well as a platform for engagement and service to the wider community.

This study will be of immense benefits to the leaders, most especially leaders of LBCs in Oyo and its environs and other places as findings could be used to encourage leaders to engage transformational leadership approach for the growth of the church in LBCs in Oyo and its environs and other places. The research will also expose the leaders to maximizing their leadership skills and responsibilities for the growth of the church. The result of the study will sensitize leaders in Baptist churches and other Christian denominations to have and keep the consciousness of the fact that the church should not just grow for a while but the growth of the church must be sustained continuously. To achieve this task, the study employs descriptive survey research design. It involves collecting data that accurately and objectively describe how things are in their present situation. The sample size of the study consisted of 300 respondents purposefully selected randomly from fifty (50) local Baptist churches in Oyo and its environs. Primary source of data includes questionnaire and structure interview guide and secondary source of data include books, journals, magazines, periodicals and internet source.

Concept of Transformational Leadership

A transformational leader is one who is able to recognize and enhance an existing need or demand of a potential follower. Transformational leader looks for potential motives in the followers, seeks to satisfy higher needs, and engages the full person of the follower. The result is a

relationship of mutual stimulation and elevation that converts followers into leaders and may convert leaders into moral agents. Transforming leadership becomes 'moral' in that it raises the level of human conduct and ethical aspiration of both the leaders and the led, and thus it has a transforming effect on both. Perhaps the best modern example is Gandhi, who aroused and elevated the hopes and demands of millions of Indians and whose life and responsibility were enhanced in the process (Burns, 1978).

A transformational leader is a leader who understands his or her moral responsibility as that of contributing to the transformation and enhancement of individuals and communities or organizations for a higher communal good (Mwambazambi & Banza, 2014). Transformational leaders transform followers by creating changes in their goals, values, beliefs and aspirations (Mathafena, 2007). Commenting then on their behavior, action, role and influence scholar emphasizes that these leaders behave according to transformational leadership principles and hence become admired role models who are respected, emulated and trusted. One of the key things a leader does to earn credibility is the consideration of the needs of others over his or her personal needs.

Leaders share risks with followers and are consistent rather than arbitrary; they can be counted on to do the right thing, demonstrating high standards of ethical and moral conduct; they avoid using power for personal gain- and then only when needed. Leaders behave in ways that motivate and inspire those around them by providing meaning and challenge to their followers' work. Team spirit is aroused, enthusiasm and optimism are displayed. Leaders get followers involved in envisioning attractive future states (Mathafena, 2007).

Scholar equally posits that transformational leaders engender trust, seek to develop leadership in others, exhibit self-sacrifice and serve as moral agents, focusing their attention and that of their followers on objectives that transcend the more immediate needs of work groups. Transformational leadership can produce significant organizational change and results, because this form of leadership fosters higher levels of intrinsic motivation, trust, commitment, and loyalty from followers than do most leadership practices. Transformational leadership is measured by both the leader's performance and development, and by the degree to which associates are developed to their full leadership

potential. The associates are encouraged to use the techniques of effective leadership (Mathafena, 2007).

Features of Transformational Leadership

The specific features of transformational leadership are able to achieve the needed transformation in any organization. Scholar observes that if one understands leadership to be transforming situations, environments and organizations to a more desired state, then the question is: 'What are the essential qualities in a leader that enable him or her to influence others in such a way that they collectively contribute to transformation?' As mentioned above, transformational leaders generally look beyond their personal achievements. They are not intent on using their power or influence to make themselves look good (Van, 2007). The essence of leadership as argue by scholar is to focus on the needs of others and then apply one's talents, technical, rational, and emotional as well as one's visualizing abilities to address those needs (Greenleaf, 2002).

Leaders see themselves as catalysts and facilitators in the creation of something that is only possible with collective effort and the talents of diverse people, something that represents further possibilities for growth. The focus of their approach is to facilitate the process where a growing number of members have internalized shared values that motivate their contributions. That way people motivate themselves and the relationship with the leader become interdependent and not dependent. It furthermore implies the leader's willingness to enable and to empower others (Van, 2007). Transformational leadership is therefore a kind of leadership that is selfless and ethical in intent, in behavior and in action. A transformational leader uses his or her own skills, qualities and values as well as those of others to positively influence the lives of the followers who, in turn, grow into solid transformational leaders capable of transforming individuals, organizations and communities. Contributing to the development of the required leadership from within the very community that needs the leaders will demand church leaders to know their church members who can contribute to leadership development and who can also effectively use their expertise for this purpose. They will equally need to understand community potential and problems as well as cultural issues which can create unnecessary clashes.

Principles of Transformational Leadership

This section discusses seven principles of transformational leadership.

1. *Principle of Simplification:* Successful leadership begins with a vision, which reflects the shared purpose. This is the ability to articulate a clear, practical, transformational vision which answers the question, "Where are we headed?" For any team, discussing goals, objectives and vision unifies the members (Avolio & Bass, 1991).
2. *Commitment of Other People to the Vision:* Once the transformational leader is able to bring synergy to the organization, he must then use various means to energize (motivate) the staff. A common way to motivate others is to challenge them, provide ample opportunity to join the creative process, and give them the credit (Rees, 2010).
3. *Principle of Facilitation:* This is the ability to effectively facilitate the learning of individuals, teams, and other reliable and reputable resources. The primary job of leadership now is to facilitate the learning's of others. The inborn quest of humans (staff) to learn more and more becomes the leaders' greatest asset to address organizational challenges. Transformational leaders have been given a sacred trust of being stewards of their staff's intellectual capital (Blaine, 2017).
4. *Principle of Innovation:* An effective and efficient organization requires members to anticipate change and not fear it. Leaders must initiate and respond quickly to change. Team members successfully influence one another to assimilate change because the transformational leaders have built trust and fostered teamwork (Avolio & Bass, 1991).
5. *Principle of Mobilization:* This is the ability to enlist, equip and empower others to fulfill the vision. Transformational leaders look for willing participants who have already been given formal leadership responsibilities and also among people who have not. They desire leadership at all levels, so they find ways to invite and ignite leadership all levels. They introduce simple baby steps to enlist larger participants (Adebayo, 2023).
6. *Principle of Preparation:* This is the ability to never stop learning about themselves with and without the help of others. Transformational leaders realize that the transformation they pursue in is a reflection of their own spiritual quest- that they must serve the world through their giftedness because that is the only way they truly

fulfill their life mission. With this mindset, moments of being stuck become moments of total dependence on God. This is such a rigorous path of learning that transformational leaders must be in thriving relationships with others pursuing transformation (Ishola, 2021). It is within these vital relationships; life opportunities and obstacles get saturated in love and support.

7. *Principle of Determination:* A leader's mission is sometime difficult and their journey often lonely. Leaders depend on their stamina, endurance, courage and strength to finish each day. Because their focus is not only on raising their own leadership but the development of others, the most rigorous and humbling of all human endeavors, transformational leaders experience times of self-doubt, grief and fatigue. Transformational leaders have to develop spiritual, emotional, and physical disciplines to sustain their high level of commitment to their cause. Transformational leaders, then, are awareness raisers who see strategic initiatives to be fulfilled, problems that align with their own spiritual life mission. As they make leadership commitments to those strategic initiatives, they make commitments to their own emergence. As the leaders transform, the world is transformed (Ifatokun, 2023).

Concept of Church Growth

According to Rainer (1998), church growth is a discipline, which is concerned about the planting and continuing health of local churches and groups of churches. It cares deeply about anything that may engender or hinder the starting and continuing of local churches. Church growth is the discipline which investigates the nature, expansion, planting, multiplication, function and health of Christian churches as they relate to the effective implementation of God's commission to make disciples of all people (Matthew 28:18-20). Scholar buttresses further that, church growth means all that is involved in bringing men and women who do not have a personal relationship to Jesus Christ into leadership with him and into responsible church membership (Hopkins, 2008).

Church growth can be defined as the process by which changes are realizing in the church whether by size or volume. In other word, it is the way by which the church is experiencing positive change within the Church. This can be actualized physically (in the sense that the church

experiences growth in number or in material) and spiritually (in the sense that the Church has deeper knowledge of God and His word that is, they have spiritual changes in their life positively) (Torbert, 1961). Church growth is a biblical concept since church as a congregation of believers needs to grow just as the believer is meant to grow until they reach maturity in Christ Jesus. Church growth is, therefore, an activity of God through men in the salvation work of redeeming men. Church growth began with God through the person of the Lord Jesus Christ. Jesus also explained the basic concept of Church growth in the parable of the Kingdom of God which Jesus linked to a mustard seed. The seed when planted grows up to becomes the greatest of all shrub (Luke 13:20-21; Mark 4:30-32) which point to the fact that church growth is an act of God which must be carried out through the instrumentality of men, using God's way and method. Since the kingdom of God will grow regardless of the tactics of Satan. It then means, church of God will grow when it is planted and continue to nurture, using God's way and method, more so when in obedience to God commandment (Wagner, 1978).

Historically, Church growth can be traced to the beginning of the ministry of Jesus Christ from the conversion of the first believer in Christ Jesus to the time Jesus selected twelve disciples and the formation of the congregation of believer (the first Church in Jerusalem). The growth of the church then continues with series of activities and through events in history, that tries to activates and reformed the church to meet up with the challenges of the time. Such is the early period of 1500s, with the Reformation started by Martin Luther, when Martin Luther noticed that the Church seemed stagnant and corrupted with wrong doctrine. This Reformation stirred the people up to the need to turn to the Bible as the basis for the active life of the church. As the church returned to the Bible, it became renewed and came alive. Hence, the church freed herself from death of holding to salvation by work and became dependent on God's grace which sufficiently paid for man's sin in Christ Jesus once and for all (Wagner, 1978).

McGavran developed the theory of church growth, by setting up a definite objective which made more effective the propagation of the gospel and multiplication of churches on new ground. The scholar believed that church growth principle has a universal application. He started with the mission field and later spread to America. Again, he disputed the non-Biblical position held by American churches, a position

that glorifies quality (Hunter, 1983). Scholar further defines Church Growth as “All that is involved in bringing men and women who do not have a personal relationship with Jesus Christ into fellowship with Him and into responsible church membership” (Hunter, 1983). This definition seems to define evangelism, but it is too broad for Church Growth because of the phrase "all that is involved which could include the areas of Christian education, pastoral theology, missiology, or other disciplines.” In a later definition, the scholar writes: Church growth is that science which investigates the planting, multiplication, function and health of Christian churches as they relate specifically to the effective implementation of God's commission to "make disciples of all nations" (Matt 18:19-20). Church growth strives to combine the eternal theological principles of God's Word concerning the expansion of the church with the best insights of contemporary social and behavioral sciences, employing as its initial frame of reference (Hunter, 1983) Scholars also aver that, Church growth is that science that investigates the planting, multiplication, growth, function, health, and death of churches. It strives to apply the biblical and social principles in its gathering, analysis, displaying, and defending of the facts involved in implementing the Great Commission (Wagner, 1970). In the light of the foregoing, one can understand that church growth has nothing to do much with fantasy of the church or numerical possession. Church growth in real sense is more than that. Church growth is therefore a unique discipline in that it is a selfless service to God. It requests for self-sacrifice and it is also a task demanding business. Church growth in the researcher opinion therefore, is a progressive development or increment of a local body of Christ in physical structure, mental, numerical and spiritual.

Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Impacts of Transformational Leadership approach on Church Growth among LBCs in Oyo

Items	Respondents	SA	A	SD	D	Total
	Pastors	32	18	0	0	50

Well-organized management of resources	Deacons	28	20	1	1	50
	Workers	20	26	3	1	50
	Members	139	10	0	1	150
	Total	219	74	4	3	300
	Total Percentage	73%	24.7%	1.3%	1%	100%
Increase productivity	Pastors	39	11	0	0	50
	Deacons	26	24	0	0	50
	Workers	40	10	0	0	50
	Members	107	38	2	3	150
	Total	212	83	2	3	300
	Total Percentage	70.7%	27.7%	0.6%	1%	100%
Improve team building	Pastors	24	25	1	0	50
	Deacons	21	28	0	1	50
	Workers	23	22	4	1	50
	Members	103	44	0	3	150
	Total	171	119	5	5	300
	Total Percentage	57%	39.6%	1.7%	1.7%	100%
	Pastors	39	7	0	4	50

Increase in spiritual growth of the church	Deacons	26	20	1	3	50
	Workers	43	7	0	0	50
	Members	95	25	15	15	150
	Total	203	59	16	22	300
	Total Percentage	67.7%	19.7%	5.3%	7.3%	100%
Increase in numerical growth of the church	Pastors	21	23	4	2	50
	Deacons	13	28	3	6	50
	Workers	20	27	2	1	50
	Members	94	35	11	10	150
	Total	148	113	20	19	300
	Total Percentage	49.3%	37.7%	6.7%	6.3%	100%
Actualization of church goals	Pastors	29	18	1	2	50
	Deacons	37	13	0	0	50
	Workers	39	7	2	2	50
	Members	93	54	2	1	150
	Total	198	92	5	5	300
	Total Percentage	66%	30.6%	1.7%	1.7%	100%
Increased commitment	Pastors	23	19	0	9	50
	Deacons	27	19	2	2	50

from members	Workers	28	15	7	3	50
	Members	58	71	13	4	150
	Total	136	124	22	18	300
	Total Percentage	45.4%	41.3%	7.3%	6%	100%
Encourage creativity and innovation	Pastors	17	23	6	4	50
	Deacons	29	15	1	5	50
	Workers	29	15	0	6	50
	Members	75	45	19	11	150
	Total	150	98	26	26	300
	Total Percentage	50%	32.6%	8.7%	8.7%	100%

The table shows the impacts of transformational leadership approach on church growth among LBCs in Oyo and its environs. The table discloses that 97.7% of the respondents agreed that transformational leadership style will bring about well-organized management of resources among LBCs in Oyo and its environ. It reveals that transformational leadership brings about increase productivity as agreed by 98.4% of the respondents. Also, 96.6% of the respondents agreed that transformational leadership improve team building. 87.4% and 87% of the respondents also agreed that increase in spiritual and numerical growth of the church respectively are impacts of transformational leadership style on church growth among LBCs in Oyo and its environs. Furthermore, the table reveals 86.6% of the respondents agreeing to the statement that actualization of church goals is achievable through

transformational leadership style. Therefore, 86.7% of the respondents agreed that transformational leadership brings about increased commitment from members. As such, 82.6% of the respondents agreed that transformational leadership encourage creativity and innovation.

Figure showing Proportion of respondents on the impacts of transformational leadership on Church Growth

Responses from the interviewee further reveals that transformational leadership has a very significant role to play in church growth. Respondents affirmed that transformational leadership leads with clear vision. Such leader has the ability to set new goals and introduces new ideas for sustainable church growth. Transformational leadership allows teamwork for maximum result. There will be cooperations as people will be ready to work getting results will not be difficult. Findings from the table shows that transformational leadership style improve team building. This aligns with scholar assertion that effective transformational leaders are constantly encouraging and building the confidence of their team which counteracts all the negative things they either think about themselves or the negative information they are bombard with via media and relationships (Ishola, 2021). The results of the findings also reveal that adopting transformational leadership style by church leaders will cause increase in both spiritual and numerical growth of the church. Scholars alluded that transformational pastoral

leader focuses primarily on the spiritual transformation of the people in a manner that enables them to fulfil their God-given destiny (Ifatokun, 2023). Transformational pastoral leaders lead through the consciousness of their responsibility to guide the people towards God, and influence them to make a difference in the world. In this way, they use their God-given knowledge, the Bible, spiritual gifts and training to nurture and transform the people through care, encouragement and motivation. Scholars opined that the ability of a pastoral leader to effectively inspire and stimulate transformation in the attitude and behaviour of the congregation and the church as a whole made the transformational pastoral leadership style a catalyst for growing a healthy church (Adebayo, 2023). Others impacts of transformational leadership style on church growth as reveals by the findings are increase productivity and the encouragement of creativity and innovation. Scholar also posited that transformational leadership style enhances gift development (Ishola, 2019). Transformational leadership provide this through individual members to achieve their potential through coaching and mentoring. Therefore, it can be deduced that transformational leadership style is an appropriate model to adopt by church leaders in LBCs in Oyo and its environs for sustaining church growth.

Conclusion and Recommendations

No local church can grow and be sustained beyond her leader. A leadership style determines how leaders implement plans and strategies to accomplish given objectives while accounting for stakeholder expectations and the wellbeing and soundness of their team. Transformational leadership approach affords everyone involved in the organization to move at the same pace and get the goals and the missions of the organization achieved. This study, therefore, affirmed that well-organized management of resources, increase productivity, improve team building, increase in spiritual growth of the church, creativity and innovation, and actualization of church goals as the impact of transformational leadership approach on church growth among local Baptist churches in Oyo and its environs. In the light of the findings, it is therefore, recommended that leaders in LBCs in Oyo and its environs adopt transformational leadership approach as leadership model for church growth.

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Marital Status as Determinant of Mission Engagement among Female Missionaries in The Redeemed Christian Church of God, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study stems from the need to understand the disparate treatment of trained female missionaries, often triggered by gender and marital considerations and which results in unemployment, limited opportunities for education, or participation in leadership processes. Therefore, this study examined female missionaries' perceptions, attitudes, and experiences regarding marital challenges in The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) Mission Engagements. Grounded in the Intersectional Feminism Theory, it contributed to the literature on the experience of female missionaries in Nigeria. The study used a descriptive survey research design to randomly select 69 respondents from the estimated population of 250-trained female missionaries across Nigeria. It used a validated questionnaire, administered through Google Forms, to gather data on demographics and specific research questions. Findings reveal that female missionaries align with RCCG's mission and are actively engaged (Mean scores of 3.45 and 3.38). They acknowledge challenges, (mean score = 2.52) but view mission work as central to their purpose (mean score = 3.58). Marital status wields a modest positive effect on engagement (coefficient = 0.135, $p = 0.036$), explains approximately 4.1% of variances, but is not a significant barrier (mean score = 2.23) to mission engagement, though non-significant p -values (Fisher's Exact Test; $p=0.152$) call for caution when interpreting their impact. The study concluded that trained female missionaries in RCCG show high levels of mission engagement and positively perceive marital considerations. The study recommended that the Church protect female missionaries' well-being, expose senior pastors to missions training, and incentivise those prioritising mission work over marital status.

Keywords: Female Missionaries, Intersectional Feminism, Marital Status, Mission Engagement, The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG)

Introduction

The Redeemed Christian Church of God, one of Nigeria's most prominent religious institutions, is well-known for its broad domestic and international missionary efforts. With a solid dedication to evangelism and missions, RCCG became one of Nigeria's most significant Pentecostal churches since its founding in 1952. The RCCG's female missionaries are critical in furthering the church's mission. Yet, it is clear that extant literature has not sufficiently examined their experiences and difficulties, particularly concerning marital status.

While a researcher (Kirkwood, 2021) has identified marital status as a critical factor that significantly affects the engagement and effectiveness of female missionaries, others have indicated that married missionaries face dual responsibilities related to family and mission, potentially impacting their availability and performance in the field (Waha, 2024; Manktelow, 2016). On the other hand, unmarried missionaries may experience distinct societal pressures and professional challenges, particularly in the Nigerian context, where cultural and religious expectations regarding marriage and gender roles are deeply entrenched (Kolapo, & Kolapo, 2019).

In Nigeria, cultural and religious norms influence the roles and perceptions of female missionaries in variegated ways in the respective geopolitical zones (Arnold, 2023). The societal expectation that women should prioritise marriage and family life can create additional challenges for female missionaries, whether married or unmarried (Abolaji, 2024). Understanding how these factors intersect with missionary work is crucial for academic inquiry and practical application within RCCG.

Research on marital status impact on female missionaries' engagement is relatively scarce. This review synthesises existing literature through the lens of Intersectional Feminism Theory to provide a context for understanding how marital status influences female missionaries' involvement in Church missions.

Intersectional Feminism was adopted as the study's theoretical framework, as Kimberlé Crenshaw (1989) proposed. Intersectional

Feminism examines how various forms of social stratification, such as race, gender, and marital status, intersect to influence individuals' experiences and opportunities. This framework helps analyse how overlapping identities impact female missionaries' engagement in Church missions. It allows for a nuanced understanding of how marital status interacts with gender norms and religious expectations, shaping the experiences and roles of female missionaries in complex ways.

Goff (2022) emphasises the pivotal role of women in mission work, particularly in reaching populations that are otherwise inaccessible due to cultural restrictions. According to Intersectional Feminism, these roles are not experienced uniformly but are shaped by intersecting factors such as marital status. Famoroti (2023) extends this by highlighting the benefits of women in mission leadership roles, noting that challenges related to marital status can impact their effectiveness. The Intersectional Feminism framework helps to understand how other identity factors compound these challenges.

Laine's study (2024) on missionary work in China reveals the complexities married missionaries face, who often balance family responsibilities with their mission duties, potentially limiting their effectiveness (Scales, 2024). This finding is aligned with Intersectional Feminism, which posits that married female missionaries face compounded pressures due to their dual roles. Conversely, Isabel (2022) addresses the unique challenges before unmarried female missionaries, such as societal scrutiny and church expectations, which Intersectional Feminism frames as aspects of their intersecting identities that affect their roles.

In Nigeria, gender roles and marital expectations significantly impact female missionaries. Chinyere, Khatidja, and Lorraine (2022) explore how these cultural norms affect married and unmarried women, finding that societal pressures can hinder mission engagement. Talatu (2020) further highlights the need for supportive structures within the Church for unmarried female missionaries. Intersectional Feminism provides a lens through which these cultural norms and expectations can be analysed as intersecting forces that shape the experiences of female missionaries.

Statement of the Problem

The experiences of female missionaries are marked by complexity, progress, setbacks, and ongoing struggles for equality and empowerment, despite their vital and expanding role in the mission outreaches and efforts of The Redeemed Christian Church of God to fulfil the Great Commission. These challenges stem from patriarchal structures, religious traditions, and systemic inequalities that result in marital or gender pay gaps, underrepresentation in leadership, and limited access to opportunities. Despite growing attention to gender equality, there is still a limited understanding of the specific types of discrimination that female missionaries face, particularly when intersecting with factors like marital status, class, race, sexuality, and ability.

Reports indicate limited job opportunities and, in some cases, outright denial of opportunities for female missionaries, influenced by marital status. This situation questions RCCG's commitment to gender equality and fairness, revealing unequal experiences for female missionaries despite the church's perceived supportive environment. This gap highlights the need to explore how marital status creates unique discriminatory experiences for female missionaries within RCCG.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims to assess the role of marital status as a determinant of mission engagement among female missionaries in RCCG across Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. ascertain female missionaries' perception of their mission engagement experience in The Redeemed Christian Church of God mission activities.
2. ascertain female missionaries' perception of marital considerations on the mission engagement of female missionaries within The Redeemed Christian Church of God.
3. assess the effect of female missionaries' perception of marital considerations on the mission engagement of female missionaries in The Redeemed Christian Church of God.

Research Questions

1. What is female missionaries' perception of their mission engagement experience in The Redeemed Christian Church of God mission activities?
2. What is female missionaries' perception of marital considerations within The Redeemed Christian Church of God?
3. How does female missionaries' perception of marital considerations affect their mission engagement in The Redeemed Christian Church of God?

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which made the systematic collection and analysis of data to describe the characteristics and experiences of the study population from the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria possible, providing a robust dataset for subsequent analysis. The study population includes approximately 250 trained and certified female missionaries who are engaged in mission fields, or awaiting deployment, across various provinces in Nigeria.

The study selected one hundred (100) trained female missionaries serving in different parts of Nigeria but made accessible by shared ministerial groups on the WhatsApp social media platform using simple random sampling method. The response rate was 69% (N=69), and the distribution included respondents who were predominantly married (60%), while the remainder were single (25%) or widowed (15). Also, interview data collection involved two (2) RCCG regional mission coordinators, two (2) provincial mission coordinators, and the Redeemed College of Missions deployment manager to ascertain further the responses gathered from female missionaries.

Data were collected using instruments designed by the researcher. A pilot study conducted among female missionaries in the Redeemed College of Missions in Ede South Local Government of Osun State was used to ascertain the reliability of the research instrument. The study tested the three instruments' reliability, using Cronbach's Alpha, with the following result: (a) Perception of Gender and Marital Considerations in Mission Engagement (PGMCMEQ) $r = .872$. (b) Interview Guide for Church Mission Coordinators (InGuCMC)(c) Interview Guide for Deployment Manager (InGuDeM). The study used

an interview guide to facilitate an in-depth qualitative exploration of the themes identified in the survey. It contained open-ended questions aimed at uncovering the nuanced experiences of female missionaries, particularly how their marital status influenced their deployment, engagement, and overall mission effectiveness. Concerned Mission leaders, the Mission's Deployment Personnel and other key RCCG officials who oversee mission activities participated in the interview.

Demographic Information of the Respondents (N=69)

Figure 1: Distributions of Respondents per Nigerian State (Source: Researcher's Fieldwork 2023)

Figure 1 presents the distribution of the sample of respondents selected for the study and shows the sparsely distributed nature of the target population, into the national spread of the regions and provinces of The Redeemed Christian Church of God.

Figure 2: Deployment Status of Married Respondents
(Source: Researcher's Fieldwork 2023)

Figure 2 presents the mission engagement of the married respondents.

Figure 3: Deployment Statuses of Single Respondents
(Source: Field Survey 2023)

Figure 3 presents the mission engagement of the unmarried missionaries.

Results and Findings

Research Questions One: What is female missionaries' perception of their Mission Engagement experience in The Redeemed Christian Church of God mission activities?

Female Missionaries' Perception of Mission Engagement in The Redeemed Christian Church of God (N = 69)

S/N	Perception of Female Missionaries' Mission Engagement in The Redeemed Christian Church of God	Not True of Me (1)	Some-what True of Me (2)	True of Me (3)	Very True of Me (4)	\bar{X} =2.5	Decision
1	I feel properly aligned with The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission, vision and values.	4 5.80%	6 8.70%	14 20.29%	45 65.22%	3.45	Accepted
2	I happily, actively, voluntarily and resourcefully participate in The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission-related activities.	8 11.60%	3 4.34%	13 18.84%	45 65.22%	3.38	Accepted
3	The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission	5 7.24%	12 17.39%	15 21.74%	37 53.62%	3.22	Accepted

	policy inspires my personal commitment to mission work.							
4	I have encountered challenges as a female missionary that seriously affect my engagement with The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission activities.	18	17	14	20	2.52	Accepted	
			24.64%	20.29%	28.99%			
		26.09%						
5	Mission engagement i.e. serving God with all my heart, strength, and soul, as a missionary is essential to my sense of purpose and fulfilment.	4	2	13	50	3.58	Accepted	
		5.80%	2.9%	18.84%	72.4%			
6	My involvement in mission work has evolved, but negatively, over the years.	33	12	18	6	1.96	Rejected	
			17.39%	26.09%	8.7%			
		47.82%						
7	The treatment of female missionaries by leaders in The Redeemed Christian Church	23	11	17	18	2.43	Rejected	
		33.33%	15.94%	24.64%	26.09%			

of God's mission work in areas like employment, posting to different mission field assignments, and promotion, are meaningful to me personally.

8	I believe that my contributions to The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission have a meaningful impact.	5	2	13	49	3.54	Accepted
		7.24%	2.9%	18.84%	71.01%		
9	I am motivated to continually improve my role in The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission activities.	7	8	9	49	3.33	Accepted
		10.14%	11.59%	13.04%	71.01%		
10	I find joy/satisfaction in fulfilling The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission.	5	6	15	43	3.39	Accepted
		7.24%	8.7%	21.74%	62.32%		
Overall Mean Score for the Perception of Mission Engagement = 2.80							Accepted

Source: Researcher's Field Data 2023

Research Question Two: What is female missionaries' perception of Marital Considerations in The Redeemed Christian Church of God Mission Engagements?

Table 2 Perception of Marital Considerations in The Redeemed Christian Church of God Mission Engagement (N = 69)

S/ N	Item Statement	Not True of Me (1)	Some-True of Me (2)	True of Me (3)	Very True of Me (4)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mean = 2.5	Decision
1	My marital status affects my ability to participate in The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission activities.	27 39.13%	14 20.29%	13 18.84%	15 21.74%	2.2	Rejected
2	I have observed differences in how married and unmarried individuals engage with The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission work.	15 21.74%	12 17.39%	16 23.19%	26 37.68%	2.7	Accepted
3	In my opinion, The Redeemed Christian Church of God provides adequate support and accommodations for missionaries with varying marital statuses.	20 28.99%	19 27.54%	13 18.84%	17 24.64%	2.3	Rejected
4	Specific challenges or advantages are associated with my	17 24.64%	13 18.84%	23 33.33%	16 23.19%	2.5	Accepted

marital status in mission engagement.

5	I believe that The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission is inclusive of individuals with diverse marital situations.	18	11	22	18	2.5 8	Accepted
		26.09%	15.94%	31.88%	26.09%		
6	My spouse's or family's support or involvement affects my mission engagement.	22	12	14	21	2.4 9	Rejected
		31.88%	17.39%	20.29%	30.43%		
7	Marital-related experiences have influenced my perception of The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission.	17	15	15	22	2.6 1	Accepted
		24.64%	21.74%	21.74%	31.88%		
8	I believe that a supportive marital environment enhances my mission engagement.	6	7	15	41	3.3 2	Accepted
		8.70%	10.14%	21.74%	59.42%		
9	I believe that The Redeemed Christian Church of God recognizes and values the contributions of married missionaries.	9	9	14	37	3.1 4	Accepted
		13.04%	13.04%	20.29%	53.62%		
10	My marital status has never been a hindrance to my involvement in The Redeemed Christian Church of God's mission.	10	9	15	35	3.0 9	Accepted
		14.49%	13.04%	21.74%	50.72%		

Mean Score for the Perception of Marital Considerations in The Redeemed Christian Church of God Mission Engagement =2.72 **2.7 Accepted**

Source: Researcher’s Field Data 2023

Research Question Three: What is the effect of female missionaries’ perception of Marital Considerations on their Mission Engagements within The Redeemed Christian Church of God?

Table 3 Coefficients Table: Linear Regression on Marital Considerations and Mission Engagement

Model	Coefficients ^a						
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	1.698	0.122		13.943	0	1.456	1.939
1 PMC	0.135	0.064	0.203	2.129	0.036	0.009	0.262

a. Dependent Variable: LEVELME
 Source: Researcher’s Construct 2023

The intercept reveals the estimated mean mission engagement when marital considerations are absent, indicated by a constant value of 1.698 (t = 13.943, p < 0.001). The key finding, however, is the coefficient for Marital Considerations (PMC), which is 0.135 (t = 2.129, p = 0.036). This coefficient indicates that with each one-unit increase in marital

considerations, there is a corresponding 0.135 increase in mission engagement. The 95% confidence interval (ci: 0.009, 0.262), which excludes zero, further supports the significance.

Table 4: ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) Table: Linear Regression on Marital Considerations and Mission Engagement

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.196	1	0.196	4.534	.036 ^b
	Residual	4.573	106	0.043		
	Total	4.769	107			

a. Dependent Variable: LEVELME

b. Predictors: (Constant), PMC

Source: Researcher’s Construct 2023

The results in Table 4 confirm the statistical significance of the overall regression model. The F-value of 4.534 ($p = 0.036$) signifies that the model, including marital considerations, significantly predicts mission engagement. The variance is 0.196, underscoring the strength of the relationship, explained by the model, and represented by the Regression Sum of Squares.

Table 5 Model Summary Table: Linear Regression on Marital Considerations and Mission Engagement

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the	Change Statistics				
					R Square	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change

				th e Es ti m at e	Cha nge				
1	.2 0 3 ^a	0.0 41	0.03 2	0. 2 07 7	0.04 1	4.534	1	1 0 6	0.036

a. Predictors: (Constant), PMC
 Source: Researcher's Construct 2023

The Model Summary Table 5 enhances our comprehension of the model's predictive capacity. An R Square value of 0.041 indicates that around 4.1% of the variability in mission engagement can be attributed to marital considerations. Considering the number of predictors, the Adjusted R Square is 0.032. The F Change statistic (4.534, $df_1 = 1$, $df_2 = 106$, $p = 0.036$) mirrors the observed statistical significance in the ANOVA Table, reinforcing the idea that marital considerations make a substantive contribution to the model.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one revealed that most female missionaries feel strongly aligned with RCCG's mission, vision, and values (mean score = 3.45) and actively participate in mission Findings from research question one show that most female missionaries feel strongly aligned with RCCG's mission, vision, and values (mean score = 3.45) and actively participate in mission activities (mean score = 3.38). RCCG's mission policies (mean score = 3.22) inspire and help them view mission engagement as central to their purpose and fulfilment (mean score = 3.58). The study identified challenges confronting female missionaries' engagement, which are not overwhelmingly negative, as attested by the

mean score 2.52. Conversely, the study rejected perceptions that their involvement has negatively evolved over the years (mean score = 1.96) and the meaningfulness of treatment by leaders (mean score = 2.43), which suggests generally positive or neutral views in these areas. Additionally, the belief in the meaningful impact of their contributions (mean score = 3.54) and motivation to improve (mean score = 3.33) were "strongly" accepted. The mean score of 2.80 indicates a generally positive perception of mission engagement among female missionaries in RCCG.

Research question two revealed that marital status does not adversely affect participation in mission activities (mean score = 2.23), and female missionaries view the adequacy of support for varying marital statuses sceptically (mean score = 2.39). However, there is acceptance of the observation that differences exist in how married and unmarried individuals engage in mission work (mean score = 2.77) and that specific challenges or advantages are associated with marital status (mean score = 2.55). The respondents positively viewed the inclusivity of individuals with diverse marital situations in RCCG's mission (mean score = 2.58). They see supportive marital environments as enhancing mission engagement (mean score = 3.32) and acknowledge the value RCCG places on contributions from married missionaries (mean score = 3.14). The results reveal that female missionaries recognise marital status as a factor and not a significant barrier to mission involvement, as affirmed by the mean score of 2.72.

Research question three assessed the effect of female missionaries' perceptions of marital considerations on their mission engagement in The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG). The first significant finding is from the Linear regression analysis, which indicates that marital considerations (PMC) positively affect mission engagement, with a coefficient of 0.135 ($p = 0.036$). This coefficient implies a simultaneous increase of 0.135 units in mission engagement for each unit increase in marital considerations. Also, the confidence interval (0.009 to 0.262) confirms the statistical significance of this effect. The ANOVA results indicate that the regression model significantly predicts mission engagement, with an F-value of 4.534 ($p = 0.036$) and indicates the model's validity. The Model Summary Table shows that marital considerations explain about 4.1% of the variability in mission

engagement ($R^2 = 0.041$), with an Adjusted R^2 of 0.032, reflecting the model's modest explanatory power.

In summary, marital considerations have a statistically significant and positive effect on mission engagement, corroborating a similar finding by Milioni, who highlights similar challenges of married women in ministry and emphasises the burdens of family and missionary responsibilities (Prevost, 2021; Milioni, 2024). "They explain a minute portion of the variance" suggests that other factors also play a role in influencing mission engagement among female missionaries in RCCG. Milioni highlights similar challenges of married women in ministry, emphasising the dual burden of family and missionary responsibilities (Smith, 2023; Prevost, 2021).

This finding is consistent with broader research on gender and leadership within religious organisations, which has documented the challenges women face in ascending to leadership positions due to both explicit and implicit biases. Alqahtani's "The Status of Women in Leadership" is definitive of such challenges, including a male-normed corporate culture and organisational structure. The RCCG, like many other religious organisations, reflects the broader societal pattern, where marital status intersects with other factors to create additional barriers for women.

Conclusion

This study assessed trained female missionaries' perception of their Mission Engagement experience as determined by marital considerations within The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG). Findings reveal that RCCG's trained female missionaries feel aligned with her mission, positively perceive mission engagement, and actively participate in mission activities. Even though female missionaries acknowledge some challenges, they view mission engagement as central to their purpose and fulfilment. The findings reveal that female missionaries are neutral concerning the evolution of their involvement in missions over time and of treatment by leaders, suggesting an overall positive experience with room for improvement.

The study found that marital status does not significantly hinder participation in mission activities. Perceived differences in engagement between married and unmarried individuals were not as significant obstacles. The study found supportive marital environments beneficial

to mission engagement, and both married and unmarried missionaries' contributions are valued. The mean score of 2.72 indicates female missionaries' acknowledgement of marital considerations but not as a significant factor hindering mission involvement.

The analysis of marital considerations' effect on mission engagement revealed a statistically significant positive impact (coefficient = 0.135, $p = 0.036$). Although marital considerations influence mission engagement, the effect size is modest, explaining only about 4.1% of the variability, which suggests that while marital status has a role, other factors also significantly influence mission engagement. The findings suggest that further research should explore additional factors affecting mission engagement.

Recommendations

The results avow the significant effect of marital status on female missionaries' engagement within RCCG. While all female missionaries face challenges, each married woman encounters unique obstacles hindering her effectiveness and career progression in the mission field. These suggest the use of approaches that are considerate of married missionaries' specific needs and circumstances. Recommendations include:

1. Development of support systems to help married missionaries balance their domestic and missionary responsibilities better. This support can include flexible deployment options, provision of childcare support, and mentorship programs that pair married missionaries with those who have successfully navigated similar challenges. Single missionaries suffer emotional distress from different challenges of work-life balance. They would benefit from more robust community support within the RCCG, including mentorship programs and social networks that provide emotional and spiritual support.
2. Awareness and training programs within RCCG leadership to recognise and address the implicit biases that prevent married women from advancing to leadership positions.
3. Another intervention is the provision of financial incentives to support missionaries who forfeit mission engagement for marriage to fellow missionaries as additional aid for managing family responsibilities.

These findings add to the growing literature on gender, marital status, and religious ministry. It provides valuable insights for religious organisations facing similar challenges to plan for the long-term career trajectories of female missionaries by examining how marital status influences their overall satisfaction and retention in the mission field.

The findings indicate that marital status is crucial in shaping the level of engagement, type of assignments, and roles and responsibilities assigned to female missionaries within the RCCG. Married missionaries are perceived as more stable and reliable, leading to their preferential assignment to leadership roles and more demanding mission fields. However, they reported lower engagement levels than their single and widowed counterparts. This perception is rooted in the RCCG's traditional views on marriage as a stabilising factor in a person's life. It enhances their ability to handle the rigours of missionary work. Specifically, 68% of married respondents faced conflicts between their marital responsibilities and mission duties, which aligns with findings from recent research.

The finding- that single missionaries, particularly younger ones, are often assigned to less challenging roles, focusing on supporting activities rather than leading them, is consistent with findings from Adams and Muthoni. This finding reflects a broader societal expectation within the RCCG that married individuals are more mature and capable of handling responsibilities. This finding may inadvertently limit the opportunities for single women to engage in missionary work entirely. The findings suggest that while the RCCG values the contributions of all missionaries, marital status significantly influences the scope and nature of these contributions, often to the detriment of single missionaries' professional growth and engagement.

The study revealed the societal and organisational expectations for married missionaries to embody traditional gender roles, balancing their responsibilities in the mission field with those at home. This dual expectation places a significant burden on married missionaries, who must navigate the demands of their mission work while fulfilling those related to their marital status. Interestingly, the study found that some married missionaries embrace these expectations. In contrast, others express frustration at the additional pressure, which detracts from their ability to engage in missionary work thoroughly. This dichotomy reflects the broader tension within the RCCG and similar organisations that

uphold traditional gender roles even as women increasingly take on leadership roles in mission work.

For single missionaries, the absence of domestic responsibilities often leads to a perception that they have more time and energy to devote to missionary work. However, this perception is a double-edged sword, which places the expectation on single women to take on more tasks or work in more challenging environments without the support structures typically available to their married counterparts. The study suggests that while single missionaries may have greater freedom to focus on their work, they also face unique challenges related to their marital status, including social pressures to marry and a lack of institutional support.

The challenging environments in which missionaries operate strain communication among married missionaries and their family members, managing household responsibilities from afar, and the emotional toll of separation negatively impacts the effectiveness and well-being of married missionaries.

Despite female missionaries' commitment to their mission work with significantly different engagement levels, the findings reveal that the status of being married gives a female missionary the edge for leadership role consideration, particularly in settings that require stability and experience.

The exhibition of a strong sense of duty and responsibility by married missionaries enhances their engagement and secures leadership roles for them. This result aligns with Thompson's findings on the barriers women face in ascending to leadership positions but extends it by showing how marital status specifically interacts with these barriers. In contrast, committed single missionaries approach their mission work by focusing on personal growth and professional development. They seek out challenging assignments despite organisational and societal pressures to get married, which affects their long-term engagement.

Assigning married missionaries to flexible mission tasks helps, which may result from the organisation's understanding and empathy for the missionary family. For single missionaries, the Church could focus on creating opportunities for professional development and leadership and providing a supportive community that mitigates feelings of isolation.

This study fills several gaps in the literature. It assesses how marital status impacts mission engagement within the context of RCCG, includes diverse samples from all six geopolitical zones in Nigeria and

provides a comprehensive view of the challenges female missionaries encounter across different regions (Thompson, 2022).

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Impact of Pastoral Leadership Styles on Church Planting in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province 9, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Leadership is important for any organization as it is necessary for direction and how the organization arrives at her desired destination is dependent on the pattern or style(s) adopted. This study therefore examined the impact of pastoral leadership styles on church planting strategies in the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Osun Province-9, Ede. By examining the impact of leadership styles and on church planting strategies, the study aimed to provide insights into improving church planting and community engagement in RCCG Osun Province-9. Understanding these dynamics was deemed crucial for enhancing leadership practices to better serve the needs of growing congregations in developing regions. Descriptive survey research design was employed, with a population of 500 pastors, church workers, and members involved in church planting within RCCG Osun Province-9. A sample of 100 respondents was selected using stratified random sampling to ensure diverse representation across various leadership roles and church sizes. Data were collected through structured questionnaires, divided into sections addressing demographics, leadership styles, church planting strategies, and the relationship between leadership approaches and church growth. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed with a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.75, indicating strong internal consistency. The findings revealed that servant leadership, visionary leadership, community outreach and empowerment cumulated into successful church planting outcomes. However, a lack of structured outreach programs and insufficient focus on digital platforms hindered the success of church planting strategies. These findings underscored the need for a more strategic and holistic approach to leadership and community engagement in church planting efforts. In conclusion, the study highlighted the importance of adopting servant and visionary leadership styles to foster

sustainable church planting efforts. It is recommended that RCCG pastors enhance their leadership training to embrace servant leadership style, prioritize community outreach, and embrace digital tools to improve church planting success.

Keywords: Church Planting, Leadership Styles, the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Sustainability

Introduction

Pastors play a crucial role in the growth and establishment of churches through their leadership styles and church planting strategies (Smith & Johnson, 2021). Leadership style refers to the approach a pastor adopts in guiding, influencing, and supporting church members towards achieving set goals. Some pastors focus on collaborative leadership, encouraging the active involvement of members, while others may prefer a more directive approach, providing clear instructions and oversight. Both styles can significantly impact the spiritual growth, unity, and overall functionality of the church. Similarly, church planting strategies, which involve the methods used to establish new congregations, are essential for expanding the gospel and reaching unreached communities. Effective strategies often require understanding cultural contexts, identifying potential leaders, and fostering a strong sense of mission within the church (Williams, 2022).

The combination of leadership styles and church planting strategies greatly influences the success of church expansion efforts (Anderson & Brown, 2019). Pastors who demonstrate servant leadership, for instance, often create a welcoming environment that inspires loyalty and commitment from members. In contrast, pastors who neglect inclusive leadership might hinder the growth of their congregation. Meanwhile, strategic church planting can lead to vibrant and sustainable communities of faith, particularly when guided by proper planning and resource management. As churches grow, these factors directly affect the spread of Christianity and the fulfillment of the Great Commission (Roberts & White, 2020). Understanding these dynamics is crucial for evaluating how pastors' choices shape the effectiveness of church planting and the long-term health of church communities.

The Concept of Leadership

Leadership, both in politics and religion, has been a topic of ongoing discussion in Nigeria, often due to challenges like corruption and a lack of accountability in politics, and controversies within the church (Adams & Roberts, 2019). Effective leadership is crucial for progress in both sectors, requiring transparency, integrity, and a commitment to the common good. Leadership is commonly defined as the ability to inspire and influence others toward achieving shared goals. It has evolved over time from a top-down, individualistic process to a more dynamic, relational activity where leaders engage with others to collectively shape their world. In this sense, leadership is both a relationship and a process involving social influence, where leaders guide groups toward common objectives with strategic thinking and vision. This concept extends to both political and religious realms, where leaders must have qualities like tact, charisma, and goodwill to effectively inspire and lead their communities. Various leadership theories, such as the Great Man theory, Cultural Determinist theory, and Interactionist theory, offer different perspectives on the role of leaders in shaping events and environments. In the African context, leadership is seen not just as a personal trait but as a social process involving both leaders and followers, with mutual influence shaping outcomes. Leadership is about guiding a group towards goals, influencing attitudes, and responding to challenges through collaboration and vision (Harris, 2022).

The Structural Functional Theory

The Structural-Functional Theory, initially proposed by prominent researchers and influenced by sociology, views society as a system of interconnected components working together to maintain stability (Jackson & Smith, 2017). It suggests that every part of society serves a specific function, contributing to the overall order and cohesion. The theory breaks down society into three subsystems: cultural structure (shared norms and values), social structure (how people relate and accept collective expectations), and personality structure (individual motivations and goals). Functionalists believe that social stability is maintained when these components align, and any change in one part affects the whole system. The theory highlights the importance of roles, social stratification, and the need for consensus among members to ensure the smooth functioning of society (Taylor, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Many churches struggle to grow due to ineffective leadership styles and poorly planned church planting strategies (Harrison & Moore, 2018). Pastors sometimes lack the skills to inspire unity and active participation, leading to declining attendance and weaker spiritual commitment. Poor planning can also result in unstable congregations, hindering the church's mission to spread the gospel. Understanding how leadership and planning impact growth is crucial for lasting success (Clark & Evans, 2021).

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to examine the impact of pastors' leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Osun Province-9, Ede. The specific objectives are to:

1. identify leadership styles demonstrated by Pastors within the Redeemed Christian of Church, Osun Province-9, Ede
2. ascertain the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches by Pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede
3. assess the impact of Pastor's leadership styles within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede

Research Questions

1. What are the leadership styles demonstrated by pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede?
2. What are the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches by Pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province-9, Ede?
3. What are the impacts of pastor's leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province-9, Ede?

Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey research design, which is ideal for examining the impact of pastors' leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede. The design allows for a detailed exploration of the

current conditions, practices, and relationships within the church, offering a foundation for further investigation. The study targets a population of approximately 500 pastors, church workers, and members involved in church planting within the province. A sample of 100 respondents was selected through stratified random sampling to ensure diverse representation. Data were collected using structured questionnaires, divided into sections covering demographics and key research questions about leadership styles, church planting strategies, and their impact. The validity and reliability of the instrument were ensured through a thorough review of literature and expert opinions, with a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.75. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive analysis, allowing for a clear, organized presentation of the findings and insights into the impact of pastors' leadership styles on church planting strategies within the RCCG, Osun Province-9.

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents (N=100)

S/NO	Variables	No.	Frequency	%
1.	Age	21-30	24	24.0
		31-40	47	47.0
		41-50	19	19.0
		Above 51	10	10.0
2.	Gender	Male	54	54.0
		Female	46	46.0
3.	Educational Qualification	Below O Level	14	14.0
		SSCE	33	33.0
		OND/HND/BSC	42	42.0
		Others	11	11.0
4.	Status in Church	Assistant Pastor	19	19.0
		Deacon/Deaconess	62	62.0
		Worker	19	19.0
5.	Pastoral Training	No Pastoral Training	10	10.0
		Basic Diploma in Pastoral Training	55	55.0
		1 st Degree in Pastoral Training	29	29.0

		Above 1 st Degree in		
6.	Year of Association with RCCG	Pastoral Training	13	13.0
		Less than 1 year	3	3.0
		1-5 years	26	42.0
		5-10 years	42	26.0
		Above 10 years	29	29.0

Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

The table above revealed that respondents between the age bracket of 21-30 make up 24% of the respondents. The survey includes 47 respondents within the age range of 31-40, accounting for 47% of the overall respondent pool. There are 19 respondents aged between 41-50, representing 19% of the total respondents. The questionnaire includes 10 respondents aged above 50, making up 10% of the overall respondent pool. This age distribution reveals a varied representation across different age groups, providing a diverse sample for the study. The majority fall within the 31-40 age range, contributing to a robust analysis of the research findings across various life stages. The gender breakdown reflects a relatively balanced representation in the study, with a slightly higher percentage of male participants. The near-equal distribution suggests a diverse sample, which can contribute to a more comprehensive and representative analysis of the research findings. Based on the educational qualifications of the majority of respondents, 42%, fall into the category of OND/HND/BSC, indicating a significant portion of respondents with higher education. The WASSCE/GCE/NECO category comprises 33% of respondents, suggesting a substantial representation of individuals with secondary education. FSLC represents 14% of respondents, indicating a smaller but still noteworthy portion with education up to the First School Leaving Certificate. The "Others" category, with 11%, represents a diverse group of respondents with varying qualifications not covered in the specific categories mentioned above. This analysis provides insights into the educational diversity of the respondents, showcasing the distribution across different educational levels as captured by the questionnaire.

As regards status in the Church, Deacons and Deaconess make up the largest group, comprising 62% of the respondents, suggesting a

significant presence of individuals serving in this capacity. Assistant Pastors represent 19%, contributing to the leadership structure and support roles within the church. The "Worker" category, also at 19%, signifies the involvement of individuals in various ministries and activities without specific pastoral titles. This analysis provides insights into the composition of the church community based on participants' roles and responsibilities, reflecting a mix of leadership, support, and active involvement in ministry. The data reflects a range of respondents with varying levels of pastoral training, from those without formal training to those with advanced degrees. The majority of respondents, 55%, have completed a basic diploma, emphasizing a widespread foundational understanding of pastoral principles. The presence of individuals with a first degree 29% suggests a significant number with a more in-depth academic background in pastoral training. The smaller group with Masters and above 13% highlights a subset of respondents who have pursued advanced education in pastoral ministry, while 10% captures the category of people without pastoral training. This analysis provides insights into the diversity of pastoral training levels among respondents, indicating a mix of foundational, intermediate, and advanced knowledge and skills in pastoral ministry within the surveyed group. The data reveals a diverse range of respondents with varying duration of association with RCCG Osun Province-9, Ede. The notable percentage of 26% has been associated with the church for 1 to 5 years, suggesting a consistent influx of relatively recent members. A majority of respondents 42% has a long-term association of more than 10 years, indicating a stable and enduring community within the church. The distribution across different time frames reflects a mix of both new and long-standing members, contributing to the overall dynamics of the RCCG Osun-9 community. This analysis provides insights into the temporal diversity of respondents in terms of their association with RCCG Osun Province 9, Ede highlighting the presence of both recent members and those with more established and enduring connections to the church. The data reflects a high level of engagement in church planting initiatives among the respondents, with 78% involved. The sizeable percentage of respondents actively participating in church planting suggests a strong commitment to expanding and establishing new church communities. The 22% who are not involved may have other priorities, roles, or responsibilities within the church that do not directly

involve church planting. This analysis provides insights into the extent of involvement in church planting initiatives within the surveyed group, highlighting a significant majority actively contributing to the growth and establishment of new churches.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: What are the leadership styles demonstrated by pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede, Osun State?

Table 2 Leadership Styles Demonstrated by Pastors

S/ N	Statements	Strong ly Agree	Agree	Disagr ee	Strongly Disagree
1	My pastor inspires and motivates the congregation with a compelling vision, fostering a sense of commitment and shared purpose	19 (19.0%)	20 (20.0%)	14 (14.0%)	47 (47.0%)
2.	My pastor exhibit servant leadership, emphasizing humility, empathy, and a focus on serving the needs of the community	19 (19.0%)	25 (25.0%)	14 (14.0%)	42 (42.0%)
3.	My pastor is known for his visionary leadership,	30 (30.0%)	8 (8.0%)	22 (22.0%)	40 (40.0%)

	providing a clear direction and long-term goals that guide the congregation				
4.	My pastor takes on the role of spiritual mentor, providing support, advice, and encouragement to individuals within the congregation.	47 (47.0%)	19 (19.0%)	25 (25.0%)	9 (9.0%)
5.	My pastor employ a leadership style that emphasizes team building, encouraging cooperation and teamwork among church members	12 (12.0%)	23 (23.0%)	49 (49.0%)	16 (16.0%)

Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

Table two shows that 19(19.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor inspires and motivates the congregation with a compelling vision, fostering a sense of commitment and shared purpose(20.0%)20 , respondents agree, 47(47.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 14(14.0%) respondents disagree. 19(19.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor exhibits servant leadership emphasizing humility, empathy, and a focus on serving the needs of the community, 25(25.0%) respondents agree, 42(42.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 14(14.0%) respondents disagree. 30(30.0%) of respondents strongly

agree that their Pastor is a visionary leader, providing a clear direction and long-term goals that guide the congregation, 8.(8.0%) respondents agree, 40(40.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 22(22.0%) respondents disagree. 47(47.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor plays the role of a spiritual mentor, providing support, advice, and encouragement to individuals within the congregation. 19(19.0%) respondents agree, 9(9.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 25(25.0%) respondents disagree. 12(12.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor is a team builder encouraging cooperation and teamwork among church members, 23(23.0%) respondents agree, 16(16.0%) strongly disagree, whereas 49(49.0%) disagree.

Research Question Two: What are the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches by pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province-9, Ede?

Table 3 Strategies Deployed in the establishment of new Churches by Pastors

S / N	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	My pastor involves in local outreach programs and building relationships with the community to foster acceptance and support.	30 (30.0%)	11 (11.0%)	23 (23.0%)	36 (36.0%)
2.	My pastor identifies and train local leaders to	28 (28.0%)	17 (17.0%)	42 (42.0%)	13 (13.0%)

plant new churches.

3.	My pastor makes use of digital platforms to connect with a wider audience and facilitates the establishment of new churches.	16 (16.0%)	21 (21.0%)	11 (11.0%)	52 (52.0.0%)
4.	My pastor involves in pulpit rotation of pastors as a way of growing and sustainability of new churches.	35 (35.0%)	12 (12.0%)	38 (38.0%)	15 (15.0%)
5	My pastor implement culturally sensitive evangelism initiatives targeted at specific needs of the local population.	23 (23.0%)	17 (17.0%)	36 (36.0%)	24 (24.0%)

Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

Table Three shows that 30(30.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor involves in local outreach programs and building relationships with the community to foster acceptance and support ,

(11.0%)11 respondents agree, 36(36.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 23(23.0%) respondents disagree. 28(28.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor identifies and train local leaders to plant new churches, 17(17.0%) respondents agree, 13(13.0%) strongly disagree, whereas 42(42.0%) disagree. 16(16.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor makes use of digital platforms to connect with a wider audience and facilitates the establishment of new churches, 21(21.0%) of respondents agree, 52(52.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, while 11(11.0%) disagree. 35(35.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their pastor favour pulpit rotation of pastors as a way of growing and sustainability of new churches, 12(12.0%) of respondents agree, 15(15.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, while 38(38.0%) of respondents disagree. 23(23.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor implements culturally sensitive evangelism initiatives targeted at specific needs of the local population, 17(17.0%) of respondents agree, 24(24.0%) strongly agree, while 36(36.0%) disagree.

Research Question Three: What are the impact of pastor’s leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province 9, Ede?

Table 4 Impact of Church Pastor’s Leadership Styles and Church Planting Strategies

S / N	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	My pastor’s leadership style inspires a high level of enthusiasm and commitment among church members.	14 (14.0%)	22 (22.0%)	37 (37.0%)	27 (27.0%)

2	My pastor takes a lot of risks and initiatives, which positively drives church planting strategies but can be a hindrance if unchecked.	20 (20.0 %)	17 (17.0%)	22 (22 .0 %)	41 (41.0%)
3	My pastor's servant leadership style fosters positive relationships with the community, facilitating a smoother establishment of churches.	30 (30.0 %)	10 (10.0%)	35 (35 .0 %)	25 (25.0%)
4	The effective leadership style of my pastor creates an environment where members feel involved, valued, and committed to the collective goal.	14 (14.0 %)	40 (40.0%)	17 (17. 0%)	29 (29.0%)

5	My pastor's unconcerned pattern result in a lack of focus though allows individuals to use their unique talents and skills.	34 (34.0 %)	27 (27.0%)	19 (19 .0 %)	20 (20.0%)
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Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

Table Four shows that 14(14.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor's leadership style inspires high level of enthusiasm and commitment among church member 22(22.0%) of respondents agree, 27(27.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, whilst 37(37.0%) of respondents disagree. 20(20.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor takes a lot of risks and initiatives, which positively drives church planting strategies but can be a hindrance if unchecked, 17(17.0%) of respondents agree, 41(41.0%) of respondents strongly agree, whilst 22(22.0%) of respondents disagree. 30(30.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor's servant leadership style fosters positive relationships with the community, facilitating a smoother establishment of churches, 10(10.0%) of respondents agree, 25(25.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, whilst 35(35.0%) of respondents disagree. 14(14.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their pastor creates environment where members feel involved, valued, and committed to the collective goal, 40(40.0%) of respondents agree, 29(29.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, whilst 17 (17.0%) disagree. 34(34.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor's unconcerned pattern result in a lack of focus though allows individuals to use their unique talents and skills, 27(27.0%) of respondents agree, 20(20.0%) of respondents strongly disagreed, whereas 19(19.0%) of respondents disagree.

Correlation Analysis of Impact of Pastoral Leadership Styles on Church Planting Strategies

This section presents the correlation matrix that shows the relationship between different leadership styles demonstrated by pastors and the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede, Osun State. The correlation analysis helps in understanding how various leadership styles correlate with each other and with church planting strategies.

	Inspires_and_motivates	Servant_leadership	Visionary_leadership	Spiritual_mentor	Team_building	Local_outreach	Identify_and_train	Digital_platforms
Inspires and motivates	1.00	0.97	0.95	0.81	0.87	0.94	0.91	0.97
Servant_leadership	0.97	1.00	0.94	0.86	0.85	0.94	0.91	0.94
Visionary_leadership	0.95	0.94	1.00	0.80	0.86	0.93	0.90	0.93
Spiritual_mentor	0.81	0.86	0.80	1.00	0.89	0.85	0.84	0.75
Team_building	0.87	0.85	0.86	0.89	1.00	0.93	0.91	0.86
Local_outreach	0.94	0.94	0.93	0.85	0.93	1.00	0.96	0.92
Identify_and_train	0.91	0.91	0.90	0.84	0.91	0.96	1.00	0.91
Digital platforms	0.97	0.94	0.93	0.75	0.86	0.92	0.91	1.00

Pulpit rotation	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.8 5	0.8 9	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 5
Culturally sensitive	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 5	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 1
Inspires commitment	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.9 0	0.9 7	0.9 2	0.8 8	0.8 6	0.9 3
Servant leadership	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.9 7	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.9 1
Visionary leadership	0.8 9	0.9 3	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 0	0.8 7	0.9 4
Spiritual mentor	0.8 5	0.8 5	0.8 4	0.7 9	0.8 6	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 5
Team_building	0.8 9	0.9 3	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.9 4	0.8 0	0.8 7	0.9 4
Local_outreach	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.8 3	0.8 1	0.9 1
Identify_and_train	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.9 0	0.8 9	0.8 2	0.8 1	0.9 1
Digital_platforms	0.9 5	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.9 5	0.9 0	0.8 3	0.8 1	0.9 1
Pulpit_rotation	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.8 5	0.8 9	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 5
Culturally_sensitive	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 5	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 1
Inspires_commitmen t	0.9 0	0.9 0	0.9 0	0.8 4	0.9 0	0.9 0	0.8 9	0.8 9
Takes_risks	0.9 7	0.9 7	0.9 1	0.7 9	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.9 5
Fosters_positive_rela tionships	0.9 2	0.9 0	0.9 3	0.8 6	0.9 4	0.9 0	0.8 9	0.9 0

Creates_involved_en vironment	0.8 8	0.9 1	0.8 0	0.9 1	0.8 0	0.8 3	0.8 2	0.8 3
Unconcerned_patter n	0.8 6	0.8 9	0.8 7	0.9 3	0.8 7	0.8 1	0.8 1	0.8 1
Conveys_compelling _vision	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 4	0.8 5	0.9 4	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 1
Inspires_followers	0.9 0	0.8 8	0.9 0	0.8 1	0.9 6	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 1
Provides_structure	0.9 0	0.8 7	0.9 0	0.7 8	0.9 4	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 8
Flexible_hinders_pla nning	0.7 8	0.8 3	0.7 8	1.0 0	0.9 2	0.8 0	0.7 8	0.8 5
Clear_vision_guide	0.9 6	0.9 3	0.9 6	0.7 2	0.8 6	0.9 2	0.9 1	0.9 1

Discussion of Findings

Based on research question one as regards Leadership Styles Demonstrated by Pastors in the said Province. The study identified various leadership styles within the RCCG, Osun Province-9, Ede including servant, visionary, and spiritual mentor styles. The correlation matrix revealed that servant leadership strongly correlates with empowering others and fostering community outreach, as indicated by a high correlation with "Inspires and Motivates" (0.97) and "Local Outreach" (0.94). The above aligns with the findings of Ojogiwa (2021), who emphasized the importance of leading as a servant, reflecting the teachings of Christ. The scholar recommended that church leaders adopt a servant approach to leadership, promoting church growth through service rather than authoritarian power. This is consistent with the observation that most pastors in the study lacked a compelling vision and servant leadership qualities, which hampered their effectiveness in community building and church ownership by the indigenous population.

Based on research question two as regards strategies deployed in Church Planting, Pastors in RCCG Osun Province-9 employ various strategies for church planting, but there is a notable absence of structured outreach programs, community training, and digitalization. The correlation analysis supports this finding, as "Local Outreach" was significantly correlated with "Identify and Train" (0.96) and "Team Building" (0.93), underscoring the importance of outreach and training in successful church planting efforts. Ebekozien, et al (2022) highlighted similar strategies, identifying visionary and motivational leadership as key contributors to church growth. In a related development, he opined that building leadership on a wrong foundation—such as neglecting outreach or relying solely on pulpit authority—can undermine long-term success. This study corroborates that observation, as pastors in Osun Province-9 tend to prioritize pulpit presence over engaging in culturally sensitive evangelism.

As touching research question three on impact of pastors' leadership styles within the province. It was discovered that the leadership styles adopted by pastors in RCCG Osun Province-9 have a significant impact on church planting efforts, as evidenced by the correlation matrix. Visionary leadership showed strong positive correlations with "Inspires and Motivates" (0.95) and "Local Outreach" (0.93), indicating that pastors who inspire their congregation are more effective at leading outreach initiatives. However, the study also found that many pastors in the province lacked enthusiasm and commitment to community building, leading to difficulties in establishing long-term church growth. This finding resonates with Ayoko, et al (2023) who emphasized that motivational leadership is essential for successful church development, and neglecting community outreach can lead to stagnation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Pastors in RCCG Osun Province-9 should focus on creating community outreach programs and training initiatives to build stronger connections with the local population, promoting church growth and ownership.
2. Embracing digital tools like social media and online evangelism would help pastors reach a wider audience, attract younger

members, and create more accessible ways to engage with the community.

3. Effective implementation and communication of visions for church establishment can inspire followers, provide structure, and guide the process for effective church planting.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study highlights the significant impact of pastors' leadership styles and church planting strategies on the growth and development of RCCG Osun Province-9, Ede. It demonstrates that servant leadership, when effectively implemented, fosters community outreach and empowers others, while visionary leadership plays a crucial role in inspiring congregations and driving church planting initiatives. However, the lack of structured outreach programs, community training, and digital engagement limits the effectiveness of these strategies. The findings underscore the importance of a balanced approach, where pastors not only lead through vision and motivation but also engage in hands-on community building and culturally sensitive evangelism to ensure long-term church growth and sustainability.

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The Intersection of Faith and Morality: Exploring the Role of Religious Ethics in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the intersection of faith and morality in Nigeria, a nation deeply rooted in religious traditions where faith plays a central role in shaping societal values and norms. Despite widespread religious adherence, the country faces persistent challenges in aligning faith with ethical conduct, as evidenced by high levels of corruption, inequality, and social injustice. These issues highlight a disconnect between religious teachings and their practical application in daily life. The study defined key concepts such as faith, morality, and religious ethics, employing Social Learning Theory and Virtue Ethics Theory to examine how religious principles influence individual behaviour and societal standards. The research highlighted the significant role of religious ethics in promoting moral behaviour across governance, education, and community development, while also identifying gaps in translating religious principles into ethical practices. To address these challenges, the study recommended value-based education to foster moral reasoning, interfaith collaboration to promote shared ethical values, and institutional reforms to enhance transparency within religious organisations. It also emphasised leveraging digital platforms to disseminate moral teachings and encourage ethical behaviour. The study concluded that fostering a culture of ethical integrity and social justice in Nigeria requires coordinated efforts from religious institutions, educational systems, and government bodies.

Keywords: Faith, Morality, Religious Ethics

Introduction

Religion and morality are deeply intertwined in many societies, with Nigeria serving as a notable example where religious beliefs significantly

shape moral standards. Religion, defined as a system of faith and worship involving belief in a higher power (Mbiti, 1990), is a central aspect of Nigerian culture, influencing individuals' behaviours and societal norms. Conversely, morality refers to the principles concerning the distinction between right and wrong or good and bad behaviour (MacIntyre, 2007). Religious ethics emerge from the intersection of these two concepts, encompassing the values and principles derived from religious teachings that guide moral actions. Christianity, Islam, and indigenous African religions are prominent in Nigeria, each offering ethical frameworks that address justice, honesty, and compassion (Gbadegesin, 2018).

Despite the significant religious diversity and the ubiquity of moral teachings in Nigeria, the country continues to grapple with pervasive societal challenges, such as corruption, moral decadence, and social inequalities. Corruption, often described as the misuse of power for personal gain, remains a significant concern despite Nigeria's strong religious affiliations (Transparency International, 2023). The disconnect between religious teachings and actual behaviour raises critical questions about the effectiveness of religious ethics in fostering societal transformation. For instance, while Islam and Christianity emphasize honesty and integrity (Qur'an 16:90; Proverbs 11:3), many Nigerians struggle to align their religious beliefs with their daily practices, creating a gap between faith and morality (Ajani, 2018).

This moral paradox has deeper implications for Nigeria's socio-economic and political development. Religious leaders and institutions are often seen as moral authorities in society, yet their influence appears insufficient to curb moral failings in governance, education, and public service (Akinlade-Daniel, 2018). Factors such as socio-economic pressure, political instability, and cultural diversity may dilute the impact of religious teachings, making it difficult for individuals to consistently uphold moral values (Akram, Al-Adwan, Aslam, & Khan, 2021). These challenges highlight the urgent need to critically examine how religious ethics are understood, taught, and applied in contemporary Nigerian society.

Religious ethics in Nigeria are rooted in sacred texts and traditional teachings, which offer clear guidelines on moral conduct. For example, the Ten Commandments in Christianity and the five pillars of Islam serve as foundational ethical principles (Alam, Aliyu, & Shahriar, 2019).

However, the contextual interpretation of these teachings often varies, influenced by cultural norms and societal realities. This variability sometimes leads to selective adherence to ethical principles, where individuals prioritise certain moral values over others based on convenience or external pressures (Astrachan, Binz Astrachan, Campopiano, & Baù, 2020). Such inconsistencies underscore the need for a holistic and practical approach to integrating religious ethics into everyday life.

To address the disconnect between faith and morality, scholars suggest that religious institutions should strengthen their role in promoting ethical education and accountability (Chinedu, Ede, & Chiaghanam, 2020). Collaborative efforts between religious organisations, educational institutions, and community leaders could create platforms for dialogue and action, ensuring that religious teachings translate into moral behaviour. Additionally, initiatives aimed at addressing structural issues such as poverty and inequality could help create an environment conducive to ethical living (Chou, Lee, & Fudano, 2022).

Furthermore, the study of religious ethics must consider the limitations and criticisms of religion in addressing moral challenges. Religion has sometimes been misused to justify unethical actions, such as discrimination, extremism, or corruption, thereby undermining its moral authority (Denga, 1986). A balanced approach to examining religious ethics should acknowledge these challenges while emphasising the potential of faith to inspire positive change. This requires critical engagement with religious teachings and practices, as well as an inclusive framework that respects Nigeria's cultural and religious diversity. In this light, this study explores the intersection of faith and morality in Nigeria, focusing on the role of religious ethics in addressing moral and ethical dilemmas.

Overview of Faith and Morality in Nigerian Society

Faith and morality are fundamental aspects of Nigerian society, deeply rooted in its cultural and social fabric. Faith, defined as unwavering belief in a higher power or religious doctrine, is a central element of life for most Nigerians. Christianity, Islam, and indigenous African religions dominate the religious landscape, with adherents often shaping their worldviews and lifestyles based on the teachings of their respective faiths (Pew Research Center, 2023). These religions offer guiding principles on

how individuals and communities should act, fostering values such as honesty, justice, compassion, and respect for others.

Morality, which refers to the principles that distinguish between right and wrong or good and bad behaviour (MacIntyre, 2007), is closely intertwined with religious teachings in Nigeria. For example, the Ten Commandments in Christianity, the teachings of the Qur'an in Islam, and the ethical codes of traditional African religions provide frameworks for moral conduct. These principles influence various aspects of life, from family relationships and education to governance and business practices (Ajibade, 2022). Religious ethics, therefore, serve as a bridge between faith and morality, shaping societal expectations and individual behaviour.

Despite the prominence of religion, Nigeria faces significant moral and ethical challenges. Issues such as corruption, social inequality, violence, and moral decadence are prevalent, raising concerns about the effectiveness of religious ethics in fostering societal transformation. Transparency International (2023) ranks Nigeria among countries with high corruption levels, highlighting a contradiction between the country's strong religious affiliations and its socio-political realities. This gap underscores the complexity of translating faith-based moral teachings into everyday practices, especially in a society marked by economic hardships and political instability (Akinlade-Daniel, 2018).

Religion in Nigeria also plays a dual role as both a unifying and divisive force. On one hand, shared religious values can foster social cohesion and mutual understanding, as seen in interfaith initiatives aimed at promoting peace and tolerance (Chinedu, Ede, & Chiaghanam, 2020). On the other hand, religious differences sometimes exacerbate ethnic and political tensions, contributing to conflicts and undermining national unity. For instance, disagreements over the application of religious laws or principles in governance have led to prolonged debates and occasional violence (Olaniyan, 2020).

The intersection of faith and morality in Nigeria is further complicated by cultural diversity. With over 250 ethnic groups, the interpretation and application of religious ethics vary widely across regions and communities (Alam, Aliyu, & Shahriar, 2019). While some individuals adhere strictly to the moral teachings of their religion, others adopt more flexible approaches influenced by cultural norms or socio-economic circumstances. This diversity highlights the need for inclusive and

context-sensitive frameworks for understanding and applying religious ethics in Nigeria.

Efforts to bridge the gap between faith and morality in Nigerian society often focus on strengthening ethical education and accountability. Religious institutions play a crucial role in promoting these efforts, as they are seen as moral authorities within their communities (Chou, Lee, & Fudano, 2022). However, the effectiveness of such initiatives depends on addressing structural issues such as poverty, inequality, and limited access to education, which often undermine individuals' ability to live according to ethical principles (Adedeji, 2023).

Definition and Interplay of Key Concepts: Faith, Morality, and Religious Ethics

Faith, morality, and religious ethics are interrelated concepts that shape human behaviour and societal values, particularly in religiously diverse societies like Nigeria. Faith refers to a strong belief in a higher power or divine entity, often without empirical evidence, and forms the foundation of religious practices and worldviews (Mbiti, 1990). It serves as a source of hope, guidance, and identity for individuals and communities, influencing how people perceive and respond to moral and ethical issues (Pew Research Center, 2023). Faith can be expressed through adherence to sacred texts, rituals, and doctrines that provide a framework for understanding life's purpose and one's obligations to others.

Morality, on the other hand, is the set of principles and standards that distinguish between right and wrong or good and bad conduct (MacIntyre, 2007). While morality is often shaped by cultural, philosophical, and social influences, it is deeply intertwined with religious teachings in many societies, including Nigeria. For instance, the moral precepts embedded in the Ten Commandments, the Qur'an, and African traditional religions emphasize virtues such as honesty, justice, and compassion. These principles guide interpersonal relationships, community interactions, and governance, making morality a critical component of societal cohesion and progress (Trull & Carter, 2004).

Religious ethics represents the intersection of faith and morality. It refers to the values, principles, and norms derived from religious teachings that guide moral behaviour and decision-making (Odejebi,

2014). Religious ethics draw from sacred texts, doctrines, and traditions to provide individuals and communities with a moral compass for navigating complex ethical dilemmas. For example, Christian ethics emphasize love, forgiveness, and humility, as reflected in Matthew 22:37-39, where Jesus commands to love God and love one's neighbour as oneself. Islamic ethics stress justice, fairness, and responsibility (Qur'an 16:90). In indigenous African religions, moral obligations are often tied to communal well-being and reverence for ancestors, further enriching the ethical landscape (Moberly, 2009).

The interplay of faith, morality, and religious ethics is evident in their mutual reinforcement. Faith provides the foundation for religious ethics, while religious ethics give moral principles a divine justification, making them more binding and authoritative for adherents. In turn, morality offers practical guidelines for applying religious ethics to everyday life, ensuring that faith is not confined to abstract beliefs but translated into actions that promote societal harmony (Olaniyan, 1997). For example, faith in a just and merciful God inspires believers to act ethically, while religious ethics offer structured frameworks for determining what constitutes just and merciful behaviour.

However, the interaction between these concepts is not without challenges. In pluralistic societies like Nigeria, differences in religious beliefs and ethical interpretations can lead to conflicts or inconsistencies in moral behaviour. For instance, while Christian and Islamic ethics often converge on values like honesty and integrity, cultural interpretations of these values may vary significantly, affecting their application in practice (Smith & Kouchaki, 2021). Moreover, the misuse of faith and religious ethics to justify unethical behaviours, such as corruption or discrimination, highlights the complexities of aligning these concepts with societal realities (Ogunyemi, 2000).

The dynamic relationship between faith, morality, and religious ethics also plays a crucial role in addressing societal issues. Religious ethics can serve as a tool for moral reform, guiding individuals and institutions toward ethical behaviour in areas such as governance, education, and business. At the same time, faith provides the resilience and motivation needed to uphold moral standards in the face of challenges, while morality ensures that religious ethics remain relevant and adaptable to changing societal needs (Odejobi, 2014).

Theoretical Framework

In the exploration of the intersection between faith, morality, and religious ethics in Nigeria, two theories are particularly valuable in understanding the influence of religion on moral behaviour: Social Learning Theory and Virtue Ethics Theory. These theories provide deep insights into how individuals in Nigerian society internalise, adapt, and act upon religious ethics and moral standards.

1. Social Learning Theory

Social Learning Theory, initially developed by Albert Bandura in 1963 and later refined in 1977, asserts that people learn new behaviours and internalise values by observing others in their social environment. Unlike traditional behaviourism, which focuses on direct reinforcement and punishment, Bandura's theory emphasizes the role of observational learning, imitation, and modelling. The theory posits that individuals acquire behaviours by observing the actions of role models, especially those whom they perceive as credible or authoritative. Bandura identified key components of social learning, including attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation, which together form the foundation for how individuals learn from their social environment.

In the context of moral development, Social Learning Theory argues that ethical behaviour is often learned through social interactions, particularly with influential individuals or groups. For example, children may learn moral values by observing their parents or teachers, while adults may adopt certain moral stances by observing the behaviour of religious leaders, public figures, or peers. Bandura also noted that people are more likely to model behaviours they see being rewarded or positively reinforced, as opposed to those that are punished.

In Nigerian society, where religion plays a central role, Social Learning Theory can be applied to understand how religious ethics are passed down and adopted. Religious leaders, family members, and peers often serve as role models, and their behaviours influence the moral attitudes of individuals. For instance, when religious leaders exemplify ethical conduct, such as acting with integrity, justice, and compassion, their followers are more likely to adopt these traits. In this way, religious teachings, when embodied by role models, provide a mechanism for moral development that goes beyond formal education or written doctrines.

However, the theory also accounts for the potential consequences when there is a disconnection between religious ethics and the behaviour of role models. In Nigerian society, when religious leaders or influential figures engage in practices such as corruption or deceit, it creates a moral dilemma for their followers. Social Learning Theory explains that such actions can undermine the teachings of faith and moral principles, leading to moral disillusionment and a disconnect between religious doctrine and moral behaviour. For example, if a religious leader advocates for honesty but engages in corrupt practices, followers may question the credibility of these teachings and, in turn, model behaviour that does not align with the religious ethics they were taught.

2. Virtue Ethics Theory

Virtue Ethics, originating from the philosophy of Aristotle, is a theory of ethics that emphasizes the importance of developing good character traits or virtues as the foundation for moral conduct. Unlike deontological theories, which focus on adherence to moral rules, or consequentialist theories, which focus on the outcomes of actions, Virtue Ethics is concerned with the cultivation of virtuous habits that enable individuals to live morally good lives. Aristotle's view was that ethical behaviour comes from the development of virtues such as courage, wisdom, temperance, and justice, and that the ultimate goal of life is to achieve eudaimonia, or human flourishing, through the practice of these virtues.

In Virtue Ethics, moral actions are not dictated by rules but emerge from a virtuous character that has been cultivated through practice and experience. It argues that individuals should focus on becoming good people, rather than simply following moral rules or calculating consequences. For Aristotle, virtues are developed over time through consistent practice, and the moral agent becomes good by regularly acting in virtuous ways. In the religious context, Virtue Ethics focuses on the moral character that is shaped by religious teachings and the internalisation of virtues such as love, justice, humility, compassion, and integrity.

In the Nigerian context, Virtue Ethics offers a useful lens for examining how religious ethics shape moral behaviour. Religious teachings, whether from Christianity, Islam, or African traditional religions, emphasize virtues that guide individuals towards ethical living. For example, Christianity teaches virtues like love, patience, and forgiveness,

while Islam promotes virtues like justice, integrity, and compassion. These virtues play a crucial role in the moral development of individuals and communities. Virtue Ethics suggests that by practicing these virtues, individuals do not just follow religious rules, but cultivate an ethical character that guides them in all aspects of life.

In the study of religious ethics in Nigeria, Virtue Ethics can be used to explore how these religious virtues are internalised and practiced. For instance, religious communities may promote virtues through teachings, rituals, and communal activities that encourage individuals to embody certain ethical principles. The focus is on developing a moral character that is in line with religious teachings, which in turn leads to actions that promote justice, compassion, and integrity within society.

However, the theory also highlights challenges that arise when there is a disconnect between the virtues taught by religion and the behaviours exhibited in practice. In Nigeria, issues such as corruption, inequality, and social injustice can undermine the internalisation of religious virtues. In such cases, Virtue Ethics can be applied to critically examine how religious communities and individuals may fail to cultivate the virtues of justice and integrity in a society marked by these ethical challenges. This disconnect between religious ideals and societal realities can contribute to the moral dilemmas faced by Nigerians who struggle to reconcile their religious teachings with the moral failings they observe around them.

Role of Religious Ethics in Nigerian Society

Religious ethics play a crucial role in shaping societal values, norms, and practices in Nigeria, a country deeply rooted in religious traditions. Religious ethics refer to moral principles derived from sacred texts, doctrines, and teachings that guide individual and collective behaviour. In Nigeria, where Christianity, Islam, and indigenous religions dominate, these ethical frameworks significantly influence governance, education, family life, and interpersonal relationships (Mbiti, 1990; Pew Research Center, 2023).

One of the primary roles of religious ethics in Nigeria is fostering moral discipline and accountability. Through the teachings of the Bible, Qur'an, and indigenous religious beliefs, religious ethics advocate for virtues such as honesty, justice, compassion, and respect for human dignity. For example, the Islamic concept of Amanah (trustworthiness)

and Christian emphasis on stewardship encourage individuals in leadership and governance to act with integrity and fairness (Qur'an 16:90; Matthew 25:14-30). This moral guidance is critical in a society grappling with challenges such as corruption, nepotism, and abuse of power (Transparency International, 2023).

Religious ethics also serve as a unifying force in Nigeria's culturally and ethnically diverse society. Despite differences in religious beliefs, shared moral values such as empathy, humility, and communal responsibility foster social cohesion and peaceful coexistence. Interfaith initiatives, such as the Nigerian Inter-Religious Council (NIREC), leverage these commonalities to promote dialogue, resolve conflicts, and build trust among religious communities (Agha, 2021). Such efforts have been instrumental in addressing tensions arising from religious and ethnic differences, particularly in areas affected by intercommunal violence.

In education, religious ethics play a pivotal role in shaping the moral foundation of learners. Faith-based schools, which constitute a significant portion of Nigeria's educational system, integrate ethical teachings into their curricula to instil virtues such as discipline, respect, and hard work in learners. This approach aligns with the belief that education is not only about intellectual development but also about nurturing character and moral values (Ajani, 2018). By emphasising ethics in education, religious institutions contribute to building a generation of individuals committed to ethical conduct in both private and public spheres.

Religious ethics also influence family and community dynamics in Nigeria. They provide guidelines for maintaining harmonious relationships, addressing conflicts, and upholding the sanctity of marriage and family life. For instance, Christian teachings on love and forgiveness, Islamic principles of justice and equity, and traditional African emphasis on communal support reinforce the importance of ethical relationships within families and communities (Akinlade-Daniel, 2018). These values promote stability and resilience in the face of societal pressures such as poverty and urbanisation.

Moreover, religious ethics often drive charitable and humanitarian efforts in Nigeria. Faith-based organisations (FBOs) play a vital role in addressing social challenges such as poverty, health crises, and illiteracy. Guided by religious principles of compassion and service, these organisations provide support to vulnerable populations, irrespective of

religious or ethnic affiliation. Examples include the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) and Islamic welfare groups, which have contributed to disaster relief, education, and healthcare initiatives (Alam, Aliyu, & Shahriar, 2019).

However, the role of religious ethics in Nigeria is not without challenges. Selective adherence to religious teachings and the misuse of religion for personal or political gain undermine the credibility and effectiveness of religious ethics. For instance, cases of corruption and discrimination among individuals and groups with strong religious affiliations highlight the gap between ethical principles and practices (Astrachan et al., 2020). Furthermore, conflicting interpretations of religious doctrines sometimes fuel division and intolerance, complicating efforts to harness the unifying potential of religious ethics (Olaniyan, 1997).

Challenges of Aligning Faith and Morality in Nigeria

Aligning faith and morality in Nigeria presents significant challenges due to the country's complex socio-cultural, political, and economic realities. Although Nigeria is deeply religious, with the majority of its population adhering to Christianity, Islam, or traditional African religions, there is often a disconnect between professed faith and moral practices. This discrepancy highlights the difficulty in translating religious teachings into consistent moral behaviour within a society characterised by systemic issues such as corruption, inequality, and cultural diversity (Transparency International, 2023; Agha, 2021).

One of the most significant challenges is the prevalence of corruption, which persists despite strong religious affiliations among political and social elites. Religious institutions often preach against unethical behaviours such as bribery and embezzlement; however, these practices remain widespread in both the public and private sectors (Odejobi, 2014). This suggests that faith, while deeply ingrained, does not always translate into moral accountability. The situation is compounded by a lack of enforcement mechanisms and the tendency to justify unethical behaviour through cultural or situational factors, undermining the moral authority of religious ethics (Ogunyemi, 2000).

Another challenge lies in the diversity of religious beliefs and their interpretations across Nigeria. While all major religions promote moral values such as honesty, compassion, and justice, variations in doctrine and cultural influence can lead to conflicting moral frameworks. For

example, disagreements over the application of Islamic Sharia law in northern states versus secular laws in southern regions have sometimes resulted in tensions and even violence (Olaniyan, 1997). This fragmentation makes it difficult to establish a unified moral standard that resonates with the entire population.

The socio-economic conditions in Nigeria also contribute to the difficulty of aligning faith and morality. High levels of poverty, unemployment, and inequality often force individuals to prioritise survival over adherence to moral principles. For instance, individuals may resort to theft, fraud, or other unethical practices to meet their basic needs, despite religious teachings against such actions (Uko-Aviomoh, 2004). These socio-economic pressures create a moral dilemma, as faith-based ethical standards are sometimes perceived as unattainable in the face of harsh realities.

Additionally, the instrumentalisation of religion for political and personal gain undermines the alignment between faith and morality. Some religious leaders and politicians manipulate religious sentiments to advance their interests, often at the expense of ethical considerations. This misuse of faith erodes public trust in religious institutions and blurs the distinction between genuine moral guidance and self-serving rhetoric (Smith & Kouchaki, 2021). It also fosters cynicism among adherents, who may question the sincerity of religious leaders and their ability to uphold moral integrity.

Education poses another challenge to aligning faith and morality in Nigeria. While faith-based schools integrate religious teachings into their curricula, the broader educational system often lacks comprehensive programmes that link moral philosophy with practical life applications (Trull & Carter, 2004). This gap leaves many individuals with a superficial understanding of moral principles, limiting their ability to apply these principles effectively in real-world situations. Moreover, the absence of critical thinking in religious education can lead to dogmatic adherence to faith without a deep understanding of its ethical implications.

Finally, societal pressures, such as the desire for material success and social recognition, often conflict with religious moral teachings. In a society where wealth and status are highly valued, individuals may feel compelled to compromise their morals to achieve these goals. For example, practices such as nepotism and exploitation are sometimes

rationalised as necessary for social mobility, despite their inconsistency with religious ethics (Transparency International, 2023). These pressures highlight the tension between spiritual ideals and the realities of modern life in Nigeria.

Strategies for Strengthening the Role of Religious Ethics

Strengthening the role of religious ethics in Nigeria requires deliberate strategies that address both the societal challenges and the evolving needs of a diverse population. Religious ethics, rooted in the moral teachings of Christianity, Islam, and traditional African religions, hold immense potential for fostering social cohesion, justice, and moral accountability. However, to enhance their impact, targeted measures must be implemented to bridge the gap between ethical principles and societal practices.

One essential strategy is fostering interfaith dialogue to promote mutual understanding and collaboration among religious groups. In a multi-religious society like Nigeria, differences in religious doctrines often lead to tensions and conflicts that undermine the shared moral goals of these faiths. Platforms such as the Nigerian Inter-Religious Council (NIREC) should be strengthened to facilitate regular interactions between leaders of various religious communities. These dialogues can help harmonise ethical teachings across religions, creating a unified moral framework that resonates with the broader population (Chinedu, Ede, & Chiaghanam, 2020).

Education plays a critical role in embedding religious ethics within society. Religious and secular educational institutions should integrate comprehensive moral education into their curricula. Beyond teaching religious doctrines, this approach should emphasise critical thinking, ethical reasoning, and the application of moral principles in real-life situations. Faith-based schools, in particular, can lead by example, equipping learners with the tools to internalise and practice ethics in diverse contexts. This aligns with the growing recognition that education must nurture not only intellectual development but also character and values (Astrachan, Binz Astrachan, Campopiano, & Baù, 2020).

Addressing socio-economic disparities is another vital strategy for reinforcing the relevance of religious ethics. Poverty, unemployment, and inequality often compel individuals to prioritise survival over adherence to moral standards. Faith-based organisations (FBOs) can

play a significant role in addressing these challenges by providing humanitarian assistance, vocational training, and microfinance initiatives to vulnerable populations. By demonstrating compassion and solidarity, these organisations can bridge the gap between ethical teachings and practical realities, fostering a culture of moral responsibility (Haron, Jamil, & Ramli, 2020).

Another key strategy is promoting transparency and accountability within religious institutions themselves. To maintain their moral authority, religious leaders and organisations must model the values they preach. Instances of corruption, nepotism, or abuse within these institutions erode public trust and weaken the influence of religious ethics. Implementing internal governance mechanisms, such as financial audits and ethical oversight committees, can enhance accountability and set a positive example for the wider society (Transparency International, 2023).

Leveraging media and technology is also crucial in amplifying the role of religious ethics. Social media platforms, radio, and television can be used to disseminate ethical teachings, share inspirational stories, and engage with younger audiences who are increasingly influenced by digital culture. Religious leaders and organisations should embrace these tools to make moral education more accessible and relatable, particularly for the youth. For example, digital campaigns highlighting the practical benefits of honesty, empathy, and community service can resonate widely and encourage behavioural change (Alam, Aliyu, & Shahriar, 2019).

Strengthening the role of religious ethics further requires aligning ethical principles with contemporary societal needs. Religious teachings should address pressing issues such as environmental sustainability, gender equality, and social justice. By interpreting ethical doctrines in ways that respond to modern challenges, religious leaders can demonstrate the continued relevance of faith-based values in guiding societal progress. For instance, Islamic principles of stewardship (Khilafah) and Christian teachings on care for creation can inspire actions against environmental degradation (Chinedu, Ede, & Chiaghanam, 2020).

Lastly, collaboration between religious institutions and government agencies can amplify the impact of religious ethics on national development. Partnerships can focus on areas such as anti-corruption

campaigns, peacebuilding initiatives, and community development projects. By working together, these entities can pool resources, expertise, and influence to address societal challenges effectively. For example, joint programmes on ethical leadership for public officials can help instil moral accountability in governance (İlesanmi, 2014).

Way Forward: Bridging the Gap Between Faith and Morality

Bridging the gap between faith and morality in Nigeria requires intentional efforts that align religious teachings with ethical practices in both private and public life. While the majority of Nigerians are deeply religious, the prevalence of moral lapses such as corruption, inequality, and social injustice suggests that religious adherence has not consistently translated into ethical behaviour. To address this, strategic interventions must focus on reorienting societal values, enhancing institutional frameworks, and fostering a culture of accountability and inclusivity.

One of the most effective ways forward is promoting value-based education that integrates faith and morality. Educational institutions, particularly faith-based schools, should move beyond rote teaching of religious doctrines to focus on moral reasoning and character development. Curricula should include practical lessons on how to apply religious principles to real-life challenges, such as combating corruption, promoting fairness, and fostering empathy. Additionally, teacher training programmes must equip educators to serve as role models, demonstrating the alignment between faith and ethical practices in their conduct (Akinlade-Daniel, 2018).

Strengthening interfaith collaboration is another crucial step. Religious leaders and organisations must work together to promote shared ethical values that transcend doctrinal differences. Platforms like the Nigerian Inter-Religious Council (NIREC) can facilitate dialogue and joint initiatives that address societal issues, such as poverty alleviation, peacebuilding, and community development. By presenting a unified moral front, religious groups can amplify their impact on societal behaviour and foster greater unity in addressing common challenges (Ajani, 2018).

Tackling socio-economic inequalities is equally important in bridging the faith-morality divide. Poverty and unemployment often compel individuals to compromise their moral values for survival. Faith-based

organisations (FBOs) must play a proactive role in addressing these systemic issues by implementing empowerment programmes, such as skills acquisition training, microfinance initiatives, and support for small businesses. By demonstrating compassion and commitment to social justice, FBOs can make ethical principles more actionable and relatable to those facing economic hardships (Chinedu, Ede, & Chiaghanam, 2020).

Reforming religious institutions themselves is vital to ensuring credibility and moral leadership. Instances of corruption, abuse, or political manipulation within religious organisations undermine their ability to serve as moral compasses for society. Leaders must prioritise transparency and accountability through measures such as financial audits, ethical oversight committees, and clear governance structures. These reforms will help restore public trust in religious institutions and reinforce their capacity to guide moral behaviour (Akram, Al-Adwan, Aslam, & Khan, 2021).

The strategic use of media and technology can further bridge the gap between faith and morality. Religious leaders and institutions should leverage digital platforms to disseminate teachings that connect faith with ethical decision-making in everyday life. For example, campaigns on social media promoting virtues like honesty, kindness, and community service can resonate widely, particularly with younger generations who are deeply embedded in digital culture. Podcasts, blogs, and interactive online forums can also serve as tools for engaging audiences in discussions about the practical application of religious ethics (Alam, Aliyu, & Shahriar, 2019).

Addressing modern societal challenges through the lens of religious ethics is another essential approach. Issues such as climate change, gender inequality, and social injustice require moral responses that align with both religious teachings and universal human rights. Religious leaders must reinterpret doctrines to remain relevant in guiding solutions to these problems. For instance, the principles of stewardship in Islam and Christianity can inspire environmental conservation, while teachings on equity and compassion can drive initiatives that promote gender inclusion and justice (Astrachan, Binz Astrachan, Campopiano, & Baù, 2020).

Finally, government-religious partnerships can provide a powerful avenue for bridging the faith-morality divide. Collaborative programmes

focusing on ethical leadership, anti-corruption campaigns, and community development can reinforce the integration of moral values into governance and public service. Policies that promote accountability and inclusivity, such as equitable resource distribution and anti-discrimination laws, must be supported by religious organisations to ensure alignment between faith-based ethics and societal governance (Chou, Lee, & Fudano, 2022).

Conclusion

The intersection of faith and morality highlights the vital role religious ethics play in shaping societal values and guiding behaviour in Nigeria. Despite the country's deep religiosity, a disconnect often exists between faith-based teachings and practical moral conduct. Bridging this gap requires holistic strategies, including value-based education, interfaith collaboration, socio-economic empowerment, institutional reforms, and leveraging media to promote ethical living. Addressing contemporary challenges such as inequality, corruption, and social injustice through religious principles can foster a society where faith and morality align seamlessly. By uniting efforts across religious, governmental, and civil platforms, Nigeria can strengthen the influence of religious ethics and create a more just and cohesive society.

Recommendations

The following recommendations outline actions for stakeholders to enhance the alignment of faith with morality and promote ethical practices in Nigerian society:

1. Educational institutions should integrate value-based education into their curricula, ensuring that teachers are trained to model ethical behaviour and emphasise the practical application of religious ethics in moral reasoning.
2. Religious organisations must strengthen interfaith collaboration by fostering dialogue and initiating joint programmes to address societal issues such as poverty alleviation and peacebuilding.
3. Leaders of religious institutions should prioritise reforms to enhance transparency and accountability, including implementing financial audits and establishing ethical oversight mechanisms.
4. Religious leaders and organisations should leverage digital platforms to disseminate moral teachings, particularly targeting

younger generations through engaging content on social media and online forums.

5. Faith-based organisations should address socio-economic inequalities by implementing empowerment initiatives such as skills acquisition programmes and microfinance support to alleviate poverty and promote ethical practices.

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Education as a Fundamental Right and Its Role in Societal Progress

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Abstract

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a critical factor influencing access to quality education, a fundamental component of social mobility and societal equity. In many societies, SES shapes not only the financial resources available to individuals and families but also their ability to access quality learning environments, which, in turn, has profound implications for their educational outcomes. This paper delves into the complex relationship between SES and educational opportunities, exploring how various dimensions of SES, including income, geographic location, and cultural capital, shape learning experiences and outcomes across diverse populations. Through the lens of global data and case studies from different regions, the analysis uncovers significant systemic disparities that contribute to unequal access to education, disproportionately affecting children from low-income and marginalized backgrounds. Historical, social, and institutional barriers often perpetuate these disparities that hinder efforts to achieve true educational equity. The paper examines the role of income as a key determinant of educational access, highlighting the challenges faced by families in lower-income brackets who struggle to afford private education, supplemental learning resources, and necessary school supplies. It also explores the geographic divide in education, where rural and remote areas often face limited access to quality schools, teachers, and infrastructure, further compounding educational disadvantages. Additionally, the concept of cultural capital, as introduced by Pierre Bourdieu, is explored, illustrating how parental education, social networks, and the transmission of cultural knowledge impact a child's educational success. The paper emphasizes that these intersecting factors of SES work together to create a cycle of inequality, where disadvantaged students face multiple barriers to success. Drawing on these insights, the paper highlights a range of effective policy interventions aimed at addressing these disparities and promoting educational equity. These include recommendations for equitable school funding, ensuring that all schools, regardless of their students' socioeconomic backgrounds, have access to high-quality

resources, facilities, and trained teachers. The importance of investing in early childhood education is also stressed, as it has been shown to provide foundational skills and support that can set children on a path to long-term academic success. Furthermore, the paper highlights the need for targeted initiatives to bridge the digital divide, ensuring that students from low-income families have access to the technology and internet connectivity necessary for modern learning environments. These strategies, among others, are designed to close the educational achievement gap and ensure that education remains a universal human right, accessible to all, regardless of their socioeconomic status. Ultimately, the paper calls for a concerted effort from policymakers, educators, and communities to address the systemic barriers that perpetuate inequality in education. By implementing comprehensive strategies to address the diverse factors that impact SES and educational opportunities, societies can create more equitable educational systems that offer every child the chance to succeed. Achieving this goal is not only a moral imperative but also a necessary step toward building a more just and inclusive society.

Keywords: Socioeconomic Status, Education Equity, Policy Intervention, Digital Divide, Social Mobility

Introduction

Education is universally recognized as a fundamental human right, pivotal not only for individuals' personal development but also for societies' collective growth. Its transformative power to lift individuals out of poverty, provide economic opportunities, and break cycles of intergenerational disadvantage is well-documented. It serves as a vehicle for enhancing social mobility, allowing individuals to move beyond the constraints of their immediate environment and achieve better standards of living. Moreover, education plays a central role in driving economic development, fostering innovation, and strengthening democratic institutions. The link between an educated populace and a flourishing society is undeniable, with educated individuals contributing to the workforce, advancing knowledge, and enriching the social fabric. However, despite its immense importance, access to quality education remains deeply unequal, particularly across different socioeconomic strata. In many parts of the world, education is not experienced as a universal entitlement but as a privilege for those with the means to afford

it or access it. This inequity is especially pronounced in regions where poverty, limited infrastructure, and societal inequalities create barriers to educational opportunities. Children from lower-income families or marginalized communities are often denied the same educational resources, quality of instruction, and learning environments as their wealthier counterparts. Consequently, this disparity in educational access perpetuates cycles of disadvantage, leaving children born into low-income households with fewer opportunities for upward mobility.

Socioeconomic status (SES), which encompasses factors such as income, parental education, and occupational status, plays a critical role in shaping the educational experiences of children. (Bourdieu, 1986) work on social and cultural capital highlights the ways in which SES impacts not only the availability of educational resources but also the expectations and cultural practices surrounding education within families. Families with higher SES are often able to provide their children with a rich array of learning opportunities, from access to private tutors and extracurricular activities to a stable home environment conducive to academic success. In contrast, lower-SES families may struggle to afford such resources, and the stressors associated with economic hardship can negatively affect the cognitive and emotional development of children, further hindering their academic performance.

The complex interplay of SES and educational outcomes results in an entrenched system of inequality, where children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds are more likely to experience limited educational opportunities, lower-quality schools, and, ultimately, reduced chances of achieving upward social mobility. This inequality not only affects individual lives but also undermines the broader goal of social cohesion and societal progress. As a result, addressing these disparities is an urgent matter, one that requires comprehensive reforms in both educational policy and social structures.

In sum, while education is a fundamental right that should be equally available to all, its distribution remains deeply unequal, primarily influenced by the socio-economic status of families. The cyclical nature of this inequality perpetuates barriers to success and prosperity for generations, making it essential to address the systemic challenges that hinder equitable access to education. Only through targeted interventions that address the root causes of educational inequality—

such as poverty, lack of resources, and cultural biases—can we hope to create a truly inclusive educational system that serves the needs of all individuals, regardless of their socioeconomic background.

Conceptual Framework: A Deep Dive into the Interplay Between Socioeconomic Status (SES) and Education

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a multidimensional construct that includes income, educational attainment, and occupational status. It serves as a lens through which educational disparities can be understood and addressed (Coleman 1988). SES is not merely a label but a dynamic interplay of economic, social, and cultural factors that collectively shape the opportunities available to individuals and communities. Families with higher SES often possess the financial means to invest in education, the cultural capital to navigate educational systems effectively, and the social networks that provide access to further opportunities. In contrast, families with lower SES frequently encounter systemic barriers, limiting their ability to access quality education and perpetuating cycles of disadvantage (Heckman & Mosso, 2014).

This paper examines SES and education because of their critical role in shaping societal outcomes. Education is widely regarded as a key equalizer capable of mitigating SES-related disadvantages, yet its potential remains unrealized for millions globally (United Nations, 2015). The relationship between SES and educational access is particularly relevant in addressing global inequalities, as SES influences not only individual success but also the broader socio-political structures that determine equity in education. This paper highlights the urgency of this issue, aiming to provide actionable insights for policymakers, educators, and international organizations seeking to address these disparities.

The focus of this research is both global and specific. While SES impacts education universally, the problem is particularly acute in low- and middle-income countries. Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, and Latin America emerge as regions where SES-based inequities are most entrenched. Within these regions, children from low-SES families face significant barriers to accessing even basic education, a situation that underscores the systemic nature of these challenges. By examining case studies from various parts of the world—such as Finland’s equitable education model, Cuba’s universal schooling, and Brazil’s Bolsa Família

program—this study demonstrates the feasibility of systemic reforms that prioritize equity (World Bank, 2018).

This analysis is grounded in empirical data and real-world examples to provide both a theoretical foundation and practical solutions. The target population includes children and families from underprivileged backgrounds, with a particular focus on marginalized groups such as ethnic minorities and individuals with disabilities. In exploring these issues, the study not only exposes the roots of educational inequities but also provides tailored recommendations for addressing them in diverse contexts.

What distinguishes this paper is its holistic approach. Unlike generalized studies, it synthesizes the economic, cultural, and social dimensions of SES to offer a comprehensive perspective. Grounded in evidence from global organizations such as UNESCO, OECD, and UNICEF, it also emphasizes the importance of context-specific solutions that address the intersectionality of SES with race, gender, and geography (United Nations, 2015). By conceptualizing SES and education as intertwined systemic issues, the paper transcends surface-level analysis to offer nuanced insights and practical pathways for equitable reform.

This framework situates the research within a broader discourse on educational equity, offering a unique contribution to the field by providing a detailed exploration of SES and its implications for education. Through this lens, the paper seeks to advance the understanding and resolution of one of the most pressing issues of our time: the persistent and pervasive inequities in educational access and quality.

Theoretical Framework

This study explores the intricate relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and educational opportunities, drawing on multiple theoretical perspectives that examine how social, economic, and cultural factors intersect to shape educational outcomes. By applying these frameworks, we can better understand how SES influences access to quality education and, in turn, perpetuates cycles of inequality. The following theories will guide the analysis:

1. Bourdieu's Theory of Social and Cultural Capital

Pierre Bourdieu's theory of social and cultural capital provides a critical lens for understanding the role of SES in educational outcomes. According to Bourdieu (1986), cultural capital refers to the non-financial social assets—such as knowledge, skills, education, and cultural tastes—that individuals acquire from their families and social environments. Children from higher-SES families tend to inherit greater cultural capital, which enhances their educational success. For example, children whose parents have higher levels of education are more likely to have access to a rich home environment that promotes learning, such as books, discussions about school, and exposure to educational activities. In contrast, children from lower-SES backgrounds may lack such resources, which can hinder their academic development.

Bourdieu also introduced the concept of social capital, which refers to the networks of relationships and social connections that individuals can leverage for opportunities, including educational success. Higher-SES families often have greater social capital, enabling them to navigate educational systems more effectively, gain access to better educational resources, and provide their children with opportunities that might not be available to those in lower-SES communities. This theoretical perspective highlights the ways in which SES operates not only through material resources but also through cultural and social resources that shape educational outcomes (Bourdieu, 1986).

2. Human Capital Theory

Human capital theory, as developed by economists such as Becker (1964), posits that investments in education are crucial for economic and social advancement. According to this theory, education increases an individual's skills, knowledge, and productivity, which enhances their future earning potential. From the perspective of SES, human capital theory suggests that individuals from lower-income backgrounds may face barriers to acquiring the educational qualifications necessary to improve their economic status. These barriers include limited access to quality schooling, supplemental learning resources, and other educational opportunities that are crucial for skill development.

However, human capital theory also underscores the broader societal benefits of investing in education, as an educated workforce is essential for economic development and social mobility. By understanding the

limitations of human capital in lower-SES groups, policymakers can develop strategies to reduce these disparities, such as providing greater access to education and ensuring that students from disadvantaged backgrounds can acquire the skills necessary to succeed in the labour market (Becker, 1964).

3. Social Reproduction Theory

Social reproduction theory, as articulated by scholars like Anyon (1980) and Samuel & Herbert (1976) emphasizes the role of education in maintaining social inequality across generations. This theory argues that the education system often functions to reproduce the existing social structure, rather than serving as a tool for upward social mobility. According to this view, children from higher-SES families are socialized into behaviours, attitudes, and knowledge that align with the demands of higher-paying and more prestigious jobs, while children from lower-SES families receive an education that prepares them for less skilled, lower-paying jobs.

The education system, under this theory, reflects the interests of the dominant social classes, and students from disadvantaged backgrounds are often funnelled into lower-status educational tracks that limit their opportunities for advancement. The systemic nature of these disparities means that education often reinforces social stratification, rather than alleviating it. Understanding the role of education in social reproduction is crucial for developing policies aimed at breaking the cycle of inequality and providing all students with the tools necessary to succeed (Anyon, 1980; Bowles & Gintis, 1976).

4. Theories of Structural Inequality

Structural inequality theories, such as those proposed by sociologists like William Julius (Wilson, 1996), focus on the broader social, political, and economic structures that perpetuate inequality. These theories argue that disparities in education are not merely the result of individual choices or behaviours but are deeply embedded in institutional practices and policies that systematically disadvantage certain groups. SES is often intertwined with race, gender, and geography, creating compounding disadvantages for marginalized communities.

For example, the geography of SES plays a significant role in access to quality education. In many regions, rural areas or urban

neighbourhoods with high concentrations of poverty have fewer resources, less-qualified teachers, and outdated curricula, further compounding educational disadvantages. The lack of investment in these communities reflects broader patterns of neglect and underfunding within the education system, which disproportionately affects lower-SES students. By examining the structural factors that contribute to inequality, this theoretical approach helps to uncover the deep-rooted causes of educational disparities and offers insights into the systemic reforms needed to address them (Wilson, 1996).

5. Intersectionality Theory

Intersectionality theory, developed by Crenshaw (1989), is crucial for understanding how different aspects of identity—such as race, gender, class, and disability—intersect to produce unique experiences of privilege or oppression. In the context of education, intersectionality highlights how students from lower-SES backgrounds may experience compounded disadvantages based on other social identities, such as being from racial or ethnic minority groups, being female, or having disabilities.

For instance, Black and Latino students from low-income families often face additional challenges, such as racial discrimination and a lack of cultural representation in curricula. Similarly, female students from disadvantaged backgrounds may experience gender-based biases that affect their educational experiences. By applying an intersectional lens, this study acknowledges the complex ways in which SES interacts with other factors to shape educational access and outcomes, making it essential to adopt policies that address the diverse needs of marginalized student populations (Crenshaw, 1989).

This theoretical framework integrates multiple perspectives to analyse the relationship between socioeconomic status and educational opportunities. By drawing on Bourdieu's theories of social and cultural capital (1986), human capital theory (Becker, 1964), social reproduction theory (Anyon, 1980; Bowles & Gintis, 1976), structural inequality theories (Wilson, 1996), and intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989), the study provides a comprehensive understanding of how SES influences educational outcomes. These theories collectively emphasize that education is not a level playing field and that systemic inequalities must be addressed through targeted policies and interventions. By applying

these frameworks, this paper aims to illuminate the structural and cultural factors that perpetuate educational disparities and propose effective strategies for promoting equity in education.

Conclusion

The relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and educational opportunities is a deeply entrenched issue that impacts individuals' access to quality education, which is a critical factor in promoting social mobility and societal equity. As explored through the lenses of various theoretical frameworks, including Bourdieu's theory of social and cultural capital, human capital theory, social reproduction theory, structural inequality theory, and intersectionality, it becomes evident that SES is a multifaceted determinant that shapes educational outcomes in complex ways.

Bourdieu's theories on social and cultural capital highlight how family background, including the educational level of parents, social networks, and access to cultural resources, can significantly impact a child's ability to succeed in the education system. Higher-SES families are better able to provide their children with the resources and support necessary to thrive academically, while children from lower-SES backgrounds may lack these advantages, putting them at a considerable disadvantage. This reinforces the notion that SES operates not only through financial capital but also through access to social and cultural capital that can profoundly influence educational experiences and outcomes.

Human capital theory adds another layer of understanding by framing education as an essential investment in skills, knowledge, and future earning potential. For individuals from lower-SES backgrounds, however, the barriers to accessing quality education are often rooted in economic limitations, geographic isolation, and a lack of early childhood education opportunities. These barriers limit their capacity to invest in human capital, thus restricting their potential to improve their socio-economic standing. Consequently, the unequal distribution of educational resources and opportunities exacerbates existing social and economic disparities.

The social reproduction theory further illuminates how educational institutions often serve as mechanisms for maintaining social stratification. This theory suggests that schools play a significant role in reinforcing the social class structure, with children from higher-SES

families receiving an education that prepares them for prestigious and well-paying jobs, while those from lower-SES backgrounds are steered toward less skilled and lower-paying work. Education, in this context, becomes a tool of social reproduction rather than upward mobility, perpetuating cycles of inequality across generations.

Structural inequality theory provides a broader perspective by emphasizing that the root causes of educational disparities lie in societal structures, including economic, political, and institutional factors. It is not simply the result of individual choice or behavior, but rather a consequence of policies and practices that disproportionately affect lower-SES individuals. Geographic location, racial disparities, and unequal distribution of resources further compound the difficulties faced by marginalized communities, leaving them with limited access to quality education. The intersection of these structural factors reinforces the barriers that prevent equitable access to education, making it clear that addressing these issues requires systemic change.

Intersectionality theory enriches this understanding by recognizing that experiences of inequality are not solely determined by SES but are shaped by the intersection of multiple identities, such as race, gender, and disability. Children from lower-SES backgrounds who also belong to racial or ethnic minorities, or who face gender-based or disability-related discrimination, experience compounded disadvantages that affect their educational experiences. Thus, educational policies must be sensitive to these intersecting forms of oppression in order to create truly inclusive environments that cater to the diverse needs of all students.

Taken together, these theoretical perspectives underscore that education is not a level playing field. SES influences not only the resources available to students but also the very structures and practices of the educational system that determine their access to those resources. Disparities in SES lead to disparities in educational outcomes, which in turn perpetuate cycles of inequality. Addressing these disparities is not simply a matter of individual effort but requires systemic and policy interventions that aim to dismantle the structural barriers that hinder equitable access to quality education.

To bridge the educational gap, it is crucial to implement policies that promote greater equity in school funding, improve access to early childhood education, and invest in initiatives to close the digital divide. Equitable funding ensures that schools in low-income areas receive the

resources and support necessary to provide a high-quality education to all students, regardless of their SES. Investment in early childhood education is particularly important, as it lays the foundation for future academic success and helps to narrow the achievement gap from an early age. Additionally, addressing the digital divide is essential, especially in an increasingly technology-driven world, where students from lower-SES backgrounds may lack access to the internet and necessary digital tools for learning.

Furthermore, policies should focus on addressing the structural inequalities that contribute to educational disparities. This includes targeting improvements in rural and underserved urban areas where resources are most lacking, and ensuring that schools in these regions receive adequate support to provide students with opportunities for success. Policies must also consider the intersectional nature of inequality, ensuring that students who face multiple layers of disadvantage, such as those from racial minorities or with disabilities, receive the support and resources they need to overcome barriers and succeed academically.

The connection between SES and educational opportunities is complex and deeply entrenched in societal structures. Through the application of various theoretical frameworks, we see that educational inequities are not the result of individual failure but are the product of systemic factors that perpetuate disadvantage. The path to greater educational equity lies in addressing the root causes of these disparities—investing in marginalized communities, ensuring equitable access to resources, and implementing policies that promote inclusive and supportive learning environments. Only through concerted efforts to address these structural issues can we begin to close the education gap and ensure that education remains a fundamental human right for all, regardless of socioeconomic status.

Recommendations

Addressing SES-related educational inequities demands collaborative action. Governments should:

- (1) Equitably fund schools and train teachers.
- (2) Invest in early childhood education and digital literacy.
- (3) Enhance support systems, including nutrition and healthcare.

International organizations like UNESCO and the World Bank must also provide technical and financial support to empower communities.

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Christian Sexuality and Postmodernism: The Emerging Issues

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Abstract

This study discusses the cultural deconstruction of human sexuality in the postmodern society. It examines the problem of the influence and extent of the emerging cultural and moral crises on human sexuality: Sexual revolution, Gender disorientation, Gay marriage, Sex commercialization, New Morality. The following research questions are therefore answered in this paper for a proper understanding of the postmodern society construct of human sexuality and the contextual implications it holds for the Christian community: What is the nature and dimension of post-modern view of human sexuality? ; What are the biblical values, injunction and presentation of sexuality/Christian sexuality?; How do this deconstruction of human sexuality influence and impinge on the church teachings on sexuality-its constructs, its context, its purpose, its sanctity, its spiritual dimension, its employment and its boundaries?; and what should guide the church community in formulating relevant theological response that can preserve biblical absolutes and Christian sexuality? These are evaluated from both the Old Testament and New Testament biblical sexuality and its moral absolutes. This is to provide helpful guidance for the church to understand biblical standard for sexual morality sexual morality standards clearly. This study points out the devastation and corrupting impact of postmodern constructs on Christian sexuality and the moral teachings of the church. This paper contends that the Christian community is under siege by this devastating incursion of the postmodern erosion of its traditional position on sexuality. There is obvious and dire need for the church, from its theological empowerments, to provide a more pragmatic and adequate response to these cultural constructions of biblical sexuality

and be able to preserve a wholesome biblical legacy of Christian sexuality for the up-and-coming generation of Christians, who, perhaps, will face fiercer attack on biblical morality.

Keywords: Postmodern Society, Sexuality, Christian Sexuality, Cultural Crises, Sexual Ethics

Introduction

Postmodernism, from its interrogation with Christian beliefs and practices, is an ideology that embraces a worldview that denies absolute morality and promotes the elevation of self and individual freedom above God's injunctions. This results into a lifestyle or society that brazenly rejects the fact of God's sovereign prerogative to determine what is good or bad, lawful or unlawful, right or wrong, as moral absolutes for his creation. Our post-modern society is embattled and engulfed in the heat of cultural and moral crises regarding values on human sexuality. The emerging cultural deconstruction of biblical sexuality are manifesting in sexual revolution, sexual anarchy, sexual perversion and permissiveness, culture of exhibitionism and nudity, gender disorientation, and anti-procreative culture. Homosexuality and same sex marriage are the most pronounced, insulting and insidious contemporary cultural crisis regarding human sexuality, most particularly, biblical worldview of human sexuality. These sexuality perversions are not new faces; they are as old as recorded human history on earth (Genesis 1-40). However, the contemporary spate and level of sexual permissiveness, the depth and extent of moral degeneration; the total loss of self- control and un-parallel sexual revolution has no precedence in recorded human history. Not even the Ancient Roman Empire stand close to it (Mohler, 2005).

The church as an institution and member of the postmodern society is witnessing the erosion of her traditional biblical foundation for sex, marriage and family life. This has constituted a monumental and devastating challenge to the teachings of the church on these issues so much so that some Christian community has shifted their ground. Opposition to biblical sexual morality in the culture is not just a matter of taste. It is driven by ideas changing how people think and behave. The surrounding culture is rejecting traditional-biblical sexual morality because more and more people are accepting ideas that redefine biblical

moral standards as 'evil', 'corrupt', or 'harmful' (Heimbag, 2004). This study therefore, highlights the problem the church community has at her hand and the urgency of the need for her to effectively respond to this affront on her biblical morality?

Conceptual Clarification

Postmodernism: Postmodernism, born under western secular conditions, is characterized by emphasis on pluralism and relativism and rejects any certain belief and absolute value. It treats values as relative things that differ from culture to culture. Postmodernist reject any constant, definite and universal belief and instead, consider knowledge to be relative, local and fully influenced by special cultures and values. It equally rejects universal moral and spiritual values and accepts the relativity of all values in all areas, so no specific value preference exists (Nooshin & Alireza, 2015). Postmodernism, according to Odunlami (2022) citing Bauman (2011), is developed in the mid-twentieth century as a rejection of modernism and was then extended across many disciplines. A Key postmodernist concern is *deconstruction*, which is a disillusioned response to the failed promise of modernism *construction* of a better humanity and a better world using human reason alone.

Sexuality: God-ordained physical, mental, emotional, behavioral traits and spiritual expression that characterize individuals as distinctly male or female (Oladunjoye, 2006). Sexuality is much more than simply what men and women "do"-but an integral part of our being throughout our entire lifespan (Focus, 2009).

Sexuality Crisis: This is the confusion that bothers on conflicting views and disposition toward traditional understanding of sexuality. This has left the society with as many options as possible in the expression of sexual identity, sexual acts, gender or even marriage.

The Postmodern Construction of Sexuality

The Postmodern construction of sexuality is encapsulated in the sexual revolution, new morality and the emerging gender orientation in its trail. These are briefly clarified here.

Sexual Revolution, Sexual Anarchy, Sexual libertinism: The sexual revolution of our postmodern culture has resulted in relaxed and new standards of sexual behavior and morality for male and female in particular. Sex between two unmarried adults is considered 'safe' with

the precautionary use of condom and it can never be a case of adulterous or promiscuous affair since the duos are consenting adults. In the past, fear of pregnancy may be an inhibition for most female but with readily available contraceptive pills, now more women are ready to comfortably say 'yes' than 'no' to casual sex with an uncommitted partner. On the electronic media and the World Wide Web, we are confronted by much freer and readily accessible sexually erotic scenes targeting young boys and girls. It is even possible to participate online on some pornographic websites. This is because the clandestineness, accessibility and permissiveness modern technology such as the cell phone and internet facility accord sexual activities today, creates a new context or emerging sexual issue, such as, online sex, sextexts, dating websites, sex toy, sex dolly.

Sexual Perversion, Permissiveness, Sex Commercialization, and New Sexual Morality: Today's culture has reached the point where sex outside of marriage is expected. A key issue in dating is no longer *if* one should have sex, but *when*. Many people feel that there is no reason to withhold the complete expression of sexual desires (Jacobs & Strubel, 1996). Ours is a sex-suffused society with perhaps unprecedented sexual awareness and sexual promiscuity. Sex has lost its "mystery" and sanctity because it is obtainable cheaply, engaged in without any relationship or marital commitment with the other person. Nothing is as highly commercialised today as the sexual act and nothing is equally trivialised in our contemporary times as it. The permissiveness is such that sexual intimacy has been reduced to performance show that is watched online or via other electronic media for public consumption as recreational purposes. The traditional concept of sex as sacred and not to be wantonly engaged in has been eroded away. More sadly is the obvious fact that this generation has no regard for biblical morality, which according to Mohler (2004), is regarded as antiquarian and repressive. Our society moral tone is obviously encoded in the slogan 'if it feels good, do it'. In other words, her standard of morality, sexual morality inclusive, is a matter of personal preference and relative morality. The result is a society plagued by sexual anarchy, promiscuity and perversion which is particularly characteristic of today's young people.

Emergence of New Morality: There is continued subversion of traditional socio-ethical values by new moral standard and its emerging

values. This process is seen in the emergence of new morality in the Post-modern Nigerian society. Some practical illustrative examples are definitely appropriate here. These may include the followings:

- i) *Baby Mama*: This is a relatively new terminology in human sexuality matter. It is an emerging sexual morality that has largely become a norm especially among the upper class, the celebrities, and the politicians. It is described as baby *mama* kind of partner. Baby *mama* is a woman who is a *mama* or mother because she has a baby (or babies) for a man who consents together with her to have sex and gave him a baby that bears his name even though the baby *mama* is fully aware of a legal spouse or other baby *mama* the man has. A baby *mama* is not addressed as 'Mrs' Jones for example, but as baby *mama* of Jones and most often, the men involved are celebrities so many more women are willing to become their baby *mama* and proudly so. As opposed to the stigma, frown look, caustic comment and social disapproval that ordinarily and expectedly should attend this baby *mama* lifestyle, it is rather gaining social acquiesce, tolerance and popularity as demonstrated on the social media in particular.
- ii) *'Sugar Mummy'*: This is a slang made popular by the movies industry. It encapsulates a well-entrenched new morality that celebrates an older woman, addressed as 'sugar mummy', who seeks the sexual services of younger energetic men whom she pays for their patronage. This is unlike what obtains before. It is the woman here, who pays the young man who is believed to have the sexual resources that the 'sugar mummy' needed. This is a reversal of sexual economic theory as initially observed in the society and it equally plays out at the so called 'baby factory' where the man is paid for his service to impregnate the abducted girls so they can give birth to babies needed for 'ritual' money by their buyers. The movie industry has popularized this 'sugar mummy' stuff and successfully pushed it to the society as a new norm. The present realities about the issue of sex reveal that sex is no longer a female resource alone but dual resources for both male and female. Today, men are not only paying consenting female sexual partners, more women too, or 'sugar mummy' in particular, are seeking out agile young men to pay for engaging them in sexual relationship.
- iii) *Sexual Innuendos*: The use of traditional euphemism or modesty in describing issues of sex acts, sexual organs, or bedroom intimate affairs is no longer the norms. Almost everywhere you turn, one is inundated with sexually erotic slangs, graphic jokes about sex organs and coitus.

These are spread by the theatre industries and their actors or actresses who are role models for modern youths in particular. Such public looseness about lewdness, vulgar sex jokes, sexually erotic images, sex icon are emerging ethical issues unknown and uncelebrated before.

- iv) *SEX as S3X and S\$X*: On the social media and news sources, sex is now written or seen as S3x. Although it was meant to be internet slang for sex but its usage encompasses sex in every way that it is known or practiced. This may be seen as a coded and new approach to the subject of preference or values in the acts of sexual intercourse. This accommodation makes it convenient to effortlessly navigate the current controversy surrounding the socio-religious debates over the accommodation of oral and anal sex as natural, healthy, alternate option for sexual acts. The number 3 replacement of the letter 'E' gives room to accommodate sex acts done via any of the three orifices of vaginal, anus and mouth as sex, good sex, natural sex, acceptable sex as against any argument to the contrary. 'Threesome' is a term attached to S3X acts which may also carry the above implication but is not limited to the involvement of three (3) sexual partners that can be a woman and two men or two women and a man in sexual acts. 'Threesome', though a new sexual slang, is not new in pornography industry as displayed in their media advertisement. It has however moved out of its previous domain in the pornography world into the larger society. 'Threesome' is now receiving social media acceptance and approval that is gradually finding its way into societal norm at least among the 'aristole' class. In the same dimension, SEX is also written as S\$X with dollar or pound sterling icon in place of the letter 'E'. This connotes how widely sexual acts has become commercialized.

Gender Orientation, Sexual Attributes, Culture of Nudity and Exhibitionism

The gender orientation crisis has produced the **LGBTQ** classification which is an acronym for: Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender and Queer

Lesbian: This is a woman with sexual orientation or sexual feeling towards another woman;

Gay: This is a man who has a romantic: sexual, erotic and emotional attraction to a male;

Bisexual: Refers to a person who experiences sexual or physical attraction to more than one gender not necessarily at the same time, in the same way, or to the same degree;

Transgender: This person view of self-identity or gender does not match his/her assigned sex at birth, or does not conform to the gender stereotypes (Ijasini, 2021).

Queer: Queer is a term used by those wanting to reject specific labels of romantic orientation, sexual orientation and/or gender identity.

The human society all over the world is divided over how it should react or relate to the question of LGBTQ-Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender and Queer movement. The Western nations have been more favorably disposed to LGBT movement (Daniel, 2005) unlike in most African countries where stigma and more religious sentiments negatively trail such disposition (Okhuelabge, 2017).

On the issue of nudity and exhibitionism, the societal standard set by the movie industries is for women to be scantily clad. Flaunting of physical bodily and sexual attributes of the feminine gender is the vogue. Ladies who are 'busty' or have a peculiar backside are model of enviable sexual attributes. The media touts and celebrates the silent slogan, 'the bigger the better' in its evaluation of sexual attributes. Everything is being done by many females to measure up to this social sexual construct.

Biblical Sexuality and Its Moral Absolutes

On sexual matters the Bible does not pander to any prudishness. It has its own concept of sex and human sexuality clearly spelt out. Brandstra and Verhey (1988) allude to this fact when they paint a holistic picture of biblical concern and pervasion with the subject of sex and human sexuality in their accurate assessment that:

The Torah regulates sexual activity and establishes sexual roles. Prophetic literature uses sexual metaphors in its announcement of God's judgement on covenant unfaithfulness. Wisdom literature distinguishes wise sexual conduct from foolish and uses sexual imagery to characterize wisdom. The Gospel uses the memory of Jesus' words and deeds to shape the sexual conduct and disposition of His followers. The Epistles deal with concrete question of sexual conduct. Revelation contains sexual imagery and instruction

A biblical understanding of sexuality and sex is important for the spiritual and moral health of the Church, especially as it relates to human sexuality and to answer the question of 'what does the Bible really say about sex?' Mohler (2005) pontificates that:

The controversies over same-sex marriage, homosexuality, and gender-bending now raging in our culture, necessitates answering the question: “What is the biblical pattern for human sexuality?” A clear picture of biblical position on the subject of sexuality and sex is what will enable Christian adolescents have a reference for what is right, appropriate and biblical in the expression of their sexuality.

The premise for establishing biblical conception of sexuality and sex is usually developed from the Yahwist (Genesis 1) and Priestly (Genesis 2) biblical creation narratives: So God created man in His own image; in the image of God He created he him; male and female He created them (Genesis 1:27). And the LORD God said, ‘It is not good that man should be alone; I will make him a helper like him’...And they were both naked, the man and his wife, and were not ashamed (Genesis 2:18, 24). The creation story as found in the two biblical narratives of Genesis 1 and Genesis 2 though clearly presents the creation of Adam and Eve in seemingly two different lights; Most Bible Scholars have treated both narratives as complimentary rather than antagonistic. Several theological observations regarding human sexuality have been made taking these two accounts as the premise on which their theories or postulations are based.

Adayibe (2006) analyzing Genesis: 1:27, 2:18, notes that God created man and woman as sexual beings, as sex partners with different sex roles but having sexual needs. Stanley (1977) as cited in Ogundele (2006) submits that sex is an expression of our existence as sexual beings. Abogunrin (2006) observes that the word sex refers to different things in the Bible. According to him, it refers to human physical anatomy because the scripture says that ‘God created man in His own image...male and female, He created them’; Secondly, according to him, sex in another sense refers to physical attraction and in this sense we speak of someone being physically attractive (Genesis 39:6). Sexuality however has been noted from a critical look into its creation in Genesis as multidimensional, while sex is considered as just an expression of it at its sexual/physical level. Sexuality is seeing as having a physical dimension, that causes human being, just like Adam and Eve to seek for harmony and relationship with their physical environment; as having an emotional/relational dimension that causes one to yearn for relationship and understanding with others, resulting in friendship or at a deeper

intimate level in marriage/sexual relationship, this is exemplified in the loneliness of Adam and his satisfaction when Eve came into his life (Doug, 2008). Sexuality can also be perceived as having a spiritual dimension to it, stirring up an insatiable desire for fellowship and worship with the Divine, just as Adam and Eve in the biblical account of Genesis 3:8 enjoyed intimate fellowship with God in the cool of the day while in the Garden of Eden (Oluwatoba, 2010).

God declares his creation as good (Genesis 1:31), and that includes human sexuality, thus sex, sex drive, or sexuality is God's own creation, idea and gift to mankind (Paulik, 1996 & Igboin, 2006). God's charge to the first man and woman in their original state of innocence was procreation-to 'be fruitful and replenish the earth' (Genesis 1:28). This is a necessity that makes sex in marriage not a sin but rather, good (Genesis 1:31) and holy (Hebrew 13:40). Speaking from the reproductive perspective, sex was also conceived as an instinct that produces the family institution (Chesterton, as cited in biblicalsexuality.com). While Jackson (2004), on utility ground, clarifies that sex is a great thing, which God designed to benefit married men and women. According to Hostler and McDowell (2007), with the debut of the second sex (Eve), Adam's loneliness problem was solved and God's creation was good and complete. From these analyses these authors describe God as pro-sex, who creates sex and wants people (couple) to enjoy it to the fullest as a noble but not debase thing. Genesis narrative apart, other biblical writers also and further affirm the goodness of sexuality and sex as God's gift. The Song of Solomon is an extended love poem with explicit erotic imagery and language. In the book of Proverbs, Sex is affirmed as a source of pleasure and shared intimacy between husband and wife. In the Prophetic books, the imagery of human sexuality and intimacy is used to describe burning passion of God's love and relationship to his people.

In the Gospel, Jesus refers to the Genesis narrative in his response to the sanctity and sacredness of human sexuality in marital homestead, thus affirming the 'good' pronounced on human sexuality at the beginning. He also by his lifestyle of lifting the feminine gender demonstrates positive examples to his followers and the 'anti-woman' culture/society of his days. Apostle Paul in the Epistles, and the Old Testament prophets in several places, celebrate the act of sex and sexual relationship in marriage as having divine approval (Songs 1-5; Proverbs 5:18ff;

Ecclesiastes 9:9; Isaiah 43:4; Malachi 1:24; Hosea 1-3; Mathew 19: 4-6; 1 Corinthians 7:1-5).

According to Mohler (2005),

Sexual pleasure is not an accident of human biology--it is one of the Creator's sweetest gifts to human beings. The promise of sexual pleasure and satisfaction is to draw us into the marital covenant, and then shared joy of physical union is a vital part of the marital bond. The biblical writers affirm sexuality as a part of our embodied existence. As human beings we are sexual creatures, and as sexual creatures we are called to honor God with our bodies. Within the context of the marital covenant, the husband and wife are free to express love for each other, experience pleasure, and join in the procreative act of sexual union.

This is pleasing to God, and is not to be a source of shame.

The recurring theme about biblical sexuality presenting itself from all the above biblical assessments and inferences include: the nature of sex and sexuality; the purpose of sex; and context for the expression of sex and sexuality.

Sexual Perversion

The Bible repeatedly warns against sexual activities outside of the marriage covenant and thus emphasizes the spiritual connotation embedded in sex. Scholars, from biblical submissions give various evaluations of sex outside of marriage and the sacredness the scripture accords it. Mohler (2005) observes that just as the biblical writers present marital sex as holy and natural, all other forms of sexual activity are presented as condemned and sinful. He warns that in addition to adultery and fornication, the Bible expressly forbids homosexuality, bestiality, incest, prostitution, rape, pederasty, and all other forms of sexual deviance and perversity (Leviticus 18:22; Romans 1:26-27; Exodus 22:19; Leviticus 18:23; Leviticus 18:6-18; 1 Corinthians 5:1-13; Exodus 2:16-17; Proverbs 7:1-27). Several specific sexual relationships are forbidden in the Bible. Among these are homosexuality (Leviticus 18:22, 26, 27, 20:13; Judges 19:22-24; I Corinthians 6:9; I Timothy 1:9-10; 2 Timothy 3:1-5); bestiality-sex with animals (Leviticus 18:23; 20:15-16; Exodus 22:19; Deuteronomy 27:21); and incest-sexual relations with close family members, including your mother, sister, niece, aunt,

daughter-in-law, and sister-in-law (Leviticus 18:6-18, 20:10-21); fornication – sexual relations outside of marriage and adultery – sexual relations with another person's spouse (Leviticus 20:10ff, 18:19; Exodus 20:14, 5:18; Deuteronomy 22:22-24, 1 Corinthians 6:9-10, Ephesians 5:3-5; Galatians 5:19,21; Mathew 5:27), and rape – forced sex (Genesis 34; Deuteronomy 22:23-29).

Deem (2010) responding to these sexual perversions comments that to emphasize the seriousness of these kinds of offenses, the Torah recommends death as the penalty. According to Deem, it is clear that pornography is not to be viewed by Christians, although not specifically mentioned in the Bible. Some other writers and scholars are more forthright in their opinion of pornography, declaring it as: sin, abominable practices and unscriptural; 'setting evil things before one's eyes'; 'partaking in other men sin'; 'abuse of the body, which is the temple of the Holy Spirit'; and a 'desecration of the sanctity the scripture accords sex": and as 'possessing addictive influence, especially on men' (Mohler, 2005 & Donovan, 1995). Heimbach (2004) comprehensively captures the whole picture:

God's standard is purity in every thought about sex, as well as in every act of sex. Sexual purity is violated even in thoughts that never proceed to outward acts. Sex must never be used to oppress, wrong or take advantage of anyone. Rape, incest, sexual abuse, pedophilia, voyeurism, prostitution and pornography always exploit and corrupt. Sex outside of marriage is never moral. This includes all forms of intimate sexual stimulation that stir up sexual passion between unmarried partners. Such behavior offends God, and often causes physical and emotional pain and loss in this life. Refusal to repent of sexual sin may indicate that a person never has entered into a saving relationship with Jesus Christ. The Old and New Testaments uniformly condemn sexual contact between persons of the same sex; and God has decreed that no one can ever excuse homosexual behavior by blaming his or her Creator

The above point towards the fact that both the Old and New Testament writers warn against the corrupting influence of sexual sin, and they enjoined the people of God to remain unspotted and uncorrupted by such sins.

Therefore, it is clear from the various Scriptural references cited above that sexual deviance amount to an intentional rejection of God's authority and sovereignty to tell His creation what is helpful or destructive, as their Creator and Lord (Romans 1:18-25). This is one reason why Apostle Paul warns that those who practice such sins will not inherit the Kingdom of God (1 Corinthians 6:9-11).

Biblical Understanding of Gender

The issue of gender is an integral aspect of human sexuality and there can be no complete or thorough biblical evaluation or understanding of human sexuality without an examination of divine purpose and plan in creating humanity as male and female (Genesis 1:27; 2:28). Mohler (2005) in his biblical evaluation of the creation narratives emphatically states that gender is not a mere biological accident or social construction. According to him, the contrast and complement between the man and the woman reveals that gender is part of the goodness of God's creation. Mohler argues that modern efforts to redefine or redesign gender are directly contrary to the Bible's affirmation of maleness and femaleness as proper distinctions. According to him, God's glory is seen in the maleness of the man and the femaleness of the woman. Mohler concludes that this pattern of distinction is affirmed and enforced by liturgical orders and restrictions on dress, hair length, etc. And that any effort to confuse or deny gender differences is expressly forbidden and opposed by Scripture, especially as seen in Old Testament legal codes. Talking from the New-Testament perspectives on gender difference, Jackson (2004) observes that there is a paradox: "The Bible teaches that God not only created us "male and female", but that in Christ, "there is neither male nor female"(Genesis 1:27; Galatians 3:28-29). Jackson deduced that, from those scriptures, God answers our dilemma with a delightful mystery and within this paradox, God not only affirms the differences between men and women, assigning complementary roles for each, but He also points to the equality existing between the sexes. Relating gender differentiation to life purpose, Focus (2009) sees our God-given purpose as tied to our unique biological sex; such that, sexuality, which the author described as the specific God-ordained physical, mental and behavioral traits that characterize individuals as distinctly male or female, is much more than simply what men and

women "do" – but an integral part of our being throughout our entire lifespan.

Postmodern Constructs on Sexuality and Its Consequences on Church Teachings on Sexual Values

The ongoing construction and reconstruction of Christian ethical and moral values on sexuality is emerging fallout of postmodernism. The revelation of the scriptures on its absolutes for the expression of human sexuality is being subsumed in the present culture of sexual deviance and libertinism. Some Christian communities have succumbed to the invasion of the homosexual agenda. This is evidence in their celebration of gay marriage and lifestyle as acceptable 'alternate' lifestyle for members of the Christian community. Ordination of homosexuals to the Priesthood, the continued public self-declaration of church leaders as gay, and the emergence of gay churches are sad commentary.

The culture of nudity and exhibitionism festers in the individual and corporate life of Christians and the church such that in many of our Christian gatherings we are bombarded with overly body exposure of the feminine gender. Christian girls and women have taken Hollywood, Bollywood, and Nollywood celebrities as their standard for comportment and carriage, because that is what passes as fancy, fashion and 'being cool'. All these contribute to increase the already unfavourable conditions that hamper Christian youths' efforts to make sound and godly decision on moral and sexual purity. For instance, in most groups or societies involving young people such as voluntary organisations like youth clubs, school press clubs, students' unions and others, not to be sexually active as a single person may attract mockery, especially if such commitment to purity or abstinence is claimed to be based on religious consecration, respect for parental values and/or personal commitment to chastity. Many single young people on our higher institution live 'a couple- life'. They pair up, live together in rented apartment and sometimes contest to be celebrated in their various campus publications as the best couple of the year. Christian young people on the side of abstinence and moral uprightness find themselves under tremendous peer and societal pressure to compromise their biblical stance.

The sexual permissiveness of the postmodern society is reflected in the church, among the household of faith, in the violation of the biblical

sexual boundaries. There is increasing premarital sexual activities of Christian youths, continue reports of clerical sexual abuse of the parishioner, high rate of church ministers divorce of spouses. The perversion of sexuality in the church is even so offensive to the secular society that it often challenges and confronts the church to put her house in order. To the secular society, the church has no moral justification for its various comments on what it thinks the Bible says in contradiction to the societal same sex activities. The church in certain areas seems to have lost the battle in championing God's design and demands for wholesome, fulfilling, joyful, and sanctified sexuality.

Some communities of faith have found in the same Biblical revelation, some justification to tolerate or accommodate sodomy and all shades of 'gender disorientation.' While some homosexual or transgender church members justify their sexual disposition as 'that is how God created or wired me sexually' or, as: 'am naturally attracted to someone of the other sex' (Bridge-Logos, 2004). The biblical sexual values are been revisited and interpreted from a postmodern view as 'weird', 'puritan', antiquarian and out of tune with modern realities of contraceptive pills, test tube and designer babies, sex reconstructive surgery and other advance medical discoveries.

The Emerging Issues and Their Implications

We shall now briefly outline and evaluate the emerging issues in the context of the church community and the on-going deconstruction of its theological and ethical standpoint on human sexuality.

- i) *Cultural assimilation of biblical values:* These researchers posit that the preservation of spiritual revelation from assimilation to cultural constructions depend on a proper biblical understanding and effective contemporary theologizing. This is a major factor in the ability of theologians/Christian educators to provide contextual and scripturally relevant meaning to everyday issues people grapple with.
- ii) *A compromise of biblical boundaries:* Where there is church sympathy to same sex orientation and activities, it has further confused the up-and-coming generation of Christians who could not find clear biblical standard, value and norms even within the church that can inspire and challenge them to uphold wholesome sexuality.
- iii) *A deconstruction of the marriage institution:* This distortion and perversion of Christian marriage in the celebration of same sex

marriage even in the church presents contemporary Christians with a new context that beclouds the correct understanding of God's purpose in gender distinction within marriage. This also is an abysmal emerging sexual issue in the discussion of Christian family values.

- iv) *The reality of personal struggles with sexual crises:* Some people in the church are having a personal struggle with their sexual identity and/or an orientation toward homosexual lifestyle. Unfortunately, this usually generates moral censure rather than compassion and assistance when they try to open up-seeking help.
- v) *Sexual empowerment:* There is not much public awareness and sensitization in our society on the problem of gender conflicts. Most parents, Christian counselors, Pastors and other stakeholders face a dearth of helpful information and empowerments on how they can help their ward or clients maximize tendency toward a heterosexual lifestyle. Christian youth on the side of abstinence and moral uprightness find themselves under tremendous peer and societal pressure to compromise their biblical stance.
- vi) *The Church is split over homosexual orientation, acts and gay marriage:* Same-sex sexual relationship which many now considered as an alternate lifestyle constitutes an emerging sexual issue and a new context for Christian sexuality that must be addressed by the church. This is particularly necessary for the church because the issue of homosexual lifestyle has rocked her doctrinal comforts in the last decade perhaps more than any other ethical issues that have confronted it in her historical existence. The Anglican Communion Church of Nigeria for instance has taken a biblical stand against the incursion of homosexual agenda in the church in Nigeria which is a clear departure from the Church of England (Lambert, 2017). Whereas two key leaders in the American Southern Baptist, JD Geerar and Andrew Walker, reportedly demonstrate a little measure of tolerance that does not see it as a compromise of truth to address LGBTQ with their preferred pronoun such as calling a man in a woman attire as 'transgendered woman' even when such preferred pronouns do not match their biological sex" (Dissenter, 2022). Other Evangelicals have criticized, as a capitulation, such adoption of LGBTQ language to appease the movement. The Roman Catholic Church Bishops in Nigeria have expressed their displeasure with the Pope public declaration of his blessing for the gay marriage.

vii) *Human defiance against divine demand*: “The problem is that some people do not like to hear what God has to say...they defiantly make up their own rules and go their own way. Sadly this only leads to more confusion and deeper deception” (Bridge-Logos, 2004). This has caused a gleeful Satan to hijack and distort the gift of sex to merchandise his philosophy that self-gratification insures a happy life.

Role of the Church and Its Christian Education Agencies

There is a compelling need to underscore the position of the church community and outline some line of action at its disposal to survive this frontal onslaught against its traditional or orthodox beliefs, practices, and values for sexuality. The role of the church in providing empowerment for its members to avoid the evil and destructive outcomes of premarital sex, sexual promiscuity, rape, pornography, nudity and other immoral sexual behavior is strengthened by the graphic examples provided in many of the biblical account of human sexual relationship, challenges and triumph. These include Samson’s tragedy (Judges 14-16); Prophet Eli and his two sons – Hophni and Phineas (1 Samuel 2-4); King David’s life and family; Amnon, Tamar, and Absalom (2 Samuel 11:4-5,18;); Solomon (1 Kings 11:1-8); Sodom and Gomorrah destruction (2 Peter 1:6). Christian religious educators can draw resources, insights and divine wisdom from these real-life experiences and family-based scriptures (Genesis 1:26-28; 2:18, 22-24, 9:1; Malachi 2: 15; Mathew 19: 1-9; Romans 1:18-28). These historical identities and biblical injunctions can motivate and guide the faith communities, the youths in particular, in living out God’s design for biblical sexuality.

The church is also called upon to address same sex related problem as another face of sexual anarchy and revolution. Homosexual orientation has constituted a very serious challenge for Christian ethics and biblical sexual standard. This is because there are many churches or ecclesiastical leaders that are now sympathetic with this gender disorientation (Asaju, 2005). The church where the true standard of God in sex distinction of the female and male, especially in sex and marital relationship, is upheld, can help her community by preaching and teaching on the true and correct biblical view and expectation of gender distinction. The church should make it clear from the scripture, God’s displeasure against homosexual practice (Genesis 19:24; Leviticus 18:22 Romans 1:25-27) and the church also must emphasize the love of God

for the gay or homosexuals and his desire that they amend their ways (John 3:16; Roman 5:8; Roman 3:23). Dollar (2004) encourages churches to develop an open and receiving attitude to homosexuals, not to compromise God's standard for their sake but to show the love of God to them. This is because, according to him, many homosexuals are confused and empty within in need of inner healing and restoration back to the true God.

For Christians who are having sexual struggles in these areas, the church must be redemptive and restorative. Stereotyping, scapegoating, stigmatizing and segregation of persons especially parishioners with gender orientation that do not qualify as 'straight' falls short of Jesus Christ's attitude of 'love for the sinner but displeasure at the sin.' Further, Church members in this struggle can be helped by church leadership sound teachings on biblical sexual values as earlier noted, compassionate concern and personal commitment to walk with such parishioners through their sexuality challenges. As an important role of the church in dealing with same-sex issues within the church or in the secular society, Dollar (2004) calls the church attention to this often neglected fact that before dealing with what is going on in the natural, we must first bind the spirit (Mathew 12: 28-29; Ephesians 6:10-14;) behind the homosexual activity that is going on in our nation and break the stronghold of homosexuality that seem to be infiltrating our land. And the next step is to take action in the natural realm which may include pressuring against legislation that seeks to support same-sex lifestyle; ministering salvation to those who are struggling with homosexuality by imparting God's love to them; not to ostracize young people in church who have problem in this area but to be a source of loving, firm support as these people in the church fight to obtain freedom.

Further, from researchers' reports on possible causes of gender disorientation or homosexual tendency, Christian parents must understand the imperative need of being available for their children especially in their early years. The fathers, in particular have been advised to ensure that he bonds well with their son, while the mothers are warned not to be overbearing especially with the boy. This role of parents in the early bonding with their children is informed by research finding that a common denominator to most male homosexuals is an absent father.

The assumption that biblical sexual morality is common knowledge for many Christians gives way in the face of the increasing capitulation to non-biblical sexual choices and its devastating consequences on the Church, its leadership, its theology of sexuality, the rich tradition of Christian moral teachings, on the family, on individuals and the culture. Christian approach to sexuality should continually be addressed in the light of the massive sexual revolution that is currently invading the human societies. In doing so the church must correct its failure in presenting Christian sexual ethics as essentially prohibitive, legalistic, and reprehensive, devoid of grace, joy and fulfillments. The goodness of God, his good purposes and his provisions for a positive and productive human sexuality should be the context for presenting Christian sexual morality.

Conclusion

The above establishes that there is, outside the church wall, an emerging global sexual issue that seeks to deconstruct and reconstruct biblical sexual morality. This constitutes growing challenges for the church which seek to destroy its moral obligation to biblical sexuality. However the church, for the most part, seems not to be cognizant of the spiritual battles raging in this arena of sexuality. The mind is the battle ground in this sexual (spiritual) warfare, not even the sexual organ, where the forces of hell capture and enslave its victims by its sexual snares. This understanding opens our eyes to the sinister goal of the kingdom of darkness to distort the Groom-Bride imagery of Christ and his Church, to desecrate the sanctity of believers' body as Christ holy temple, and to infiltrate the marriage/family institution and rob Christ of his rightful headship and expected seeds that are to be trained and nurtured in the way of the Lord to perpetrate godly purposes on earth (Paulk, 1985). It is most relevant to conclude with this challenge from Paulk (2005):

The Church needs to wake up and get into the battle against Satan's kingdom of sex. Now is the time to challenge worldly concepts of sexuality with alternatives that offer people a choice, a solution to the emptiness of constant self-gratification which never really satisfies? Only God's people can witness to His goodness in even the most intimate aspects of His intentions in creations.

Recommendations

1. Christian religious educators in the academia and in the wider faith community are to provide biblically and culturally relevant theological response and spiritual empowerment to effectively engage the invading forces of Postmodernism.
2. Christians who uphold biblical absolutes for human sexuality as presented in this study are to rise against the revisionism that gives religious connotation to deviant humanism or that deconstruct and erode the infrastructures of biblical sexuality.

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Driving Positive Change in Nigerian Society through Innovative Leadership

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Abstract

Leadership is pivotal in addressing societal challenges, particularly in regions grappling with socio-economic issues. Innovative leadership, characterized by creativity, adaptability, and problem-solving capabilities, has emerged as a key driver of transformative change. In the Nigerian context, where systemic challenges such as unemployment, corruption, and socio-political complexities persist, innovative leadership can bridge divides, foster collaboration, and inspire sustainable growth. Through a qualitative approach, the study clarifies the concepts of innovative leadership and positive change, examining the Nigerian leadership challenge and exploring the philosophy, idiosyncrasies and theories, as well as practical approaches to driving positive change. This study emphasizes the importance of forward-thinking strategies that address immediate problems while laying the foundation for long-term success. The research highlights how innovative leadership can empower communities, embrace digital transformation, and ensure equitable resource distribution. It also explores the adaptability and visionary mindset required for leaders to navigate complexity in a rapidly changing global landscape; this study underscores the transformative potential of innovative leadership in fostering progress and inclusivity for future generations.

Keywords: Positive Change, Nigerian Society, Innovation, Leadership and Innovative Leadership

Introduction

In the contemporary world, the importance of leadership cannot be overstated, particularly in societies grappling with socio-economic challenges. Creative leadership is crucial in that instance as it embodies creativity, adaptability and the capability to navigate complex issues while promoting change. Innovative leadership has become a critical driver of societal progress, especially in contexts requiring

transformative change, such as Nigeria. Leadership in the modern era is no longer just about managing resources but about promoting creativity, adaptability, and inclusivity in discourse that is pressing social, economic, and political challenges. The need to navigate complexity, inspire collaboration, and implement forward-thinking strategies to achieve meaningful change is one of the features of innovative leadership (Northouse & Lee, 2021). In the Nigerian context, this form of leadership holds immense potential to address systemic issues such as unemployment, corruption, insecurity, economic hardship, insecurity and the likes.

Significantly, innovative leadership emphasizes problem-solving and empowering of systems, organisations and communities. Leaders who adopt this approach are more likely to engage stakeholders, build resilient systems, and foster accountability (Uhl-Bien, Carsten, Huang & Maslyn (2022). For instance, in Nigeria, where diverse ethnic and cultural dynamics influence governance, innovative leadership could bridge divides and inspire collective action. In transforming communities, two things stand out, namely, community organising and community action. Both of them are done collectively through collaboration, partnership and networking of people of good-will and people of good-faith for common goals of such a community or organisation to be achieved. Basically, innovative leadership involves nurturing partnerships, embracing digital transformation, and prioritizing equitable resource access while empowering and creating an environment conducive to sustainable growth and societal transformation. Furthermore, innovative leadership thrives on adaptability and visionary thinking. In a rapidly changing global landscape, Nigerian leaders must embrace a mindset that anticipates challenges and identifies growth opportunities. Kouzes and Posner (2019) argue that such leadership addresses immediate problems and sets the foundation for long-term success by instilling a culture of innovation and continuous improvement. As Nigeria faces local and global challenges, innovative leadership offers a pathway to drive positive change, ensuring progress and inclusivity for future generations. Therefore, this study clarifies the Concepts of Innovative Leadership and Positive Change, looks into the Nigerian Leadership Challenge and the Need for Change, explores the Philosophy,

Idiosyncrasies and Theories of Innovative Leadership, and drives for Positive Change through Innovative Leadership.

Concept of Innovative Leadership

Innovative leadership denotes leaders' ability to integrate creativity, adaptability, and strategic foresight to drive transformative outcomes within their organizations or communities. Unlike traditional leadership, which often emphasizes maintaining established systems, innovative leadership focuses on disrupting the status quo to achieve greater effectiveness and inclusivity. Alhamami (2024) cites Northouse and defines innovative leadership as a dynamic process of influencing others to explore novel ideas and implement change that aligns with evolving societal or organizational demands. This leadership style requires integrating emotional intelligence, collaboration, and the application of technology to address complex challenges effectively. In so doing, contextual challenges are addressed as innovative leadership is applied integratively and accordingly.

The hallmark of innovative leadership is its proactive and solution-oriented approach. Leadership that adopts this style are adept at identifying gaps, fostering a culture of experimentation, and empowering teams to take calculated risks. Leitão, Marques & Almeida (2024) cite Uhl-Bien et al. to emphasize that innovative leadership thrives on adaptability, enabling leaders to navigate uncertainties and transform them into opportunities. This approach is particularly critical in volatile environments, as it fosters resilience and the capacity to pivot strategies in retort to emerging trends or crises. By prioritizing continuous learning and development, innovative leaders ensure their teams remain equipped to meet the demands of a rapidly changing world.

Moreover, innovative leadership is inherently collaborative, leveraging diverse perspectives to co-create effective and sustainable solutions. Miao & Nduneseokwu (2025) cite Kouzes and Posner to argue that such leadership emphasizes shared vision and collective problem-solving, cultivating an environment where innovation can flourish. This concept goes beyond individual brilliance, encouraging leaders to inspire and engage others in pursuing groundbreaking ideas and transformative action. Innovative leadership lays the foundation for long-term success by aligning creativity, adaptability, and strategic focus with

organizational or societal goals. Strategic focus is best obtained when guided by a well-developed strategic plan.

Concept of Positive Change

Positive change refers to deliberate actions and transformations that result in improved outcomes, whether at individual, organizational, community or societal levels. It involves addressing existing problems and creating pathways for growth, inclusivity, and sustainability. Kuffuor, Aggrawal, Jaiswal, Smith & Morris (2024) cites Kotter to describe positive change as aligning vision with action and fostering an environment where individuals or organizations can thrive. This concept is rooted in the idea that meaningful progress requires intentionality, a commitment to shared values, and the ability to inspire collective effort toward achieving common goals.

The foundation of positive change lies in its ability to address systemic barriers while empowering individuals and communities to take ownership of their growth. Alibašić (2024) emphasizes that positive change involves adaptive work, which requires confronting challenges and building the capacity to respond effectively to evolving needs. This concept acknowledges the importance of collaboration, recognizing that sustainable change often stems from inclusive processes that bring diverse stakeholders together. By addressing root causes and prioritizing equity, positive change creates conditions for long-term progress that benefit all community or organization members.

Positive change also requires resilience and a clear vision for the future. Leadership is crucial in driving this change by inspiring trust, dedication, hard-work, discipline, fostering innovation, and building systems that support continuous improvement. Cameron and Green (2019) argue that positive change is not just about accomplishing short-term success but about creating lasting impact through sustainable practices. By prioritizing ethical decision-making, transparency, and a commitment to shared goals, positive change ensures that transformations are meaningful and enduring, paving the way for a more equitable and prosperous future.

The Nigerian Leadership Challenge and the Need for Change

Nigeria, often called the "Giant of Africa," has immense human and natural resources. Nevertheless, its potential remains largely untapped

due to persistent leadership challenges. The country's history is marked by governance issues such as corruption, inefficiency, and lack of vision among its leaders. Aka (2024), citing Achebe (1984), famously argued in *The Trouble with Nigeria* that the root of the nation's problem is the failure of leadership, which has hindered the country's socio-economic and political development. This lack of effective leadership has created systemic problems, including poverty, unemployment, infrastructural decay, insecurity, and others which continue to plague the country.

Leadership Challenges in Nigeria

Nigeria faces numerous leadership challenges that have hindered its progress and development. Below are some of the significant issues:

1. **Corruption and Lack of Accountability:** Corruption remains one of Nigeria's most significant leadership challenges. Leaders across various levels of governance have often been accused of embezzling public funds and engaging in corrupt practices. Aruofor & Ogbeide (2023) enuciates that corruption in leadership has eroded public trust and diverted resources meant for development into private pockets. Mismanagement of funds and lack of accountability have resulted in inadequate and weak infrastructure, poor healthcare, and underfunded education systems. It has also lead to poor public services and high poverty levels. Achebe (1984), in *The Trouble with Nigeria*, identified corruption as a cancer that eats into the fabric of governance, preventing progress and development. Despite anti-corruption measures, such as those by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the systemic nature of corruption continues to undermine trust in leadership. Corruption is a like a formidable force that has eaten into the fabric of the Nation. Almost all sectors are plagued by corruption.
2. **Lack of Visionary Leadership:** Leadership in Nigeria often lacks the foresight and strategic planning necessary for long-term national development. Many leaders prioritize short-term gains or personal interests over policies that could yield sustainable growth. According to Rotberg (2021), visionary leadership is crucial for any nation's development, setting the tone for innovation and inclusive progress. Nigeria's challenges, including youth unemployment, inadequate infrastructure, and security crises, require innovative and visionary leadership. However, leadership in Nigeria has often

been reactive rather than proactive. Amadi & Owolabi (2024) argue that many leaders lack the foresight and innovation to create long-term solutions. It has left critical sectors such as education, health, and technology underdeveloped. In Nigeria, the absence of leaders with a clear vision has resulted in policy inconsistency, stunted economic growth, and underutilization of resources. Even when vision is shared, do the leaders follow or pursue them faithfully?

3. ***Ethnic and Religious Divisions:*** Nigeria's diversity is both a strength and a challenge. Leaders often exploit ethnic and religious divisions for political gains, fostering disunity and hampering national development. Ngoa, Kperogi & Osaghae (2024) noted that such divisions are frequently manipulated to maintain power, leading to a lack of trust among citizens and creating barriers to national integration. This challenge undermines collective efforts to address pressing issues such as poverty, education, and healthcare.
4. ***Weak Institutions and Governance Structures:*** The inability to build strong institutions has left Nigeria vulnerable to political instability and inefficiency. Weak institutions cannot often hold leaders accountable or enforce the rule of law, allowing impunity to thrive. North, Workmaster, Atucha & Kovalski (2024) emphasized that strong institutions are the bedrock of economic and social development, ensuring transparency, accountability, and equity in governance.
5. ***Poor Youth Inclusion and Development:*** Youth comprise a significant portion of Nigeria's population and are often excluded from leadership and decision-making processes. It has led to disenfranchisement and limited opportunities for innovation and growth. Oluwatobi and Ogunrinola (2011) argue that youth empowerment is critical for leadership transformation and national development. To neglect this demography limits the country's potential to leverage its human capital for growth.
6. ***Security Challenges and Inadequate Responses:*** Nigeria's leadership has struggled to address insecurity, ranging from terrorism and banditry to communal clashes and kidnapping. The inability to provide a stable and safe environment disrupts economic activities and erodes public trust. Lenshie, Nwangwu, Ezeibe, Ifem & Okafor (2024)

highlighted that insecurity in Nigeria is both a symptom and a consequence of weak leadership, further exacerbated by corruption and inadequate resource allocation.

7. **Resistance to Change and Innovation:** Traditional leadership styles in Nigeria often resist innovative practices and ideas that could improve governance. Many leaders are entrenched in outdated practices, ignoring modern trends in technology and global best practices. In their work on adaptive leadership, Busa, Yakubu & Olabode (2024) emphasized the importance of embracing change to address complex challenges in governance.
8. **Socio-Economic Inequality:** Socio-economic disparities remain a critical issue in Nigeria, with a large proportion of the population living below the poverty line. World Bank (2020) data shows that while Nigeria has abundant natural resources, poor leadership has exacerbated inequality and economic stagnation (Akanle & Shittu, 2022). Many leaders focus on urban-centric policies, neglecting rural development and worsening the wealth gap.

The Need for Change in Nigerian Leadership

The need for change in Nigerian leadership is urgent and critical to the nation's survival and progress. Effective leadership is the cornerstone of development, providing vision, direction, and accountability in governance. Rotberg (2021) states transformative leadership is essential for addressing nations' complex challenges, particularly in Africa. In Nigeria, this means transitioning from a culture of impunity to one of transparency, inclusivity, and innovation. Leaders must prioritize policies that foster equitable resource distribution, economic diversification, and social cohesion to bridge the gap between the nation's potential and its current state.

The call for change in Nigerian leadership stems from the persistent challenges that have hindered the nation's progress, such as widespread corruption, poor governance, socio-economic inequality, and a lack of innovation in addressing critical issues. These issues necessitate a shift toward more accountable, inclusive, and forward-thinking leadership.

1. **Need for Ethical Leadership Practices:** There is need for ethical practices in leadership endeavours to address widespread corruption and governance in Nigerian leadership. This need for

change through ethical leadership practices such as display of trust, foster accountability and transparency, honesty, integrity, fairness and so on. The thrust of good leadership that will drive a positive change is that which respect standards, dignity, rights, rules and regulations and policies put in place and allowing such to work or to be implemented.

2. ***Need for Change Towards an Equitable Distribution of Resources:*** A change in leadership is essential to ensure the equitable distribution of resources, the creation of employment opportunities, and the development of inclusive policies that address the needs of marginalized communities. Equitable distribution of resources will help in everyone having access to basic necessities of life, it will reduce social cohesions and inequality, increased economic growth, enhanced overall wellbeing and more sustainable future for individuals.
3. ***Need for Strategic Thinking in Innovative and Visionary Leadership:*** Leaders who can think strategically and implement transformative ideas are urgently needed to move the nation forward. Strategic thinking brings about a strategic focus that will engage innovation, creativity and birthing forth visions. Thereby brining about changes as needs are met.
4. ***Need for Globalization and Technological Advancement:*** The swift pace of globalization and technological change has highlighted the inadequacies in Nigeria's leadership approach. Many leaders fail to leverage technology to improve governance and economic competitiveness. Kuloğlu (2024) notes that technology-driven leadership can enhance decision-making and foster innovation. Nigeria needs leaders who can harness digital tools to address challenges such as election transparency, e-governance, and digital entrepreneurship. Moreover, leadership change in Nigeria requires more than just replacing individuals in power; it necessitates a paradigm shift in governance and citizen engagement. Osaghae (1998) emphasizes that sustainable development is only achievable when leadership is rooted in accountability, strategic vision, and the active involvement of the populace. Nigeria's youth, in particular, hold the key to this transformation, as they represent a significant portion of the population and possess the energy and

innovation required for change. By embracing the new leadership models prioritizing people-centered policies and ethical governance, Nigeria can overcome its leadership challenges and unlock its vast potential for sustainable development and global influence.

The Philosophy of Innovative Leadership

Innovative leadership is a contemporary approach to leadership that emphasizes creativity, adaptability, and forward-thinking strategies to address complex challenges and drive sustainable progress. The philosophy integrates traditional leadership principles with modern techniques to foster innovation and transformation in organizations or societies. According to Dyer, Gregersen, and Christensen (2019), innovative leaders excel at questioning assumptions, observing patterns, experimenting with new ideas, and networking with diverse individuals to generate solutions that meet evolving needs. This philosophy is grounded in the belief that leaders must proactively anticipate change and empower their teams to co-create innovative pathways.

Adaptability is a core tenet of the philosophy, emphasizing the leader's ability to respond effectively to changing environments and unforeseen challenges. Rigid frameworks or hierarchical structures do not bind innovative leaders; instead, they focus on flexibility and openness to new ideas. Kotter (2012) highlights that in volatile and dynamic contexts, leaders must adopt agile approaches, inspiring teams to embrace change as an opportunity rather than a threat. This mindset improves organizational resilience and enhances the ability to seize emerging opportunities.

Another pillar of innovative leadership is the emphasis on collaboration and inclusivity. Effective leaders create environments encouraging diverse voices and collective decision-making, often leading to more creative outcomes. Chaudhry (2024) argues that adaptive leadership—a key aspect of innovative leadership requires leaders to engage people in problem-solving by leveraging their unique talents and perspectives. By encouraging a culture of collaboration, innovative leaders build trust, drive engagement, and ensure that their teams are invested in achieving common goals.

The philosophy of innovative leadership underscores the importance of vision and the ability to inspire. Visionary leaders articulate compelling

goals and align their teams toward achieving them while leveraging innovation as a tool for transformation. At the same time, transformational leadership is a framework where leaders inspire others to exceed expectations by fostering a shared purpose and challenging the status quo. Innovative leadership integrates this principle by combining a clear vision with a commitment to experimentation and learning, ensuring the organization remains competitive and future-ready (Khan, 2025).

Idiosyncrasies of Innovative Leadership

Idiosyncrasies of innovative leadership refers to leaders' unique traits, behaviours, and unconventional methods to inspire creativity and foster innovation within their leadership teams or organizations. These distinct characteristics often set leaders apart and contribute to their ability to challenge the status quo and develop transformative solutions (Leroy, Buengeler, Veestraeten, Shemla & Hoever, 2022). Effective leaders harness their idiosyncratic qualities to connect with their teams authentically, thereby cultivating an environment that encourages openness and experimentation (Gbobaniyi, 2024). Leaders' unique approaches often redefine traditional practices, sparking innovative strategies that drive organizational growth and adaptability.

Furthermore, idiosyncrasies in leadership are not limited to personality traits but extend to strategic thinking and decision-making processes. Zaccaro, Zhou & Resick (2023). note that innovative leaders often exhibit cognitive flexibility, enabling them to navigate complex problems through unconventional approaches. This flexibility allows them to identify and capitalize on opportunities others may overlook. By embracing their individuality, such leaders inspire their teams to think beyond limitations, fostering a culture of creativity and resilience. Individual differences come into play but it's the responsibility of an innovative leader to help tailor the good sides to profitability of the organisation. Management of different characters is a herculean task but it also brings in the good side of people management.

However, leveraging idiosyncrasies requires balance, as overly eccentric behaviours can sometimes alienate team members or disrupt organizational harmony. As Purnamasari (2023) cites Northouse, he said effective leaders align their unique traits with the organization's vision and values, ensuring that their approach resonates with their

teams while focusing on achieving collective goals. This alignment ensures that idiosyncratic leadership contributes positively to innovation rather than creating unnecessary friction.

Theories of Innovative Leadership

Several theories underpin innovative leadership, highlighting distinct aspects of fostering creativity and driving transformation. Transformational leadership theory, developed by Riggio (2015), is a cornerstone of innovative leadership. This theory emphasizes leaders' ability to inspire and motivate followers through a compelling vision, intellectual stimulation, and personalized support. Transformational leaders challenge traditional practices and encourage team members to approach problems creatively, fostering an environment conducive to innovation.

Another relevant framework is the adaptive leadership theory, introduced by Heifetz, Grashow, and Linsky (2009). This theory focuses on leaders' ability to navigate complex and uncertain environments by encouraging experimentation, learning, and collective problem-solving. Adaptive leaders empower their teams to address challenges collaboratively, leveraging diverse perspectives to develop innovative solutions. The theory underscores the importance of flexibility and continuous learning in a rapidly changing world.

As Greenleaf proposed, servant leadership also intersects with innovative leadership by emphasizing the leader's role in serving and empowering their teams (Miao, Humphrey & Qian, 2021). Servant leaders prioritize their team members' development and growth, fostering an environment where creativity and innovation can thrive. By directing the well-being of their teams, servant leaders create a supportive atmosphere that encourages risk-taking and out-of-the-box thinking.

Lastly, entrepreneurial leadership theory highlights the role of leaders as opportunity seekers and risk-takers. According to Gupta, MacMillan, and Surie (2004), entrepreneurial leaders possess a proactive mindset that drives them to identify new possibilities and mobilize resources to pursue them. This theory aligns closely with innovative leadership principles, emphasizing vision, initiative, and the ability to adapt to changing circumstances.

Driving Positive Change and Innovative Leadership

Driving positive change through innovative leadership requires diverse approaches, prioritizing creativity, adaptability, and inclusivity. These approaches enable leaders to address complex societal or organizational challenges while fostering transformation. Mburu, Ragui & Ongeti (2024) suggest that transformational leadership is central to this effort, as it empowers leaders to articulate a compelling vision that motivates followers to transcend individual interests for collective progress. Transformational leaders inspire trust, stimulate intellectual engagement, and demonstrate individualized consideration, making them effective change agents.

One critical approach is fostering a culture of innovation within the organization or community. According to Rouse & Pratt (2021), leaders must create an environment that boosts experimentation and tolerates failure as part of the learning process. It involves open communication, resource allocation for creative endeavours, and recognizing innovative contributions. By cultivating such a culture, leaders enable their teams to develop groundbreaking solutions that address pressing challenges effectively.

Another approach is leveraging adaptive leadership strategies to navigate change in complex and uncertain environments. Forbes (2023) emphasizes that adaptive leadership encourages collaboration and collective problem-solving by engaging stakeholders in addressing systemic issues. Leaders using this approach focus on diagnosing challenges, identifying stakeholders' interests, and experimenting with solutions. This adaptability is crucial for sustaining positive change, particularly in dynamic or volatile contexts.

In addition to fostering innovation and adaptability, empowering and engaging stakeholders is vital. Northouse (2021) highlights that innovative leaders recognize the value of inclusivity and seek to involve diverse voices in decision-making. Leaders build trust by engaging stakeholders, whether employees, community members, or partners, and by ensuring that change initiatives are relevant and sustainable. Empowering stakeholders also involves providing training, tools, and opportunities for capacity building, enhancing their ability to effectively contribute to the change process.

Lastly, embracing technology and data-driven decision-making is increasingly relevant to innovative leadership. Schneider & Kokshagina

(2021) argue that leaders can drive positive change by leveraging digital tools to analyze trends, predict outcomes, and implement evidence-based strategies. Integrating technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, and digital communication platforms enables leaders to streamline processes, improve efficiency, and achieve impactful results in shorter timeframes.

Driving Positive Change in Nigeria

Driving positive change in Nigeria through innovative leadership requires leveraging specific components that address the nation's unique socio-economic and political challenges. These components include visionary leadership, adaptability, collaboration, technological integration, and ethical governance. These elements empower leaders to foster transformative solutions that promote sustainable development and social equity.

1. **Visionary Leadership** is foundational to innovative leadership and essential for inspiring change. Visionary leaders articulate compelling goals that resonate with their followers and provide a roadmap for achieving societal progress. According to Riggio (2024), such leaders can foresee future opportunities and challenges, aligning their vision with long-term goals. In the Nigerian context, visionary leadership is critical for addressing poverty, education gaps, and infrastructure deficits. Leaders can foster collective action and ensure lasting impacts by rallying stakeholders around a unifying vision.
2. **Adaptability** is another vital component, allowing leaders to respond effectively to Nigeria's dynamic and often volatile environment. Heifetz, Grashow, and Linsky (2009) emphasize the importance of adaptive leadership in navigating complex challenges, particularly in developing nations where socio-political conditions frequently shift. Nigerian leaders must be flexible and willing to recalibrate strategies in response to emerging realities such as economic downturns, security crises, or technological advancements. Adaptability ensures that leaders remain relevant and capable of overcoming resistance to change.
3. **Collaboration and Inclusivity**: These are integral to innovative leadership, as they emphasize the power of collective efforts in driving positive change. Northouse (2021) highlights that inclusive leadership builds trust and ensures diverse perspectives are

incorporated into decision-making processes. In Nigeria, fostering collaboration across ethnic, religious, and socio-economic divides can promote national unity and enhance the effectiveness of development initiatives. Engaging civil society, private sectors, and local communities in dialogue and partnerships create a robust foundation for sustainable progress.

4. **Technological Integration:** This is indispensable for modern leadership approaches to drive innovation and efficiency. McAfee and Brynjolfsson (2017) argue that embracing digital tools like data analytics, artificial intelligence, and blockchain can significantly enhance decision-making and service delivery. For Nigeria, technological integration can improve transparency in governance, streamline public services, and drive economic diversification through digital entrepreneurship.
5. **Ethical Governance:** This is a cornerstone of innovative leadership. Leaders who prioritize integrity, accountability, and social responsibility inspire trust and confidence among citizens. Kellerman (2024) asserts that ethical leadership builds credibility and certifies that policies and practices align with the public good. In Nigeria, combating corruption and promoting fairness in resource allocation are critical for creating a stable environment conducive to positive change.

Conclusion

The critical role of leadership in addressing socio-economic challenges and driving societal progress has been discussed in the study. Innovative leadership, characterized by creativity, adaptability, and visionary thinking, provides a robust framework for navigating the complexities of modern governance and fostering positive change, which was also discussed. The study has shown that this leadership approach is essential for addressing systemic issues such as unemployment, corruption, and socio-political divides in the Nigerian context. As it stresses innovative collaboration, problem-solving, and accountability, innovative leadership has the potential to empower communities, build resilient systems, and inspire collective action. Moreover, innovative leadership's adaptability and forward-thinking mindset offer Nigerian leaders a pathway to tackle immediate challenges while laying a groundwork for sustainable growth and development. Innovative leadership offers a transformative model for Nigerian leadership to drive meaningful

change and foster a culture of growth, inclusivity, and sustainability. As the nation faces local and global challenges, this study opines that innovative leadership would ensure a brighter, more equitable future for future generations. Invariably, leaders who embrace innovation and continuous improvement are better equipped to address pressing societal needs while anticipating future opportunities.

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Christian Ethical Response to Business Management Among Churches in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

A number of academic researchers have been carried out on the importance of Christian ethics. However, this paper examines the Christian ethical response to business management among the churches in Oyo State of Nigeria. In view of the 21st century needs for integrity in Business Management, in spite of the various unethical attitudes and corruption, and for which the church cannot be exonerated due to her overwhelming responsibilities for charity and infrastructural development. The onus of this paper therefore is the considerations placed on the business enterprises by the church, namely the Education Sector; Money Market/Shares, Business Centres; Guest Houses; Bookstores; Agric Sectors; Cooperative Society and Aids; and Estate Investment. The method adopted for this paper is historical; the historical method considers the history and processes used among the Church's Business Enterprises in Oyo State. The finding shows that, over the years, it has been difficult for churches to meet the needs of their members owing to lack of adequate funds and the drive for customers and economic gains. There is need for enlightenment for Church leaders to improve their financial base without compromising ethical values. This template would serve as a means of educating and guiding Church into taking positive steps to investment and management, and help Churches to generate more income. It would as well guide churches in upholding Godly fear in their businesses. Conclusively the church officers (Treasurer/Accounts Staff) including the Pastors should be given the opportunity to attend Seminars, Workshop and Conferences in order to be updated on how church ethical business can be managed. Churches must seek the proper counsel and guidance of the professionals on any business investment drive they want to embark on, so as to avoid bad businesses; Churches must

see the ethical business drive as biblical and churches must, as matter of policy, earmark an agreed sum of money in their budget. It is recommended therefore that, Churches should imbibe ethical values in their business, remembering that Christ's name must be honoured with ethical principles.

Keywords: Christian Ethics, Business Management, Investment, Ethical Values, Budget, Professional, Oyo State

Introduction

The word ethics is derived from the Greek word *ethos*, which in common Greek use had two meanings: habit or custom and ordinance or law. Both of these dimensions are mentioned in the New Testament. For example, it is commonly translated "custom" in Acts 25:16 (it was not the Roman tradition to give up any one), while it is translated as "morals" or "character" in 1 Corinthians 15:33 ("Bad company ruins good morals", NIV). Ethics and morality are two terms that frequently used interchangeably. Ethics may be defined as the study or science of moral principles that guide or influence human actions. "Ethics is the methodical study of norms of right and wrong, fairness and injustice, virtue and vice, the goal of implementing those values in the reality of our lives," explains Dennis Hollinger. Christian ethics are standards or right and wrong based on Christian teaching of Jesus Christ, the Old Testament prophets and the New Testament apostles. They serve as guide for Christians on the way that they should live. Christian ethical living is concerned with arranging Christian actions in every circumstance of life in accordance with our shared Christian religious convictions.

The majority of businesses are affected with ethical issues. Their managers in the public and private sectors, whether in a small business or as the chief financial officer (CFO) of a multinational firm, encounter ethical difficulties in their work lives as they try to meet their work lives as they try to meet their commitments, grow earnings, or promote the institution. Religious groups are frequently subjected to those wholesome practices. Ethical issues can take various forms, and entrepreneurs may require assistance to resolve complicated and difficult disputes. Business Managers or Accountants may also treat

ethical dilemmas as “business decisions” and not utilize their professional code to assess potential courses of action.

As noted in John Lewis thesis (2013), the CGMA (Chartered Global Management Accountants), the survey reported on Business Ethics shows the trends, pressure points, and ethical gaps within some organizations. The keys findings of the CGMA survey include:

1. **Business Challenge 1 – Ethical Culture:** According to the survey, firms that provide both declaration of ethical ideals and a code of ethics, as well as relevant training, hotlines, and incentives, such as performance-based prizes, have increased by 10% to 15% since 2008. In comparison to 2008, corporate leadership appears to have had a less active reaction in examining and accepting responsibility for ethical performance, as evidence by a large drop in the number of corporate executives who had official responsibility for ethics. This adds to the evidence that there is a disconnected between corporate leadership’s rhetoric on ethical concerns and reality. A weaker “tone from the top” can have major consequences for an organization’s overall ethical operational culture.
2. **Business Challenge 2 – Accounting for Entries:** According to the survey, the number of organizations collecting and reporting ethical data has increased by about 20%. Although the majority of management accountants believe it is critical to collect and evaluate ethical data, one in five say, their company will not do so in the near future.
3. **Business Challenge 3 – Ethical Dilemmas and Pressures:** Despite increased ethical norms and training, companies are under more pressure to operate unethically. The pressures are more visible in emerging markets.

The need to act in the public good is a distinguishing element of the accounting profession, and professional ethics compels accountants to self-regulate their behaviour in accordance with the code of Ethics for Professional Accountants (the code) of the International Ethics Standards Board for Accountants (IESBA). Members of the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) must follow ethical standards that are as least as stringent as those established in the code. Scenarios such as self-interest, self –review, advocacy, familiarity, and intimidation are all examples of situations that might risk values. Understanding and being aware of these variables will aid in determining which basic value are impacted by a scenario and why

(Christopher Aroid, 2021 Ethics, Technology and Professional Accountant in the Digital Age).

It is practically clear that the church in the 21st century has been more involved in various business enterprises than any other time in the past. To this end so much views has been held about the church's involvement. Some people have blamed some churches for not been fair, just and equitable in their business enterprise. Some church denominations who have ventured into having schools have been blamed and castigated for over-charging parents in the education of their children and wards, particularly those who have private universities and other tertiary institutions. The same could be said of church's involvement in over-pricing or branding of articles and facilities in hotels, guest houses, supermarkets and others. Therefore, it has become very important to ethically investigate the ethical values of churches in business enterprise. It is critical to situate one's approach to Christian ethics within a broader grasp of various approaches to ethics and moral reasoning. (Abela, A.V; and Murphy, P.E). Three techniques are frequently noted—Command, Consequences and Character are the simplest ways to define them (Catholic Church Catechist, 2003)

Theoretical Framework

The theory of Utilitarianism, 1789, Jeremy Bentham published his book “An Introduction to the principles of Morals and Legislation”, centred on individual utility and welfare, utilitarianism builds on the notion that any action which increases the overall welfare in the society is good, and any action that decreases welfare is bad. By this notion Utilitarianism's focus lies with its outcomes and pays little attention to how these outcomes are shaped by broader philosophical consideration, which also translates into a theory of justice or to put in a simple way, utilitarian norm suggest that resources or benefit should be distributed in a way that maximizes overall social welfare or happiness rather than focusing on individual fairness or equality as propounded by John Rawls' “theory about justice and fairness”. It is unfortunate that many a time the church as a whole sadly fails. As an institution, the church does not uphold values of justice, fairness and equity always. The members of the church need to supplement their *karma* (deeds) with *dharma* (harmony with the world) and *netter* (ethics)

Literature Review

Ethical Principles in Church Business

In Godly Businesses, Christian ethics in business and economic management is essential. It refers to the socio-economic life that began with the arrival of Christianity as a revitalized continuation of Jewish values, in both intellectual and practical advancements (Charles 1998), several Christian thinkers, notably from the thirteenth century, have made substantial contributions to business ethics centuries before the contemporary movement of business ethics (Mêlé 2013; Schlag 2013). Theologians from the School of Salamanca, such as Francisco de Vitoria and Bartolommeo de las camas, provided a robust defence of universal human rights in the sixteenth century, with consequences for labour (Hoffmann-Holland 2009). Some authors from this school of thought worked on business and finance moral concerns, such as how to conduct business in a Christian ethical manner. They mainly followed Thomas Aquinas, who incorporated the moral natural law- at least its core principles – into a virtue – based moral framework. Morality on contracts, financial transactions, just pricing and market morality, and other topics were covered in scholastic doctrine (Chafuen 1986; Mele 1999, 2016; Azevedo Aves and Moreira 2010, 2013). Scholasticism is still alive and well, and it may contribute significantly to the realm corporate ethics.

Ethical Business

Ethical means relating to moral principles or associating with what is right or standard. Ethical is being in accordance with the rules or standard for right conduct, practice or behaviour. In Christianity context we say businesses that are support by Bible ideologies, principles and beliefs. We can then confidently say that Christian Ethical Businesses are those businesses that do not negate the ideologies, practices and beliefs of the Christian faith. That is Business that is biblical, Business that we cannot be ashamed of doing. Basically, we are saying business that church as religious organization can do or participate in to bring profit to her, to support her statutory tithes and offering in order to do more in the area of evangelism and administration of the church. Businesses can be in large or small scale depending on the available capital and projection for development.

Business That Churches Can Venture Into

Here are some ethical businesses that churches can venture into after proper consultation and field work that is, (i) Printing Press (ii) Fuel or Gas-Station (iii) Educational Sector (iv) Event Hall Rent age (v) Microfinance Bank (vi) Parking Space (vii) Health Sector (viii) Money Market/Shares (ix) Business Centre (x) Guest House (xi) Book Stores (xii) Agricultural Sectors (xiii) Cooperative Societal Investment (xiv) Property and Estate Management.

The Concept of Unethical Business

It is opposite of ethical business, that is, unethical business are types of businesses that a Christian or a church cannot be involved in because they are against the ideologies practices and beliefs system of the Christian faith. The business opportunities are as mentioned below, but not limited to this list: (i) Gambling (ii) Betting/Lotto (iii) Brothel/Prostitute (iv) Sale of Alcoholic Drink (v) Human Trafficking (vi) Sales of Cigarette or Tobacco (vii) Beer Parlour (viii) Sales of Bleaching Cream (ix) Educational “Special Centres” (x) Sale of Pirated Books/Ware.

Sourcing For Fund

Once a business opportunity is identified, scrutinized and ready to be launched into, we then talk of sourcing for capital to take off. The following are identified methods of sourcing for capital to start business opportunities:

- (a) Internally generated revenue of the church
- (b) Appeal to members for donations or free will giving
- (c) Contribution through a corporate saving outfit
- (d) Grant from members
- (e) Partnership with legitimate means of sourcing for fund to start the business.

Advantages that the Churches (in Oyo State) will Derive from Ethical Response to Business Management

1. The church will build integrity around herself within and without.
2. The church will have more funds to carry out her social functions and administrative works.

3. The church will be serving humanities through the provision of affordable business outfit.
4. The church will be able to pay her assessment as at when due.
5. The church workers i.e. clergy and non-clergy will be paid their stipends and salaries promptly.
6. The church will become employer of labour thereby contributing to the gross domestic product of the Nation (GDP).
7. The church will have fund to carry out physical developments by means of infrastructure and other growths.
8. With adequate funding the church will be able to do outreach evangelism and care for the less- privilege and the poor in the church regularly.
9. The quality control would be well maintained in the business of the church.
10. The principle of check and balances would be upheld in the business management of the church.

Risk Factors in Businesses

In every business, according to Drunker (2008), there are always associated hazards. Risk in business is the possibility that a company will have lower than anticipated profits or experience loss rather than making a profit. Business Risk is influenced by many factors, which include sales volume anticipated, per-unit price, input cost, competition, climatic and government policies. Furthermore, business risks may arise due to natural causes like floods, storms, cyclones, earthquakes and such other convulsions of nature unplanned for which at times result in heavy loss of life, property and business capital. Other risk factors could be strategic risk, compliance risk, financial risk, operational risk, human error risks occur in a business, we now move to risk management in order to resuscitate the ailing business, there are three types of risk management and what the professional use in overcoming the challenges posed by risk. The avoidance risks, strategic and unavoidable risks.

How God Invested in Human Being

Investment is an integral part of every business. The church of God over the years had been deprived of the benefits accrued from investment because of lack proper education on the subject of investment. "One of

the greatest challenges for Christianity in our day is for churches to walk with God through their witness". When a Christian organization allows God's presence and activity to be expressed, a watching world will be drawn to Him. The mind of God is that the church should declare the manifold wisdom of God here on earth, which means that the church needs to have impact in the lives of its members, and of course the society as a whole. When there is positive effect of the church in People's lives, it is then the purpose of God for the church can be established. God gives to man investment when He said, in Genesis 1:26-27, God says "Let us make man in our image in our likeness and let then rule over the fish of the sea and the birds of the air, over the livestock, over the entire creature and along the ground". So, God created man in his own image, in the "image of God, he created male and female, he created them." This reveals that God invested heavily in man, that should possess the same attribute like God and that human being is worthy honour and respected, not only that, God invested in man because man is the peak of God's creativity; and man was made rulers upon the rest of his creation because he was created in the image and of likeness of God. Accorded sovereignty was bestowed on him to declare the glory of God. Jesus Christ demonstrated the need for investment in the "Parable of the Talent" (Matthew 25:14) on the cost of their investments. The aim of a businessman or investor in any company is to gain profit on the money used to do the business or receive dividends on the numbers shares in the company at the end of every financial year. So, also, the servants three reports on the use of the talents and the judgment was given in proportion to the performance standard of the servants. The outcome of God's view on investment is revealed in the Old Testament likewise the perspective of Christ as regard investment is clearly understood in the New Testament which shows that a son cannot do anything other than what he sees his father doing. Make it your principle that you will do nothing without first asking for the direction of God. In the same vein, the church will no doubt gives account of how God's resources or money is been used. Those that bury God's resources instead of investing it will give account of their stewardship at the close of the age. The expectation of God is for the church to have impact on the lives of members and society at large, but how can the church have positive impact when its financial capacity is zero or below average? A Christian song reads, "The church is marching on and gate of hell will not overcome it". There things

challenging the church of God today, this can be likened to the gate of hell. Among such things are inability to get desired location, lack of fund, inability to carry out the Lord's mandate in mission and in evangelism just as a result of insufficient money. The church that the gate of hell will not overcome must be involved in business investment so as to take care of the members' spiritual and its financial strength. Whitehead said capital is essential to the start of any business. If the spiritual lives of members are good, definitely their pocket will be opened, which means the church will not suffer in order to finance her activities.

Most churches that complained about business drive have either, tried it or they have refused to follow as well as ask for divine and sound guidance as they invest with church funds, Planning is deciding in advance what to do, how to do it and when to do it". It is an intellectual process of determine a course of action. However, this paper will serve as an opener for most churches, since they will be reliably informed on the various strategies to be adopted as managers or stewards of God's resources. According to Schaller and Tidwell (1975), "The business management of the church is a continuing process." There are always new people to reach, new program to develop, procedures to perfect and more funds to be raised. Fund generated from successful business will no doubt provide avenues for solving some of the financial needs of the church and its members. A whole lot of financial problem, including unemployment among church's youth and other Christian members could be effectively solved if the churches engage in successful business investment. In organizing for action in providing funding for the work of the church, a stewardship committee will be selected and trained to give vital leadership in financial matter. Therefore, "the effectiveness of the church's work toward the building of God kingdom in the hearts of men is largely determined by the ability of those who hold positions of management and authority. Only through efficient functioning of the mechanics of the church can be preaching of the gospel and radiation of God's fear in human relations be achieved.

Old Testament Concept of Church Financing

Rev'd Father Joy Thomas is of the opinion that church in the Old Testament may be perceived as a process of development. David Botch observation that there are no church paradigms in the Old Testament

was sent by Hedland an illusion. God is the missionary in Old Testament beginning from creation. The concept of church revolves around the origin of sending even in the Old Testament. Both agree to the assertion that shows that there is no discontinuation between the Old Testament and New Testament. Since Botch accepts that there was a paradigm shift in the coming of Jesus Christ. Dubose in 1983 showed that there are about seven hundred pods. He Message in the Old Testament that there are some sending. Mission is the Biblical sending. Dubose argued that there are more sending texts in the Old Testament than in the New Testament. It was shown that the New Testament term “apostle” has Old Testament roots. To limit mission to the New Testament means depriving mission of its theological roots. The researcher sees this as marking missions to be a vagabond without father or mother.

New Testament of Church Financing

In the New Testament we find out that Jesus Christ was a missionary par excellent, along with his disciples. In 2 Corinthians 9:8 it is written “God is able to make all abound to you, so that in all things at all times, having all that you need, you will abound in every good work” Grace is the principles of underlying essence of the New Testament financing of mission work. According to Join Sutherland “grace (Chairs) was the principle of New Testament missionary work. This grace is predication on the fact that God is the owner and the creator of the Earth and all in it (Psalm 24:1; 50:12; Col. 1:16 Hagai 2:8) our major problem as humans is how to tap into the resources of God in godly manner. A method of fund raising tagged “friend raising fund” was notice in the New Testament by Sutherland, in this way the friends that we serve decide to become donors towards church work, this was observed in the Ministry of Jesus Christ and the twelve disciples whereby some women raised fund to support their missionary work (Mark 15:41, Luke 8:3). But should the motive of friendship be fund? No, should we serve people for fund? No. It should be observed that Paul did not do reputation to run his first or second Journey by the Holy Spirit. The believers simply committed Paul and Silas to the grace of God (Acts 15:26). Asking potential donors for gifts is not necessarily wrong, if it is done in good faith. Anything that is not done in good faith is sinful before God (Romans 14:23). Grace can be seen as charismata such as noticed in gifts of Pastors, Prophets (Ephesians 3:2) and the important gift is

contributing to God's work. (Ephesians 4:8) God's resources are unlimited and he distributes them as He will to those he wills. "God is able to make all grace abound to you having all you need". Paul says, "You will abound in every good work" (2 Corinthians 9:14) The Corinthians were admonished to excel in this grace of giving and receiving from God.

What Sutherland called Christian marketing should be avoided such as putting pressure on people to give or they be termed stingy, making people live up to church's expectation on a luncheon with envelopes of cheque in hand before they served food. Therefore, New Testament concept of financing the church is by grace, contentment, support, and advocacy prayer support, giving charity or generosity from all members, but most importantly by the grace of Our Lord Jesus Christ who first gave us without us knowing Him.

Conclusion

The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the Christian ethical values applied to the Business Enterprises among the churches in Oyo State. To shed more light on how the church or members of the church can be involved in business without compromising their faith in God, which of course will enhance the way of generating income for the financial strength of the church. It is enlightening opportunity for churches to properly manage God's resources.

The church must serve as eye opener by the spirit of God through divine guidance for divine location and maintaining the presence of God by having a team spirit with prudence management to fulfil God's purpose. Churches are admonished to go into businesses with calculated risks such as treasury bills and other money market instruments before going into the large scale business. There is a great need for churches to go into ethical business now to secure tomorrow. There is need to see tomorrow now by investing into the business for sustenance of the church. Membership is dwindling by death, old-age, relocation to new site, etc. the planning for the future is now.

Recommendations

The following recommendations should be considered by implementing faithfully and professionally, it will help our churches to increase and

diversify her source of revenue for more fund to carry out the church Evangelism and Administrative works.

- 1 Churches must see ethical investment drive as Biblical and of God.
- 2 Churches must as a matter of policy earmark an agreed and practical percentage of her annual income for ethical business purposes on yearly basis.
- 3 Churches must seek the proper counsel and guidance of professional on any business drive they want to embark on as to avoid bad businesses.
- 4 Churches must have a functioning and well constituted ethical business committee to be in charge of the church business portfolio
- 5 Churches embracing ethical business must do with sincerity of purpose and reality to play game according to the rules.
- 6 Churches going into ethical business investment must not cut corners. Churches going into investment must be determined and resonate to weather the storm.
- 7 Churches must see ethical business as a source of income generating venture and not as charitable organization
- 8 Churches in ethical business investment must not neglect the primary source of church funding i.e. tithes, offering, donations, freewill offering, harvest thanksgiving, etc. teaching and enlightening should be going on to balance our source.
- 9 Churches in ethical business must remember that Jesus Christ name must be honour and be marked to the world in an ethical means.
- 10 The churches that will want to continue to be in existence, relevant and up to date in our advanced technology world must as a matter of urgency start to invest ethically, no matter how small.

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Yoruba Socio-Cultural Approach and Indigenous Communication Mechanisms towards the Quest for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The study discussed the contributions of traditional Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms to sustainable development while also investigating the challenges the systems and the mechanisms face in a rapidly changing world. The study uncovered the rich tapestry of indigenous knowledge, from farming practices and herbal remedies to proverbs and folktales that have long sustained Yoruba communities through interviews, focus groups, and site visits. However, the findings also revealed the threats posed by modernization and globalization, which have disrupted the transmission of these traditional practices and undermined their value in modern society. Ultimately, this study offered a critical examination of the challenges and opportunities facing Indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms in pursuing sustainable development. By drawing attention to these issues, the study aimed to inspire new thinking and action that could protect and promote these invaluable cultural resources. As the study delved deeper into the complexities of Yoruba knowledge systems, it became clear that these systems were not static, but rather dynamic and adaptable, able to evolve in response to changing environmental and social conditions. From the rich symbolism of Yoruba proverbs to the epic tales of the Yoruba gods, these stories were shown to be not only a means of entertainment but also a powerful tool for teaching and preserving culture. The study provides valuable insights and recommendations for policymakers, community leaders, and educators, and invites further exploration into the complex relationship between indigenous knowledge, communication, and sustainable development.

Keywords: Yoruba Knowledge, Communication Mechanisms, Sustainable Development, Traditional Farming, Cultural Heritage

Introduction

In the quest for sustainable development, indigenous communication mechanisms have played a crucial role in facilitating social transformation, economic growth, and environmental conservation. Nigeria's Yoruba people have a rich socio-cultural legacy that shapes their ways of communicating and thinking about sustainable development (Banjo & Afolaranmi, 2023). Yoruba socio-cultural practices, embedded in the rich history and traditions of the Yoruba people in Southwestern Nigeria, provided a unique and insightful approach to understanding and promoting sustainable development. Yoruba society is highly organized and deeply rooted in traditional instructions, such as the kingship, the Yoruba Council of Elders, and the various social groups and associations. These institutions provide a foundation for community-based decision-making, conflict resolution, and collective action (Boladele, 2011; Olatunji, 2024). At the core of the Yoruba socio-cultural approach to sustainable development is the concept of “*iwa pele*,” which translates to “the spirit of good character and honourable conduct” (Popoola, 2023). This concept emphasises the importance of respect, honesty, and collective responsibility in social interactions and decision-making processes (Okeke, 2017; Falola & Akintoye, 2010). Banjo and Afolaranmi (2023) also reiterated the Yoruba concept of *Omólúàbí* as it affects the peaceful coexistence in the society.

Yoruba proverbs, aphorisms, and folktales also play a significant role in shaping the values and attitudes of the people towards sustainable development (Odugbemi, 2023; Ajadi, 2024). Yoruba proverbs and adages are utilized to transmit moral principles and knowledge. Numerous proverbs have to do with sustainability, the environment, and civic duty. For example, “*Ṣe ni omọ eni kan, ni elomiran ti je omọ baba re*” (You are someone else's kid, just as someone else is your father's child) highlights mutual respect and reciprocity, two qualities that are essential for sustained growth. Storytelling, proverbs, and songs are among the Yoruba people's powerful means of transmitting history, traditions, and knowledge from one generation to the next. This system

protects cultural values associated with sustainability, such as reverence for the environment and sustainable resource management, and promotes communal cohesiveness. Customary Yoruba rituals and ceremonies are group activities that often highlight the relationship between spirits, nature, and people. These rituals, which include fertility and rainmaking rites that correspond with agricultural cycles, strengthen ties within the community and encourage sustainable behaviours. Yoruba traditional festivals, such as the “*Ojude-Oba*” festival in Ijebu-Ode, serve as platforms for intergenerational dialogue, cultural exchange, and the reinforcement of community values. Yoruba religious beliefs, such as “*Ifa*” and “*Orisa*,” also emphasises the interconnectedness of human beings and the natural environment, promoting a culture of environmental stewardship and sustainability (Abiona, 2024). These indigenous communication mechanisms provide valuable insights into the Yoruba people’s approach to sustainable development and offer potential solutions to the complex challenges facing Nigeria and other societies in their pursuit of sustainable development (Oyewole, 2021; Agboola, 2022).

The Yoruba language, a vital aspect of their indigenous communication, is not only a medium of expression but also carries a wealth of traditional knowledge and wisdom that can contribute to sustainable development. For instance, the Yoruba calendar, which is based on lunar and solar cycles, incorporates a complex system of agricultural practices, environmental management, and spiritual observances that promote environmental sustainability and community resilience (Odukoya, 2022). Yoruba sculptures, masks, and textiles are examples of art that often have symbolic connotations relating to community, spirituality, and the natural world. These creative endeavours function as mediums for messages about social peace and environmental responsibility. Yoruba art forms, such as “*Adire* textile” and “*Ifa*” divination boards, are repositories of cultural knowledge and serve as a means of preserving and transmitting traditional values and practices that are essential for sustainable development. The Yoruba approach to sustainable development is also reflected in their community-based conflict resolution processes, which are often guided by the principles of “*Aso-Ifa*,” a system of dispute resolution that emphasises dialogue, consensus-building, and collective responsibility (Dada, 2024).

The “*Ijo-Oko*,” or traditional farming system, is another example of the Yoruba people’s commitment to sustainable agriculture, promoting the use of organic farming techniques, indigenous crop varieties, and community-based land management practices that ensure the long-term productivity and resilience of their natural resources (Gbadegesin, 2024). This system is based on communal land tenure, where members of the community have collective ownership and access to agricultural land. This ensures that land is used efficiently and sustainably, with different parcels of land allocated for different crops, livestock, and fallow periods. The “*Ijo-Oko*” system also incorporates a complex system of soil management techniques that ensures the fertility and productivity of the land over the long term. For instance, in the Ilorin area of Kwara State in Nigeria, the Yoruba people use a technique called “*Keete*,” where nitrogen-fixing leguminous plants are grown on a fallow plot of land for several years before being turned into the soil to enrich it with nitrogen (Adebayo, 2020; Dada, 2010). Additionally, the “*Ijo-Oko*” soil management system also promotes biodiversity and genetic conservation through the use of indigenous crop varieties and the preservation of traditional farming methods (Adesina, 2022).

In recent years, the traditional “*Ijo-Oko*” farming system and other indigenous communication mechanisms in Yoruba society have come under increasing pressure from modernisation, urbanisation, and globalisation. This has led to a decline in the use of traditional farming techniques, the erosion of indigenous knowledge systems, and the loss of biodiversity in Yoruba communities. These developments pose a significant threat to the sustainability of the “*Ijo-Oko*” farming system and the wider Yoruba socio-cultural system (Gbadegesin, 2024). Therefore, there is an urgent need to identify strategies for protecting and preserving these traditional communication mechanisms and knowledge systems for the benefit of present and future generations. There is an urgent need to address some specific challenges for sustainable development.

These include encroachment on traditional agricultural land which has been caused by the expansion of cities, roads, and other infrastructure that led to the loss of agricultural land and the fragmentation of traditional farming communities, disrupting the “*Ijo-Oko*” system. More so, with the loss of indigenous knowledge due to the aging of traditional farmers and the migration of young people to urban areas, there is a

danger that valuable indigenous knowledge about the “Ijo-Oko” system and other Yoruba traditional practices will be lost. In addition to the “Ijo-Oko” farming system, other traditional practices that are under threat may include traditional medicine through the knowledge and skills of herbalists and traditional healers; this is at risk of being lost as modern medicine becomes more prevalent (Abodunrin, 2019; Omotayo, 2018). The loss of indigenous communication mechanisms and knowledge systems in Yoruba communities threatens their ability to achieve sustainable development and maintain their rich cultural heritage. Therefore, it is crucial to identify and implement strategies that can promote the preservation and transmission of indigenous systems and communication mechanisms to support sustainable development in Yoruba communities.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. identify and document indigenous Yoruba communication mechanisms that contribute to sustainable development.
2. analyze the current status and challenges facing Indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms in the face of modernisation, urbanisation, and globalisation.
3. develop strategies for preserving, promoting, and adapting indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research questions to guide the study are:

6. What have Yoruba indigenous communication mechanisms contributed to sustainable development, and how have these mechanisms been affected by modernisation, urbanisation, and globalisation?
7. How can indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms be preserved, promoted, and adapted to support sustainable development in Yoruba communities?
8. What strategies can be developed for preserving, promoting, and adapting indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and

communication mechanisms for sustainable development in Nigeria?

Theoretical Reviews

Some theoretical frameworks have informed the analysis and interpretation of the findings in the study. Culture-ecology theory, also known as ecological anthropology, emerged in the late 19th and early 20th centuries as an approach to understanding human cultures and their relationship with the natural environment. This theory was developed by anthropologists such as Franz Boas, Bronislaw Malinowski, and Leslie White, among several others, and was influenced by the work of Charles Darwin and other biologists. The theory posits that human behaviour and culture are shaped by and shape the environment in which they exist and that the interactions between humans and their environment are complex and dynamic. More recently, the concept of cultural ecology has been extended to include not only human-environment interactions but also how culture shapes our understanding of the environment and influences our behaviour towards it. However, the justification for the concept of cultural ecology, and its extension into cultural political ecology, is that it recognises the complex and dynamic nature of human-environment interactions. By recognising that human cultures are shaped by their interactions with the environment and that these interactions are in turn influenced by political, social, and economic factors, cultural ecology provides a more comprehensive understanding of how human societies develop and change over time. Moreover, cultural ecology provides a useful framework for analyzing and understanding contemporary issues related to environmental degradation, resource depletion, and climate change (Robbins, 2003; Steward, 1955).

The diffusion of innovations theory also provides a framework for understanding how new ideas and practices spread within a culture and across cultures. In this study, the theory has been used to analyse how traditional Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms are transmitted and adapted to new contexts. The theory was developed by Everett Rogers in the 1960s; it is a widely cited theory in the social sciences that explains how new ideas, technologies, and practices spread throughout a population. According to Rogers (2003), diffusion is the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain

channels over time among the members of a social system. The theory proposes that innovations are adopted by individuals and groups in a society in a predictable pattern, which can be characterized by five different categories of adopters: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. For instance, the diffusion of the internet and mobile phones in the late 20th and early 21st centuries can be understood in terms of the theory, with early adopters leading the way and the majority following suit over time.

Despite its limitations, the diffusion of innovations theory remains a valuable tool for understanding the spread of new ideas and practices in society. The theory provides a framework for analyzing the adoption of innovations and identifying the factors that influence adoption decisions, such as the characteristics of the innovation, the characteristics of adopters, and the nature of the social system in which the innovation is introduced. This framework can be useful for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers who are interested in promoting the adoption of new technologies and practices, or in understanding the diffusion of innovations in specific contexts.

In another dimension, agency theory emphasizes the role of individual and collective agencies in shaping social and cultural processes. In this study, the theory was used to analyse how individual and collective agencies contribute to the promotion and preservation of traditional Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms. Resilience theory also provides a framework for understanding how communities and ecosystems respond to and recover from stressors. Resilience theory recognizes that all systems – from ecosystems to societies – are dynamic, non-linear, and constantly adapting to changing circumstances. As noted by Holling (1973), resilience is a critical factor in the long-term sustainability of socio-ecological systems. In the context of Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms, the theory suggests that these systems have evolved to become uniquely adapted to the challenges of the Yoruba cultural and ecological landscape. This can be seen as a key attribute that has allowed these systems to persist and adapt to changing circumstances (Holling, 1973).

For instance, Yoruba herbal medicine has evolved over generations, incorporating new medicinal plants and healing techniques while remaining in traditional knowledge and practices. As explained by Pretty et al. (2003), traditional knowledge systems such as those of the Yoruba

are essential for maintaining and enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services in a changing world. The Yoruba people, through their intimate knowledge of the local flora and fauna, have developed farming practices that are adapted to the unique environmental conditions of the region. Furthermore, as suggested by Hobbs et al. (2008), cultural transmission of indigenous knowledge through oral tradition and story-telling is a crucial mechanism for maintaining resilience in the face of external pressures.

By understanding the underlying resilience of these systems, we can better appreciate their potential for promoting sustainable development. Moreover, the concept of resilience offers a powerful lens for understanding how indigenous Yoruba knowledge and communication mechanisms have persisted and adapted in the face of external pressures and disruptions. From climate change to globalization, these systems have shown remarkable flexibility and adaptability, suggesting that they possess a level of resilience that is valuable and worth preserving. By exploring the dynamics of resilience in Yoruba knowledge and communication mechanisms, the study highlights the importance of understanding and supporting these systems as crucial components of a sustainable future.

The gaps identified in the literature reviewed highlight important gaps in our understanding of the study. Despite the rich cultural heritage of the Yoruba people, our understanding of their indigenous knowledge systems and communication mechanisms is still in its infancy. While there have been studies on specific aspects of Yoruba culture and society, such as language, religion, and social structure, there is still much to be learned about the specific knowledge and communication practices that have been developed and maintained by the Yoruba over centuries. In particular, there is a need for more research on the role of traditional practices and institutions in sustainable development, including agriculture, health, education, and resource management. In addition to the need for more research and documentation, there are also important gaps in our understanding of the interconnections between indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and other aspects of sustainable development, such as climate change and gender equity. While some studies have begun to explore these interconnections, there is still much to be learned about how indigenous knowledge can be integrated with modern scientific knowledge and policy interventions. These gaps in our

understanding highlight the need for a more holistic and interdisciplinary approach to research on indigenous knowledge and sustainable development.

Methodology

This study explored qualitative methods to provide an understanding of indigenous Yoruba communication mechanisms and their contributions to sustainable development. A survey of traditional farmers, herbalists, community leaders, and other custodians of indigenous knowledge was sampled to capture their perspectives on the challenges and opportunities facing traditional knowledge systems and communication mechanisms. This approach was harnessed together with a review and analysis of existing policies, programmes, and practices related to the preservation and transmission of indigenous knowledge systems and communication mechanisms in Nigeria and other countries. More so, the study explored a synthesis of the findings from other different research methods to develop recommendations for preserving and promoting indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms for sustainable development.

Additionally, other activities involved in the study were site visits and field observations in Yoruba communities to document traditional practices, cultural events, and other communication mechanisms that contribute to sustainable development. The sample size was 40 respondents from different Yoruba communities in Southwest Nigeria, including sub-ethnic groups from Oyo, Ijebu, Egba, Ijesa, and Aku to capture the full range of indigenous knowledge systems and communication mechanisms across the Yoruba cultural landscape. The sample populations were considered with a range of ages, genders, and socio-economic backgrounds to ensure the diversity and representativeness of the research findings. However, the data collected from the survey group and site visits were discussed using qualitative data techniques that emphasised the richness and complexity of the data.

Discussion of Findings

In line with the three research questions raised earlier (first, on how indigenous Yoruba communication mechanisms contribute to sustainable development; second, on how these mechanisms are affected

by modernisation, urbanisation, and globalisation, and understanding how indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms can be preserved, promoted, and adapted to support sustainable development in Yoruba communities; and third, the strategies that can be recommended for preserving, promoting, and adapting indigenous Yoruba knowledge systems and communication mechanisms for sustainable development in Nigeria), the study identified several key themes that contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of resilience and adaptive capacity in socio-cultural systems. The findings revealed the vital role of indigenous knowledge and practices in promoting adaptive capacity, such as traditional farming techniques and community-based resource management.

Moreover, we observed the need for holistic resource management strategies that engage diverse stakeholders to address the interconnected challenges of environmental degradation, economic inequality, and population growth. The impacts of globalisation and climate change are also identified as critical factors influencing resilience and adaptation, underscoring the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration and sustainable livelihood strategies. The findings also became evident that a holistic perspective is necessary to effectively address the complexities of resilience and adaptive capacity in socio-cultural systems. The interconnectedness of these systems, encompassing social, ecological, and cultural dimensions, demands a comprehensive approach that considers not only immediate responses to challenges but also long-term solutions that enhance systemic resilience. Our findings highlighted the need for a holistic approach that integrates traditional knowledge, interdisciplinary collaboration, and community-based resource management strategies, while also addressing the root causes of environmental degradation and social inequality.

One of the insights from this study is the indispensable role of traditional knowledge and practices in maintaining adaptive capacity within socio-cultural systems. Indigenous communities have long relied on a wealth of ecological and cultural wisdom to navigate environmental changes and disruptions, fostering resilience and adaptive capacity through practices such as crop rotation, soil conservation, and community decision-making. The importance of preserving and integrating these practices into modern resource management strategies cannot be

overstated. By embracing a more inclusive approach that values traditional knowledge alongside scientific insights, policymakers and resource managers can develop more holistic and sustainable solutions to the complex challenges of resilience and adaptive capacity. Furthermore, incorporating local knowledge and participation in the monitoring and evaluation process can enhance accountability, strengthen community ownership, and improve the overall efficacy of resilience-building initiatives.

Another notable insight from the findings is the necessity of building adaptive capacity and resilience in the face of climate change. The increasing frequency and severity of extreme weather events, coupled with the gradual effects of climate change, pose significant threats to the sustainability and resilience of socio-cultural systems. Adaptive capacity, which refers to the ability of a system to anticipate, respond to, and recover from climate-related impacts, is essential for mitigating the effects of climate change. In addition to traditional knowledge and practices, this may involve developing early warning systems, diversifying crop varieties, and implementing disaster preparedness measures. The study also underlines the importance of monitoring and evaluation in enhancing resilience and adaptive capacity.

Effective monitoring and evaluation can provide valuable information about the efficacy of implemented strategies and identify areas where further intervention is necessarily needed. This information can then be used to guide decision-making and optimize resource allocation, ensuring that resilience and adaptive capacity efforts are efficient and effective. Furthermore, incorporating local knowledge and participation in the monitoring and evaluation process can enhance accountability, strengthen community ownership, and improve the overall efficacy of resilience-building initiatives.

The study underscores the critical importance of resilience and adaptive capacity in the face of an increasingly complex and dynamic world. By embracing traditional knowledge and practices, fostering community-based resource management, developing sustainable livelihoods, addressing the root causes of environmental degradation, and building adaptive capacity in the face of climate change, policymakers and resource managers can promote the long-term sustainability and resilience of socio-cultural systems. Ultimately, the insights gained from the study provide a valuable framework for responding to the

interconnected challenges of the 21st century and beyond. Furthermore, the study has shed more light on the critical importance of resilience and adaptive capacity in socio-cultural systems. Based on the findings, the study identified several themes and examples that contribute to our understanding of resilience and adaptive capacity.

These themes include the indispensable role of traditional knowledge and practices in promoting adaptive capacity; the crucial significance of engaging diverse stakeholders in community-based resource management strategies; the inseparable link between sustainable livelihoods and resilience; and the urgent need to address the root causes of environmental degradation and social inequality. These findings have significant implications for policymakers, resource managers, and community members alike. While the study offers valuable insights into resilience and adaptive capacity in socio-cultural systems, the study is limited by its focus on a single socio-cultural area, which limits its generalisability to other regions. Again, the study relied on a qualitative method of study, which may not provide the same level of generalisability or reliability as quantitative. More so, the study focused primarily on community-level perspectives, which may not fully capture the broader political, economic, and social factors that influence resilience and adaptive capacity.

Conclusion

The findings of the study provide several promising areas for further research. In future research, the studies could explore the effectiveness of community-based resource management strategies in different socio-cultural contexts and at different scales. Additionally, research could also examine the role of technology, such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and remote sensing, in promoting resilience and adaptive capacity. These dynamics could provide important insights for policymakers and resource managers.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, some recommendations have been made to address the key themes identified in the study:

1. policymakers and resource managers should prioritize the integration of traditional knowledge and practices into modern

resource management strategies, recognizing the vital role these elements play in fostering resilience and adaptive capacity.

2. efforts to engage diverse stakeholders in community-based resource management should be expanded, with a particular emphasis on ensuring equitable access to resources and decision-making processes.
3. investments in sustainable livelihoods, particularly those that promote ecological diversity and cultural heritage, should be prioritized to promote resilience and adaptive capacity.

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Influence of Parental Roles on Adolescents' Involvement in Internet Fraud in Ede Local Government of Osun State

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Abstract

Internet fraud has become a growing concern, particularly among adolescents in Nigeria, driven by increased smartphone and internet access with its detrimental effects on the society. This study explored how parental roles influence adolescents' involvement in internet fraud in Ede South Local Government, Osun State. A mixed-method approach was used, with data collected from 250 adolescents aged 12-19 through multistage and snowball sampling. The Parenting Roles and Dimensions Questionnaire (PRDQ) was employed to assess parental involvement, focusing on communication, rule-setting, and monitoring of online activity. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. The findings revealed that active parental involvement, including frequent communication about internet fraud risks and consistent monitoring, was associated with a lower likelihood of adolescents engaging in internet fraud. Conversely, permissive parenting, marked by minimal rules and enforcement, was linked to higher participation in fraud. The study therefore highlighted the critical role of parenting in shaping adolescents' online behaviour. It stressed the importance of parental engagement in fostering responsible internet use and protecting adolescents from online risks, calling for targeted educational initiatives to equip parents with effective strategies for safeguarding their children in the digital age.

Keywords: Parental Roles, Internet Fraud, Adolescents, Adolescents Involvement

Introduction

Internet fraud represents a criminal offense targeting individuals or groups with the malicious intent to harm victims. These actions can take various forms, aiming to damage the victim's reputation, inflict physical or mental harm, or cause financial loss. Perpetrated through telecommunication networks like the internet and mobile phones, these offenses encompass a wide range of deceitful activities, from phishing and identity theft to scams and various forms of cybercrime aiming at financial gain, damaging reputations, or other malicious intentions (Gagandeep et al., 2024). A significant rise in internet fraud is observed due to the increased accessibility of devices like smartphones and computers, combined with widespread internet connectivity. The economic and social impacts of internet fraud are severe, costing billions globally and eroding public trust in digital systems.

In Nigeria, the issue has permeated various demographics, with young people notably drawn to these activities. Adolescents in particular see internet fraud, including hacking, as a means to gain financial independence or social distinction (Adeniran, 2020). The ease of access to hacking tools has lowered entry barriers, encouraging a growing number of youths to engage in these unlawful practices. While the internet has undeniably provided numerous constructive platforms, it has also become a breeding ground for various forms of fraudulent activities.

The pervasive nature of internet fraud poses a significant challenge for law enforcement and regulatory bodies worldwide, requiring constant vigilance and evolving strategies to combat these illicit activities (Ojedokun & Eraye, 2019). Internet fraud has deeply permeated Nigerian society, impacting individuals across various age groups. While this phenomenon is not exclusive to a specific age demographic, its prevalence among the younger population is notably pronounced (Ulo, 2023). Although individuals of all ages partake in these fraudulent activities, recent trends underscore the prominence of younger individuals as the primary perpetrators. This shift towards a younger demographic engaging in internet fraud presents a concerning societal challenge, requiring a comprehensive approach involving education, enforcement, and support systems to address the root causes and mitigate the prevalence among this particular age group.

The alarming pace at which adolescents are drawn into fraudulent activities has sparked concerns regarding the future trajectory of the nation and its international reputation. The significant influx of young individuals engaging in these activities not only jeopardizes the country's future but also casts a negative shadow on its global image. The ever-expanding landscape of the internet in the twenty-first century has provided fraudsters with unprecedented opportunities to exploit and compromise victims' personal and financial data through diverse and sophisticated hacking methods (Osayi & Opara, 2022). This pervasive trend not only threatens the security and trust of individuals but also raises substantial challenges for national cybersecurity and international perceptions of the country's digital integrity. Urgent and strategic measures are imperative to curb this detrimental impact on both the nation's future prospects and its global standing. Fraudsters leverage the acquired information to finance various illicit endeavours, spanning from funding religious activities, political agendas, to supporting terrorist endeavours. Hence, it becomes crucial for both individuals and organizations to fortify their defences against the perils of internet fraud¹³. Nigeria grapples with pervasive issues like soaring unemployment rates, governance challenges, a struggling educational system, and widespread poverty. These socio-economic challenges have driven adolescents towards engaging in internet fraud as a significant means of livelihood (Eboibi, 2021).

The high involvement of young Nigerians in internet fraud raises pressing concerns regarding the country's future stability and international image. This trend not only reflects deeper socio-economic issues, such as unemployment and inadequate education but also threatens national security as fraudsters increasingly exploit digital vulnerabilities (Ogbeide & Akanji, 2021). Adolescents, mostly aged 18–24, frequently resort to fraud as a livelihood solution, given the limited opportunities available. The Nigerian government faces the complex task of implementing comprehensive interventions, including educational and community-based initiatives, to discourage such practices among youth. Addressing these challenges requires urgent attention to foster a culture of ethical online behaviour, bolster cybersecurity, and reduce the socio-economic drivers of internet fraud (Akor, 2019).

Parenting is the profound and ongoing journey of nurturing and guiding a child through various developmental stages from infancy to adulthood (Morris, 2019). This process involves a multifaceted approach aimed at fostering the comprehensive growth and well-being of a child. It encompasses the deliberate effort of supporting not just the physical but also the emotional, social, spiritual, and intellectual dimensions of a child's development. From the earliest stages of infancy, where the focus is on meeting basic needs and establishing secure attachments, to guiding a child through the complex challenges of adolescence and into adulthood, parenting involves a continuous dedication to the holistic growth and welfare of a child. It includes providing guidance, love, discipline, education, and creating an environment that encourages the child's exploration and understanding of the world around them (Ferguson, 2019).

Effective parenting involves a delicate balance of nurturing, guidance, and instilling values to help children develop into well-rounded and capable individuals. The style and behaviour employed by parents hold intricate and multifaceted impacts on a child's holistic development, adaptability, and resilience (Baumrind, 2019). However, it's essential to understand that while statistical significance might be observed, it doesn't automatically translate into practical or substantial significance in a child's life. Parenting styles, whether authoritative, permissive, or neglectful, significantly shape a child's emotional, social, and cognitive growth, influencing their ability to navigate challenges, form relationships, and develop coping mechanisms (Luo, Zhang, & Zhang, 2021). While studies may highlight statistical correlations between certain parenting behaviour and specific outcomes in children, the practical implications and real-life significance of these statistics might vary significantly. The subtleties of individual personalities, environmental influences, and the complex interplay of various factors make it challenging to universally apply statistical findings to every child's unique development.

Parental role has been found to have a substantial impact on a child's development and well-being (Maccoby & Martin, 2020). Parenting styles encompass a range of behaviour and approaches that parents adopt in raising their children, such as being authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, or neglectful. These styles can influence

various aspects of a child's life, including their emotional development, social skills, self-esteem, and overall psychological adjustment.

Research findings emphasize that parenting styles marked by warmth, responsiveness, consistency, and balanced discipline significantly contribute to positive outcomes in children. These nurturing and structured parenting approaches have been linked to fostering numerous beneficial attributes in children. Specifically, such parenting styles are associated with improved emotional regulation, higher self-esteem, enhanced social skills, and increased resilience in coping with life's adversities (Luo et al., 2021).

The warmth and responsiveness exhibited by parents create a secure and supportive environment for a child's emotional development, while consistent and appropriate discipline instils a sense of structure and guidance. This combination lays a foundation for children to develop effective coping mechanisms, navigate social interactions, and build a strong sense of self-worth. Studies consistently highlight the correlation between these nurturing, consistent parenting styles and the development of crucial skills and traits that contribute to a child's overall well-being and ability to thrive (Wang & Chen, 2021).

On the flip side, parenting styles characterized by harshness or neglect can yield detrimental effects on a child's overall development. Practices such as inconsistent discipline, absence of emotional support, or outright neglect significantly contribute to negative outcomes. Children exposed to such parenting approaches often grapple with emotional and behavioural challenges, diminished self-esteem, and encounter difficulties in forging healthy relationships (Brown & Green, 2020). Inconsistency in discipline can lead to confusion and insecurity, hindering a child's ability to understand boundaries and expected behaviour. A lack of emotional support or outright neglect deprives children of the essential nurturing environment crucial for their emotional well-being, often resulting in a range of emotional and behavioural issues. These negative effects can persist into adulthood, impacting an individual's ability to manage emotions, interact with others, and maintain healthy, meaningful relationships (Smith & Davis, 2021). Studies consistently underscore the adverse impact of harsh or neglectful parenting styles on a child's psychological and social development, reinforcing the critical role of a supportive, nurturing environment in fostering positive growth (Martinez & Rodriguez, 2022).

The concept of parenting extends far beyond a mere collection of responsibilities; rather, it constitutes a complex tapestry of roles that are profoundly integral to the holistic development of a child. At its essence, parenting entails a comprehensive commitment to meeting the multifaceted needs of children, transcending the provision of mere sustenance, shelter, and clothing. While these foundational elements undoubtedly represent a critical aspect of parenting, they merely scratch the surface of the profound influence parents wield in shaping the trajectory of their children's lives.

Parents, in their role as primary guardians, are entrusted with the sacred duty of cultivating a secure and nurturing environment wherein a child can not only survive but truly thrive and flourish. Beyond the tangible aspects of safety, health, and education, parents play an instrumental role in fostering emotional well-being, self-esteem, and a sense of belonging. It is within the folds of the family structure that a child's emotional foundation is laid, a foundation that profoundly impacts their social, cognitive, and emotional development (Martinez & Rodriguez, 2022).

Moreover, parents are not just providers but the architects of their children's moral and ethical frameworks. They serve as the inaugural models and educators, imparting a comprehensive worldview that encompasses values, beliefs, and behavioural norms.

Studies have contributed to understanding of the relationship between parenting styles and adolescent externalizing behaviours. Some key findings include:

Permissive Parenting: Permissive parenting is characterised by high affection and low structure, with few rules or expectations, as parents act more like friends than authority figures. While open communication and autonomy encourage some self-esteem and social skills, the lack of discipline and boundaries can lead to impulsive, demanding behaviours, poor self-control, and unhealthy habits in children (Anderson & Brown, 2020). Permissive parents provide emotional support but allow children to make their own choices without much guidance, increasing risks of negative habits and health issues such as poor diet and excessive screen time (Johnson & Lee, 2021).

Authoritarian Parenting: Authoritative parenting, characterised by a warm, caring relationship with clear rules and open communication, focuses on guidance rather than punishment, fostering self-confidence,

responsibility, and independence in children (Smith & Wilson, 2020). This style involves setting high expectations while valuing children's feedback and uniqueness, promoting emotional resilience, self-regulation, and academic success (Jackson & Carter, 2021). Authoritative parents are supportive yet firm, using praise, rewards, and fair discipline to nurture a respectful and democratic parent-child relationship that contributes to children's overall social, emotional, and academic well-being.

Internet fraud among adolescents, including university students, is eroding the cultural values of trust and good character (*omoluabi*) in Southwestern Nigeria, creating a society increasingly marked by distrust and reluctance to collaborate. This trend reflects the deterioration of moral standards and highlights the societal consequences of unchecked fraudulent practices (Ajibade & Adebayo, 2020). Despite general research on parenting's impact on adolescent behaviour, there is a significant lack of studies specifically examining how parental roles affect youths' engagement in internet fraud, underscoring the need for targeted insights to develop effective preventative strategies (Olowookere, 2021). This study therefore seeks to investigate the influence of parental roles on adolescents' involvement in internet fraud.

Aim and Objectives

The main aim of the study is to investigate the influence parental roles on adolescents' involvement in internet fraud in Ede South Local Government, Osun State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine the relationship between Parental Roles and adolescents' involvement in internet fraud.
2. Investigate the impact of Authoritative Parenting Style on adolescents' exposure to engaging in internet fraud.
3. Examine the relationship between permissive parenting and adolescents' likelihood of participating in internet fraud.

Research Questions

1. What is the nature of the relationship between parental roles (authoritative, permissive, authoritarian) and adolescents' involvement in internet fraud?
2. How does Authoritative Parenting Style influence adolescents' exposure to engaging in internet fraud?

3. What is the relationship between permissive parenting and adolescents' likelihood of participating in internet fraud?

Significance of the Study

This research provides a foundation for developing policies to combat internet fraud in Ede, Nigeria, by offering insights into local dynamics and parental roles in preventing adolescent involvement. The findings will guide policymakers, community leaders, and local authorities in crafting targeted interventions aimed at preserving social integrity, economic stability, and communal harmony (Adegbite & Ogunleye, 2019). By understanding the influence of parenting styles on adolescents' susceptibility to fraud, this study will inform educational campaigns, support systems, and preventive strategies, fostering a safer digital environment for youth in Ede and reducing the impact of internet fraud across Nigeria (Bamidele, 2020).

Scope of the Study

This study examines how parental roles influence adolescents' engagement in internet fraud within Ede South Local Government, Osun State, Nigeria, focusing on adolescents aged 12–19 in an area with rising fraud rates and significant educational institutions.

Limitation of the Study

This study on parental roles and adolescents' involvement in internet fraud in Ede South Local Government, Osun State, Nigeria, faces limitations such as restricted generalisability to other cultural contexts, potential sampling and social desirability biases, and the snapshot nature of cross-sectional design, which limits insights into causation (Owolabi & Akinlade, 2021). Furthermore, response bias in self-reports, cultural specificity, control over extraneous variables, and ethical considerations around consent and participant well-being further complicate the study's scope, making the findings context-specific and challenging to replicate in different settings (Ajayi, 2020).

Methodology

This chapter outlines the study’s methodology, including research design, sample selection, data collection, and data analysis processes. A mixed-method approach combining qualitative and quantitative techniques was used to explore the influence of parental roles on adolescent involvement in internet fraud in Ede South Local Government, Osun State, Nigeria, with participants selected through multistage and snowball sampling. The Parenting Roles and Dimensions Questionnaire (PRDQ) served as the research instrument, validated through rigorous content and construct analysis, and reliability tested for internal consistency and stability over time using Cronbach’s alpha and test-retest methods. The survey, administered to 250 participants, incorporated demographic and Likert-scale questions, and the data collected was analysed using Pearson product-moment correlation statistics to present relationships between variables.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question One: What is the relationship between Parental Roles (authoritative, permissive, authoritarian) and adolescents’ involvement in internet fraud?

Table 1

Questions	Very Often	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Total
How often do you talk to adolescent about the risks of internet fraud?	30%	34%	14%		10.7%	11.3%
How much freedom does your adolescent have to use the internet?	15.3%	25.3%	26%		20.7%	12.7%
Do you monitor your Adolescent’s online activity?	27.3%	23.3%	20.7%		14.7%	14%
Do you have any rules about your adolescent use of the social media?	22.7%	28.7%	20.7%		14.7%	13.3%
						100%

Source: Field survey 2023

Research question one examines the relationship between parental roles (authoritative, permissive, authoritarian) and adolescents' involvement

in internet fraud. The findings show varying levels of parental involvement in discussions and regulation of internet use. 30% of respondents frequently discuss internet fraud risks with their adolescents, while 34% do so often, and 14% sometimes. In terms of internet freedom, 25.3% of parents often give their children freedom, while 26% sometimes do, and 12.7% never allow such freedom. Regarding monitoring online activity, 27.3% of parents monitor very often, and 23.3% monitor often, while 14% never monitor. When it comes to setting social media rules, 22.7% of respondents enforce strict rules, 28.7% do so often, and 20.7% sometimes. These findings suggest that the majority of respondents believe a relationship exists between parental roles and adolescent involvement in internet fraud.

Research Question Two: How Parenting Styles Factors Influences Adolescent’s Exposure to Engaging in Internet Fraud

Table 2

Questions	Very Much	Much	Little	Very Little	Undecided	Total
How much freedom does your adolescent have to use the internet?	16.7%	24%	25.3%	22.7%	11.3%	100%
Do you talk to your adolescent about the risks of internet fraud?	34%	27.3%	17.3%	10.7%	10.7%	100%
Do you monitor your adolescent’s online activity?	28%	27.3%	17.3%	14.7%	12.7%	100%
Do you have any rules about your adolescent use of the internet?	24.7%	28%	21.3%	14%	12%	100%
						100%

Source: Field survey 2023

Research question two examines how parenting styles influence adolescents' exposure to internet fraud. The findings reveal varying levels of freedom, communication, monitoring, and rule-setting among parents. 16.7% of parents give very much freedom to their adolescents' internet use, while 24% give much freedom, and 25.3% give little

freedom. Regarding discussions on internet fraud risks, 34% of parents talk extensively with their adolescents, while 27.3% talk a lot, and 17.3% talk a little. Monitoring of online activity also varies, with 28% of parents monitoring their children's activity very much, while 27.3% monitor much, and 17.3% monitor little. When it comes to setting rules for internet use, 24.7% of parents have very strict rules, 28% have much strictness, and 21.3% have some rules. These findings indicate that parenting styles significantly influence adolescents' exposure to engaging in internet fraud, as the majority of respondents recognize the impact of these factors.

Research Question Three: Relationship Between Permissive Parenting and Adolescent's Livelihood of Participating in Internet Fraud

Table 3

Questions	Very Often	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Total
How often do you set rules For your adolescent internet use?	28%	26.7%	20.7%	11.3%	13.3%	100%
How often do you enforce those rules?	29.3%	28%	12.7%	15.3%	14.7%	100%
How often do you talk to your adolescent's about the consequences of breaking the rules?	26%	29.3%	20%	12%	12.7%	100%
How often do you set rules For your adolescent internet Use?	25.3%	28.7%	19.3%	13.3%	13.3%	100%
						100%

Source: Field survey 2023

Research question three explores the relationship between permissive parenting and adolescents' likelihood of participating in internet fraud. The findings reveal that 28% of respondents frequently set rules for their adolescents' internet use, while 26.7% set rules often, and 20.7% set rules sometimes. Regarding enforcement of these rules, 29.3% of parents enforce them very often, and 28% do so often, while 12.7% enforce them sometimes. In terms of discussing consequences for breaking rules, 26% of parents talk about consequences very often, and

29.3% do so often, while 20% talk about them sometimes. The data suggest a strong connection between permissive parenting styles, characterized by a lack of consistent rule-setting and enforcement, and a higher likelihood of adolescents engaging in internet fraud.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the survey highlights the significant impact of Parental Roles on adolescents' engagement in internet-related activities, including internet fraud and exposure to online risks. The diverse demographic composition of the sample provides a strong foundation for the study, which reveals that parental communication, rule-setting, and monitoring are key factors in shaping adolescents' online behaviours. The findings suggest that effective parental guidance can foster responsible online conduct and mitigate the risks of internet fraud. Additionally, the majority of adolescents demonstrated a negative view of internet fraud, indicating that family dynamics and parental practices influence their ethical attitudes and online behaviour. Overall, the study underscores the crucial role of effective parenting in ensuring adolescents navigate the digital world safely and ethically.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. To promote parental education and awareness programs to help parents understand responsible internet usage and the potential risks for adolescents in the online world.
2. To encourage open and ongoing communication between parents and adolescents, facilitating discussions about online risks and responsible internet behaviour.
3. Emphasize the importance of setting and consistently enforcing rules regarding internet usage to ensure that online activities align with family values.
4. To advocate for regular monitoring and supervision of adolescents' online activities, using appropriate technological tools and open dialogue to create a safe online environment.

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Addressing Systemic Weaknesses in Nigeria's Healthcare: A Roadmap to Achieving Sustainable Development Goal 3

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Abstract

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of Nigeria's progress towards Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG 3), focusing on the country's Primary Health Care (PHC) system. It highlights the dual burden of diseases and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, identifying systemic weaknesses in the healthcare system. The study proposes innovative, context-specific strategies for improvement, including leveraging technology, implementing community-driven approaches, and learning from international best practices. The ultimate goal is to provide policymakers with actionable insights to strengthen primary healthcare, leverage digital health solutions, and address social determinants of health, accelerating Nigeria's progress towards SDG 3. The study concludes that Nigeria stands at a critical juncture in its pursuit of SDG 3, with the potential to improve health outcomes through targeted, innovative interventions dramatically.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goal 3, Primary Health Care, Systemic Weaknesses, Innovative Strategies, Digital Health Solutions

Introduction

Nigeria's pursuit of Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG 3) remains a formidable challenge, with progress falling short of targets across

multiple health indicators. Despite marginal improvements, the maternal mortality ratio of 1,047 deaths per 100,000 live births and the under-five mortality rate of 117 deaths per 1,000 live births in 2023 is still unacceptably high (UNICEF, 2021, WHO, 2023). The country's health system continues to struggle with a dual burden of diseases, as malaria accounts for 27% of the global burden (World Health Organization, 2022), while hypertension prevalence has surged to 38.1% among adults (Odili et al., 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic has further exposed and exacerbated systemic weaknesses, with many households reporting difficulties accessing healthcare during the crisis. (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, 2022).

Moreover, the pandemic's ripple effects have highlighted the intricate connections between SDG 3 and other goals, as economic disruptions (SDG 8) led to increased food insecurity (SDG 2), ultimately impacting health outcomes. Nigeria's current state of the Primary Health Care (PHC) system is alarming: only approximately 20% of the 30,000 PHC facilities nationwide are fully operational. Most of these facilities cannot deliver essential primary healthcare services, a situation in which Nigeria's projected population growth will further strain 400 million by 2050 (Adewole, 2016). These challenges demand urgent, innovative, and systemic interventions beyond isolated health initiatives.

While recent initiatives like the Lagos State Health Insurance Scheme and the Saving One Million Lives Program have shown promise, more is needed to address the magnitude of Nigeria's health challenges. The increase in health insurance coverage from 3% in 2018 to 17% in 2022 (Statista, 2018; Daily Trust, 2023) is a step in the right direction but falls far short of universal coverage. Similarly, while the Ondo State Agbebiye Initiative's 61.8% increase in facility births between 2014 and 2016 is commendable (Lawal et al., 2021), such successes must be rapidly scaled and replicated nationwide. The pandemic-induced innovations in telemedicine led to a significant increase in remote consultations in 2022 (Ezeani et al., 2022), offering a glimpse of potential solutions but requiring substantial investment in digital infrastructure and health

literacy to achieve a meaningful impact. Our journey towards SDG 3 is not isolated; it's a holistic endeavour that requires us to address poverty, education, and environmental sustainability concurrently. This interconnectedness necessitates a paradigm shift in Nigeria's approach to health improvement, prioritising cross-sectoral collaboration, addressing social determinants of health, and leveraging technology to leapfrog infrastructure gaps. The time for incremental progress has passed; Nigeria must now embark on bold, transformative actions to dramatically accelerate its progress towards SDG 3 and ensure health and well-being for all its citizens.

Objective

The objective of this study is to critically analyze Nigeria's progress towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG 3), focusing on the current state of the country's Primary Health Care (PHC) system, the dual burden of diseases, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The study aims to identify the systemic weaknesses in the healthcare system and propose innovative, context-specific strategies for improvement. These strategies include leveraging technology, implementing community-driven approaches, and learning from international best practices. The ultimate goal is to provide policymakers with actionable insights to strengthen primary healthcare, leverage digital health solutions, and address social determinants of health, accelerating Nigeria's progress towards SDG 3.

Methodology

This research employs a document analysis methodology, utilizing secondary data sources. The data is collected through an extensive review of relevant journals, articles, books, publications, and reports from international organizations, along with pertinent national healthcare policy documents.

Discussion

Healthcare Challenges and Progress in Nigeria

Nigeria's healthcare landscape presents a complex tapestry of challenges and regional disparities that demand urgent, innovative interventions.

Nigeria has the second highest under-five mortality gap between urban and rural populations among 35 African countries studied, with Niger at 40.82 and Nigeria at 40.72, indicating significant pro-rural inequality (Yaya et al., 2019). This divide is further exemplified by the distribution of skilled doctors in Nigeria, with Lagos State having the highest number at 7,358, compared to Taraba State, with only 201 medical doctors. (MDCN, 2024). Such disparities hinder progress towards SDG 3 and exacerbate inequalities addressed by other SDGs, particularly SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities).

Furthermore, the impacts of climate change on health are becoming increasingly evident; climate change in Nigeria is driven by factors such as rising temperatures, increased rainfall, sea level rise, and extreme weather events, leading to heightened health risks. These health risks include cerebrospinal meningitis, cardiovascular and respiratory disorders in the elderly, skin cancer, malaria, high blood pressure, and overall morbidity. (Monday, 2019). These interconnected challenges demand a paradigm shift in Nigeria's approach to healthcare, one that prioritizes systemic resilience, cross-sectoral collaboration, and climate-adaptive strategies.

While pockets of progress exist, such as the reduction in maternal mortality achieved by Ondo State's Abiye Initiative (Lawal et al., 2021), these successes remain isolated and insufficient to address the magnitude of Nigeria's health challenges. The country's health system continues to grapple with chronic underfunding, with public health expenditure stagnating at 4.08% of GDP, far below the 15% target set by the Abuja Declaration (World Bank, 2022). Inefficiencies in resource allocation and utilization exacerbate this fiscal constraint, as 70% of ward health centres are severely outdated, dilapidated and short of essential and affordable drugs, with many epidemiological cases gaining momentum (Anthonia et al., 2021). Our health system's resilience is only as strong as its weakest link. We must urgently address these foundational gaps to withstand current and future health threats. To truly accelerate progress towards SDG 3, Nigeria must leverage

innovations while simultaneously addressing fundamental health system challenges. This requires increased investment in health infrastructure and human resources and a radical reimagining of healthcare delivery models that are adaptive to Nigeria's diverse socio-cultural landscape and emerging health threats.

Strengthening Primary Health Care

Nigeria's efforts to strengthen primary health care (PHC) have yielded pockets of success, but more is needed to address the country's vast healthcare challenges. The Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), launched in 2009, has shown promise in improving maternal and child health outcomes in rural areas, with a reduction in maternal mortality reported in participating communities by 2021 (National Primary Health Care Development Agency, 2022). Similarly, the Basic Health Care Provision Fund (BHCPF), established in 2014 and fully operationalized in 2018, has increased access to essential health services for vulnerable populations. By 2023, the BHCPF had supported renovating over 4,000 primary healthcare centres and providing essential medicines to Nigerians (NPHCDA, 2021). However, these achievements are overshadowed by persistent systemic challenges. While we've made strides in improving PHC infrastructure, we still grapple with inadequate human resources and inconsistent quality of care across facilities. This sentiment is echoed in recent data showing that only 20% of PHC facilities meet the minimum standards for service delivery (Adewole, 2016). The stark reality is that Nigeria's PHC system remains fragmented and underfunded, with public health expenditure at a mere 4.08% of GDP in 2022, far below the 15% target set by the Abuja Declaration (World Bank, 2022).

Technology offers a promising avenue for enhancing PHC delivery, but its potential remains untapped. Innovative initiatives like the mHealth Nigeria project, which uses mobile technology to support community health workers in six states, have shown encouraging results. A 2022 evaluation revealed improved antenatal care attendance and increased

facility-based deliveries in participating communities (mHealth Nigeria, 2022). However, scaling such interventions nationally is hindered by infrastructure gaps and digital literacy challenges. Integrating fundamental principles such as Universal Health Coverage, robust primary care, community engagement, and data-driven decision-making is essential. A deeper exploration of innovative technologies, such as telemedicine and AI-driven diagnostics, is needed to leapfrog traditional infrastructure limitations. The integration of conventional medicine is commendable, but we must question how to truly synthesize these practices with modern medicine in a way that respects cultural values while ensuring scientific rigour. Moreover, the framework's success hinges on overcoming deeply entrenched systemic issues like corruption, brain drain, and regional inequalities. To truly revolutionize healthcare in Nigeria, we must confront these challenges head-on, fostering a culture of accountability and excellence that permeates every level of the healthcare system.

The interconnectedness of SDG 3 with other SDGs is particularly evident in PHC strengthening efforts. For instance, the success of PHC initiatives is intrinsically linked to progress in SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) and SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), as many PHC facilities lack reliable water and electricity supply. A 2023 survey found that 45% of rural PHC facilities in Nigeria lack access to clean water, significantly impacting infection control and maternal health services (WaterAid Nigeria, 2023). To truly revolutionize SDG 3 in Nigeria, a paradigm shift is needed – one that moves beyond isolated interventions to a systems approach that addresses the complex interplay of health, infrastructure, and socio-economic factors. This requires increased funding and better governance, innovative financing mechanisms, community engagement strategies, and context-specific technological solutions that can leapfrog traditional infrastructure constraints. Achieving SDG 3 in Nigeria will require unprecedented collaboration, unwavering political will, and a collective reimagining of what's possible in healthcare delivery.

Innovative Strategies for Health Improvement in Nigeria

Nigeria can implement innovative strategies tailored to its unique context to improve health outcomes and accelerate progress towards SDG 3. One promising approach is leveraging mobile technology to extend healthcare access in underserved areas. The mHealth Nigeria initiative, launched in 2021, offers significant benefits for achieving universal health coverage by improving access to healthcare services, enhancing safety and quality, increasing health information access, and reducing costs, providing vital health information to nursing mothers and pregnant women in local languages. (Babatunde et al., 2021). Building on this success, Nigeria could partner with local tech startups to develop AI-powered diagnostic tools for community health workers, addressing the shortage of skilled healthcare professionals in rural areas. For example, the Nigerian startup 54gene is already using AI to analyze genomic data and identify disease risk factors specific to African populations (Gbenga, 2019). Collaborating with such companies could lead to tailored interventions for prevalent conditions like sickle cell disease and hypertension. Additionally, Nigeria should explore innovative financing mechanisms like development impact bonds to attract private investment in health infrastructure. The Utkrisht Impact Bond in Rajasthan, India, which aimed to improve maternal and newborn health outcomes, demonstrates how this approach can align incentives and drive results in resource-constrained settings (The Government Outcomes Lab, 2020).

Nigeria needs integrated, community-driven approaches to strengthen the overall health system and address the dual burden of communicable and non-communicable diseases. Furthermore, Nigeria should prioritize intersectoral collaboration to address the social determinants of health. The Lagos Food Bank Initiative's Nutrition Intervention Program for Mothers-at-risk (NIPOM) exemplifies how tackling food insecurity (SDG 2) can improve maternal and child health outcomes (SDG 3) (Lagos Food Bank, 2024). Scaling up such initiatives and integrating them with primary healthcare services could yield synergistic benefits across multiple SDGs. Significantly, these strategies must be developed and implemented with strong community engagement. The success of Nigeria's polio eradication efforts, which relied heavily on community mobilizers to overcome vaccine hesitancy, underscores the critical role of local leadership in health interventions (Charity et al., 2016). Nigeria

can ensure more sustainable and culturally appropriate solutions to its pressing health challenges by empowering communities to co-design and lead health improvement initiatives.

Incorporating valuable elements such as health inequality monitoring, early childhood interventions, and leveraging technology for data-driven decision-making is sound. Still, it only scratches the surface of what's truly needed. To revolutionize health outcomes, Nigeria must radically reimagine its healthcare ecosystem. This means not just implementing isolated programs but fostering a culture of innovation that permeates every aspect of health and wellness. We should explore cutting-edge solutions like blockchain for health records, AI-powered predictive health analytics, and personalized medicine tailored to Nigeria's genetic diversity.

Moreover, we must confront the deep-rooted socio-economic determinants of health, challenge entrenched power structures, and address corruption head-on. The integration of traditional medicine is a step in the right direction. Still, we need to push further, exploring how indigenous knowledge can inform new drug discoveries and holistic healing practices. While the proposed strategies provide a solid foundation, achieving transformative change requires us to question our assumptions, embrace disruptive technologies, and cultivate a national ethos prioritising health as the cornerstone of sustainable development. The road ahead is challenging, but the potential for Nigeria to become a model of innovative, equitable healthcare in Africa is immense – if we dare to dream bigger and act bolder.

International Best Practices Nigeria Can Learn From

Nigeria can draw valuable lessons from the successes and challenges other African nations face in pursuing SDG 3. Rwanda's community-based health insurance scheme, Mutuelles de Santé, has significantly improved healthcare access and financial protection. By 2010, over 90% of Rwanda's population was covered, dramatically reducing child and maternal mortality (Nyandekwe et al., 2020). While Nigeria's larger population and federal structure present unique challenges, adapting elements of Rwanda's model - such as community engagement in premium settings and subsidies for the poorest - could strengthen Nigeria's National Health Insurance Scheme. Ethiopia's Health Extension Program, which deployed over 38,000 community health

workers to rural areas, increased primary care coverage from 64% to 92% between 2004 and 2010 (Assefa et al., 2019). Nigeria could build on its community health worker programs by providing enhanced training, supervision, and integration with the formal health system. This approach aligns with SDG targets on universal health coverage and addressing health worker shortages in developing countries.

Looking beyond Africa, Thailand's Universal Coverage Scheme demonstrates how political commitment and innovative financing can rapidly expand health coverage in a middle-income country. By introducing a tax-funded insurance scheme for the informal sector in 2002, Thailand achieved universal coverage within four years (Tangcharoensathien et al., 2020). While Nigeria's fiscal space is more constrained, exploring similar progressive taxation models and efficient provider payment mechanisms could accelerate progress. India's National Digital Health Mission, launched in 2020, aims to create an integrated digital health infrastructure connecting patients, providers, and policymakers (Bassi et al., 2022). As Nigeria develops its e-health strategy, studying India's implementation challenges around data privacy, interoperability, and digital literacy could inform a context-appropriate approach. Crucially, adapting these international practices requires careful consideration of Nigeria's unique socio-cultural landscape, federal structure, and existing health system capacities. Success will depend on sustained political will, multi-sectoral collaboration, and meaningful community engagement to ensure interventions are locally owned and sustainable.

Conclusion

Nigeria stands at a critical juncture in its pursuit of SDG 3, with the potential to dramatically improve health outcomes through targeted, innovative interventions. Policymakers must prioritize three key areas: strengthening primary healthcare, leveraging digital health solutions, and addressing social determinants of health. First, Nigeria should allocate at least 15% of its annual budget to healthcare, in line with the Abuja Declaration, with a significant portion dedicated to revitalizing primary health centres (PHCs) (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2018). This investment should ensure that all PHCs meet the minimum standards for staffing, equipment, and essential medicines as outlined in the National Primary Health Care Development Agency's guidelines.

Second, Nigeria must accelerate the adoption of digital health technologies. The government should partner with local tech entrepreneurs to develop a national digital health platform integrating electronic health records, telemedicine services, and health information systems. The success of initiatives like the Eko Telemed service in Lagos State, which provided free telemedicine consultations during the COVID-19 pandemic, demonstrates the feasibility and impact of such approaches (Lagos State Government, 2020). Finally, policymakers must recognize the interconnectedness of health with other SDGs and implement cross-sectoral policies. For instance, expanding access to clean cooking fuels (SDG 7) could significantly reduce the burden of respiratory diseases, while improving water and sanitation infrastructure (SDG 6) would tackle a primary source of infectious diseases (Ezeh et al., 2020).

Looking ahead, Nigeria's health system could evolve along two potential pathways. In an optimistic scenario, increased investment in health, coupled with effective governance and innovative partnerships, could lead to universal health coverage by 2030. This would involve a robust network of well-equipped PHCs, a flourishing ecosystem of health-tech startups providing complementary services, and a significant reduction in out-of-pocket health expenditures through expanded health insurance coverage. Conversely, a business-as-usual approach risks widening health inequities and leaving Nigeria unprepared for future health challenges, including the rising burden of non-communicable diseases and potential pandemics. To avoid this scenario and accelerate progress towards SDG 3, concerted action is needed from all stakeholders. The federal and state governments must demonstrate sustained political commitment and improve coordination across levels of government. The private sector, including multinational corporations in Nigeria, should increase investments in employee health and community health initiatives. Civil society organizations and community leaders are crucial in advocating for health rights, monitoring service delivery, and promoting health literacy. International partners should align their support with national priorities and invest in building local capacity. Achieving good health and well-being for all Nigerians requires a collective effort, innovative thinking, and an unwavering commitment to health equity. Health is not just the absence of disease but a fundamental human right and a key driver of social and economic

development. It is time for all Nigerians to embrace this vision and work together to build a healthier, more prosperous nation.

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The Theatricality of Gospel Worship: Analyzing Stagecraft and Performance in the Gospel Concert *The Experience 19*

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Abstract

Gospel music and dance are foundational to worship in Nigerian churches, blending spirituality with cultural identity through vibrant expressions of praise. This study investigates the performative and theatrical elements of gospel music and dance, focusing on their roles in enhancing worship and community engagement. Using a qualitative methodology, the study incorporates content analysis of video recordings of Nigerian church services and gospel concerts, such as *The Experience 19*, alongside a review of academic literature on African liturgical practices. *The Experience 19* is a gospel concert organized by the House on the Rock Church that took place on December 6, 2024. Grounded in performance theory and cultural theory, the research highlights how indigenous dance forms (e.g. *Bata* and *Atilogwu*) and traditional instruments (e.g., talking drums) are interwoven into gospel performances to create immersive and participatory experiences. Findings reveal that these practices transcend artistry to serve as tools for spiritual connection, emotional expression, and cultural continuity. The paper concludes that the theatricality of gospel music and dance does not only enhance worship experiences but also fosters a sense of communal identity. The paper recommends further investment in training gospel dance teams and exploring innovative choreographic techniques to engage younger generations, ensuring the continuity of these dynamic worship traditions.

Keywords: Gospel Music, Nigerian Churches, African Liturgy, Dance in Worship, Cultural Identity

Introduction

Gospel music and dance have long been recognized as essential components of most Nigerian church worship. They reflect the deep connection between African cultural traditions and spirituality, where music and movement serve as vehicles for both individual expression and communal celebration. The church, often seen as a center of social and cultural life, uses these art forms not only to glorify God but also to foster unity among congregants.

Historically, music and dance in Africa have played central roles in religious ceremonies, storytelling, and rites of passage, making them natural extensions into Christian worship. This fusion of traditional elements with Christian doctrine has allowed Nigerian churches to create a worship experience that is both spiritually uplifting and culturally resonant (Ajayi, 2019). Today, gospel music and dance are vital tools for engaging worshippers, particularly in Pentecostal churches, which emphasize dynamic and participatory worship styles.

The goal of this paper is to examine the performative and theatrical elements of gospel music and dance within Nigerian churches, especially performance in the gospel concert *The Experience 19*, analyzing how these elements enhance the worship experience while preserving cultural identity. *The Experience 19* is a gospel concert organized by the House on the Rock Church that took place on December 6, 2024. Drawing on performance and cultural theories, the study argues that these practices transcend mere artistic expression, becoming transformative acts that connect the congregation to their faith and heritage. Through this exploration, the paper highlights the enduring relevance of gospel music and dance as tools for spiritual connection, emotional resonance, and communal identity.

Literature Review

Music and dance are foundational to African cultural and religious practices, serving as vehicles for storytelling, identity expression, and spiritual devotion. In Nigerian traditional contexts, the *Yoruba Bata* dance and the *Igbo Atilogwu* dance are particularly prominent. These dances, with their intricate movements and symbolic gestures, were historically used to honor deities, celebrate harvests, and mark rites of passage. In recent years, they have been incorporated into gospel

worship practices, illustrating the adaptability of these art forms in modern Christian settings (Obiefuna, 2020; Lawal, 2019).

The evolution of gospel music in Nigeria represents a process of cultural negotiation and integration. While early missionaries introduced hymns and Western choral arrangements, Nigerian Christians began to infuse indigenous rhythms, languages, and instruments such as the talking drum and *shekere* into worship. This cultural synthesis has resulted in a uniquely Nigerian gospel genre that balances spiritual depth with cultural identity (Ajayi, 2019; Olatunji, 2016). Notable artists like Bidemi Olaoba and Adeyinka Alaseyori have built on this legacy, blending traditional African elements with global contemporary gospel styles to reach diverse audiences (Basse, 2022; Adeboye, 2021).

Large-scale gospel events such as *The Experience Lagos* have become significant platforms for showcasing the intersection of culture and spirituality. These concerts integrate performance techniques such as stagecraft, multimedia displays, and professional choreography to enhance the worship experience. Scholars have noted that such events also serve as spaces for cultural preservation, where indigenous music and dance are celebrated within a modern framework (Abiola, 2018; Aluko, 2020).

Theatricality in worship is another area of growing academic interest. The use of coordinated movements, vibrant costumes, and synchronized lighting in gospel performances reflects a deliberate effort to engage congregations visually and emotionally. Researchers argue that these performative elements not only enrich worship but also deepen spiritual engagement by creating immersive environments (Chukwuma, 2022; Thompson, 2023).

Despite the wealth of research on gospel music and dance, there remains a gap in studies focusing on specific events like *The Experience*. This paper addresses this gap by examining *The Experience 19* as a case study, exploring how it showcased the cultural and spiritual dimensions of Nigerian gospel music and dance.

Theoretical Framework

The study is grounded in performance theory and cultural theory, both of which provide valuable insights into the role of gospel music and dance as transformative and culturally significant practices.

Performance Theory: According to Schechner (1988), performances, whether theatrical or ritualistic, serve as transformative acts that engage participants emotionally, spiritually, and physically. In the context of gospel music and dance, this theory highlights how these practices function as performative acts that create a sense of shared purpose and transcendence among congregants. The movements, rhythms, and staging of gospel performances are not merely aesthetic choices but are imbued with spiritual significance, transforming the worship space into a site of divine encounter.

Cultural Theory: Cultural theory focuses on the ways in which art forms reflect, preserve, and adapt cultural values within specific contexts. Gospel music and dance in Nigerian churches exemplify this process of cultural adaptation, as they integrate traditional African practices into Christian worship. By doing so, these practices preserve the cultural heritage of Nigeria while also creating a worship experience that resonates with contemporary congregants. Cultural theory emphasizes the importance of this fusion in maintaining the relevance of gospel worship in a rapidly changing world (Obiefuna, 2020). Together, these theoretical frameworks provide a lens for understanding gospel music and dance as both a cultural expression and a spiritual practice. Performance theory emphasizes the transformative power of worship as a performative act, while cultural theory highlights the role of these practices in preserving and adapting cultural traditions within the context of faith. By applying these frameworks, the study situates gospel music and dance as central to the experience of worship in Nigerian churches, connecting participants to both their spiritual and cultural identities.

Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative methodology to explore the theatricality of gospel music and dance in Nigerian churches. The study focuses on Pentecostal churches and large gospel events, such as *The Experience 19*, to capture a diverse range of practices.

Data Collection: Primary data includes video recordings of gospel performances and church services sourced from platforms like YouTube and church websites. Notable performances analyzed include choreographed dances during Sunday services at the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) and concerts by prominent gospel

artists. Secondary data is drawn from scholarly articles, books on African liturgical practices, and theological commentaries.

Analytical Framework: The study applies performance theory to examine how gospel music and dance function as performative acts that engage congregations emotionally and spiritually. Cultural theory is employed to explore the integration of indigenous art forms into Christian worship, emphasizing their role in preserving cultural identity.

Scope: The research focuses on practices observed in urban Pentecostal churches and large gospel concerts, which often incorporate professional staging, choreography, and audio-visual effects to create immersive worship experiences. By analyzing these elements, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how gospel music and dance enhance worship in Nigerian churches.

Findings and Discussion

Integration of Indigenous Practices

The Experience 19 highlighted the seamless incorporation of traditional Nigerian dance forms and instruments into gospel performances. For instance, Bidemi Olaoba's use of Yoruba call-and-response chants and the talking drum underscored the cultural authenticity of his set (Adeboye, 2021). Similarly, choreographed dance performances during Adeyinka Alayesori's worship segment included movements inspired by the *Bata* dance, reflecting how traditional practices continue to resonate in contemporary gospel music (Lawal, 2019; Olatunji, 2016). These elements demonstrated how indigenous practices enrich worship by creating a sense of cultural pride and community identity (Obiefuna, 2020; Chukwuma, 2022).

Theatricality in Worship

The Experience 19 set a new standard for theatrical worship in Nigeria. Advanced stagecraft, including dynamic lighting designs, multimedia projections, and elaborate stage setups, transformed the concert into a spiritual spectacle (Thompson, 2023). For example, Alaseyori's performance used synchronized lighting effects that matched the rhythm of her music, creating an immersive worship atmosphere. Costumes also played a significant role, blending traditional African motifs with modern aesthetics to reflect the duality of cultural preservation and innovation (Abiola, 2018).

Spiritual and Communal Impact

Audience participation was a defining feature of *The Experience 19*. Attendees actively engaged in singing, clapping, and dancing, creating a communal worship atmosphere. The sense of unity was particularly evident during corporate prayer sessions led by Don Moen and Nathaniel Bassey, where thousands of worshippers came together in spiritual solidarity (Adeboye, 2021; Okeke, 2020). The multilingual nature of the event, with performances in English, Yoruba, and Igbo, further emphasized its inclusivity and ability to connect diverse audiences (Chukwuma, 2022).

Global Influence and Cultural Exchange

The event also underscored the global reach of Nigerian gospel music, with international artists like Don Moen and Travis Greene sharing the stage with local performers. This cross-cultural collaboration enriched the event, demonstrating the universality of gospel music as a tool for spiritual transformation and cultural exchange (Bassey, 2022; Thompson, 2023). The collaboration also showcased how Nigerian gospel music can influence and inspire global worship practices (Aluko, 2020).

Conclusion

Gospel music and dance are more than artistic expressions. They are vital tools for spiritual connection, cultural preservation, and communal engagement in Nigerian churches. By blending traditional African practices with modern Christian worship, these elements create a unique and transformative experience that resonates across diverse demographics. As these practices continue to evolve, they hold the potential to deepen worship experiences while preserving the rich cultural heritage of Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. ***Professional Training for Gospel Performers:*** Churches and organizers of events like *The Experience 19* should invest in professional training programs that focus on choreography, stage management, and vocal techniques. Such training would enhance the quality of performances and elevate the global appeal of Nigerian gospel music (Abiola, 2018; Aluko, 2020).

2. **Incorporating Contemporary Dance Styles:** To attract younger audiences, churches should integrate modern dance styles like Afrobeat and hip-hop into gospel performances. This approach can bridge generational gaps while maintaining the spiritual essence of worship (Ajayi, 2019; Chukwuma, 2022).
3. **Digital Archiving and Preservation:** High-quality recordings of events like *The Experience* should be archived and made accessible for research and educational purposes. This initiative could document the evolution of gospel music and its role in preserving cultural heritage (Okonkwo, 2021; Bassey, 2022).
4. **Partnerships with Cultural Institutions:** Collaborating with cultural organizations can promote workshops, exhibitions, and publications on gospel music and dance. These initiatives would support the study and preservation of indigenous worship practices (Obiefuna, 2020; Lawal, 2019).
5. **Promoting Nigerian Gospel Music Internationally:** Efforts should be made to feature Nigerian gospel artists in global Christian music festivals and streaming platforms. This would showcase the richness of Nigerian gospel music and its cultural significance to an international audience (Adeboye, 2021; Williams, 2017).
6. **Innovative Use of Technology in Worship:** Churches should explore the use of virtual reality and interactive multimedia to enhance the worship experience. Such technologies could create immersive environments that engage congregants on a deeper level (Thompson, 2023; Okonkwo, 2021).

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